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Special Issue:

**Auxiliary Verb Constructions
in Bantu Languages**

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Introduction to the Special Issue: Advancing the Study of Auxiliary Systems in Bantu

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Introduction

Bantu languages are notoriously described as “verby” (Nurse 2008, 21), referring to the highly agglutinative nature of the inflected verb, whose complexities have sparked extensive research. Now that Bantu verbal morphology is much better understood, the time has come to widen the scope of research beyond the limits of the inflected, lexical verb to auxiliary verbs, which play an important role in Bantu verbal constructions but have enjoyed relatively little dedicated attention. This special issue is the outcome of an open call for papers issued by editors of the *Nordic Journal of African Studies*, inviting contributions on auxiliary verb constructions in Bantu languages. The call was designed to capture the breadth and diversity of current research on Bantu auxiliaries, encouraging submissions that address their categorical status, functional range, diachronic development, contact-induced change, and interaction with broader grammatical systems.

A total of nine papers were accepted for publication and are included in the issue. The studies cover a plethora of Bantu languages, spoken across the entire Bantu-speaking area, from the extreme northwest and northeast all the way to the far southeast, with contributing authors based in both the Global North and the Global South. The contributions are presented in the special issue in the order of their Guthrie codes (see footnote 1), reflecting both the geographical diversity of the studies and the variation and recurring patterns in auxiliary constructions across the Bantu area.

The primary objective of these papers is to advance the systematic study of auxiliary verb constructions in Bantu languages by bringing together empirically grounded and theoretically informed research that addresses their form, function and development. The papers move beyond viewing auxiliaries merely as transitional or peripheral phenomena, instead foregrounding them as central components of Bantu grammatical systems and as key loci of morphosyntactic and semantic changes.

Bantu auxiliary constructions: Setting the scene

Bantu languages are known for their verb-centred morphosyntax, in which many functional categories are encoded on the verb, and for the tendency of new grammatical material to emerge from lexical sources. One of the most salient manifestations of this diachronic dynamic is the recurrent development of auxiliary constructions and their further evolution into bound verbal morphology. Across the Bantu family, lexical verbs are continually recruited into auxiliary functions and may subsequently grammaticalise into prefixes or other inflectional materials (Heine and Reh 1984; Heine 1993; Güldemann 1999, 2003; Nurse 2008), contributing to the rich and complex verbal systems characteristic of these languages.

From a functional perspective, auxiliary constructions can express a remarkably wide range of grammatical meanings. As noted by Anderson (2006, 36), auxiliaries can encode “virtually every non-nominal [...] category described as ‘inflectional’,” and Bantu languages provide abundant empirical evidence to support this observation. In addition to the well-documented use of auxiliaries in expressing tense and aspect (see, for example Nurse 2008), Bantu auxiliary constructions are attested in domains such as modality (Bernander et al. 2022 and further references therein), negation (Bernander et al. 2023a; Devos and Van Olmen 2013), directionality (Devos 2014; Guérois et al. 2021), focus marking (Devos and van der Wal 2010), voice (Guerois 2025), phasal polarity (many of the contributions in Kramer 2021; Zahran and Bloom Ström 2022; Bernander et al. 2023b), and a range of adverbial functions (Gibson 2025; Crane et al. forthcoming). This functional diversity emphasizes the importance of auxiliary constructions

not only for synchronic grammatical description but also for understanding pathways of grammatical change in Bantu languages.

Despite their typological and theoretical significance, Bantu auxiliary constructions have historically received relatively limited attention in the general literature (Bernander et al. 2022; Crane et al. *forthc*). Traditional research has primarily focused on the internal morphology of the simplex verbal word, often treating auxiliary constructions as peripheral, transitional, or merely substitutive structures along a presumed path towards synthetic morphology (Nurse 2008). As a result, both the formal properties of auxiliary constructions and the full range of functions they encode have remained insufficiently explored in a systematic and comparative manner. This imbalance is particularly striking, given the prevalence of auxiliary constructions in contemporary Bantu languages and their evident relevance for broader questions of morpho-syntactic organisation.

From a historical perspective, several fundamental issues remain unresolved, most notably the extent to which auxiliary constructions can be reconstructed to Proto-Bantu or to early Bantu ancestor varieties, including the core question of whether these stages featured predominantly analytic (auxiliary-like) or synthetic predicate structures (Nurse 2008, ch. 6; Nurse and Watters 2022; Güldemann 2003, 2022). Closely related questions concern the potentially cyclic nature of grammaticalization along the verb–affix continuum (Givón 1979; Heine 1993; Bybee et al. 1994). These open issues underscore the need for detailed empirical studies grounded in both synchronic descriptions and historical comparisons, including careful consideration of possible contact-induced developments and areal patterns (Bernander 2025).

At the same time, defining and delimiting what constitutes an auxiliary and auxiliary constructions in Bantu remains theoretically challenging. While heuristic definitions that position auxiliaries along a diachronic form-function continuum between lexical verbs and bound grammatical affixes (Anderson 2006, 7, 2011, 2) have proven productive, their application raises questions about categorical status, structural variation, and the interaction between auxiliary elements and their lexical counterparts. Addressing these challenges, as stated in most current literature (see, for example, Gibson 2019, 2025; Gunnink 2023; Crane et al. *forthcoming*) requires fine-grained analyses that engage with both language-internal evidence and cross-linguistic typology.

Overview of the contributions

The papers in this special issue seek to address some of the gaps mentioned in the previous section, bringing together contributions that engage with a broad range of interrelated questions concerning auxiliary verb constructions in Bantu languages. A central concern running through several papers is the definition and categorical status of auxiliaries and their place within the broader architecture of the verb phrase. Fleischhauer and Kihara examine how auxiliaries can be distinguished from both lexical verbs and light verbs in Gĩkũyũ (E51)¹, and which morpho-syntactic diagnostics are most revealing in making these distinctions. The contribution by Kerr shows that predicate structures in Northwestern Bantu (Zone A) and nearby Bantoid languages often occupy an intermediate position between analytic and synthetic constructions, challenging clear-cut categorisations.

¹ Throughout this section we cite languages with their Guthrie code (the alpha-numeric coding system of Bantu languages consisting of a letter indicating broader zones and numbers identifying the language). The inclusion or omission of language prefixes follows that chosen by the author of the specific article in which the language is referred to.

Another set of papers in the present special issue focuses on the internal structure and functions of auxiliary constructions, highlighting the role and behaviour of the lexical verb element and ways in which auxiliary systems encode complex temporal, modal and pragmatic meanings. Creissels offers a detailed look at the multiple functions of what he terms ‘dedicated’ auxiliaries in Tswana (S31), that is, auxiliaries without lexical counterparts. Botne’s study demonstrates how single and stacked auxiliary constructions in Kihehe (G62) allow speakers to express fine-grained temporal relations and modal nuances, while Bar-el, Kanijo and Petzell’s analysis illustrates the coexistence of multiple grammaticalization stages within a single system in Kagulu (G12). Savić’s study further extends the functional domain of auxiliaries beyond tense and aspect, showing how auxiliary constructions can acquire discourse-pragmatic functions related to information structure and clause linkage in isiXhosa (S41). The stacking of auxiliaries is specifically addressed in Crane et al.’s contribution, which serves as a programmatic call for further investigations into this distinct phenomenon.

Diachronic development and reconstruction form a third primary research agenda in this issue. Several contributions address how auxiliary constructions emerge, involve and sometimes recycle along the verb-auxiliary-affix continuum. Crane’s comparative survey of a large number of auxiliary functions across Southern Bantu (zone S) raises the question of whether extensive auxiliary systems reflect inherent patterns from earlier stages of Bantu or are later innovations, while Botne as well as Bar-el, Kanijo and Petzell provide language-specific case studies that indicate non-linear, potentially cyclic pathways of grammaticalization in Kihehe and Kagulu, respectively. Fleischhauer and Kihara’s analysis of partial decategorization in Gĩkũyũ likewise underscores the gradual and layered nature of auxiliarization.

Finally, the papers in the current special issue foreground the role of language contact and areal dynamics in shaping auxiliary systems. Zahran, Devos and Guérois present a compelling case of contact-induced diffusion in their study of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries in the Middle and Lower Zambezi region (zones M, N and S10), with findings illustrating multilingual interaction. Additionally, Crane notes contact with Khoisan languages as a possible factor in the maintenance or expansion of auxiliary functions in Southern Bantu.

Taken together, these nine contributions demonstrate that auxiliary verb constructions in Bantu cannot be fully understood without considering the interplay of language-internal structure, diachronic change, and areal contact. By offering detailed empirical descriptions, refined analytical distinctions, and comparative and historical perspectives, the papers collectively underscore the value of auxiliary constructions as a window onto broader issues of verb-centred morphosyntax, grammaticalisation, and the interaction between analytic and synthetic structures. Beyond their relevance for Bantu linguistics, the findings presented here contribute to cross-linguistic discussions on auxiliaries, form-function continua, and cycles of morphosyntactic change, and thus speak to a broader audience in linguistic theory and typology.

Similarly, the diversity of languages, methodological approaches, and theoretical frameworks represented in this issue highlights both the progress made and the substantial work that remains to be done in studying and understanding auxiliary constructions in Bantu languages. Future research will benefit from further fine-grained studies of underdescribed languages and varieties, expanded reconstruction efforts across different Bantu subgroups, and closer attention to the role of language contact and multilingual ecologies in shaping auxiliary systems. We hope that this special issue will not only consolidate recent advances but also stimulate continued interdisciplinary and international collaboration on auxiliary constructions in Bantu and beyond.

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Auxiliaries and Analyticity in Northwestern Bantu

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Abstract

Northwestern Bantu (NWB) languages differ from Eastern/Southwestern Bantu languages in that their verb forms are more often analytic, with pre-stem inflectional material appearing in a complex that may be unbound from the main verb. This has resulted in NWB languages being described as having Aux V word order, where ‘Aux’ stands for ‘auxiliary’. At the same time, some verb forms are analysed as synthetic, and authors vary widely in their use of terminology and their orthographic representation of pre-stem material, even for the same language. In this paper, I first review the different terminology used for NWB predicates, highlighting the corresponding variation in wordhood analyses. I then review the structure of the pre-stem ‘auxiliary’ complexes. First, I discuss the internal structure of NWB pre-stem complexes, with regard to the order of elements. Secondly, I discuss the external structure of these complexes, reviewing diagnostics for considering them as independent from the main verb (analytic) or as bound to it (synthetic). The results show variation in the degree of separation between the pre-stem material and the lexical verb across NWB Bantu languages and constructions, consistent with them being in intermediate stages of a recurrent diachronic change between analytic and synthetic verbal predication.

Keywords: Northwestern Bantu, analyticity/syntheticity, wordhood, morphosyntax, verbs

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1 Introduction

Languages from the Bantu sub-family of Niger-Congo are generally described as having highly agglutinative verb forms (e.g., Nurse 2008, 28; Good 2012, 294), also referred to in terms of exhibiting a high degree of verbal synthesis. However, languages from the Northwest of the Bantu family, particularly those of Bantu zone A, are excluded from these generalizations on account of having different verb structures (Schadeberg and Bostoen 2019, 172). These Northwestern Bantu (NWB) languages contrast with other Bantu languages in showing much more analytic verb forms, with inflectional material often described as part of an ‘auxiliary’ which is written as a separate orthographic word from the main verb (<Aux V>), as exemplified in (1)–(2).¹

- (1) **Mé-ŋò** àŋó mímé fwálábi.
H:1SG-FUT you house build:CAUS
‘I’ll build a house for you.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu];² Mous 2005, 9)

- (2) **Mèté** wô yén.
|**mà-Lté** wò L-jén
1SG-PR 2SG.NPPR INF-see
‘I see you.’ (Eton (A71) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 255)

This separation between pre-stem material and the main verb is also found in descriptions of closely-related (non-Bantu) Bantoid/Wide Bantu languages, as in (3)–(4) below.

- (3) **Ǻ** tà ka bon yenni.
he IPFP0 NEG them see
‘He doesn’t see them.’ (Tikar (N. Bantoid) [tik]; Stanley 1997, 441)

- (4) **Wù** à tǿ jántǿ.
CL1.PVB P2 come(b) yesterday
‘He arrived yesterday.’ (Mundabli (S. Bantoid) [boe]; Voll 2017, 195)

While there is variation here as to whether the authors represent the inflectional elements as bound to each other (as in (1)–(2)) or as a sequence of free forms (as in (3)–(4)), all these cases show a separation between the inflectional elements and the main lexical verb, with white-space used in the orthographic representation and non-verbal material intervening (i.e., object pronouns in (2)–(3) and both an object pronoun and an object noun in (1)). This analytic verbal morphosyntax contrasts with the highly synthetic simplex verb forms common to the rest of the Bantu family, as exemplified in (5)–(6).

¹ Throughout the paper, I leave the data presentation as in the original sources, with the exception of adding glosses to unglossed examples, changing lexical glosses and translations in other languages to English, standardizing punctuation and capitalization, adding boldface to highlight the points of interest, and italicizing and interlinearizing following the NJAS house style. A list of abbreviations is given at the end of the paper.

² I follow Bantuist convention in providing the Guthrie classification code for each Narrow Bantu language alongside examples and when a language is first mentioned in the main text, together with the ISO 639-3 code in square brackets. The Guthrie code is an alphanumeric code based primarily on the geographical position of the language rather than necessarily reflecting genealogical proximity (Maho 2003, 2009).

- (5) *Mkángó u-ma-ku-kónd-a.*
 3-lion 3_{SM}-HAB-2ND_{SING}OM-love-FV
 ‘The lion loves you.’ (Chichewa (N30) [nya]; Mchombo 2004, 34)
- (6) *Twáràkàbòòrà zyónà.*
 /tu-ára-ka-boor-a zyóna/
 SM1_{PL}-REM.FUT-DIST-return-FV tomorrow
 ‘We will return tomorrow.’ (Fwe (K402) [fwe]; Gunnink 2022, 309)

As some sources on NWB languages represent pre-stem inflectional elements as separate from the verb in constructions like (1)–(2), they have been considered as having Aux V word order, where ‘Aux’ refers to an auxiliary complex. Some languages like Tunen which also allow pre-verbal objects (OV word order) have therefore been likened to West African languages with so-called ‘S-Aux-Obj-V-Other’ word order (or ‘Aux-Obj-V’ in combination with ‘Obj-V-Other’; Creissels 2005; Gensler and Güldemann 2003; Güldemann 2008, 2018, 481–482), i.e., split predicate structure, where the main verb is separated from other material associated with it (the ‘Aux’ material).

However, there is a lot of variation in sources on NWB languages as to whether a construction is treated as analytic or synthetic, even for the same language. For example, while in (1) we saw the pre-stem material written in an auxiliary complex that was separate from the main verb in a ditransitive clause with pre-verbal object pronouns in Tunen (A44) [tvu], in clauses without intervening material the analysis is more ambiguous. Sources on Tunen differ considerably in how they represent wordhood in these cases. Dugast (1971, 1975) writes the subject marker separately and the tense marker conjoint with the verb (7), while the community orthography writes each element separately (Satre et al. 2008) (8). Kerr (2024a, 2024b) follows the community orthography in keeping each element as a separate orthographic word, adding parentheses to the surface transcription line to indicate vowel elision (9).

- (7) *A nákan ebàk’ òmbel.*
 SM.1 PST.leave 7.lizard 3.house
 ‘He went to the lizard’s house.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu]; Dugast 1975, 61)
- (8) *Yowánese a n’ akána u nioní.*
 1.Jean SM.1 PST1 leave PREP 5.market
 ‘Jean went to the market.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu]; Satre et al. 2008, 11)
- (9) *Hilóbi hé ná wéeya iti, isinjáka ɔndʒelé a n(á) ákan ase : (...)*
 /hɛ-lóbi hé ná wéeya itíá eséájáka ɔ-ndʒelé
 19-anger SM.19 PST2 PRN.EMPH.1 hold now 3-lizard
a ná akána a-séá (...)/
 SM.1 PST2 leave SM.1-say(...)
 ‘He became enraged, and now the lizard came by, and said: (...)’
 (Tunen (A44) [tvu]; Kerr 2024b, 186)

Which source is used may therefore influence how the language is interpreted in terms of its similarities to other Niger-Congo languages versus Narrow Bantu languages. In this paper I therefore aim to provide an overview of NWB pre-stem complexes, highlighting why they are sometimes considered as auxiliaries as part of analytic constructions resembling split predicate structures in other African languages, and sometimes considered as bound to the verb as part of synthetic constructions of the canonical Bantu type. I first discuss the terminological and analytical differences found in the literature (Section 3). Next, I turn to the structure of the auxiliary complexes. First, I consider their internal structure (Section 4), showing that the elements can be schematized as SM-{-NEG1-}TAM-{-NEG2-}DIR-PRN (where DIR = directional marker and PRN = a subject pronoun), which overlaps with the order of elements in synthetic Bantu verb forms. Next, I turn to the external structure of auxiliary complexes, viz. their relationship with the main lexical verb (Section 5). Here, I evaluate the evidence that can be used to support the treatment of pre-stem complexes as separate from the main verb (analytic) versus bound to it (synthetic), showing that interruptability is the most widely used criterion for justifying analyses of analytic verb structure. Finally, Section 6 concludes.

2 Methodology

The main data source for this paper is the data available in descriptive grammars and other sources on NWB languages and nearby Bantoid/Wide Bantu languages, with a focus on Bantu zone A. Here, NWB languages are considered in the narrow sense, i.e., corresponding to Bantu zone A and parts of Bantu zone B (Grollemund et al. 2015), as these languages, spoken closest to the Bantu homeland, are reported to have the most analytic verb forms.

I supplement these data with some primary data collected from fieldwork in Cameroon. The fieldwork was conducted in Feb–Apr 2025 and Jul–Aug 2025 for a period of four months, under a research permit granted by the Cameroonian Ministry for Scientific Research and Innovation (MINRESI). The fieldwork covered the four languages of the Western Mbam subgroup of Bantu languages (A40/A60), working with 28 consultants, aged 30–70, male and female, across seven field sites, and using French as a metalanguage.

The Bantu zone A and Bantoid languages discussed in this paper are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1. While I also consulted some further sources on zone B and C languages as a comparison, I do not cover them here for reasons of space.

Table 1: Languages for which examples are discussed in this paper, with classification and sources consulted

Language	Subgroup	Guthrie no.	ISO-639-3	Source(s) consulted
Akoose	Bantu	A15C	bss	Hedinger (2008)
Atomb	Bantu	A461	tff	Dihenou Djahappi (2021) + own data
Bafia	Bantu	A53	kdf	Guarisma (2003)
Basaá	Bantu	A43	bas	Hyman (2003); Makasso (2023)
Duala	Bantu	A42	dua	Ittmann (1978)
Eton	Bantu	A71	eto	Van de Velde (2008)
Ewondo	Bantu	A72	ewo	Redden (1979)
Gunu	Bantu	A62	yas	Rekanga (1989)

Language	Subgroup	Guthrie no.	ISO-639-3	Source(s) consulted
Gyeli	Bantu	A801	gyi	Grimm (2021)
Iyasa	Bantu	A33a	yas	Brown (2021)
Koonzime	Bantu	A842	ozm	Beavon (1983, 1991)
Kwakum	Bantu	A91	kwu	Njantcho Kouagang (2018); Njantcho Kouagang and Van de Velde (2019)
Makaa	Bantu	A83	mcp	Heath (2003); Ibrahīm (2021)
Mmala	Bantu	A62	mmu	Nzang-Bie (1989); Boyd (2015)
Mpiemo	Bantu	A86c	mex	Festen (2008); Thornell (2003)
Mundabli	Bantoid	N/A	boe	Voll (2017)
Nomaandé	Bantu	A46	lem	Wilkendorf (1986, 2001); Taylor (1999); Boyd (2015) + own data
Nuasúe	Bantu	A62	yav	Bébiné (2019); Boyd (2015)
Nyokon	Bantu	A45	nvo	Boyd (2015); Mous (2014, 2022); Kerr (2024a) + own data
Oroko	Bantu	A11	bdu	Kuperus (1985); Friesen (2002)
Tikar	Bantoid	N/A	tik	Stanley (1997)
Tuki	Bantu	A601	bag	Musada (1996); Boyd (2015)
Tunen	Bantu	A44	tvu	Dugast (1971, 1975); Mous (2003, 2014); Boyd (2015); Kerr (2024b, 2024c) + own data

3 Terminology

3.1 Pre-stem complexes and analyticity

In this section I define the two key terms of this paper, namely pre-stem complexes and analyticity.

I use ‘pre-stem complex’ as a descriptive term for all pre-verbal inflectional material. This inflectional material is dependent on the main verb, where the main verb contributes the lexical core of the predicate. The inflectional material expresses various grammatical features, such as subject indexation, negation, and tense. These features may be encoded using unbound morphological forms, agglutinative morphology, or fusional morphology. ‘Pre-stem complex’ is most useful as a term for languages in which these elements are separate from the main lexical verb. However, I will use ‘pre-stem complex’ as a descriptive term for all the Bantu languages considered, even if the actual degree of separation from the main verb is not yet proven. This parallels the use of ‘pre-stem cluster’ in some other sources. As we will see, (parts of) this pre-stem complex may also be referred to as an ‘auxiliary’ in certain sources.

The term ‘analyticity’ stems from work in the German philological tradition conducted by A. W. von Schlegel (1818) and F. von Schlegel (1808) and developed by linguists such as Sapir and Greenberg (see Arkadiev 2020 for a historical overview), where languages were grouped into different morphosyntactic types on the basis of the morphological complexity of the word,

analytic languages containing few morphemes per word. As this typology has been refined, analyticity is seen as the other end of a continuum from ‘syntheticity’, where syntheticity is defined as having a high number of morphemes expressed on the same word. Here I discuss analyticity with respect to split predication, a notion I will define further in Section 3.3 after reviewing previous treatments of Bantu verb forms along the analytic-synthetic continuum.

3.2 Bantu verb forms

As stated above, one of the hallmarks of the Bantu languages is the complexity of verb forms. Within the Africanist literature, Bantu verbs are usually described as ‘highly agglutinative’ (see, e.g., Good 2012, 294). In this paper I follow the general linguistic literature in using ‘synthetic’ as the more appropriate counterpart of ‘analytic’, as agglutination refers to the specific type of morphological realization (one morpheme per form, in contrast to ‘flexional’/‘fusional’ morphology), which is an independent axis of variation from the current issue of free versus bound forms (see, e.g., Comrie 1989, 42–52; Arkadiev 2020; Bostoen to appear).

Based on the high syntheticity observed across Bantu languages, the Bantuist Achille Meeussen reconstructed a highly synthetic verbal template for the proto-language (Meeussen 1967, 108–111), as represented in Table 2 below (cf. Güldemann 2022, 388; Nurse 2008, 226–283).

Figure 1: Languages for which examples are discussed in this paper, based on coordinates in Glottolog (with Dimbong used as proxy for Atomb). Plotted in R using lingtypology (Moroz 2017)

Table 2: Meeussen’s (1967) schema of Bantu finite verbs, as represented in Güldemann, (2022, 388), where (...) indicates optional material, + indicates the possibility of recursion, T = tense, A = aspect, M = mood, and P = polarity

Prefix aka pre-stem cluster				Stem cluster			
-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
(pre-initial)	initial	(post-initial) +	(pre-radical)	radical	(pre-final) +	final	(post-final)
	subject		object	verb	derivation		participant
TAMP		TAMP			TAMP	TAMP	P
clause		clause					clause
type		type					type

More recent work on Proto-Bantu (PB) reconstruction has profited from the larger and higher-quality data that has become available since Meeussen’s time. In discussions of PB reconstruction in Bostoen et al. (2022), a common observation is that Meeussen’s reconstructions, while often still considered valid, most likely represent the ancestor language of a slightly later time point than PB itself. This is related to the fact that Meeussen’s sample contained fewer examples from NWB languages (and non-Bantu Niger-Congo), which form the first branches of Bantu and show a high degree of linguistic diversity (see, e.g., Bostoen to appear; Marten 2020). A resultant question is whether the synthetic verbal template reconstructed in Table 2 is valid for PB, or whether it represents a later development, which would mean that present-day NWB verb forms did not descend from it. While syntheticity going back to PB is still assumed in various sources (e.g., Hyman 2011; Nurse 2008, 231), Güldemann (2011, 2022) instead argues that NWB analytic verb forms show the conservation of split predicate structure types already found in the proto-language (see also Gensler 1994, 1997; Gensler and Güldemann 2003; Güldemann 2003), the present-day syntheticity observed in canonical Bantu being a later development.

A final nuance is that analyticity/syntheticity should be defined at the level of the construction, rather than the language. As pointed out by Van de Velde and Idiatov (2025, 183), the reconstruction presented by Meeussen in Table 2 should not be interpreted as a statement that Proto-Bantu had no auxiliary constructions existing alongside such simplex verb forms. The same is true synchronically, as shown by the discussion of auxiliary verb constructions in present-day Narrow Bantu languages in the other contributions to this special issue. In any language, it is to be expected that there are constructions varying in the degree of V>AUX>TAM grammaticalization, resulting in different degrees of synthesis (see, e.g., Ledgeway 2012, 12–15 for parallel discussion about synchronic variation in Romance varieties).

3.3 Split predicates and STAMP morphs

As pre-stem complexes are treated as unbound from the lexical verb in many constructions found in NWB languages, pre-stem complexes are sometimes discussed under the terms ‘split predication’ and ‘STAMP morphs’. I discuss these here.

‘Split predication’ refers to constructions in which the main verb is phonologically and syntactically separated from other verbal elements associated with it. The term is used by Güldemann (2011) and attributed to Bearth (1995), who used it in the description of Mande languages of West Africa (Güldemann 2011, 123, fn. 7). Examples (10)–(11) below shows a split predicate structure in the Mande languages Soninke [snk] and Koranko [knk], where the

main verb *qóbó* ‘buy’ / *lábùì* ‘throw’ is split from the pre-stem material (glossed in (10), following Mandeist tradition, as PM for ‘predicative marker’).

- (10) *Fààtú dà tíjè-n qóbó sáχà-n ḡá.*
 Fatou PM meat-DEF buy market-DEF Po
 ‘Fatou has bought meat at the market.’ (Soninke (Mande) [snk]; (Creissels 2005, §0)

- (11) *Û sí wò lá-bùì yí rò.*
 1SG PROSPECTIVE that.one CAUS-fall water in
 ‘I’m going to throw her into the water.’
 (Koranko (Mande) [knk]; Kastenholz 1987, 117 via Güldemann 2008, 160)

Split predicates in African languages have been argued to be an areal feature of languages in the Macro-Sudan Belt/Central Sudanic Zone linguistic area (Güldemann 2008, 2011). Some authors have argued that the African cases of split predication are cross-linguistically rare, differing from split predication in languages such as Germanic varieties in that material such as adjuncts consistently follows the verb (see, e.g., Gensler and Güldemann 2003). In terms of the distribution of split predication, some authors include NWB languages from Bantu zone A, extending the area southwards to Cameroon. However, one question is where the cut-off point is between split predication and bound verb forms, given the variation in data sources. As most Narrow Bantu languages are taken to have synthetic verb forms, where does the split occur? Güldemann (2022, 389) acknowledges the “important caveat” that his conclusions about split predication are based on orthographic wordhood in the sources, which we will see in the next subsection is an unreliable proxy to linguistic boundedness.

A related term is ‘STAMP morphs’ (or ‘STAMP morphemes’), which has been particularly employed recently in work by Anderson (2016, 2025a, 2025b), who defines it as “portmanteau subject-tense-aspect-mood-polarity morphs exhibiting functional and formal properties of both pronominals and auxiliary verbs” (Anderson 2016, 513). Anderson’s definition is bipartite, relying on (i) fusional morphology, and (ii) separation from the verb. Examples (12)–(13) show canonical STAMP morphs, with multiple STAMP features expressed in non-clearly decomposable morphology, and with the STAMP morph written as separate from the main verb.

- (12) *Mân hé ò-kót.*
 1.FUT.NEG go to-bush
 ‘I won’t go to the bush.’
 (Duka (Kainji) [dud], Bendor-Samuel et al. 1973, 13 via Anderson 2016, 517)

- (13) a. *náá soo Gindiríḡ.*
 1.PRF go Gindiri
 ‘I went to Gindiri.’

- b. *ín soo dirámméka.*
 I.IPFV go farm.your.OBLQ
 ‘I will go to your farm.’

(Fyem (Plateau) [pym], Nettle 1998, 32, 35 via Anderson 2016, 518)

Like split predicates, STAMP morphs have been proposed as an areal morphosyntactic characteristic of languages spoken in the Macro-Sudan Belt. However, authors differ in their operationalization of the term, which affects the validity of conclusions about areal distribution. While the canonical STAMP morph expresses multiple grammatical features (viz., subjecthood, tense, polarity, etc.) via fusional morphology, some authors use ‘STAMP morphs’ to refer to clearly agglutinative sequences within pre-stem complexes. For example, Güldemann (2022, 389) treats Ewondo *a-kad* in (14) as a “STAMP morpheme”, while the form is clearly segmentally decomposable into two morphemes, *a* ‘SM.1’ and *kad* ‘HAB’.³

- (14) *A-kad mə soób bī-yé.*
 3SG-HAB 1SG wash 8-cloth
 ‘He washes clothes for me.’

(Ewondo (A72) [ewo]; Redden 1979, 56 via Güldemann 2022, 389)

STAMP morphs *sensu stricto* involve fusional morphology: under that part of the definition, Ewondo fails. However, there is no hard-and-fast cut-off point between fusional and agglutinative morphology, as fusional morphology may result from the merger of erstwhile agglutinative morphology, as is commonly assumed (e.g., Croft 2003, 252; cf. Haspelmath 2018 for some scepticism). Rolle (2022) moreover shows that even forms in the Nigerian language Ebirá [igb] that appear to be highly fusional may be morphologically decomposed, provided a certain level of abstraction and irregularity is allowed in the analysis. Still, there is a qualitative difference in the degree of fusion observable in canonical STAMP morphs found in West African languages and in the pre-stem material found in NWB/Bantoid languages. And if NWB/Bantoid pre-stem material is described as a STAMP morph, this raises the question of where the cut-off point is with other Bantu languages – do (5)–(6) also involve STAMP morphs combining with a lexical verb, and if so, what is different about NWB languages? This issue is raised by Van de Velde and Idiatov (2025):

Güldemann (2022: 395) points out that subject indexes hardly ever attach directly to the stem in Benue-Congo languages outside of Bantu, where they are often integrated into a so-called STAMP cluster (or “morph”). This, however, is not a difference between Bantu and the rest of Benue-Congo, as subject indexes typically precede a TAM marker or auxiliary in the Bantu languages, rather than directly the stem of the main verb. The main difference is that STAMP clusters show a greater degree of fusion, generally suggestive of older morphology (i.e. older combinations of specific forms).
 (Van de Velde and Idiatov 2025, 190–191)

Similarly, Rolle (2022) points out that his use of the term ‘STAMP marking’ “has the potential to show a lack of areal clustering within the Macro-Sudan Belt, which would warrant rejecting

³Note here that the morphological segmentation was added by Güldemann, with the original source having *Akad mə soób bīyé* with no glosses (Redden 1979, 56).

STAMPs as a defining feature of this macro-area” (Rolle 2022, 174). As a permissive definition of ‘STAMP morph’ loses the insight into the areal distribution of fused forms found in the Macro-Sudan Belt, I propose that the more restrictive definition is kept and thus not applied to NWB languages, unless there is clear evidence for fusional morphology, i.e., a single morph expressing multiple STAMP features. Moreover, it needs to be evaluated as to whether a given source provides good motivation for the orthographic wordhood choices made before these are taken as evidence for areal generalizations regarding STAMP material being separate from the main verb.

As a final note, Grimm (2025) extends the term ‘STAMP morpheme’ to six NWB languages from zone A, based on tonal alternations on segmental forms encoding TAMP. I discuss in Sections 4.4 and 4.7 how some of these may be considered as agglutinative.

3.4 Orthographic wordhood

We have seen that discussions of analyticity, split predication, and the identification of STAMP morphs relate to the identification of separate words. In transcribing NWB languages in Roman orthographic systems, it is necessary to decide where to use whitespace in order to mark word boundaries, meaning that sources contain implicit analyses of wordhood boundaries. These orthographic word boundaries may vary between authors based both on their interpretation of the linguistic evidence for bound versus unbound word forms as well as arbitrary factors such as personal preference or research tradition. Indeed, Nurse (2008) highlights that sources for the NWB languages in particular vary considerably in orthographic wordhood demarcations:

The phrase ‘have a tendency to’ [use analytic strategies] is used advisedly, partly because they don’t all behave in the same way, partly because it is necessary to distinguish morphological analysis from writing conventions. Francophone countries in West Africa have a strong francographic convention to write as separate words what would be written as one word in the anglographic tradition. (Nurse 2008, 169)

Besides this influence of francophone versus anglophone orthographic conventions, a case can be made for a difference in practice between scholars working in the Bantuist tradition and scholars working on non-Bantu Niger-Congo languages from other traditions: due to the large number and geographical spread of Bantu languages, a Bantuist tradition has developed which has its own notational conventions. Overrepresentation of Eastern/Southwestern languages may bias analyses of Northwestern languages towards synthetic analyses, as discussed above regarding Meeussen’s reconstruction in Table 2.

Some sources provide other non-linguistic justifications for wordhood decisions. Friesen (2002), for example, contrasts with Kuperus (1985) in writing Oroko (A11) [bdu] pre-stem material as separate from the verb stem, which he advocates for the following reasons: (i) to follow a precedent set by Duala (A24) [dua]; (ii) to appear more familiar to readers literate in English; and (iii) due to an idea that longer words are harder to read, with synthetic verb forms suggested to be “inordinately long” (Friesen 2002, 64–65, 95). However, Friesen notes explicitly that phonetic and phonological criteria do not support such a separation, meaning that this orthographic wordhood convention proposed for the community orthography does not reflect phonological wordhood (Friesen 2002, 95, 98–99).

Orthographic wordhood is therefore not fully reliable as a proxy to linguistic boundedness. While this is a perennial problem cross-linguistically, the case is particularly striking in NWB/Bantoid languages, as they appear to be in intermediate stages between highly synthetic Narrow

Bantu verb forms and highly analytic West African Niger-Congo patterns (Hyman 2004). It is therefore pertinent to examine the justifications provided in the literature for the orthographic wordhood divisions made, which I will do in Section 5 of this paper.

3.5 Auxiliary verb constructions and quasi-/semi-auxiliaries

A final point of terminological confusion is the use of the terms ‘auxiliary’, ‘quasi-auxiliary’, and ‘semi-auxiliary’ and the relation between these and the auxiliary verb constructions of the type found in Narrow Bantu.

The use of ‘auxiliary’ common to descriptions of NWB languages refers to the sequence of functional elements that appear before the verb stem and encode STAMP features, i.e., the pre-stem complex (see Section 3.1). These elements do not necessarily have to derive from verbs (although they regularly do via V>AUX>TAM grammaticalization; Heine and Reh 1984). Such auxiliaries can appear with a single lexical verb, which is what contributes the core semantic meaning to the predicate, and therefore the constructions can be seen as simplex predicates.

These simplex predicates can be differentiated from auxiliary verb constructions which involve a main verb with one or more verbs co-occurring with it in an auxiliary relation (Anderson 2006). For this reason, the latter are also known as ‘multi-verb constructions’ (e.g., Brown 2021, 88–89) and are also discussed in terms of ‘complex predicates’ (e.g., Van de Velde 2008, 331–343) and ‘complex tenses’ (e.g., Kerr 2024c, 112–14). The Basaá example in (15) shows a multi-verb construction, where *-tìϕ* ‘conclude, finish’ is analysed as an auxiliary verb that co-occurs with the main verb *l̥* ‘come’, the latter appearing without a SM. In the Tunen example (16), habituality is expressed with the auxiliary verb *bá* ‘be’ and the main verb *ǎndók* ‘buy’, each appearing with a SM.

- (15) *Màlér à βí-tìϕ l̥.*
 1.teacher SM1 PST2-finish come
 ‘The teacher had just arrived.’ (Basaá (A43) [bas]; Makasso 2023, 109)

- (16) *Maliá a bá-aka a belama betótó ǎndók.*
 /Maliá a bá-aka a be-lama be-tótó ǎndók-aka/
 1.Maria SM.1 be-DUR SM.1 8-vegetable 8-young buy-DUR
 ‘Maria (regularly) buys fresh vegetables.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu]; Kerr 2024c, 112)

For reasons of space, I restrict myself to the discussion of simplex Aux V constructions in this article, rather than also discussing different types of complex predicates. In other words, I investigate the extent of analyticity in the canonical expression of simplex predicates in NWB.

However, as verbal affixes may develop from verbs through cycles of V>AUX>TAM grammaticalization, the analytical distinction between pre-stem material being an auxiliary verb as part of a complex predicate versus a grammaticalized marker within a simplex predicate is not clear-cut. This is particularly relevant in assessing the analysis of TAM markers and directional markers, which are sometimes treated as affixes/clitics and sometimes as auxiliary verbs within auxiliary verb constructions. Some authors propose an intermediate stage. For example, Van de Velde (2008) uses the term ‘quasi-auxiliary’ to refer to the pre-stem element that may be followed by a non-finite form in Eton, and Grimm (2021) uses the term ‘semi-auxiliary’ for similarly intermediate forms in Gyeli, such as the aspectual semi-auxiliary *sile* ‘finish’ in (17).

(17) *Nà wè sɪlé wòm̀bè̀lè̀?*

nà wɛ sɪlɛ-H wòm̀bɛlɛ
Q 2SG.PST1 finish-R sweep

‘Have you finished sweeping?’

(Gyeli (A801) [gyi]; (Grimm 2021, 425)

These terms refer to material that is in an intermediate stage of V>AUX>TAM development, for example in still having some lexical meaning while also being able to combine with a non-finite main verb. Languages also differ here in whether the main verb is explicitly marked as non-finite: while Eton and Gyeli have non-finite marking (see Section 5.4), in languages like Tunen and Basaá, the verb is a bare form with no additional marking (e.g., (15)).

Having reviewed the necessary terminology, I turn now to consider the internal structure of pre-stem complexes across NWB languages, i.e., the component elements and their respective order.

4 The internal structure of NWB pre-stem complexes

4.1 Schema of NWB pre-stem complexes

NWB pre-stem complexes have a strict order of segmental material, as shown in (18) below.⁴

(18) **Generalized schema of segmental material in NWB pre-stem complexes**

SM- {NEG1-} TAM- {NEG2-} -DIR-PRN

Here, there is variation in which elements may be found in a given utterance (e.g., the negation slots are only filled in negative clauses) and between languages (e.g., there is variation in whether the subject marker (SM) is obligatory, and whether the subject pronoun (PRN) occurs). However, the elements that occur are found in the order of this general template. This order closely matches the one found in synthetic Bantu verb forms, as seen in Table 2 above, corresponding to the initial, post-initial, and pre-radical slots within Meeussen’s (1967) template.

The schema in (18) represents segmental material. One point of complexity is that TAMP features may be expressed suprasegmentally via tonal alternations. I come back to this in Section 4.7, after first discussing each segmental slot.

4.2 The SM slot

The SM slot is the slot for the subject marker, i.e., subject indexation. The treatment of the SM as a prefix, a (pro)clitic, or a pronoun is often not motivated in descriptions (Grimm 2025b, 6, fn. 9). In this paper I use the term ‘SM marker’ as a general term, following common practice within Bantu linguistics. There is variation between NWB languages as to whether this SM is always present or only found when there is no lexical subject (i.e., no noun phrase subject). For example, non-dislocated lexical subjects can co-occur with SMs in Tunen (19).⁵

⁴ This is the maximal schema for segmental material; the inclusion of DIR and PRN is debatable, as I will discuss in Sections 4.5 and 4.6 respectively.

⁵ These data from present-day Tunen differ from the data in Dugast (1971, 1975), where non-dislocated subjects do not co-occur with SMs, as observed in Kerr (2024c, 363–365).

(19) *Elisabete a ná məkóló bénókə.*

/elisabete a ná mə-kóló bé-nókə/
 1.Elizabeth SM.1 PST2 3-foot MID-break

‘Elizabeth broke her foot.’

(Tunen [A44] [tvu]; own data)

However, in other languages, the SM only appears when there is no lexical subject. For example, Bébiné (2019, 388) writes that it is ungrammatical to have both a lexical subject and the SM in Nuasúe (A462A) [yav], with no SM found if a lexical subject is present in the same prosodic domain. This is illustrated in (20), where a class 1 SM is used for the 3rd person singular in the absence of a nominal subject, while no SM is used in example (21) where the 3rd person singular subject *Yésús* ‘Jesus’ appears.

(20) *òsòólò ókwàsìkòttí.*

ò-sàà-ól á= kò-àsì=-kòt-ít
 S3S-P2-come.SGL.SIT LOC=INF-VTF =work-SGL.MOT

‘He came to work in the morning.’

(Nuasúe (A462A) [yav]; (Bébiné 2019, 525)

(21) *Yésús mó¹ólíní Násálèt.*

Yésús má-ól-[-Ø-m-ə]H Násálèt
 Jesus P2-come-[SGL-APPL-VF]PFT Nazareth

‘Jesus came from Nazareth.’

(Nuasúe (A462A) [yav]; (Bébiné 2019, 372)

When the SM co-occurs with a non-dislocated nominal subject, it can be considered as agreement. When it appears by itself, it can be considered as a pronoun. The variation could be seen as NWB languages showing different stages of the common evolution of pronominal subject markers into agreement markers; see Creissels (2006, 44–45) for further discussion.

For some languages, class 1/2 (i.e., 3rd person human) SMs behave differently, in that they may be omitted while other SMs are required (see, e.g., Heath 2003, 344 for Makaa). In Kwakum (A91) [kwu], SMs are optional with plural noun phrases and disallowed after singular ones (Njantcho Kouagang 2018, 274). A final type of variation in subject indexation observed in zone A languages is seen regarding the presence of a subject pronoun in the PRN slot, which I return to in Section 4.6.

4.3 The NEG slots

The NEG slots are slots in which segmental negation markers appear. There is a large amount of variation in where negation is expressed, both in terms of the position of negative markers within the pre-stem complex and in terms of the use of negation markers in other positions, such as clause-final negation markers (which may be the sole marker of negation or may co-occur with pre-stem negation marking). In some languages (e.g., Londo (A11) [bdu] – Kuperus 1985, 146–148; Tunen – Mous 2003; Kerr 2024c), NEG1/NEG2 is the only position for segmental negation markers; in other languages, negation may also be expressed using markers outside of the pre-stem complex, e.g., via a final negative marker that appears after the verb. As this paper’s focus is on the pre-stem complex, I do not consider these alternative negative strategies

here. I also exclude the pre-initial negation marker found in languages like Nsong (B85d) [soo] from discussion (which is incidentally a less common negation strategy in that language).⁶

Restricting ourselves to consideration of where negation is expressed within the pre-stem complex, negative markers can be found directly before TAM marking (NEG1) or directly after it (NEG2). The segmental form and the tone of the negative marker may vary depending on the TAM context (see, e.g., Grimm 2025, 365 for Gyeli (A801) [gyi]), but the position with respect to other elements of the pre-stem complex is consistent. Example (31) below illustrates negation via the NEG1 slot. In other languages, negation follows the tense marker, marked in the NEG2 slot. For example, Hedinger (2008) shows the negative marker as following rather than preceding the tense marker in Akoose (A15C), and Kwakum also has negation following the tense marker (along with a negative marker that appears after the verb stem) (22).

(22) *Àfèéwéédzi búpà.*

/à-fèéL-wééL-dziH búpà/

3SG-FUT1-NEG-eat 1.meat

‘He will not eat meat.’

(Kwakum (A91) [kwu]; Njantcho Kouagang and Van de Velde 2019, 411)

4.4 The TAM slot

NWB languages are known for having a large number of tenses, often with three or four past tense distinctions, present tense, and multiple future tenses (Nurse 2008). The TAM slot in the pre-stem complex refers to the position in which segmental tense markers (TMs) are found; aspect and mood are typically marked by other strategies (although see Guarisma 2003 for the argument that aspect is more relevant than tense for the pre-stem complex in Bafia). TMs appear consistently after subject indexation, matching the order found in synthetic Bantu verb forms (cf. (5)–(6)).

It should be stated that the TAM slot is far from being the sole marker of TAMP information, as TAMP is reflected by a complex interplay of tonal changes in other parts of the pre-stem complex (such as the subject marker; Grimm 2025) and the main lexical verb, with NWB languages matching other Bantu languages in using melodic tone on verb stems to encode this inflectional information (Odden and Bickmore, 2014). Gyeli (A801) [gyi] is exceptional in that there are no segmental TMs at all (Grimm 2021, 370), with tonal changes therefore taking on a higher functional load of tense marking (Grimm 2022, 2025b). At the same time, Gyeli suprasegmental markers (e.g., the present tense high tone -H ‘PRS’ in (23)) appear in the same position as segmental TMs in other NWB languages, namely after the SM. This is consistent with the idea of the tone being preserved after the loss of segmental material in the TAM slot (which is still visible in the very closely-related language Kwasio (A81); cf. Grimm 2022, 487, 2025b, 24).

⁶ Note also that Koni Muluwa and Bostoen (2019) present Nsong verbs as synthetic, with the negation markers treated as verbal prefixes and written as part of the same orthographic word as the main verb. Pre-initial negation marking may also be considered for zone A languages if tonal markers are included in the schema, as I return to in Section 4.7.

(23) *Mé dè.*

/mɛ-H dè/

1SG-PRS eat

‘I eat.’

(Gyeli (A801) [gyi]; (Grimm 2021, 370))

In many cases, the interaction between tone and tense marking presents challenges for glossing, resulting in different glossing practices. There is also variation in whether TMs are analysed as affixes, auxiliaries, or semi/quasi-auxiliaries. I use ‘tense marker’ as a general term.

4.5 The DIR slot

The DIR slot refers to markers of directionality. These are sometimes referred to as ‘auxiliaries’ or ‘semi-auxiliaries’ and sometimes treated as affixes or clitics. In Nomaandé, there is a general directional marker *ka* (24). In other languages, there are multiple directional markers, with a distinct anadative (hither) marker and venitive (thither) marker, e.g., Tunen *nda* ‘VEN’ and *ka* ‘AND’ (25).⁷

(24) a. *Ba-násé ḡá ka bó tǎkɔna əhəníá.*
 2-child PRS DIR PRN.SBJ.2 play DEM.LOC.DIST
 ‘The children go to play over there.’

b. *Ba-násé ḡá ka bó tǎkɔna aaha.*
 2-child PRS DIR PRN.SBJ.2 play DEM.LOC.PROX
 ‘The children come to play over here.’ (Nomaandé (A46) [lem], own data)

(25) Context: You went to visit the house, and are now close by.

a. *Mi nú ndə húl(ə) ú miím.*
 /mɛ nó nda húlə ɔ miímə/
 SM.1SG PST1 VEN come_from PREP 9.house
 ‘I just made a visit to the house (over here).’

Context: You went to visit the house, and are now far away from it.

b. *Mi nú kə húl(ə) ú miím.*
 /mɛ nó ka húlə ɔ miímə/
 SM.1SG PST1 AND come_from PREP 9.house
 ‘I just made a visit to the house (over there).’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu], own data)

Directional markers are commonly found with a main lexical motion verb and generally derive historically from motion verbs via V>AUX grammaticalization. Eton has the forms *zù* and *ke*, which Van de Velde (2008) treats as ‘quasi-auxiliaries’ (26). Similarly, Grimm (2021, 366) treats the Gyeli form *kè* ‘go’ as a “non-grammaticalized semi-auxiliary”, which encodes that the action took place at another location.

⁷ Here, the Tunen directional markers are realized in +ATR form due to regressive vowel harmony from the following +ATR verb *húlə* ‘come from’. I will come back to this vowel harmony process in Section 5.3 as a potential diagnostic of phonological wordhood. Parentheses around the end of the verb indicate vowel elision in fast speech.

(26) a. *Dgwàn yě yô ìngázû bá vá.*

|ngòn j-ě jò ì-ngá-zù L-bá vǎ|
 [9]daughter IX-her IX.SUB IX-RP-VEN INF-marry here
 ‘It’s her daughter who came to marry here.’

(Eton (A71) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 418)

b. *Mǎnyáň wòbni ángákê bó nyòň ná: [...]*

|mòHnyǎň wòbni à-ngá-kê bǒ L-nyòň nâ|
 brother I-their I-RP-AND II.PPR INF-take CMP
 ‘Their brother went to take them and said: [...]’

(Eton (A71) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 143)

Often, directional markers can also occur as the main lexical verb (e.g., Redden 1979, 119 for Ewondo and Heath 2003, 245 for Makaa), supporting their analysis as instantiating V>AUX grammaticalization. While I indicate directional markers in the pre-stem complex, they may be treated as auxiliary verbs (or semi-auxiliaries/quasi-auxiliaries) in languages in which they are less grammaticalized.

In other Narrow Bantu languages, directional markers appear as prefixes in the same slot with respect to the other verbal elements, as seen in the Fwe example in (6) and further illustrated in the Chichewa example below, where *ká-* is glossed as DIR and analysed as a prefix as part of a synthetic verb form (27).

(27) *Anyani a-ku-ká-b-á mikánda.*

2-baboons 2SM-PRES-DIR-steal-FV 4-beads

‘The baboons are going to steal some beads.’

(Chichewa (N30) [nya]; Mchombo 2004, 28)

As with the NWB languages, directional markers in other Bantu languages can co-exist with cognate main verbs (e.g., Chichewa *-muka, -mka* ‘go’), showing that this V>AUX grammaticalization path is recurrent across Bantu and not unique to languages of the Northwest. What is different about NWB languages is that directional markers can be treated as unbound.

4.6 The PRN slot

Some Mbam Bantu languages are unusual in having a second slot for the expression of subject indexation, in the form of a PRN slot which appears after the other pre-stem elements and does not correspond to a slot in Meeussen’s synthetic verb template (Table 2). These PRN elements may or may not be considered as part of the pre-stem complex. They consist of a subject pronoun which is co-referential with the SM, as with *nú* in (28).

(28) *Nu ɲə nú bǎǎbǎ aamba.*

SM.2PL PRS PRN.SBJ.2PL PRN.OBJ.2 want

‘You (pl.) want them.’

(Nomaandé (A46) [lem]; Taylor 1999, §1.0)

Following a reviewer’s suggestion, I refer to this as the ‘double subject construction’, (cf. the use of ‘split subject construction’ in Kerr 2024b, 99, 261), on account of subject indexation being expressed in two places within the pre-stem complex. This double subject construction

was reported for Nomaandé (Taylor 1999; Wilkendorf 2001) and was previously considered unique to that language (Mous 2005, 412; Philippson 2022, 255). However, it is also found in the neighbouring language Tunen, albeit to a more limited extent: it is found in natural speech (Kerr 2024c, 2024b), as in example (29), where speakers report that it is optional.

(29) Context: “Because I knew it was his funeral today, I passed by.”

Me nó ka áme beleŋa bé- bí- bíúŋúnání, me nó bésuala [...]

/mɛ nó ka ámɛ bé-leŋa bé-úŋúnání mɛ
SM.1SG PST1 AND PRN.SBJ.1SG 8-clothes MID-change SM.1SG

nó bé-sáá-ala/
PST1 MID-wash-DIM

‘I went and got changed, I had a quick wash,’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu]; Kerr 2024b, 262)

This subject pronoun is presented in basic overviews of the Nomaandé TAM system (Taylor 1999; Wilkendorf 1986, 2001). In Tunen, it appears much less frequently, and is not mentioned in basic overviews (e.g., Mous 2003). The two languages also differ in the form of the subject pronoun: in Nomaandé, it is monosyllabic, while in Tunen it is generally disyllabic. The forms are given in Table 3, which shows that the PRN is formally distinct from the subject marker.

Table 3: Forms of the subject marker and subject pronoun in Nomaandé and Tunen, showing –ATR and +ATR forms, with <ə> used rather than <e> for [ə]. The data for Nomaandé are taken from Taylor (1999, §1.2) together with my own fieldnotes; the Tunen data are from Kerr (2024b) and my own fieldnotes.

	Nomaandé		Tunen	
	SM	PRN.SBJ	SM	PRN.SBJ
1SG	ɛ/i	mɛ/mi	mɛ/mi	ámɛ
2SG	ɔ/o	ɔ/o	ɔ/o	aŋɔ́á
1	ɔ/u	a/ə	a/ə	áyɛ
1PL	tɔ/tu	sɔ/su	tɔ/tu	ásu
2PL	nɔ/nu	nó/nu/nú	nɔ/nu	ánu
2	bá/bá	bá/bá/bó	bá/bá	ábu

While PRN could itself be considered as intervening material between the pre-stem complex and verb, in parallel with pre-stem object pronouns, it has also been analysed as bound to the rest of the pre-stem complex, which is why I include it in the general schema in (18). For example, Wilkendorf (1986) treats the SM, TM and PRN in Nomaandé as three morphemes that together comprise a “pronominal complex”, written as a single word in the examples in the appendix (e.g. (30)), with each element separated by a hyphen in the paradigmatic overview of the main text (Wilkendorf 1986, 67).

(30) *Tu-ŋe-sú* *bume.*

SM.1PL-PRS-PRN.SBJ.1PL hunt

‘We are hunting.’

(Nomaandé (A46) [lem], Wilkendorf 1986, 73, adapted)

On account of this wordhood representation, Nomaandé has been described as analysable as having TM and subject suffixes (Julien 2002, 222–223). Analysing the PRN as bound to the preceding pre-stem material is possible as all material that may intervene between auxiliaries and the main lexical verb follows the pronoun (as seen for the nominal object in (29)). The PRN does not have a parallel position within synthetic Bantu verb forms (Table 2). Instead, it may be a relic of former subject marking as part of an auxiliary verb construction.

4.7 Tone slots

While I have limited this overview to the order of segmental elements and how this parallels the order of elements found in synthetic Bantu verb forms, some authors describe additional slots for suprasegmental material. For example, Hedinger (2008) includes both a pre-initial and a final slot for tones in his description of Akoose (A15C) [bss] pre-stem complexes (which he analyses as prefixed to the verb stem), Kuperus (1985, 146–147) analyses Oroko H-toned subjunctive SMs in terms of a floating H tone in a pre-initial mood slot, and Beavon (1983) gives a non-linear representation of Koonzime (A842) [ozm], with both a segmental and a tonal tier.

Analyses differ as to whether tones are taken to be linearly before or after segmental material, versus analysed as co-occurring in the same slot (as in Grimm’s 2025 description of STAMP morphemes in NWB). In other cases, tone from neighbouring elements can affect the tone of another element. For example, the Tunen present tense marker ^H*ndɔ* has a floating H tone which docks onto the preceding tone-bearing unit (Kerr 2024b; Mous 2003). This results in underlyingly L-toned SMs appearing with a H tone in the present tense (31).⁸ However, if the example is negated, the floating H tone is realized on the NEG marker and the SM therefore surfaces with its underlying L tone (31b). This shows that the H tone can be treated as part of the TAM slot, rather than as portmanteau marking of SM+TAM in the SM slot, supporting the sequential analysis in (18).

(31) a. *Mé ndɔ many.*

/mɛ	^H ndɔ	many/
SM.1SG	PRS	know
‘I know.’		

b. *Mɛ lé ndɔ many.*

/mɛ	lɛ	^H ndɔ	many/
SM.1SG	NEG	PRS	know
‘I don’t know.’			

(Tunen (A44) [tvu]; own data)

Another complication is whether floating tones are considered morphemic (encoding STAMP features) or whether they function as boundary tones serving to mark the phonological phrasing of the verbal complex (as in Ibrahīm’s 2021 discussion of floating H tones as phrasal tones delineating intonational phrases in Makaa (A83) [mcp]; cf. Grimm 2022, 488–489 for arguments against a L% boundary tone analysis in Gyeli). Yet another issue is that not all descriptions take care to note tonal changes, often only transcribing surface tones without analysing

⁸ As pointed out by a reviewer, another point of variation in tonal analyses of NWB pre-stem material is whether material is treated as underlying L-toned or underlyingly toneless, receiving default L tone dependent on the surrounding material. Makasso et al. (2016) apply the latter type of analysis to pre-stem TMs in Basaá, assuming a ternary opposition between /H/, /L/ and /Ø/ tone bearing units, in contrast to the binary opposition between /H/ and /L/ described in Mous (2003) and Kerr (2024c) for Tunen.

the underlying tonal behaviour (see, e.g., Grimm 2025b, 26–27; Odden and Bickmore 2014, 12). General principles relevant for interpreting such forms are that tones survive longer than segmental material (and so tonal TMs may develop from previous segmental material) and material on the edges of the verb may have developed more recently than material closer to the stem, which is likely to be older.

5 The external structure of NWB pre-stem complexes

Having seen the internal structure of NWB auxiliary complexes in the previous section, we can turn now to their external structure, i.e., their relationship to the rest of the predicate. The goal of this section is to evaluate the accuracy of different orthographic wordhood conventions by considering syntactic and phonological wordhood tests, i.e., evidence for the pre-stem complex behaving as part of the same versus a separate syntactic and phonological word as the main verb.

5.1 Testing for a wordhood boundary

A battery of morphosyntactic and phonological constituency tests have been developed as part of the general linguistics literature on wordhood (Haspelmath 2011, 2015; Schiering et al. 2010; Tallman 2020, 2021; Tallman et al. 2024; Zingler 2020, i.a.). There is little consensus on which tests are most reliable or even whether all tests are valid – some authors for example only use morphosyntactic criteria, arguing that there is no strong evidence for a phonological word. Here, I report on the morphosyntactic and phonological justifications provided in the literature on NWB languages, with some further evidence from my own fieldwork data.

5.2 Morphosyntactic wordhood tests

5.2.1. *Non-interruptability*

One of the most widely used morphosyntactic wordhood tests – and often the only one that is explicitly mentioned in discussions of NWB languages – is non-interruptability (also known as ‘uninterruptability’). This test identifies a word on the basis of the inability of another word to interrupt its component parts: a word should not be able to be interrupted (with a small number of potential exceptions, such as expletive insertion in English; see, e.g., McCarthy 1982; Zingler 2024).

In NWB/Bantoid languages, pre-stem complexes and the verb can be interrupted by some objects and certain adverbials, as seen already for objects in (1)–(2) above. The ability for such material to intervene therefore provides evidence that there are multiple morphosyntactic words in these constructions, hence their frequent classification as split predicates (Section 3.3). I discuss the extent of interruption here.

5.2.1.1 Interruption by objects

Interruption of the pre-stem complex and the verb by full noun phrase objects has been considered to be a unique feature of Tunen (Dugast 1971; Mous 1997, 2003, 2005, 2014, i.a.). As Kerr (2024b, 2024a) shows, the canonical word order in Tunen is S-Aux-O-V-X, regardless of the TAM context, information-structural context, object type, or clause type. Moreover, ‘O’ here includes modified objects which are clearly syntactic phrases and not bound prefixes, as in the modified noun phrase example in (32), and both objects precede the verb in ditransitive constructions, as indicated in the additional line in (33).

- (32) Context: Your friend asks what happened at church. (thetic)

Motát a ná imbónu ye fəkin né Yəsəs ɔ Yerúsalem nəɣɔnak.

/mɔ-táta a ná ɛ-**mbónu** ye **fəkinə** **né**
1-pastor SM.1 PST2 9-news ASSOC.9 5.entrance ASSOC.5

Yəsəsu ɔ **Yerúsalem** nəɣɔnə-aka/

Jesus PREP Jerusalem tell-DUR

‘The pastor told the news of Jesus’ entrance into Jerusalem.’

(Tunen (A44) [tvu]; Kerr 2024b, 225)

- (33) Context: ‘What is the woman returning to the child?’ (term focus on theme object)

Muəndú á ndɔ mɔná imítá túmbi.

/mɔ-əndú a ^Hndɔ **mɔ-ná** **ɛ-mítá** túmbiə/
1-woman SM.1 PRS 1-child 9-calabash return

‘The woman returns [the calabash]_{FOC} to the child.’

(Tunen (A44) [tvu]; Kerr, 2024b, 221)

While Tunen is indeed the most extreme example of Aux-O-V word order in NWB, Aux-O-V order is found in particular TAM or information-structural contexts in several other surrounding languages (Kerr 2024b, 2024c; Mous 2014). Aux-O-V with nominal objects is found for some TAM contexts in Nyokon (A45) [nvo], with the alternate order Aux-V-O found in other TAM contexts. Examples (34)–(35) illustrate this TAM-dependent Aux-O-V/Aux-V-O alternation; Aux-O-V order is used in the subjunctive and Aux-V-O order in the present continuous (see Kerr 2024a; Mous 2022 for more details).

- (34) *M̃ mir mɔ.*
1SG:SBJV wine drink(:SBJV)

‘I should drink wine.’

(Nyokon (A45) [nvo]; Mous 2022, 12)

- (35) *M̃ nə swə ákín.*
/m̃ nə swə\ LH **ákín/**
1SG PROG wash/PR calabash

‘I am washing the calabash.’

(Nyokon (A45) [nvo]; Mous 2022, 18)

Aux-O-V order was also found in preliminary fieldwork on Atomb (also known as ‘Tuotomb’; A461 [tff]), an endangered Bantu language closely related to Nyokon and spoken by <300 speakers in the village of Boneck, which borders Tunen- and Yambasa-speaking regions in the Mbam-et-Inoubou department of central Cameroon. As shown below, modified noun phrase objects can appear between the pre-stem material and the lexical verb (35a), although objects follow the verb in the present continuous tense, which is formed by the auxiliary verb *naŋ* ‘be’ and an infinitival verb form (35b).⁹

⁹ While there is no published work on Atomb grammar, there is an unpublished PhD thesis by Dihenou Djahappi (2021). Dihenou Djahappi considers Atomb to have SVO word order, but this is based on treating examples like (36) as SVO, without considering the infinitival marker or the SOV found in other TAM contexts.

(36) Context: You went to the shop and bought various things.

a. *Tám mám pɛ-há káf-ak.*
 SM.1SG.PST PRN.POSS.1SG 8-thing share-DUR
 ‘I shared my purchases.’

b. *Mé naŋ ɔ-káf mám pɛ-ha.*
 SM.1SG:H COP INF-share PRN.POSS.1SG 8-thing
 ‘I am sharing my purchases.’

(Atomb (A461) [tff]; own data)

Besides these NWB languages from the Mbam subgroup, TAM-based Aux-O-V/Aux-V-O word order alternations are also found in Wide Bantu/Bantoid languages such as Tikar (Stanley 1997), as well as in languages from West Africa (although many of those are likely to be due to independent developments; Creissels 2005; Sande et al. 2019; Kerr 2024c).

Other NWB languages show Aux-O-V in the sense of pronominal objects occurring pre-verbally. Such a pattern was seen already for Eton in (2): pronominal objects precede the verb, while nominal objects are post-verbal. This same pattern of Aux-O_{PRN}-V/Aux-V-O_{DP} is found in various languages of Bantu zone A and Bantoid.¹⁰ Here, the pre-stem position of the object pronoun mirrors the pre-stem position of object markers (OMs) in Narrow Bantu, which has been used to support a univerbation account (Güldemann 2022; cf. Van de Velde and Idiatov 2025 for some complications).

One nuance here is that given objects (i.e., objects whose referents are easily retrievable in the discourse context) can be dropped completely (i.e., zero-expressed) in some NWB/Bantoid languages, meaning that object pronouns may have a low textual frequency (see, e.g., Van de Velde 2008, 300–301 for Eton; Kerr 2024b, 196–198, 2025, 109–111 for Tunen; Voll 2017: 270, 274 for the Grassfields Bantu language Mundabli). This lowers the number of cases in which the pre-stem complex and verb will be interrupted. However, the fact that pronominal objects are pronounced in pre-verbal position in these languages when they are present shows that Aux and V can be interrupted, providing evidence against a synthetic analysis in these cases.

One further analytical nuance is whether the pre-verbal object pronouns are free forms or bound to the verb. The pronouns are almost always written as separate orthographic words, and zone A languages are not generally considered to have object markers (although see Musada 1996, 116–122; Nzang-Bie 1989, 212–213; Rekanga 1989, 136–137 for a synthetic presentation of verb forms in Tuki (A601) [bag], Mmala (A62) [mmu], and Gunu (A62) [yas] respectively, with object pronouns treated as ‘infixes’).¹¹ Some evidence in favour of treating pre-verbal objects as unbound is that they can be prosodically heavy, as seen in the Nomaandé example (28) above and further illustrated in (37)–(38) below, where the theme object pronoun is disyllabic and trimoraic.¹²

¹⁰ This is not to say that all object pronouns are pre-verbal in NWB languages. Gyeli for example has Aux-V-O_{DP}/Aux-V-O_{PRN} word order (see, e.g., Grimm 2021, 458) and post-final and post-verbal object pronouns are reported by Nurse (2008, 49) for zones B, C, D, and H20–30. See also Güldemann (2011, 125–126) on variation between pre-verbal and post-verbal object pronouns dependent on what pre-stem material is present.

¹¹ Note here that all three sources were written following the same scholarly tradition, all being theses supervised by Claire Grégoire at the Université Libre Bruxelles / Royal Museum for Central Africa in Tervuren. The term ‘infix’ was used in early work for what would now be referred to as a prefixal object marker (see, e.g., Polak 1986, who notes that such forms are very rare in zone A).

¹² Note here that Nomaandé has a phonological distinction between long and short vowels (Boyd 2015, 43).

- (37) Context: ‘Did you find these three chickens?’ (NB: *εκωκέ* ‘chickens’ = class 10)
Έε, í mǝ mí tʃítʃi pǝŋ.
 /έε έ ma mé tʃítʃi pǝŋ/
 yes SM.1SG PST0 PRN.SBJ.1SG PRN.OBJ.10 find
 ‘Yes, I found them.’ (Nomaandé (A46) [lem]; own data)

- (38) *U ŋe mí wuúci tǝŋie.*
 3s p3 1s 3s show.
 ‘He showed it to me.’ (Nomaandé (A46) [lem]; Wilkendorf 2001, 9)

In sum, then, various NWB languages allow pre-stem material to be separated from the verb by nominal or pronominal objects, with multiple pre-verbal objects possible in ditransitive constructions (e.g., (1), (38)). The intervening nominal objects in particular show clear evidence for a morphosyntactic word boundary between the pre-stem complex and the main verb; for intervening pronouns, it should be considered whether these are bound or unbound forms.

5.2.1.2 Interruptability by adverbials

Interruptability is not just limited to objects. Pre-stem material may also be separated from the verb by certain adverbials, as with *cǝŋa* ‘first’ in (39).

- (39) *Tǝ ŋa cǝŋa esú súete.*
 we p3 first we left
 ‘We left first.’ (Nomaandé (A46) [lem]; Taylor, 1999, §1.0)

While Kerr (2024b) classifies Tunen as V-Adv, on account of this being the canonical position for adverbials, new fieldwork data show that a limited class of adverbials occupies the same pre-verbal position in Tunen as in Nomaandé (40). Unlike in Nomaandé, pre-verbal adverbials may co-occur with pre-verbal nominal objects, in which case the adverb is accepted either before or after the object (41).¹³

- (40) *Kalébe a ná hǝtú hǝnyǝ.*
 /kalébe a ná hǝtú hǝnyǝ/
 1.Caleb SM.1 PST2 early wake
 ‘Caleb woke up early.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu]; own data)

- (41) *Emalamanda yé ná {hǝtú} Kalébe {hǝtú} hunyíǝ.*
 /ε-malamanda yé ná {hǝtú} kalébe {hǝtú} hunyíǝ/
 7-thunder SM.7 PST2 quickly 1.Caleb quickly wake.CAUS
 ‘The thunder made Caleb wake up early.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu]; own data)

Adverbial interruption is also used as motivation for an analytic analysis of certain TAM constructions in Van de Velde (2008)’s grammar of Eton, which discusses these in terms of

¹³ These items were elicited using the discourse contexts in the questionnaire on the noncausal/causal alternation developed by Dom et al. (2021).

‘quasi-auxiliaries’, as in (42), where the adverbial/quasi-auxiliary *pwágó* ‘really’ occurs between the pre-stem material and the main lexical verb *yálnà* ‘answer’.

(42) *Àvúl pwágó mà yálnà.*

à-H-vúl-H	póǵá	mà	L-jálnà
I-PST-do.quickly-NF	really	1SG.NPPR	INF-answer

‘He really answered me quickly.’

(Eton (A71) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 331)

Wilkendorf (2001, 18) hypothesizes that the Nomaandé pre-verbal adverbials developed recently from verbs (i.e., V>Adv) existing as relics of previous serial verb constructions. This would explain their different position from other adverbials (which are generally in V-Adv order). Although not all adverbials have clear verbal sources, some do, e.g., *sike* ‘suddenly’ < *o-sike* ‘to remain’ (Wilkendorf 2001, 18).

5.2.2 Other morphosyntactic wordhood tests

While the general linguistics literature includes other tests for morphosyntactic wordhood besides non-interruptability – such as the coordination, ellipsis, and fragment tests – it is rare for these to be discussed in the literature on NWB languages. Although coordination is discussed in grammars, the examples provided involve the conjunction of entire clauses, which is found in NWB languages with or without overt coordinators (see, e.g., Guarisma 2003, 321 for Bafia). Such data only show that clauses as a whole are constituents, rather than identifying their internal constituency. What would be relevant for the current discussion about analyticity would be to test whether two verbs can be conjoined together without pre-stem material, i.e., [Aux [V CONJ V]], which would provide evidence for a morphosyntactic separation between Aux and V. I am not aware of any examples of such lower-level coordination in the literature on NWB languages.

Similarly, ellipsis (i.e., the deletion of material) is generally thought to be restricted to constituents and is therefore used in the general linguistics literature as another test for syntactic constituency, but I am not aware of any examples of data applying this to NWB verbs.

In terms of the fragment test – also termed the ‘minimal free form’, ‘minimum free form’, or ‘minimal free occurrence’ test (see, e.g., Auderset et al. 2024) – several sources state that the imperative verb is the minimal free form, but I ignore this here as it does not help diagnose the relationship between pre-stem material and the main verb in the indicative and subjunctive moods. Looking then at indicatives, it is common for [Aux V] to appear by itself, as seen in answers to questions (43a). In contrast, it is not possible for pre-stem material to be omitted here (43b–c).

(43) Context: ‘What did Chantelle do this morning?’ (subject and tense = given)

a. *A n(á) éfěnye taleak.*

/a n(á)	ε-fěnye	talea-aka/
SM.1 PST2	7-couscous	cook-DUR

‘She [cooked couscous]_{FOC}.’

b. **Éfěnye taleak.*

c. **N(á) éfěnye taleak.*

(Tunen (A44) [tvu]; own data)

These data from Tunen show that [Aux V] acts as a constituent, as answer (43a) can stand alone, but they do not provide evidence for the verb stem or verb phrase as a subconstituent, as these smaller parts cannot stand alone (43b–c).

In sum, then, there is very little work on morphosyntactic wordhood diagnostics in NWB languages besides non-interruptability. The scarce data available do not provide any further evidence for Aux and V as syntactically separate, as Aux and V group together, even in languages such as Tunen where we saw in Section 5.2.1 that Aux and V can be interrupted by other material.

5.3 Phonological wordhood tests

Having seen that interruptability is the main morphosyntactic criterion used to motivate an analytic treatment of pre-stem material in NWB, I turn now to consider what phonological justifications have been made to support wordhood analyses, starting with vowel harmony, which is explicitly discussed in some authors' presentation of orthographic wordhood decisions for NWB languages.

5.3.1 Vowel harmony

Although ATR harmony is not common to Bantu languages and is instead more common in non-Bantu languages of West Africa (Rolle et al. 2017), some languages from Bantu zone A have ATR systems, including many from the Mbam subgroup (A40/A60), in which ATR harmony interacts with vowel height harmony and rounding harmony (Boyd 2015). The behaviour of pre-stem material with respect to vowel harmony is therefore often used as a diagnostic of phonological constituency in these languages. Here, the logic is that pre-stem complexes should harmonise if they are part of the same phonological word as the main verb.

In Bébiné's (2019) analysis of the Mbam Bantu language Nuasúε (A462A) [yav], vowel harmony is taken to be the criterion *par excellence* for determining phonological wordhood (Bébiné 2019, 74), which Bébiné in turn takes as the criterion to follow when deciding on orthographic wordhood (Bébiné 2019, 104). Vowel harmony applies regressively from the main verb throughout the pre-stem material, and so he writes Nuasúε verb forms synthetically. Boyd (2015) similarly privileges phonological criteria, including vowel harmony, for deciding upon orthographic wordhood in the 10 Mbam languages of her study (Ginger Boyd, p.c.).

There is some variation in the data as to whether ATR harmony applies between the verb and the pre-stem material. For Iyasa (A33a) [yas], pre-stem material does not harmonise (Brown 2021, 44–45), which can be taken as evidence of it belonging to a separate phonological constituent (note however that Brown writes pre-stem material as prefixed to the verb). For Nomaandé, pre-stem material always harmonises, as seen in e.g. (38) (cf. Table 3), indicating phrasing together with the verb despite being written separately in the orthography. For Tunen, ATR harmony of pre-stem material has been reported to be possible but not obligatory (Bancel 1991). Fieldwork results confirm this, as shown in the intransitive example (44) (see also (25)), where boldface indicates vowels from the +ATR set ([i ə u o]) and unbolded forms indicate –ATR ones ([ε a ɔ]).

- (44) a. *Mε nó nda húlǎ.*
 b. *Mi nó ndǎ húlǎ.*
 /mε nó nda húlǎ/
 SM.1SG PST1 VEN come_from
 ‘I came over here.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu], own data)

Harmonising cases like (44b) could be taken as evidence for the pre-stem complex and the verb being part of the same word. However, ATR harmony can also be triggered on the pre-stem complex in Tunen when a +ATR object intervenes (a –ATR object blocks harmony) (45). This phenomenon is independent of the ATR value of the verb, as shown by the fact that the +ATR object can trigger harmony on the pre-stem complex in (46) even though the main verb *ǎnd* ‘buy’ is –ATR.

- (45) *Mi ndu mǎlukǎ hikǎkia embát.*
 /mε ^Hndǎ ma-lukǎ hikǎkia embáta/
 SM.1SG PRS 6-wine like.DUR excessively
 ‘I really love palmwine.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu], own data)

- (46) *Mi ná mǎlukǎ ǎnd.*
 /mε ná ma-lukǎ ǎndǎ/
 SM.1SG PST2 6-wine buy
 ‘I bought palmwine.’ (Tunen (A44) [tvu], own data)

While I leave a more detailed account to other work, the basic observation is that Tunen pre-stem material can harmonise with any +ATR element immediately following it, regardless of its morphosyntactic status, which suggests that vowel harmony does not match (morphosyntactic) constituency. We therefore see variation between languages as to the robustness of vowel harmony as a test for wordhood, potentially due to ongoing changes in predicate structure (cf. Boyd 2015, 375–376) or to there being vowel harmony processes that operate at a larger level of constituency, e.g., the phonological phrase (cf. Bancel 1991 for the idea of multiple different vowel harmony processes applying in Tunen).

5.3.2 Other phonological wordhood tests

Few authors explicitly discuss other phonological criteria for treating pre-stem material as synthetic or analytic. One exception relates to phonological effects sensitive to stem boundaries. For example, Van de Velde (2008) shows that Eton consonants differ in realization in stem-initial position; Hyman (2003, 259–260) and Makasso (2023, 34–36) describe similar spirantization of non-stem-initial consonants in Basaá. For example, /t/ can only appear stem-initially in lexical stems in Eton, appearing as /d/ elsewhere, which surfaces as [r] in affixes. While /t/ is found for present tense marking, supporting its treatment as an auxiliary, the Southern dialect has [r], indicating reanalysis as a prefix as part of a synthetic verb form (Van de Velde and Idiatov 2025, 183–184). Other sources similarly report phonological processes that are sensitive to morphosyntactic position, i.e., sensitive to material’s status as affixal, a clitic, or a separate word. While generally not stated explicitly, some authors seem to use such rules as justification for their orthographic wordhood decisions. See for example Rekanga (1989,

46–62) for the presentation of various phonological processes in Gunu as sensitive to whether there is a stem or word boundary.

Stem-initial prominence effects arguably show evidence for a boundary between the start of the verb and the preceding material. However, this does not necessarily have to be interpreted as a word boundary, as a parallel constituent boundary exists below the word level in Narrow Bantu languages, where certain phonological effects are restricted to the so-called ‘macro-stem’, consisting of the object marker and verb base to the exclusion of pre-stem material (Myers 1990, 1995; Hyman 1998). Still, stem-initial prominence effects appear to be stronger in NWB languages (including zone B languages; see, e.g., Paulian 1975 for Teke (B77) [kkw]) than in other Bantu languages (see, e.g., Lionnet and Hyman 2018, 651–662; Hyman et al. 2019, 196–198).

Other possibly applicable phonological criteria involve tonal phenomena, such as the reset of tonal downstep and the domain of tone spread, in addition to evidence for prosodic phrasing. In the next subsection I will return to the use of L-toned non-finite marking and link tones in Eton and Gyeli. Downdrift is reported for the level of the clause (see, e.g., Guarisma 2003, 312 for Bafia), and therefore does not tell us about smaller phonological constituents. For downstep, Hamlaoui and Makasso (2019) write that floating L tones trigger downstep on following H material in Basaá, a process they argue is found within the domains of prosodic words, phonological phrases, and intonational phrases, and can be used as a diagnostic of recursive phonological constituency. However, their discussions focus on downstep between the verb and following material, and as such do not bear on the current question of the status of pre-stem material.

When applying tonal tests in fieldwork on the Mbam languages, pre-stem material was generally phrased together with the main verb. For example, the third-degree past tense in Tunen is marked by *ka* PST3 in main clauses and ^L*ná* PST3.REL in dependent clauses (Kerr 2024c, 110). The floating low tone of the ^L*ná* PST3.REL TM triggers non-automatic downstep, with the H tone realized at a mid pitch level. Subsequent H tones of a H-toned following verb are realized at the same mid height, with the pitch not resetting until afterwards (47).

(47) *Ǿmbáná á bá ^Lná háǵíníá ǾwónǾ naáneǵol.*

/Ǿ-mbáná	á	bá	^L ná	háǵíníá	Ǿ-wónǾ	naáneǵola/
3-knife	COP	SM.2	PST3.REL	decide	INF-buy	yesterday

‘It was [a knife]_{FOC} that they decided to buy yesterday.’ (Tunen (A44), own data)

Here, the fact that the downstepped pitch height continues from the TM throughout the lexical verb could be taken as evidence for synthetic rather than analytic predicate structure, as in Dugast’s transcriptions (see (7)). In any case, it does not show any phonological separation between the pre-stem material and the main verb.

We therefore see that while some phonological processes indicate analytic structures due to stem-initial effects, other phonological tests such as vowel harmony and downstep show that pre-stem material is phrased together with the verb stem. This conjoined phonological phrasing runs contrary to the expectation of pre-stem material being in a separate phonological word from the verb in a split predicate structure (Güldemann 2011).

While the conclusion could be that these NWB predicates are actually synthetic, it is likely that these phonological processes apply to a larger constituent than the word, such as the phonological phrase, and therefore are not diagnostic of word-level constituency. This point factors into the broader theoretical debate about the validity of phonological ‘wordhood’ diagnostics

and the domain they identify; see, e.g., Aikhenvald and Dixon (2002) and Bickel et al. (2009) for relevant discussion.

5.4 The degree of ambiguity in wordhood analyses

We have seen that while the general order of pre-stem material is consistent, there are various analyses of this material as bound versus separate from the verb, both within and across languages. One relevant question is how many constructions are ambiguous between a bound and an unbound analysis, given the varying test results. This is not just a question for the linguist looking for a good description, but could also factor into language change.

An illustrative example is Eton, as Van de Velde (2008) is rare in providing a thorough description with fully glossed examples and clearly stated justifications for the analytical decisions made. Certain TAM constructions are consistently analysed as analytic, with a (semi-) auxiliary form co-occurring with a main verb that is marked as non-finite by a L-tone prefix ‘INF’ together with link tone (LT) on any following object. The L-tone ‘INF’ prefix is visible in that it triggers downstep on H-toned verbs when it follows H-toned pre-stem material, as in (48), where the underlyingly H-toned verb *sá* ‘work’ is realized with a downstepped H tone due to the prefix, which follows a H-toned present tense marker. However, this INF prefix is not visible on the surface if the verb is L-toned, or if it follows a L-toned element in the pre-stem complex, as in (49).

(48) *Áá'té 'sá.*

|à-á:-**Lt**é **L-sá**|
I-NEG-PR INF-work
'He's not working.'

(Eton (A72) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 283)

(49) *Ŋgũngúgô ìngâ vín.*

|ngũngúgô ì-**ngâ** **L-vín**|
[9]evening IX-INC INF-be.black
'The evening falls. (lit. becomes black)'

(Eton (A72) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 275)

Other evidence used by Van de Velde (2008) for an analytic analysis is the presence of link tone (glossed LT) following non-finite but not finite verb forms. This means that the link tone can carry the functional load of indicating split predication if the L-tone prefix is not visible in the surface realization due to the surrounding tonal context. Again, however, link tone is not observable in all environments. Firstly, it is only visible when material follows the verb, and therefore not applicable in many cases. Secondly, even if material follows the verb, only cases where the following element begins with a L-tone are non-ambiguous; the link tone is thus visible from the surface realization in (50) but not in (51).

(50) *Ángâ tìl bô kálâdà.*

|à-ngâ L-tìl **H** **bô** kálâdà|
I-INC INF-write LT PL letter
'S/he is writing letters.'

(Eton (A72) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 206, 275)

(51) *Mèèy gbè mál.*

mè-è:j	L-gbè	H	m-ál
1SG-FUT	INF-grasp	LT	6-canoe

‘I will have a canoe.’

(Eton (A72) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 263)

Not all TAM constructions in Eton are analysed as involving analytic verb forms, as Van de Velde (2008) also analyses some TAM forms as fully synthetic, discussing ongoing changes between analytic and synthetic constructions. The indefinite future tense is an intermediate case: Van de Velde (2008, 261–262) provides a synthetic analysis, presenting it as “VP-LṅgáL-STEM-H”, as in (52).

(52) *Àṅgá⁺wé yô.*

à-LṅgáL-wé-H	jô
I-IF-kill-IF	IX.PPR

‘He will slaughter it (i.e. the animal).’

(Eton (A72) [eto]; Van de Velde 2008, 262)

However, he notes that this construction is reminiscent of Aux V structures with a L-prefix marking the verb as non-finite (i.e., VP-Lṅgá # L-STEM-H). Van de Velde argues against this analysis based on the interruptability criterion and the lack of following link tone (Van de Velde 2008, 262). Here again we see the use of non-interruptability as a key criterion for wordhood demarcation (cf. Section 5.2.1).

The Eton case study therefore shows that there are various constructions in which particular wordhood criteria are not applicable, with an interplay of evidence needed to motivate a split predication analysis. While link tone helps disambiguate some constructions in Eton, this phenomenon appears to be rare within NWB: Grimm (2025b) suggests that such linking tone phenomena are recent innovations within languages such as Eton and Gyeli. Other NWB languages lack this kind of supporting evidence for the main verb to be taken as the non-finite element of a split predicate structure, perhaps making them more readily (re-)interpreted as part of a synthetic predicate.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have seen that Northwestern Bantu languages are sometimes described as having analytic predicate structures, in which pre-stem inflectional material appears in a complex that is semantically auxiliary to, and syntactically and phonologically separate from, the main lexical verb. The internal structure of these pre-stem complexes can be schematized as SM-{-NEG1-} TAM-{-NEG2-}-DIR-PRN, with some cross-linguistic variation in terms of which of these slots are filled and the latter two slots being of more debatable status. Whether such pre-stem complexes are analysed as forming a separate word has been influenced partly by variation in orthographic conventions, both for arbitrary reasons related to researchers’ preference and due to variation and ambiguities in the data between a free versus bound analysis. In some cases, intervening material (such as objects or adverbials) provides strong evidence for NWB pre-stem material not being part of the same syntactic word as the verb stem. However, evidence from phonological constituency tests such as vowel harmony generally shows that the pre-stem material may be phrased in the same phonological constituent as the main verb, and little supporting morphosyntactic evidence for analytic analyses of pre-stem complexes has been provided besides interruptability. These mixed results are compatible with the idea

that NWB constructions are in transitional stages between more synthetic and more analytic verb forms, highlighting the relevance of NWB languages for diachronic studies of Bantu verb forms. Given the continuous processes of change between analytic and synthetic predication, it is not surprising that sources on NWB languages vary so much in how they present pre-stem material.

Abbreviations

Abbreviations aside from those covered by the Leipzig glossing rules are given below.

[]_{FOC} = scope of focus; 1, 2, 3... = Bantu noun class; I = agreement class 1; II = agreement class 2, IX = agreement class 9; 1s, 1SG = 1st person singular; 2NDSING, 2^{SG} = 2nd person singular; 3s, 3SG = 3rd person singular; (b) = verb tone class B; AND = andative (thither); ASSOC = associative/connective/genitive; CL = noun class; CMP = complementizer; DEF = definite; DEM = demonstrative; DIM = diminutive; DIR = directional marker; DP = determiner phrase (≈ noun phrase); DUR = durative/pluractional; EMPH = emphatic; FUT1 = 1st degree future; FV = final vowel; H = high tone; HAB = habitual; INC = inceptive; IF = indefinite future; IPF = imperfective; IPFP0 = non-past imperfective; L = low tone; LT = link tone; MID = middle; MOT = motional; NEUT = neuter; NF = suffix of the non-final form of the hesternal and hodiernal past perfective; NPPR = non-final form of the personal pronominal; OBLQ = oblique; OM = object marker; P2 = 2nd degree past tense; PFT = perfect (*parfait*); PM = predicative marker; PO = postposition; POSS = possessive; PPR = personal pronominal; PR = present shape of verb with object; PREP = preposition; PRES = present; PRN = pronoun; PROG = progressive; PST0 = immediate past tense; PST1 = 1st degree past tense; PST2 = 2nd degree past tense; PVB = pre-verbal; Q = question marker; R = realis mood; REM = remote (tense gradation); RP = remote past; s3s = 3rd person singular; SGL = singulative (*singulationnel*); SIT = situational; SM = subject marker; SUBJ = subject; TAM(P) = tense/aspect/mood(/polarity); VEN = venitive (hither), VF = final vowel; VTF = venitive (hither).

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Auxiliary Verb Constructions and Decategorialization in Gĩkũyũ

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Abstract

Gĩkũyũ (E.51) exhibits several verbs that can be used both as lexical verbs and as auxiliary verbs. We compare the lexical and auxiliary usages of four verbs and show that all auxiliary verb usages display uniform restrictions concerning valency-related morphology (object marking, voice morphology). We interpret these as signs of decategorialization. Furthermore, we compare the auxiliary verbs with other desemanticized verb usages – light verbs – and argue that they differ in that light verbs do not exhibit decategorialization (compared to the corresponding lexical verb). From this, we conclude that decategorialization is a valid criterion – at least in Gĩkũyũ – for distinguishing different types of desemanticized verbs.

Keywords: auxiliaries, grammaticalization, Bantu, Gĩkũyũ, light verbs

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1 Introduction

Gĩkũyũ (< Bantu, E.51), like many other languages, has pairs of verb usages in which one of the usages can be called a ‘lexical verb’ and the other an ‘auxiliary verb’. The clearest example is the verb *korwo*, which in (1a) is the passive form of the lexical verb *kora* ‘find’. In its use in (1b), on the other hand, it is classified as an auxiliary verb by various authors (Barlow 1960; Johnson 1977, 1980; Mugane 1997). While neither Mugane nor Johnson gives a concrete indication of the meaning of the auxiliary verb construction (AVC) in (1b), Barlow (1960, 268) classifies it as a perfect aspect construction.

- (1) a. *Tũ-a-kor-wo* *ha-ha* *nĩ* *mũ-tumia*.
 2PL-PST-find-PASS 17-here by 1-woman
 ‘We were found here by the woman.’
- b. *Tũ-a-korwo* *tũ-a-rĩ-a* *irio*.
 2PL-PST-AUX 2PL-PST-eat-FV 5.food
 ‘We have just eaten food.’

In addition to *korwo*, other auxiliaries are mentioned in the literature: Barlow (1960) lists the verbs *cooka* ‘to return’, *tiga* ‘to leave’, and *rika* ‘to get into, to sink’,¹ among others, but without going into the meaning of the corresponding AVCs. Benson (1964, 386) mentions *rika* ‘to get into’, which he ascribes an inceptive meaning. In other works on Gĩkũyũ, however, auxiliaries are not mentioned at all (e.g., Mareka Gecaga and Kirkaldy-Willis 1960; Bennett et al. 1985; Englebretson 2015), or only very marginally (e.g., Johnson 1977, 1980; Mugane 1997). In particular, there have been no detailed studies on individual auxiliaries to date. A relevant question for the grammatical description of the language – namely, whether and if so how auxiliaries differ grammatically from lexical verbs – has thus not yet been addressed for Gĩkũyũ. The aim of this study is to fill this gap, at least partially.

Auxiliary verbs are the result of an auxiliarization process in which a lexical verb is successively grammaticalized into an auxiliary verb. In the course of this process, the verbs undergo desemanticization and eventually decategorialization. The present paper deals with both processes. We argue that auxiliary verbs cannot be characterized solely by the fact that they are desemanticized verbs. This is because other verbs – so-called light verbs – also exhibit this feature. Rather, we argue that auxiliary verbs show additional signs of decategorialization that we do not find in light verbs. The latter is relevant because the literature occasionally establishes a connection between light verbs and auxiliary verbs. Hook (1991) argues, based on language data from Indo-Aryan languages such as Hindi/Urdu and Marathi, that light verbs – he speaks of ‘vector verbs’ – represent an intermediate step in the auxiliarization process and stand between lexical verbs and auxiliary verbs (similarly Allerton 2002, 7; see also the discussion in Hopper and Traugott 1991, 112–114 and Anderson 2006, 17). According to Croft (2022, 423), light verb constructions – which he treats under the label ‘support verb construction’ – are “neither clear cases of auxiliary constructions, nor clear cases of lexicalization” but rather between these two poles and, as Croft says, difficult to distinguish from AVCs. A similar claim is made by Berg (2014, 501), who states that light verbs show signs of auxiliarization and “blur the distinction between main and auxiliary verbs”. Thus, he seems to argue for a continuum

¹ Barlow actually writes the verbs as *tigia* and *rikia*; we have standardized the orthography to match the one used in this paper.

‘lexical expression > light verb (construction) > auxiliary verb (construction)’ – which is not necessarily to be understood as a diachronic sequence. With explicit reference to the Bantu languages, Bernander (2024, 114) states in his analysis of the auxiliary *pata* in Swahili that “the auxiliary status associated with *-pata* can be seen as a natural progression from its basic semantic structure manifested in its use as a light verb”.

Based on four case studies, we demonstrate that the auxiliary verbs *korwo*, *rika*, *enda*, and *itĩka* (lit. meaning ‘to pour’) show signs of decategorialization. Since we cannot consider all relevant grammatical contexts, we focus on valency-related aspects in the broader sense, i.e., object realization and voice constructions (passive, applicative, causative, reciprocal, neuter).² In comparative studies of the auxiliary verbs and their corresponding lexical verbs, we show that the auxiliary verbs exhibit identical restrictions with respect to object realization and voice constructions, while the lexical verbs show more variance (a similar claim is made by Hendrikse and Mkhathshwa 1993 for isiZulu). Furthermore, we compare the light verb usage of the verb *hũra* with its corresponding lexical verb (meaning ‘beat, hit’), as well as the auxiliary verbs mentioned, to show that auxiliary verbs but not light verbs show signs of decategorialization. This provides criteria (at least for Gĩkũyũ) for distinguishing the verb types ‘lexical verb’, ‘auxiliary verb’, and ‘light verb’.

The paper presents a first detailed investigation of auxiliary verbs in Gĩkũyũ and also contributes to the differentiation between auxiliary verbs and light verbs (light verbs are a topic that has so far been largely ignored with respect to Bantu languages, with the exception of a few works on light verb constructions in Swahili, e.g., Martin 2019; Olejarnik 2009, 2011; Tramutoli 2022; and some initial analysis of light verb constructions in Gĩkũyũ by Fleischhauer and Kihara 2025).

Our analysis is limited to four verbs that are used as auxiliary verbs and one verb that is used as a light verb. The selection is partly random and partly based on the fact that they are mentioned in the literature on Gĩkũyũ as representatives of their respective categories (see above). The language data comes either from the literature or, unless otherwise stated, was contributed by the second author of the paper, who is a native speaker. The language data was tested for acceptability with other native speakers.

The structure of the paper is as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the notion of an auxiliary verb and discuss criteria by which we can distinguish auxiliaries from other verb usages. Section 3 presents the relevant grammatical data on Gĩkũyũ, which serves as a background for the discussion of the auxiliarization of verbs. We compare the auxiliary verbs with their corresponding lexical verbs in Section 4. There, we also discuss which signs of decategorialization the auxiliary verbs in question show. A comparison of the investigated auxiliary verbs with light verbs is made in Section 5.

2 Desemantized verbs and auxiliarization

With regard to the term ‘auxiliary verb’, we adopt Anderson’s (2006) explication. According to him, an auxiliary verb is “an element that in combination with a lexical verb forms a monoclausal verb phrase with some degree of (lexical) semantic bleaching that performs some more or less definable grammatical function” (Anderson 2006, 5). In contrast to Anderson, we do not

²One reason why we do not consider TAM morphology is that the AVCs we examine realize aspectual meanings and thus stronger interference effects with the meaning of the AVCs are to be expected. To describe this systematically requires a more intensive semantic analysis of the AVCs than we are able to provide in this paper.

speak of an auxiliary verb forming a verb phrase with a lexical verb, but instead we speak of a complex predicate (we explicate this notion in more detail in Section 4.5). The advantage is that the term ‘complex predicate’ does not entail a phrase-structural interpretation and is therefore compatible with syntactic approaches that do not assume the existence of a verb phrase – for example, Role and Reference Grammar (e.g., Van Valin 2005). The central point is that the auxiliary verb forms a predicative unit with a lexical verb, whereby the lexical verb can be realized in a finite (2a) as well as in a non-finite form (e.g., as an infinitive (2b) or, as in the English example in (2c), as a participle).

- (2) a. *Ma-ra-kor-et-wo* *ma-ak-a* *nyũmba*.
 2-PST-AUX-PFV- PASS 2-build-FV 9.house
 ‘They had just built a house.’³
- b. *Ngaari* *ĩ-kũ-end-ag-a* *kũ-gũ-a*.
 9.car 9-PST-AUX-IMPF-FV 15-fall-FV
 ‘The car was about to crash.’
- c. *The boy was sleeping.*

Without the lexical verb, auxiliary verbs do not form complete predications. Auxiliary verbs do not denote eventualities⁴ and are thus semantically defective. This is not to say that auxiliary verbs do not contribute to the meaning of the predication, but only that their semantic contribution is not to introduce the eventuality denoted. This is evident when we contrast AVCs of the same type but with different lexical verbs. If we compare the example in (2b) with those in (3), we see that the sentences are identical, except for the infinitives. The event denoted varies depending on the infinitive: in (2b) a crashing event is denoted, in (3a) an event of starting the engine, and in (3b) a burning event. The function of the auxiliary verb as a component of the AVC is to contribute to event perspectivization; in the case of the examples in (2b) and (3) to represent the denoted event as prospective, i.e., among other things as not yet realized at the reference time (we discuss the notion of ‘prospective aspect’ in somewhat more detail in Section 4.2).

- (3) a. *Ngaari* *ĩ-kũ-end-ag-a* *kũ-rurum-a*.
 9.car 1-PST-AUX-IMPF-FV 15-start.engine-FV
 ‘The car was about to start.’
- b. *Ngaari* *ĩ-kũ-end-ag-a* *kũ-hĩ-a*.
 9.car 9-PST-AUX-IMPF-FV 15-burn-FV
 ‘The car was about to burn.’

Desemanticization – what Anderson (2006) calls ‘semantic bleaching’ – plays a central role in the auxiliarization process.⁵ It is a gradual process in which lexical verbs are grammatical-

³ It should be noted that the perfective aspect marker separates the original passive marker *-wo* from the original stem *cor-*, as is the case with the corresponding lexical verb. Such discontinuous stems – i.e., interrupted stems – are also found in other cases in Gikūyū, as we will briefly outline in Section 3.

⁴ We use the term ‘eventuality’ in the sense of Bach (1986) as a cover term for states and events.

⁵ See Kuteva (2001) for a comprehensive discussion of desemanticization in the context of auxiliarization and also

ized into auxiliary verbs (e.g., Bolinger 1980, 295). In the course of the grammaticalization process, the verbs undergo not only desemanticization but also decategorialization, i.e., the loss or change of grammatical properties. Auxiliary verbs and the lexical verbs from which they developed often exist in parallel in a language. We already pointed out in the introduction that the auxiliary verb *korwo* is identical in form to the passivized version of the lexical verb *kora* ‘find’. But there is also a lexical verb identical in form to the auxiliary *enda*, with the meaning ‘want, like’, and the same holds true of the other auxiliary verbs *rika* and *itika*, which we analyse in this paper and for which corresponding lexical verbs meaning ‘to dip into’ and ‘to pour’ exist.⁶

We can determine decategorialization on the basis of objectively observable criteria, for example in the development of restrictions in relation to inflectional and derivational morphology. This assumes, of course, that we have a suitable standard of comparison by which we can see that the restrictions are indeed a consequence of the auxiliarization process. Since, as mentioned above, (emerging) auxiliary verbs and lexical verbs can exist in parallel in a language, the lexical verb usage of a lexeme can serve as a standard of comparison for answering the question of whether and, if so, in what form an auxiliary verb shows signs of decategorialization.

Desemanticization, i.e., the loss of lexical meaning, is often shown indirectly (see, for example, Heine 1993, 54). For example, changes in the subject selectional restrictions of a verb are interpreted as an indicator of desemanticization. Although changes in the selectional restrictions indicate a semantic change, they are not sufficient to indicate that the corresponding verb has assumed the status of an auxiliary verb. An illustrative example can be found in German, where the verb *stehen* ‘stand’ means that the subject referent is in an upright posture at a certain location (4a). In this usage, *stehen* ‘stand’ contrasts with other posture verbs such as *liegen* ‘lie’ or *sitzen* ‘sit’, in which the subject referent has a different posture. The subject argument must have certain properties (a salient axis, which can be vertically aligned; cf. Gamerschlag et al. 2013). If this is not the case, the subject referent is not compatible with this use of *stehen* (e.g., *ball* ‘ball’ – as well as other round objects like ‘moon’ – is excluded as a subject referent in 4a). However, we also find usages in which the subject referent has no salient axis and cannot be positioned in an upright posture (4b). Interestingly, *stehen* in (4b) also no longer contrasts with other posture verbs such as *liegen* ‘lie’ or *sitzen* ‘sit’.

- (4) a. *Der Hund steht vor dem Baum.*
the dog stands in_front_of the tree
‘The dog is standing in front of the tree.’
- b. *Der Mond steht vor den Sternen.*
the moon stand in_front_of the stars
‘The moon is in front of the stars.’ (Kaufmann 1995: 111)

We can say that *stehen* in (4b) is desemanticized in comparison to its use in (4a). While in (4a) a state predication is made about the location and posture of the subject referent, (4b) only makes a predication about the subject referent’s location (see Kaufmann 1995, 111; Fleischhauer

the classification of ‘bleaching’ as one of several processes subsumed under the notion of ‘desemanticization’.

⁶ Auxiliarization has also played a role in the development of aspectual suffixes, such as the perfect morpheme *-il*, which according to Voeltz (1980) developed via intermediate stages from the proto-Bantu verb *-gid-e* ‘finish’. Such developments of verbs via auxiliaries to bound morphemes are not the subject of the present study.

2021). The two uses of *stehen* differ in their selectional restrictions, but both are classified as lexical verb usages.

We therefore resort to the criterion of semantic defectiveness to determine the presence of a desemanticization process. As we have explained above, auxiliary verbs are semantically defective, i.e., they do not denote a specific eventuality type; rather, the reference depends on the semantic head of the complex predicate, i.e., the lexical verb. When used as a lexical verb, however, the verbs corresponding to the auxiliary verbs are not semantically defective. As a lexical verb, *enda* has a desiderative meaning and expresses that the subject referent is in the cognitive state of wanting. If we replace *ngaari* ‘car’ in (5a) with an infinitive (5b), for example, only the object being wanted changes, but not the fact that the subject referent does want it (i.e., is in the state of wanting something).

- (5) a. *Ndĩ-ra-end-a* *ngaari*.
 1SG-PRS-want-FV 9.car
 ‘I want a car.’
- b. *Ndĩ-ra-end-a* *gũ-kom-a*.
 1SG-PRS-want-FV 15-sleep-FV
 ‘I want to sleep.’

We propose that it is necessary for auxiliary verbs not to denote a specific eventuality type. However, this criterion is not sufficient to identify auxiliary verbs, since it is not only auxiliary verbs that are desemanticized in such a way that they do not denote a specific eventuality type. Another type of verb showing this property is light verbs.

Light verbs form a complex predicate together with a phrasal element – usually an NP, but in some languages also a PP – which is referred to as a ‘light verb construction’ (LVC). Like auxiliaries, light verbs are attested in numerous unrelated languages. They have been well studied in various branches of the Indo-European language family – e.g., Germanic, Romanic, and Indo-Iranian (see Pompei et al. 2023 for references) – but also in Japanese (e.g., Kishimoto 2025), Korean, and Mandarin Chinese (e.g., Kuo 2025). For the Bantu languages, LVCs have so far only been studied extensively for Swahili (Martin, 2019; Olejarnik 2009, 2011; Tramutoli 2022).

LVCs are similar to AVCs in that the finite verb does not determine the eventuality denoted. Instead, the eventuality denoted is determined by the phrasal element. This is evident for LVCs whose phrasal element contains an eventive noun. An illustrative example is English *to give a kiss*, which can be paraphrased as ‘to kiss’ and denotes a kissing event. Gikūyū has, among other things, the light verb *hūra* ‘beat, hit’, which is used with non-eventive nouns, e.g., *hūra thimũ* ‘make a call’ (lit. beat phone).

- (6) *Mũ-tumia* *nĩ=a-ra-hūr-a* *thimũ*.
 1-woman FOC=1-PRS-beat-FV 9.phone
 ‘The woman is making a call.’

Eventive nouns, although they are nouns, refer to an eventuality just like verbs do. Non-eventive nouns, on the other hand, refer to a non-temporal entity, such as animate beings (*mũtumia*

‘woman’), inanimate concrete objects (*thimũ* ‘phone’), or abstract concepts (*thiriti* ‘friendship’); see Fábregas et al. (2012) for criteria to distinguish between eventive and non-eventive nouns.

Although *thimũ* ‘phone’ is not an eventive noun, the event denoted by the LVC in (6) can be inferred from its meaning. In the case of *thimũ*, an event is inferred in which the referent takes on the instrumental role: a phone is the instrument in a calling event. In other words, to call someone is what phones are used for.

Whether light verbs are the result of a desemanticization process is controversial in the research literature (see Butt and Lahiri 2013); however, it is stated – for instance by Butt and Lahiri – that light verbs, unlike auxiliary verbs, show no signs of decategorialization (see also Butt and Geuder 2003 on this issue). In Section 5, we compare *hũra* LVCs with the AVCs under investigation and show that the language data from Gĩkũyũ also argue against the decategorialization of light verbs. This results in two characteristics that we can use to differentiate between lexical verbs, auxiliary verbs, and light verbs. Auxiliary verbs and light verbs are semantically defective, which – at least in the case of auxiliary verbs – is due to desemanticization. Auxiliary verbs but not light verbs show signs of decategorialization. The differentiation criteria are summarized in Table 1. The following sections serve to show evidence for the decategorialization of auxiliary verbs and the absence of decategorialization in (Gĩkũyũ) light verbs.

Table 1: Criteria distinguishing lexical verbs, auxiliary verbs, and light verbs

	Semantically defective	Decategorialized
lexical verb	no	no
light verb	yes	no
auxiliary verb	yes	yes

Before we can investigate the grammatical behaviour of auxiliary verbs, we first need to work out how lexical verbs behave in Gĩkũyũ. It will be the task of future research to test the claims made in this paper, which are based on a small dataset, using additional data from the language, as well as cross-linguistic data.

3 Gĩkũyũ: Grammatical background

Gĩkũyũ (E.51) is a Central Kenyan Bantu language spoken by slightly more than 8 million people (according to the 2019 census). In this section, we briefly discuss the grammatical features of the language relevant to our analysis: verbal morphology and argument realization. To illustrate the relevant grammatical properties, we use, among others, the verb *hũra* ‘beat, hit’, whose light verb usage we will return to in Section 5.

Like other Bantu languages, Gĩkũyũ has a rich verbal morphology. Subject and object markers, as well as negation and tense, are realized before the verbal roots (see Johnson 1977, 1980 and Cable 2013 on tense and aspect marking in Gĩkũyũ). We can distinguish between subject and object markers based on their phonological form – at least in the examples in (7) – and their linear position. The tense marker separates subject and object marking (7a). The negation prefix has different allomorphs that either precede the subject marker (7a) or follow it (7b).

- (7) a. *Nd-a-na-mũ-hũr-a.*
 NEG-1-PST-1-beat-FV
 ‘S/he did not beat him/her.’
 b. *Tũ-ti-na-mũ-hũr-a.*
 1PL-NEG-PST-1-beat-FV
 ‘We did not beat him/her.’

In addition to verb prefixes, Gĩkũyũ also has a number of suffixes, including voice markers (passive (8a), reciprocal (8b), neuter (8c), causative (8d), applicative (8e)) and aspect markers (perfective, imperfective, and perfect).

- (8) a. *Ngui nĩ=ĩ-ra-hũr-ir-wo nĩ mũ-tumia.*
 9.dog FOC=9-PST-beat-PFV-PASS by 1-woman
 ‘The dog was beaten by the woman.’
 b. *Mũ-irĩtu na mw-anake*
 1-girl with 1.boy
nĩ=ma-a-gũth-an-ir-e.
 FOC=2-PST-hit-RECP-PFV-FV
 ‘The girl and the boy beat each other.’
 c. *Thimũ n-dĩ-ra-hũr-ĩk-a.*
 9-phone 9-NEG-PRS-beat-NEUT-FV
 ‘The phone is not going through.’ (lit. The phone is not beatable.)
 d. *Mũ-thuri nĩ=a-ra-hũr-ithi-a mũ-tumia ngui.*
 1-man FOC=1-PRS-beat-CAUS-FV 1-woman 9.dog
 ‘The man caused the woman to beat the dog/ The man helped the woman the beat the dog.’⁷
 e. *Mũ-tumia nĩ=a-ra-mũ-hũr-ĩr-a ngui.*
 1-woman FOC=1-PRS-1-beat-APPL-FV 9.dog
 ‘The woman is beating the dog for him/her.’

The passive is realized morphologically as verb-final; the suffix *-wo* replaces the final vowel (FV). Syntactically, the passive is canonical in Gĩkũyũ, as the object of the active construction becomes the subject of the passive construction and the subject of the active construction is

⁷ In Gĩkũyũ – as in other Bantu languages (see Schneider-Zioga and Mutaka 2019) – causative constructions in some cases have a ‘sociative’ interpretation (see Shibatani and Pardeshi 2001) in addition to a strictly causative meaning, in which the causer performs a joint action with the causee.

optionally realized in an oblique *nĩ*-PP ‘by-PP’ (see 8a). Another morpheme that falls into the category of ‘voice’ is the reciprocal marker *-an* (8b). This marker expresses that the eventuality denoted by the verb is performed reciprocally, i.e., mutually. Frajzyngier and Curl (2000, vii) note that in a reciprocal scenario, two or more participants bear the same semantic role. In (8b), *mũirĩtu* ‘girl’ and *mwanake* ‘boy’ are both agents and patients of the hitting. Such an interpretation requires a plural subject argument. In addition to realizing the reciprocal meaning, *-an* can also be used to realize the antipassive voice (see Kihara 2024; see also Bostoen et al. 2015 for a general discussion of the antipassive voice in Bantu). This use is most evident with singular subject arguments, as these exclude a reciprocal interpretation. The object argument can either not be realizable – as in (9) – or it is realized in an oblique *kũrĩ*-PP ‘to-PP’ (see Kihara 2024 for examples).

- (9) *Nyina nĩ=a-a-hũr-an-ir-e*
 1.mother FOC=1-PST-beat-RECP-PFV-FV
 ‘The mother beat someone.’

The neuter suffix *-ĩk*, which also leads to a valency reduction, functions similarly to the aforementioned voice markers. Dom et al. (2016) classify the neuter marker as belonging to the category ‘middle voice’.⁸ Middle voice itself refers to a summary of different functions, including anticausative or, as in (8c), ‘patient-oriented potentials’ (Dom et al. 2016, 133). A characteristic feature is that in a middle voice construction, one of the object arguments becomes the subject; however, unlike in the passive voice, the subject of the active sentence is no longer realizable.

Many Bantu languages have two morphological causative markers; in Gĩkũyũ these are the short causative *-i* and the long causative *-ithi*. The long causative is composed of two segments: *-ith* + *-i*, where the second segment is identical to the short causative and can be separated from the first segment (10). Note that (10) differs from (8d) only with respect to the perfective aspect suffix *-ir* which separates the two segments of the causative marker. We gloss both segments as ‘CAUS’, without implying that this is an instance of double causativization. In fact, the iteration of causative markers is not possible in Gĩkũyũ, unlike in, for instance, Lingála (Meeuwis 2008, 453–454).

- (10) *Mũ-thuri nĩ=a-ra-hũr-ith-ir-i-e mũ-tumia ngui.*
 1-man FOC=1-PRS-beat-CAUS-PFV-CAUS-FV 1-woman 9.dog
 ‘The man caused the woman to beat the dog/ The man helped the woman the beat the dog.’

The short causative marker *-i* also occurs in lexicalized usages. In these, it does not contribute a causative meaning, i.e., an increase in valency compared to a non-causative verb form. This is the case with *ikia* ‘throw’, for instance. A corresponding verb form *ika* – from which *ikia* could be derived – does not exist in the synchronic language. That the occurrence of *-i* in the verb is a lexicalized causative marker is evident from the fact that the segment *-i* can be separated from

⁸ A characteristic feature of the Bantu languages seems to be that the various functions subsumed under the term ‘middle voice’ are not realized by a single marker (Dom et al. 2016). In Gĩkũyũ, in addition to the neuter suffix *-ĩk*, the reflexive marker also functions as an exponent of the middle voice category (Kihara 2024).

the stem (11). We gloss such forms as discontinuous stems (see Good 2007 for a more detailed discussion of discontinuous morphology in the Bantu languages).

- (11) *Nĩ=tũ-ra-ma-ik-ĩr-i-a* *mũ-bira*.
 FOC=1PL-PRS-2-throw-APPL-STEM-FV 3-ball
 ‘We are throwing them a ball.’ (Wittke 2015, 7)

The applicative marker *-ĩr* in (8e) introduces a new non-subject argument. However, like the causative, *-ĩr* also occurs in uses in which it does not cause an increase in valency. This can be observed, for instance, with the transitive verb *rũga* ‘jump (over)’ in (12). The applicative marker in (12b) does not introduce an additional argument compared to (12a). Rather, the marker has a semantic function that transforms a semelfactive event description (i.e., an iteration of single events of jumping) into a punctual (i.e., unique) event description (see Pacchiarotti 2020, 2024 for a comprehensive discussion of different uses of applicative markers from a cross-Bantu perspective).

- (12) a. *Ngui nĩ=y-a-rũg-a* *mw-ene*.
 9.dog FOC=9-PST-jump-FV 1-owner
 ‘The dog jumped over the owner.’
 b. *Ngui nĩ=y-a-rũg-ĩr-a* *mw-ene*.
 9.dog FOC=9-PST-jump-APPL-FV 1-owner
 ‘The dog jumped (just once) at the owner.’

In the remainder of the paper, we will restrict ourselves to productive valency-increasing uses of causative and applicative morphology when discussing its use in the context of auxiliarization. Uses as in (11) and (12b) are explicitly excluded.

Morphosyntactically, Gikūyū can be classified as a symmetrical non-doubling language. The distinction between symmetrical and asymmetrical languages goes back to Bresnan and Moshi (1990). Symmetrical languages treat the two non-subject arguments of a ditransitive verb in the same way with regard to the relevant object criteria. These include the realization of an argument by a bound object marker, as well as the realization of an argument as the subject of a passive construction (see Hyman and Duranti 1982). The examples in (13) and (14) show that Gikūyū is symmetrical with regard to both properties and that no distinction can be made between a direct object and an indirect object on the basis of these properties.

- (13) a. *Mũ-tumia a-a-he-ir-e* *mw-anake i-buku*.
 1-woman 1-PST-give-PFV-FV 1-boy 5-book
 ‘The woman gave the book to the boy.’
 b. *Mũ-tumia a-a-rĩ-he-ir-e* *mw-anake*.
 1-woman 1-PST-5-give-PFV-FV 1-boy
 ‘The woman gave it to the boy.’

- c. *Mũ-tumia a-a-mũ-he-ir-e i-buku.*
 1-woman 1-PST-1-give-PFV-FV 5-book
 ‘The woman gave him/her a book.’
- (14) a. *Mw-anake a-a-he-ir-wo i-buku nĩ mũ-tumia.*
 1-boy 1-PST-give-PFV-PASS 5-book by 1-woman
 ‘The boy was given the book by the woman.’
- b. *I-buku rĩ-a-he-ir-wo mw-anake nĩ mũ-tumia.*
 5-book 5-PST-give-PFV-PASS 1-boy by 1-woman
 ‘The book was given to the boy by the woman.’

Furthermore, Gikūyū is a non-doubling language (see, e.g., van der Wal 2022; Fleischhauer 2023a), which means that a bound object marker cannot co-occur with a coreferential non-subject NP within the same clause. A coreferential NP is either not realized at all or is left- or preferably right-dislocated (see Lambrecht 2001 on the notion of ‘dislocation’). If a constituent is right-dislocated, the realization of the bound object marker is obligatory, as is an intonation break between the dislocated constituent and the last constituent in the clause (in (15) after the verb).

- (15) *Ka-hĩ nĩ=ka-ra-mĩ-hũr-a, ngui.*
 12-boy FOC=12-PRS-9-beat-FV 9.dog
 ‘The boy is beating it, the dog.’

Subject arguments can always be doubled, as can be seen, for instance, in (15). However, the realization of the subject with an overt NP is not obligatory, since the subject marker can be interpreted pronominally.

Lexical verbs behave regularly with respect to the grammatical properties outlined above:

- when verbs are (di)transitive, they allow one of the non-subject arguments to be pronominalized by a bound object marker;⁹
- when verbs are (di)transitive, they can be passivized and one of the non-subject arguments can become the subject of the passive construction;
- when verbs are (di)transitive, they can undergo other valency-reducing processes as well (reciprocal, antipassive, neuter);
- verbs can (as a rule) undergo valency-increasing processes through causative and applicative morphology.

However, idiosyncratic deviations from this general pattern are possible, as we will see in the next section.

⁹ Jeon and Mauney (2015) show that some verbs in Gikūyū even allow both non-subject arguments to be realized by bound object markers on the verb.

4 Auxiliary verbs and decategorialization: Case studies

Auxiliaries have been treated rather marginally in the literature on Gĩkũyũ. The only work that presents a comprehensive list of auxiliaries is Barlow’s (1960) *Studies in Kikuyu Grammar and Idiom*. But even Barlow does not address the question of how auxiliary verbs differ from lexical verbs. In the following four case studies, we compare the grammatical behaviour of the auxiliary verbs *korwo*, *rika*, *itĩka* and *enda* with the grammatical behaviour of their corresponding lexical verbs with regard to valency-related properties (voice marking, argument realization) in the broadest sense.

4.1 *korwo*

Korwo is the only verb that is treated as an auxiliary by several authors. Barlow (1960, 183) attests to its “important” use as auxiliary. While Mugane (1997, 124) glosses it as ‘be’, Barlow (1960, 268) lists ‘be found to have’, ‘be found to be’ and ‘be found doing’ as the “primary meaning” of the auxiliary. Johnson (1980, 315) just calls it an auxiliary without an indication of its function. According to Barlow, the auxiliary verb construction realizes perfect aspect; Mugane does not explicitly specify its meaning. However, the English translations of his examples suggest that he also assumes perfect aspect to be expressed by the AVC.¹⁰

The ‘primary meaning’ that Barlow gives to the auxiliary verb is a reflection of the fact that *korwo* is a fossilized passive form of the lexical verb *kora* ‘find, meet’. While in (16a) *korwo* is used as a passive form of *kora*, in (16b) it is used as an auxiliary verb. The optional actor argument in a passive construction can be realized in Gĩkũyũ in a *nĩ*-PP, as shown in (16a). Such a PP cannot be added in (16b), as it behaves formally as an active voice construction.

- (16) a. *Tũ-a-kor-wo* *ha-ha* *nĩ mũ-tumia*.
 2PL-PST-find-PASS 17-here by 1-woman
 ‘We were found here by the woman.’
- b. *Tũ-a-korwo* *tũ-a-rĩ-a* *irio*.
 2PL-PST-AUX 2PL-PST-eat-FV 5.food
 ‘We have just eaten food.’

Not only does the auxiliary verb use of *korwo* have no passive meaning, but the lexical meaning ‘find’ is also not realized. In addition to semantic differences, there are also clear grammatical differences. *Kora* ‘find’ is a transitive verb that takes two arguments. If the object is realized by a free form and not by a bound object marker, then it takes the form of an NP (cf. the active construction in (17)). In its auxiliary use, *korwo* combines with a finite verb instead of an NP. *Tũarĩa* ‘we ate’ in (16b) is a finite indicative verb form that bears a subject prefix as well as a tense marker and has its own argument (*irio* ‘food’) licensed.

- (17) *Tũ-a-kor-a* *mũ-tumia* *ha-ha*.
 2PL-PST-find-FV 1-woman 17-here
 ‘We found the woman here’.

¹⁰ *Korwo* is also used as a conditional marker, then it appears as an uninflected particle; see Kihara (2023) for a discussion of this usage.

Korwo AVCs represent what Anderson (2006, 2011a, 803–805) terms a ‘doubled inflectional pattern’ as inflectional marking occurs twice: on the auxiliary verb as well as the lexical one. Both the subject marker and the tense marker – identical in both cases – are realized in (16b) on the auxiliary and its finite verb complement.

In addition to the passivization of *kora* (16a), it is also possible for its object argument to be realized by a bound object marker (18a). *Kora* also allows the realization of the reciprocal marker (18b). In contrast, the verb cannot realize either the neuter marker or the applicative marker, nor can it be causativized. Thus, the lexical verb shows idiomatic restrictions concerning its compatibility with voice suffixes.

- (18) a. *Tũ-a-mũ-kor-a* *ha-ha*.
 2PL-PST-1-find-FV 17-here
 ‘We found her/him here’.
- b. *Mũ-irĩtu* *na* *mw-anake* *nĩ=ma-a-kor-an-ir-e*
 1-girl with 1-boy FOC=2-PST-find-RECP-PFV-FV
bara.
 9.road
 ‘The girl and the boy found / met each other at the road.’

As an auxiliary, *korwo* has the same restrictions as the lexical verb: it is neither compatible with the neuter marker nor with the causative or the applicative marker. Furthermore, the auxiliary *korwo* can neither be passivized nor can a bound object marker be affixed or the reciprocal marker be suffixed. The fact that passivization is excluded may be attributed to the fact that the verb already formally corresponds to a passivized verb form. However, this does not explain why bound object marking is excluded, since (at least some) passivized ditransitive verbs in Gĩkũyũ do license bound object marking. This is illustrated by the minimal pair in (19). Nor does the morphological form of the verb explain why none of the other voice markers is possible.

- (19) a. *Mũ-tumia* *a-a-he-ir-e* *mũ-thuri* *ka-ana*.
 1-woman 1-PST-give-PFV-FV 1-man 12-baby
 ‘The woman gave the baby to the man.’
- b. *Mũ-thuri* *nĩ=a-a-ka-he-ir-wo* *nĩ* *mũ-tumia*.
 1-man FOC=1-PST-12-give-PFV-PASS by 1-woman
 ‘The man was given it by the woman.’

We attribute the fact that *korwo* does not license a bound object marker in its auxiliary verb use to the fact that the finite verb – *tũarĩa* ‘we ate’ in (16b) – is not the object argument of *korwo*. We will come back to this issue in more detail later.

Table 2 summarizes the morphosyntactic behaviour of the lexical verb *kora* and the auxiliary *korwo* with regard to bound object marking and voice marking.

Table 2: Comparison of the relevant morphosyntactic properties of the lexical with the auxiliary use of *kora/korwo*

	<i>kora</i> _{lexical}	<i>korwa</i> _{aux}
bound object marking	yes	no
passive	yes	no
reciprocal	yes	no
neuter	no	no
causative	no	no
applicative	no	no

4.2 *Enda*

Enda has two uses in Gikūyū which are identical in form: first as a lexical verb with the meaning ‘want, like’ (20a) and second as the verbal component of a prospective construction (20b).

- (20) a. *Ndĩ-ra-end-a* *ngaari*.
 1SG-PRS-want-FV 9.car
 ‘I want a car.’
- b. *Nĩ=kũ-r-end-a* *kũ-ur-a*.
 FOC=17-PRS-want-FV 15-rain-FV
 ‘It is about to rain.’

The use of a desiderative verb with the meaning ‘want’ is a strategy frequently found across languages for the realization of prospective aspect (see Heine 1994, 35). In addition to other Bantu languages such as Swahili, such grammaticalization paths are also found in unrelated languages (e.g., Tok Pisin < Creole (Romaine 1999); Persian < Indo-European (Davari and Naghsguy-Kohan 2017, 180–184); see Heine 1994 and Kuteva 2001 for more languages).

Prospective aspect – also called proximative (e.g., Heine 1994; Kuteva 2001) – together with perfect aspect represents a subtype of perspectival aspect in Dik’s (1997, 221) typology of grammatical aspect. Both prospective and perfect represent a relation between an eventuality and a state. With perfect aspect, the state in which the argument of the predication is located – this can be the subject as in *I already have eaten* but also the object as in *John has opened the door* – is represented as a post-state of the eventuality denoted by the lexical verb. Often, but not always, the state is interpreted as the resultant state. In the prospective aspect, the state in which the subject argument is located is understood as the pre-state of the eventuality denoted by the lexical verb (Fleischhauer and Gamerschlag 2019, 146). The subject referent is in a state such that if nothing intervenes, the eventuality denoted by the lexical verb is realized (e.g., Fleischhauer 2023b, 374–375; Boogards and Fleischhauer 2023, 16). With respect to (20b), the conditions are such that if nothing intervenes, e.g., if the wind does not drive away the clouds, it will rain.

The fact that *enda* no longer has a desiderative meaning in the prospective construction can be recognized, among other things, by the fact that it also occurs with non-animate subjects. The subject marker in (20b) is a locational marker that can be translated into English by an expletive. The changes in the selectional restrictions – as a lexical verb, *enda* requires animate subjects – are (in this specific case) an indication of the desemanticization that took place in the

course of auxiliarization. However, we also see that *enda* as the head of a prospective aspect construction is semantically defective and that the eventuality, i.e., the prospective event, is denoted by the infinitive rather than the finite verb.

As a lexical verb, *enda* is transitive and can take an NP with a lexical noun as head (20a), a subordinate clause (21a), or an infinitive (21b) as complement.

- (21) a. *Ndĩ-ra-enda* *wũ-in-e*.
 1SG-PRS-want-FV 2SG-sing-FV
 ‘I want you to sing.’
- b. *N-di-enda-et-e* *gũ-kom-a*.
 1SG-NEG-want-PFV-FV 15-sleep-FV
 ‘I do not want/ like sleeping.’

In its auxiliary verb use, *enda* is more restricted and only occurs with an infinitival complement. Infinitives are verbal stems that have an NC15 noun class marker. According to Mugane (1997), infinitives have both nominal and verbal properties. Verbal properties include the fact that infinitives can exhibit verbal morphology (aspect marking, voice marking, bound object marking). The NC15 marker replaces the subject marker and these infinitives behave syntactically like nouns. The infinitive in (21b) has object properties, which can be recognized by the fact that it can be pronominalized by a bound object marker. Since Gikūyū is a non-doubling language, the NP coreferential with the bound object marker is realized as left-dislocated (22).

- (22) *Gũ-kom-a, n-di-kũ-enda-et-e*
 15-sleep-FV 1SG-NEG-15-want-PFV-FV
 ‘Sleeping, I do not like it.’

While *enda* as a lexical verb allows a pronominalization of the infinitive (22), this is not possible in the prospective construction. A further asymmetry with regard to the infinitive can be seen in passivization. In general, infinitives can become the subject of a passive construction (23), but this does not apply to the infinitive complements of the auxiliary verb *enda*. This means, for example, that *kũura* ‘to rain’ cannot become the subject of the prospective construction in (20b). However, this is not a consequence of the fact that it is an infinitive, but rather a characteristic of the auxiliary verb construction, as the discussion of example (23) has shown.

- (23) *Gũ-kom-a* *gũ-ti-enda-et-wo* *nĩ* *ci-ana*.
 15-sleep-FV 15-NEG-want-PFV-PASS by 2-child
 ‘Children don’t like sleeping.’ (lit. Sleeping is not liked by children)

As with the comparison of *kora* and *korwo*, we can see that the obligatory complement of the auxiliary has no object status and that the relationship between auxiliary and complement cannot be described as a predicate-argument relationship.

As a lexical verb, *enda* is compatible with the reciprocal marker (24a). However, this marker is excluded in the auxiliary use. One reason for this – which also applies to other auxiliaries – is that it does not denote a process that can be performed reciprocally. It should therefore come as

no surprise that the reciprocal marker can actually be realized in the infinitive (24b). In terms of meaning, the marker has scope over the event denoted by the infinitive, so that it should also be realized on the infinitive. It makes a difference in meaning whether we have a prospective event in which the subject referent hits someone or in which this activity is performed by two subject referents on each other.

- (24) a. *Mũ-irĩtu na mw-anake nĩ=ma-end-an-ĩt-e.*
 1-girl with 1-boy FOC=2-PST-love-RECP-PFT-FV
 ‘The girl and the boy like each other.’
- b. *Mũ-irĩtu na mw-anake ma-kw-end-ag-a kũ-gũth-an-a.*
 1-girl with 1-boy 2-PST-want-IMP-FV 15-hit-RECP-FV
 ‘The girl and the boy were about to hit each other.’

The same restriction that we observed with regard to the reciprocal marker also applies to the neuter marker. As a lexical verb, *enda* licenses the neuter marker (25), but as an auxiliary, it does not. Unlike, for example, *hũra* in (8c), the neuter marker in (25) does not lead to a patient-oriented potential reading, but can best be described as an agentless passive (Dom et al. 2016, 132).

- (25) *Mũ-nene n-da-r-end-ek-a.*
 1-leader 1-NEG-PRS-like-NEUT-FV
 ‘The leader is not liked.’

The lexical verb *enda*, unlike *kora*, licenses an applicative marker. In (26), the applied object – the benefactive argument – is realized by a bound object marker. Like *korwo*, the auxiliary verb usage is not compatible with applicative morphology.

- (26) *Tũ-a-kũ-end-er-a mũ-thenya mw-ega.*
 2PL-PRS-1-want-APPL-FV 3-day 3-good
 ‘We wish you a good day.’ (lit. We want a good day for you)

Neither as a lexical verb nor as an auxiliary verb can *enda* be causativized. A summary of the morphosyntactic properties of the two verb uses can be found in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of the relevant morphosyntactic properties of the lexical with the auxiliary use of *enda*

	<i>enda</i> _{lexical}	<i>enda</i> _{aux}
bound object marking	yes	no
passive	yes	no
reciprocal	yes	no
neuter	yes	no
causative	no	no
applicative	yes	no

4.3 *rika* and *itika*

Like *enda*, *rika* is used as a lexical verb and as an auxiliary. As a lexical verb it means ‘to get into/ sink’ (27a), while as an auxiliary it is used to express inceptive aspect (27b).

- (27) a. *Nĩ=ma-a-rik-ir-e* *mũ-taro.*
 FOC=2PL-PST-get.into-PFV-FV 3-trench
 ‘They got into the trench.’
- b. *Ma-a-kiny-ir-e* *ma-kĩ-rik-a* *kũ-in-a.*
 2-PST-arrive-PFV-FV 2-NARR-start-FV 15-sing-FV
 ‘They arrived and they started to sing/ singing.’

Inceptive aspect is a subtype of phasal aspect. This type of aspect indicates “whether an action begins, continues or ends” (Longacre 1976, 238). In addition to the inceptive aspect, ‘durative’ and ‘terminative’ are two other subtypes of phasal aspect (e.g., Longacre 1976, 238; Noonan 2007, 139–140; Croft 2022, 559–560). Besides *rika*, inceptive aspect can also be expressed by using the auxiliary *itika* (28). The two AVCs have the same meaning and, as the comparison of (27b) and (28) shows, can be used at least partially with the same infinitives. We cannot make any statements about frequency differences or other differences between the constructions at this point, but require a more intensive comparative study of both AVCs. First we deal with the grammatical behaviour of *rika* and then we move on to *itika*.

- (28) *Ma-gĩ-itĩk-a* *kũ-in-a.*
 2-NARR-AUX-FV 15-sing-FV
 ‘And they started to sing/ singing.’

The two uses of *rika* differ again with regard to their complement. As a lexical verb, *rika* takes an NP complement, whose head can be a noun of any noun class but not an infinitive. As an auxiliary, *rika* combines with infinitives only. The complement NP of lexical *rika* has the usual object properties: it can be pronominalized by a bound object marker (29a) and it can become the subject of a passive construction (29b). This is different for the infinitive complement in the auxiliary usage. As with the other auxiliary verbs, it should be noted here that the infinitive cannot be pronominalized by a bound object marker nor can it serve as the subject of a passive construction.

- (29) a. *Nĩ=ma-a-ũ-rik-ir-e.*
 FOC=3PL-PST-3-get.into-PFV-FV
 ‘They got into it (e.g., the trench).’
- b. *Nĩ=ũ-a-rik-ir-wo.*
 FOC=3-PST-get.into-PFV-PASS
 ‘It (e.g., the trench) was got into.’

According to Benson (1964, 386), *rika* is polysemous. He assigns both meanings attested in (27) to the same lexeme. We deviate from Benson’s analysis and argue that diachronically both forms belong together, but synchronically we can observe that the two forms have different

morphosyntactic properties. As a consequence, we assume the existence of two clearly distinguished lexemes: an aspectual auxiliary verb and a lexical one. Evidence for this is, among other things, that in the aspectual construction no pronominalization of the infinitive is allowed and the verb cannot be passivized. Furthermore, *rika* can be causativized as a lexical verb (30a), but not as an auxiliary. And, as with the other auxiliaries discussed above, lexical *rika* is compatible with the reciprocal marker (30b) as well as the neuter marker (30c), but not in its auxiliary usage.

- (30) a. *Ma-ma-rik-i-ir-i-e* *mũ-taro.*
 2-2-get.into-CAUS-PFV-DC-FV 3-trench
 ‘They made others to get into the trench./ They dipped them into the trench.’
- b. *Thaburia* *nĩ=ci-a-rik-an-a.*
 10.cooking_pot FOC=10-PST-get.into-RECP-FV
 ‘The cooking pots have got into each other.’
- c. *Mũ-taro* *nĩ=ũ-ra-rik-ĩk-a.*
 3-trench FOC=3-PRS-get.into-NEUT-FV
 ‘One can dip into the trench.’ (lit. The trench is dippable/ can be deepened.)

Neither use of *rika* licenses an applicative marker.¹¹ A summary of the morphosyntactic behaviour or object properties and voice of both uses of *rika* can be found in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of the relevant morphosyntactic properties of the lexical with the auxiliary use of *rika*

	<i>rika</i> _{lexical}	<i>rika</i> _{aux}
bound object marking	yes	no
passive	yes	no
reciprocal	yes	no
neuter	yes	no
causative	yes	no
applicative	no	no

Itĩka, in its auxiliary verb usage, is derived from the verb *ita* ‘to pour’. The auxiliary contains the neuter voice marker *-ĩk*, which, like the passive marker in the case of *korwo*, can be considered lexicalized. In the following examples, we compare the auxiliary verb usage of *itĩka* with the neuter voice form of the lexical verb.

It(iĩk)a differs in its lexical usage from *rika* in that it also licenses an applicative marker (31a). Reciprocal marking is possible, as shown in (31b).¹² The examples in (31c) and (31d)

¹¹ There exists a verb form that morphologically appears like *rika* with an applicative morpheme (*rikĩra*), but has the meaning ‘to get deep into.’, i.e., for instance, into a philosophy or religion, meaning to get a better understanding. We analyse this as a derivational function of the applicative marker, which derives a new lexeme and thus does not present the relevant valence-increasing usage that we are exclusively considering.

¹² The example has an antipassive interpretation but it can also have a reciprocal reading, if, for instance, water is pouring simultaneously from different sources (e.g., fountains). In the latter case, we can retain a locative object

show that the applicative argument has object properties. However, *itĩka* is an intransitive verb due to the presence of the intransitivizing neuter marker. Unlike *rika*, valency-increasing morphology has to be added to *itĩka* to add an object argument (this, however, is different for *ika* which is a transitive verb). If valency-increasing morphology is realized, both bound object marking and passivization of the verb are possible. Unlike *rika*, however, *itĩka* does not license a morphological causative. The examples in (31) have consistently shown that the verb licenses the neuter marker.

- (31) a. *Maaĩ nĩ=ma-ra-itĩk-ĩr-a i-higa.*
 9.water FOC=9-PRS-pour-APPL-FV 5-rock
 ‘Water is pouring on the rock.’
- b. *Maaĩ nĩ=ma-ra-itĩk-an-ĩr-a*
 9.water FOC=9-PRS-pour-RECP-APPL-FV
 ‘The water is pouring (on something).’
- c. *Maaĩ nĩ=ma-ra-ri-itĩk-ĩr-a.*
 9.water FOC=9-PRS-5-pour-APPL-FV
 ‘Water is pouring on it.’
- d. *I-higa nĩ=rĩ-ra-itĩk-ĩr-wo nĩ maaĩ.*
 5-water FOC=5-PRS-pour-APPL-PASS by 9.water
 ‘The rock is being poured on by water.’

As an auxiliary, *itĩka* behaves exactly like *rika*: valency-increasing morphology is not possible, nor is valency-decreasing morphology (passive, reciprocal, neuter) or pronominalization of the object argument licensed. The impossibility of realizing the neuter marker may, of course, simply be due to the fact that it has already been realized formally. However, since the same restriction is observed with the other auxiliaries – which do not bear reflexes of this marker – we do not attribute the restriction to the form of the auxiliary but consider it as a general restriction of auxiliary verb usages in Gĩkũyũ.

Table 5: Comparison of the relevant morphosyntactic properties of the lexical with the auxiliary use of *itĩka*

	<i>ita</i> _{lexical}	<i>itĩka</i> _{aux}
bound object marking	yes	no
passive	yes	no
reciprocal	yes	no
neuter	yes	no
causative	no	no
applicative	yes	no

argument *i-higa-inĩ* ‘on the rock’ (lit. 5-rock-LOC).

4.4 Decategorialization of the auxiliary verbs

In Sections 4.1– 4.3 we compared the auxiliary verbs *korwo*, *enda*, *rika*, and *itika* with their corresponding lexical verbs in terms of voice morphology and the object properties of the complement. We summarize the results in Table 6.

Table 6: Comparison of the relevant morphosyntactic properties of the lexical use and the auxiliary use of the three verbs under discussion.

	<i>kora</i> _{lex.}	<i>korwo</i> _{aux.}	<i>enda</i> _{lex.}	<i>enda</i> _{aux.}	<i>rika</i> _{lex.}	<i>rika</i> _{aux.}	<i>ita</i> _{lex.}	<i>itika</i> _{aux.}
bound object marking	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no
reciprocal	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no
neuter	no	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no
passive	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no
causative	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no
applicative	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes	no

The lexical verbs differ from each other with regard to the licensing of voice morphology. Each of the four lexical verbs – unlike *hūra* ‘beat, hit’ (see Section 3) – has restrictions regarding its combination with causative and/or applicative morphology. Irrespective of the idiosyncratic restrictions of the lexical verbs, which may at least partially result from the verb meaning, none of the auxiliary verbs licenses valency-related morphology. This difference is not noticeable between *kora* and *korwo*, but the other auxiliary verbs definitely prove it. It is most clearly observed in bound object marking and passivization, as both are possible with all the lexical verbs examined, but not with the auxiliary verbs.

The auxiliary verbs show signs of internal decategorialization (Narrog and Heine 2021, 73), namely “loss of the ability to be inflected and to take on derivational morphology”. We can say that the auxiliary verbs have a smaller paradigm than their corresponding lexical verbs. Since our analysis was limited to only one area of verbal morphology, we cannot make any statement about how advanced the internal decategorialization of the four auxiliary verbs is. The auxiliary verbs also show signs of external decategorialization (Narrog and Heine 2021, 75) in the form of an “increasing dependence on some other form”. For all four auxiliary verbs, it is required that the finite complement (with *korwo*) or the infinitive (with the other three verbs) be obligatorily realized in order to obtain a complete predication. The reason is that the auxiliary verbs are semantically defective and require an eventuality-denoting expression as their complement. As a consequence, auxiliary verbs form a complex predicate with the finite complement/infinitive. We refer to this as the non-subject complement of the auxiliary.

An essential aspect of external decategorialization is that the relationship between the verb and its non-subject complement changes. Lexical verbs take object arguments as complements. In the case of auxiliary verbs, however, the complement no longer has any object properties, as it has syntactically become part of the predicate complex. It still complements the auxiliary verb, but the semantic relation between the two has changed and with it the syntactic status. This is accompanied by a detransitivization of the verb, as it now only takes one argument instead of two. The next step in the development is a categorical change in the complement: instead of an NP – with an infinitive as head – the auxiliary requires a verb. We can represent this development as follows:

(32) NP > NP_{inf} > VERB

We have no direct evidence to support the intermediate step – the change in the complement from NP to NP_{INF} – in the diachronic development of *korwo* AVCs. Indirect evidence is provided by the auxiliarization of *enda*. As a lexical verb, *enda* can be combined with NPs, NP_{INF} and also verbs as complements. As an auxiliary verb, *enda* only combines with NP_{INF}. As an auxiliary, *enda* is thus categorically more restricted than as a lexical verb. The reason is that *enda* with a verbal complement is a biclausal structure, whereas AVCs are monoclausal. The detour via a restriction to NP_{INF} before combining an auxiliary with other verbs can therefore be seen in the fact that biclausal structures are avoided in this way.¹³ We will not discuss the process(es) that create monoclausal from biclausal structures but there exists an extensive literature on this issue which the reader is referred to (e.g., Harris and Campbell 1995 and Bentley and Eythórsson 2004, among others).

4.5 Auxiliary verb constructions are complex predicates

We claimed above that AVCs are complex predicates. Butt (1997, 108) lists the following definitional characteristics for complex predicates:

- The argument structure is complex (two or more semantic heads contribute arguments).
- The grammatical functional structure is that of a simple predicate. It is *flat*: there is only one subject, one object, etc.

We mentioned above that auxiliary verbs only license one argument, even if the corresponding lexical verbs are transitive. The infinitive or finite verb complement has no argument status. The only required argument is the subject, which is only marked on the auxiliary verb in the *rika*, *enda*, and *itika* AVCs, and on the auxiliary verb plus the complement in the case of the *korwo* AVCs. The infinitive complements do not allow subject marking morphologically, as the infinitive marker occupies the subject slot. However, the requirement of the *korwo* AVCs' for the subject argument to be marked on the auxiliary verb and on the verb complement is identical. Thus, the AVC has only one subject.

Any existing non-subject arguments of the AVC are licensed by the complement. Depending on the valency of the complement, different numbers of non-subject arguments can be realized. We illustrate this with the auxiliary verb *rika*. In (33a) we have an infinitive derived from the intransitive verb *rîra* 'to cry'. Accordingly, no object argument can be realized. The addition of a post-verbal NP results in an ungrammatical sentence. In (33b), on the other hand, we have a transitive verb *ina* 'to sing something', so that a post-verbal NP (*rwîmbo* 'sing') is licensed.

¹³An alternative is that biclausal structures are reinterpreted as monoclausal. Since *kora* as a lexical verb does not occur with a verbal complement, we exclude this as a plausible scenario for the auxiliarization of *korwo*. An anonymous reviewer noted that our conclusion was "a bit too hasty." As the reviewer writes: "If the auxiliary *korwo* originated from a passive construction meaning 'be found that V', its development may have followed a resultative or inferential path, distinct from the inceptive and prospective auxiliaries. This could explain why it combines with a finite verb rather than an infinitive. The compatibility of *korwo* introducing or relating clauses can also be seen in its conditional use." We agree that this is not only a plausible scenario, but also one that fits well with conditional use. However, in order to decide which of the scenarios is most plausible, a more detailed study is needed that tests the different predictions using adequate (historical) language data.

- (33) a. *Ka-hĩĩ* *ga-kĩ-rik-a* *kũ-rĩr-a*.
 12-boy 12-NARR-AUX-FV 15-cry-FV
 ‘And the boy began to cry.’
- b. *Nĩ=ma-a-rik-ir-e* *kũ-in-a* *rw-ĩmbo*.
 FOC=2-PST-AUX-PFV-FV 15-sing-FV 11-song
 ‘They began to sing a song.’

The fact that AVCs have a joint argument structure in which each grammatical function is only assigned once is also shown by the valency-related morphology discussed in this paper. So far, we have shown that bound object marking and voice marking are not possible on the auxiliary verb. Instead, however, both can be realized on the infinitive or verbal complement.¹⁴ In (34a) we can see that the object argument of the infinitive can be pronominalized.¹⁵ In (34b) we can see that passivization of the object argument is possible. Passive marking occurs on the infinitive and the passivized argument is realized as the subject of the AVC (as well as being realized by the subject marker on the auxiliary).

- (34) a. *Nĩ=ma-a-rik-ir-e* *kũ-rũ-in-a*.
 FOC=3PL-PST-AUX-PFV-FV 15-11-sing-FV
 ‘They began to sing it.’
- b. *Nĩ=rũ-ra-rik-ir-e* *kũ-in-wo* *nĩ mũ-tumia*.
 FOC=11-PST-AUX-PFV-FV 15-sing-PASS by 1-woman
 ‘It [e.g., a song] was begun to be sung by the woman.’

The same applies to causative morphology, as shown in (35a). The causative is marked on the infinitive; the argument marked on the auxiliary verb is interpreted as the causer (i.e., the one causing the singing). The causee *andũ* ‘people’ does not have to be realized overtly. The sentence has several interpretations, including a causative interpretation and the reading ‘to conduct a song’. In (35b), the argument extension is also shown by the realization of the applicative morpheme on the infinitive.

- (35) a. *Ma-a-rik-ir-e* *kũ-in-ithi-a* (*a-ndũ*) *rw-ĩmbo*.
 2-PST-AUX-PFV-FV 15-sing-CAUS-FV 2-people 11-song
 ‘They began conducting the song/ They were making the people sing the song/
 They were leading the people to sing the song.’

¹⁴ For reasons of space, we illustrate this using the *rika* AVCs as an example, but the other AVCs discussed in this article have the same properties.

¹⁵ If the bound object marker is analysed as object agreement, (34a) can be analysed as a clear instance of a ‘split inflectional pattern’ (Anderson 2006, 2011a, 806–808, 2011b, 38–42), in which subject information is marked on the auxiliary verb and object information on the lexical verb. Arguments against an analysis of the bound object marker in Gikūyū are given in Fleischhauer (2023a), so we do not adopt the ‘split inflectional analysis’ for (34a).

- b. *Nĩ=ma-a-rik-ir-e* *kũ-in-ĩr-a* *a-geni* *rw-ĩmbo*.
 FOC=3PL-PST-AUX-PFV-FV 15-sing-APPL-FV 2-guest 11-song
 ‘They began to sing a song for the guests.’

The data show not only that the auxiliary verb and the complement have a joint argument structure, but also that all valency-related properties can be realized in AVCs. However, the realization takes place on the semantic head of the construction, i.e., the complement. There is a plausible explanation for this. We have already shown in the discussion of the auxiliary usage of *enda* in Section 4.2 that although the auxiliary verb does not allow reciprocal marking, the marker is possible in the infinitive. This can be justified semantically, since it is not the aspectual meaning specified by the auxiliary that can be performed reciprocally, but rather the eventuality denoted by the infinitive. The fact that the reciprocal marker is realized on the infinitive and not on the auxiliary is thus motivated by the principle of relevance (Bybee 1985). As Bybee et al. (1994, 22) write: “Relevance is the extent to which the meaning of a grammatical category affects the inherent meaning of the lexical stem with which it is associated.” Since it is the eventuality denoted by the infinitive that is reciprocally performed, the realization of the reciprocal suffix in relation to the infinitive and not the auxiliary is most relevant. The same applies, of course, to the other voice categories, since they either directly affect the eventuality denoted by the infinitive (i.e., represent it as caused or introduce another participant affected by the eventuality) or foreground the participants involved in this eventuality (i.e., foregrounding of the object argument in the passive or neuter voice).

5 Light verbs

In Section 4, we argued that auxiliary verbs exhibit both internal and external decategorialization. In this section, we argue that light verbs are desemanticized, but show no signs of decategorialization compared to their corresponding lexical verb – also called ‘heavy verb usage’ in the literature (see Riccio and Fleischhauer 2025). Since we argue that light verbs are not auxiliary verbs, the question arises as to what grammatical status they then have. We follow Butt and Geuder (2003) and Butt and Lahiri (2013), among others, and treat them as lexical verbs, so that lexical verbs have a light and a heavy verb usage. Accordingly, in this section we contrast light verbs with the heavy usage of the same lexical verbs (heavy verbs for short).

Light verb constructions, like AVCs, are complex predicates, but differ from AVCs in that they take neither an infinitival nor a verbal complement. Rather, their complements can only be NPs with lexical nouns as heads. Illustrative examples are given in (36). The light verb *hũra* ‘beat, hit’ takes different nouns – e.g., *thimũ* ‘phone’, *nguo* ‘clothes’, and *baĩni* ‘fine’ – as complements and denotes eventualities that are determined by the nouns.¹⁶ The eventuality denoted is not arbitrary and can be derived from the noun’s meaning – e.g., it is the event in which *thimũ* ‘phone’ plays a salient role as an instrument, or in which it fulfils its actual function. For reasons of space, we cannot go into the details of semantic composition here, as our focus is on

¹⁶ Light verb constructions are an underrepresented topic in Bantu linguistics. In addition to a study on Gĩkũyũ (Fleischhauer and Kihara 2025), there are several studies on LVCs with the light verb *piga* ‘hit, beat’ in Swahili (Olejarnik 2009, 2011; Martin 2019). The extent to which Gĩkũyũ has other light verbs besides *hũra* cannot be answered at this point due to a lack of relevant research. However, *piga* LVCs are comparable in various respects to the *hũra* LVCs examined in this paper. This allows for a contrastive comparison with corresponding constructions in Swahili (see Fleischhauer and Kihara 2025).

a comparison of the grammatical properties of LVCs with those of AVCs (but see Fleischhauer and Riccio 2025, 10–11 for a brief, informal discussion).

- (36) a. *Mũ-tumia nĩ=a-ra-hũr-a* *thimũ.*
 1-woman FOC=1-PRS-beat-FV 9.phone
 ‘The woman is making a call.’
- b. *Mũ-tumia nĩ=a-ra-hũr-a* *nguo.*
 1-woman FOC=1-PRS-beat-FV 10.clothes
 ‘The woman is washing the clothes.’
- c. *I-goti nĩ=ri-a-hũr-ir-e* *mũ-ndũ* *baĩni.*
 5-court FOC=5-PST-beat-PFV-FV 1-person 9.fine
 ‘The court fined the person.’

Jespersen (1942), who coined the term, proposed that light verbs are semantically empty. Such a position is still sometimes held; for example, Anderson (2011a, 811) writes that “the ‘light’ verb merely serves as an inflectable verbal stem or a kind of dummy placeholder to bear obligatory verbal inflectional material in order to render the clause grammatical and well-formed”. However, numerous studies have shown that light verbs are not semantically empty. Rather, they contribute to the meaning of the complex predicate (e.g., *Aktionsart* or phasal aspect, but also passive voice meaning; see Bower 2008; Butt 2010; Butt and Geuder 2003; Fleischhauer and Neisani 2020, among others; see also the literature cited in Riccio and Fleischhauer 2025). At this point, we therefore deviate from Jespersen’s and Anderson’s position and assume that light verbs are semantically reduced (compared to the corresponding lexical verbs) but not semantically empty. This is important to note because Anderson argues that certain complex predicates in Hindi/Urdu should be analysed as AVCs and not LVCs, “since the verb under consideration adds a functional specification to the overall formation” (Anderson 2011a, 811; see also Anderson 2006, 17). In our view, this is not a sufficient criterion for characterizing a complex predicate as an AVC rather than an LVC. Although we do not present a precise definition of the terms ‘light verb’ and ‘light verb construction’, we think that they can be distinguished from AVCs – at least in Gikūyū – on the basis of morphosyntactic properties (but see Fleischhauer and Riccio 2025, 14 for a definition of the term ‘light verb construction’).

We have already discussed the grammatical properties of the heavy verb corresponding to the light verb *hũra* in Section 3. With regard to the valency-based properties addressed in the current analysis, *hũra* shows no restrictions in its heavy verb use: the object can be pronominalized by a bound object marker and can become the subject by passivization; applicative and causative morphology is licensed by the verb and leads to an increase in valency. Reciprocal and neuter marking result in valency reduction and can be added to the verb stem.

In its light verb usage, *hũra* shows no grammatical differences from its heavy verb usage. To illustrate this, we take the LVC *hũra thimũ* ‘to make a call’ in (36a) as an example. In (37) we see that *thimũ* can be pronominalized, so the noun must be realized as right-dislocated. Pronominalization creates an intensifying function that we cannot currently explain and that does not show up in other LVCs.

- (37) *Nĩ=a-ra-mĩ-hũr-a, thimũ.*
 FOC=1-PRS-9-beat-FV 9.phone
 ‘S/he is (really) calling the phone regularly. / He is calling extensively.’

The example in (38a) shows that *thimũ* can become the subject of a passive construction, so the nominal complement of the light verb has direct object properties. In (38b), we see that a reciprocal marker can be realized with the light verb. As the translation indicates, the reciprocal marker can result both in a reciprocal interpretation and in an antipassive one.

- (38) a. *Thimũ nĩ=ya-a-hũr-wo.*
 9.phone FOC=9-PST-beat-PASS
 ‘A phone call was made.’
 b. *Nĩ=ma-a-hũr-an-ĩr-a thimũ.*
 FOC=2-PST -beat-RECP-APPL-FV 9.phone
 ‘They have called each other. / They called someone on behalf of other people.’

The neuter marker *-ik* is incompatible with the LVC *hũra thimũ*. The realization of the marker leads to a heavy interpretation of *hũra*, and the sentence takes on a patient-oriented potential reading (‘The phone is not going through’ lit. The phone is not beatable; cf. 8c). However, the neuter marker is compatible with other *hũra* LVCs, such as *hũra bairi* ‘to fine someone’ (39a). Unlike *hũra thimũ*, *hũra bairi* is ditransitive. *Bairi* ‘fine’, which is part of the complex predicate, is not affected by the neuter marker, but the patient argument becomes the subject (for a more detailed discussion of the LVC *hũra bairi*, see Fleischhauer and Kihara 2025).

- (39) a. *I-goti nĩ=rĩ-a-hũr-ir-e mũ-ndũ bairi.*
 5-court FOC =5-PST-beat-PFV-FV 1-person 9.fine
 ‘The court fined the person.’ (Fleischhauer and Kihara 2025, 95)
 b. *Ma-ti-ngĩ-hũr-ĩk-a bairi.*
 3PL-NEG-POSS-beat-NEUT-FV 9.fine
 ‘They cannot be fined.’

Finally, we see in (40) and (41) that the light verb allows applicativization and causativization.

- (40) *Mũ-tumia nĩ=a-ra-hũr-ĩr-wo thimũ nĩ nyina.*
 1.woman FOC=1-PRS-beat-APPL-PASS 9.phone by 1.mother
 ‘The woman is being called by her mother.’
 (41) *A-tũ-hũr-ith-ir-i-e thimũ ci-a tũhũ.*
 1-2-beat-CAUS-PFV-DC-FV 10.phone 10-ASSOC useless
 ‘S/He had made us make useless calls.’

The examples discussed in this section show that the valency-related morphology that cannot be realized with auxiliary verbs can be realized with light verbs. Unlike AVCs, however, LVCs

do not allow this type of morphology to be realized on the complement, as they are genuine nouns and not nominalized infinitives. Thus, the only option is to have this kind of marker realized on the light verb. If we now compare light verbs with auxiliary verbs, we see that although both are desemanticized – in comparison to the corresponding lexical verb /heavy verb – the grammatical restrictions that we find with *korwo*, *rika*, *enda*, and *itika* do not apply to the light verb *hũra*. Thus, there are no signs of decategorialization of the light verb with regard to the properties examined.

6 Conclusion

Gĩkũyũ has various verbal lexemes which, in combination with a verbal root – realized either as a verb or as an infinitive – form a monoclausal construction which differs aspectually from the use of the verbal root as the (only) finite element in the sentence. We have summarized these uses under the term ‘auxiliary verb’, whereby we have used the label for all four verbs examined, *korwo*, *enda*, *rika*, and *itika*, in an idealizing way. Auxiliarization, however, is a gradual process (Anderson 2011a, 797), at the end of which there is a highly grammaticalized auxiliary whose use is conventionalized. We do not observe this in the auxiliaries examined in Gĩkũyũ. Accordingly, it would also have been possible to use a label such as ‘semi-auxiliary’ or ‘quasi-auxiliary’ to indicate that the auxiliarization process is still ongoing. Due to the lack of clear criteria for differentiating between genuine auxiliaries and ‘semi-’ or ‘quasi-auxiliaries’ (see Bolinger 1980: 297), we have refrained from using such a terminological distinction.

With regard to auxiliarization, we have considered two processes: desemanticization and decategorialization (we have not addressed the related process of context extension; see Heine 1993, 48–52; Narrog and Heine 2021, 57–66). We operationalized desemanticization – as a result and not as a process – as ‘semantic defectiveness’, i.e., the loss of the denotative meaning (and thus also the denoted eventuality) of a verb. Both auxiliary verbs and light verbs prove to be semantically defective. Both are thus – in the result reading – desemanticized. Whether the semantic defectiveness of light verbs is the result of a desemanticization process is disputed in the research literature (see Butt and Lahiri 2013). For our argument, however, it is only central that ‘semantic defectiveness’ is a feature that auxiliary verbs share with light verbs and that distinguishes both from lexical verbs (heavy verb usages).

A comparison of valency-related properties has shown that auxiliary verbs exhibit morpho-syntactic constraints that their corresponding lexical verbs do not possess. We attributed these restrictions primarily to changes in the verb-complement relationship. While the non-subject complement of lexical verbs has argument status – even if it is realized by an infinitive – it has no argument status in the AVCs. However, it remains a complement in the sense that it is required as a necessary supplement to complement the predication. Auxiliary verbs and their complements form complex predicates.

We have interpreted the morphosyntactic differences between auxiliary verbs and their corresponding lexical verbs as decategorialization resulting from the formation of the complex predicate. Light verbs show no signs of decategorialization, although they also represent complex predicates. The central difference between AVCs and LVCs, however, is that the complement of an auxiliary verb is (at least originally) verbal in nature (whether a finite or nonfinite verb), whereas light verbs take NPs with genuine nouns as heads as their complements. In his definition of the term ‘light verb’, Jespersen (1942) writes that the function of the light verb is to license a noun as a predicative element and to realize verbal features that the noun cannot trivially carry. Jespersen is right about this aspect: since the light verb combines with a non-verbal

element, it must itself carry the relevant verbal features, which cannot be realized in any other way than via the light verb. Therefore, we argue, light verbs show no signs of decategorialization, since otherwise there would be a loss of verbal functions (e.g., increase in valency) that cannot be compensated for (similarly Anderson 2011a, 812). In the case of auxiliary verbs, the decategorialization of the verbs is compensated for by the fact that the affixed morphology can be realized at the semantic core – which is also relevant for licensing the arguments. This means that AVCs do not lose any functionality compared to lexical verbs. This also reflects the greater relevance of finite complements or infinitives compared to auxiliaries for the realization of voice-related markers.

Based on the results of the present study, we make the following generalizations (for Gĩkũyũ) for the categories ‘auxiliary verb’ and ‘light verb’:

1. Auxiliary verbs always show signs of decategorialization resulting from the fact that they form a complex predicate with their complement.

Accordingly, we would terminologically restrict the term ‘auxiliary verb’ to verb usages that show signs of decategorialization.

2. Light verbs never show signs of decategorialization although they form a complex predicate with their complement.

Although we use the term ‘complex predicate’ for both constructions, the analysis shows that they are two fundamentally different types of complex predicates, which require a clear terminological distinction between ‘auxiliary verb construction’ and ‘light verb construction’.

Whether light verbs are an intermediate step in the development of auxiliaries – desemantized but not yet decategorized – is left open at this point. We also cannot make any statements about the specific grammaticalization path and can only indicate the order of the steps in which the auxiliary formation of the verbs discussed took place. The reason is that we do not have any historical data for Gĩkũyũ that would allow us to draw conclusions about earlier uses of auxiliaries or light verbs.

We see the present study as a prelude to a better understanding of the categories ‘auxiliary verb’ and ‘light verb’ in Gĩkũyũ, but also in general, and hope that it inspires further studies investigating the categories of auxiliary verbs and light verbs from a contrastive and cross-linguistic perspective. Thus, the next steps in order to test whether the generalizations made above form valid language-specific or, in the best case, cross-linguistic categories, will involve examining additional desemantized verbs – both in Gĩkũyũ and in other languages – regarding the presence of possible signs of decategorialization.

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Abbreviations

APPL: applicative, ASSOC: associative, AUX: auxiliary, CAUS: causative, DC: dislocated element, FOC: focus marker, FV: final vowel, IMPF: imperfective, INF: infinitive, LOC: locative, NARR: narrative tense, NEG: negation, NEUT: neuter, PASS: passive, PFT: perfect, PFV: perfective, PL: plural, PRS: present, POSS: possibility, PST: past, RECP: reciprocal, SG: singular, Arabic numbers: noun classes

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On the Morphology, Interpretation, and Development of the Kagulu Auxiliary *ng'hali*

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Abstract

The Kagulu auxiliary verb *ng'hali* appears in a variety of auxiliary verb constructions and has several phonological realizations (*ng'hali*, *kali*, and *ng'hati*). Unlike other auxiliary verbs in the language, *ng'hali* occurs with limited morphology and is not used as a main verb. As in many Bantu languages, *ng'hali* has phasal polarity properties (see van Baar 1997; Kramer 2021): it yields 'still' and 'not yet' interpretations. The goal of this paper is to describe the morphophonological, morphosyntactic, and morphosemantic properties of *ng'hali*. We explore the development of *ng'hali* into an aspect marker and its co-occurrence with more complex auxiliary verb constructions consisting of other Kagulu verbs, namely the auxiliary *uwa* 'be' and *gendelela* 'continue'. In addition to being the first detailed description of these underdocumented properties of *ng'hali*, this study contributes to our understanding of the role that auxiliaries play in languages with reduced tense/aspect morphology, as well as the grammaticalization paths of auxiliaries in Bantu languages.

Keywords: auxiliary verbs, Kagulu (Greater East Ruvu languages), grammaticalization, tense and aspect, phasal polarity

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1 Introduction

Auxiliary constructions are a central strategy for encoding tense, aspect, and mood distinctions across Bantu languages (Gibson 2025). Like many other language families, Bantu languages employ both simple verb forms, consisting of a single inflected verb, and auxiliary verb constructions (AVCs) (Anderson 2011), which involve one or more auxiliaries¹ followed by a lexical verb (Nurse 2008; Nurse and Devos 2019, 206; Gibson 2019; Gunnink 2023). Morphosyntactically, auxiliaries as well as the main verb host subject agreement and tense-aspect (TA) morphology. However, this is not always the case: in some Bantu languages the auxiliary alone may host agreement, leaving the main verb in the infinitive.² Functionally, auxiliaries serve to encode TA distinctions, negation, polarity, and adverbial-like functions (Nurse and Philippson 2006; Gibson 2025). When auxiliaries are followed by finite main verbs, it is often the case that they convey temporal information, while the main verb supplies aspectual detail (Nurse 2008, 29), as shown in (1), where future morphology (*ta-*) appears on the auxiliary *wa* ‘be’ and the progressive morpheme *na-* appears on the main verb *imba* ‘sing’.

- (1) Swahili
Atakuwa anaimba.
 a-**ta**-ku-w-a a-**na**-imb-a
 SM1-FUT-INF-be-FV SM1-PROG-sing-FV
 ‘S/he will be singing.’

Bantu AVCs also allow for cross-referencing of object arguments and the expression of negation, either via negative auxiliaries or by marking polarity on an auxiliary or main verb. Historically, auxiliaries in Bantu languages often emerge through the grammaticalization of lexical verbs that once selected infinitival complements, some of which later fused with main verbs or retained infinitival markers (Givón 1971; Botne 1989, 169; Nurse 2008, 60; Bernander 2018, 673; Bernander et al. 2022, 68).

The East African Bantu language Kagulu (ISO 639, *kki*) has an auxiliary with the phonological realizations *ng'hali*, *kali*, and *ng'hati* (henceforth *NG'HALI*). *NG'HALI* occurs with both finite and infinitive complements, displays varying degrees of grammaticalization, and yields ‘still’ (2a) and ‘not yet’ (2b) readings, depending on the construction in which it appears. (2a) below shows that the ‘still’ interpretation arises when *NG'HALI* is followed by a finite main verb prefixed with tense morphology, while (2b) shows that the ‘not yet’ interpretation arises when *NG'HALI* is followed by a subjunctive finite main verb.

- (2) a. *Mwana yang'hali yakusoma.*
 mu-ana ya-**ng'hali** ya-ku-som-a
 1-child SM1-PER SM1-NON_PST-read-FV
 ‘The child is still studying.’ (2403162roz, sau)

¹ This description does not preclude some of these auxiliaries from functioning as main verbs in other sentences.

² AVCs are referred to in different ways in the literature. Schadeberg (1992) refers to an auxiliary with an infinitival main verb as a compound verbal construction and an auxiliary with a finite main verb as a complex verbal construction, while Gibson (2025) and Nurse (2008) refer to an auxiliary with a finite main verb as a compound construction, and have no dedicated term for an auxiliary with an infinitival complement.

b. *Amina yang'hali yamanye.*

Amina ya-**ng'hali** ya-many-e

Amina SM1-PER SM1-know-SBJV

'Amina does not yet know.' (8445roz, sau)

NG'HALI differs from most auxiliary verbs in Kagulu since it is never used as a main verb, and appears with limited morphology (e.g., it is not suffixed by a final vowel).

The first mention of NG'HALI is in Last (1886), who lists the verbal paradigm of a form *k'ali*, translated as 'not yet' (Last 1886, 76). The form is briefly mentioned in two other sources (Beidelman 1963, 65; 1967, 27), where it is translated as 'still':

(3)... *we nghali wadodogi* 'while still infants' (Beidelman 1967, 27).

Although sources on neighbouring languages are scarce, *ng'ali*, which we take to be a cognate of NG'HALI, is found in Kami (Petzell and Edelsten 2024, 303; Velten 1900, 29) and Luguru (Petzell and Khül 2017, 45). A similar auxiliary is reported for Swahili: *ngali*³ 'still' (Ashton 1944, 270). However, this auxiliary does not seem to be used today (Zahran 2020, 21).

NG'HALI exhibits phasal polarity properties. Phasal polarity is the term used to refer to the group of meanings 'still', 'not yet', 'already', and 'no longer'. These sets of meanings are related to each other via negation. For example, 'still' encodes that an eventuality persists at a reference time, while its negated counterpart corresponds to 'no longer'. Conversely, 'not yet' encodes that an eventuality has thus far not come to be, while its affirmative counterpart corresponds to 'already'. Bantu languages are known for having expressions with phasal polarity (see van Baar 1997; Kramer 2021). As illustrated in (2) above, Kagulu NG'HALI yields both 'still' and 'not yet' meanings. Although these meanings arise in different constructions, they are in a sense the same meanings and differ only in whether the eventuality holds. We gloss NG'HALI as persistive and show that the 'still' and 'not yet' interpretations are dependent on the constructions in which NG'HALI is found. Persistive marking has been described for other Bantu languages. For example, Abe (2015) examines the Bende persistive verbal marker *sí-/syá-* that shares similarities with NG'HALI with respect to the types of constructions in which it appears and the meanings that arise.

The goal of this study is to describe the morphophonological, morphosyntactic, and morphosemantic properties of the largely undescribed NG'HALI in Kagulu. This paper offers the first detailed description of these properties in Kagulu and establishes a foundation for future comparative work on cognate auxiliaries in Greater East Ruvu languages, as well as in other Bantu languages where this auxiliary has yet to be explored. This study is significant given the typological profile of the Greater East Ruvu Bantu languages, which lack the dense TA paradigms characteristic of other Bantu subgroups (Nurse and Devos 2019). Auxiliaries in such languages shoulder much of the functional load in tense, aspect, and mood expression, and the study of NG'HALI provides a window into how such systems adapt and expand. More broadly, the development of NG'HALI into a TA prefix points to ongoing grammaticalization processes, in which auxiliaries gradually fuse into the verbal template (Heine 1993; Bernander et al. 2022).

The paper is organized as follows. We first provide a brief background of Kagulu, focusing on a synopsis of its TA system (Section 2). We then describe the morphophonological, morphosyntactic, and morphosemantic properties of the auxiliary NG'HALI in Kagulu (Section

³According to Ashton (1944, 270), the allomorph *kali* is used in Mombasa.

3). Following this description, we provide an account of the development of NG'HALI into a TA prefix (Section 4). We then examine the co-occurrence of NG'HALI with other Kagulu auxiliaries in more complex AVCs (Section 5). We conclude with a summary of the main findings of this study and a discussion of the implications of this analysis within the study of Bantu languages and beyond (Section 6).

2 Language background and language data

Kagulu is one of the eight Greater East Ruvu Bantu languages spoken in the Morogoro region in Tanzania (Petzell and Hammarström 2013, 129). It is spoken by approximately 336,000 speakers (Languages of Tanzania Project 2009, 2), and is categorized as a G12 language, following Guthrie's referential classification (1967/1971). The Kagulu-speaking population is surrounded by Ngulu (G34) and Luguru (G35) to the east, Sagala (G39) to the south, and Gogo (G11) to the west. The Nilotic language Maasai is spoken to the north, making Kagulu part of a diverse linguistic area where contact and diffusion have historically played a role in shaping morphosyntactic structures (Kießling et al. 2008). There are dialectal varieties of Kagulu, such as the one spoken in the Nongwe area, which is part of the prestigious mountain variety (Petzell 2012, 24).

Although Bantu languages are known for their rich TA morphology, Kagulu is comparatively restricted in this regard. Kagulu has three overt tense morphemes: a non-past morpheme (4a), a non-obligatory past morpheme (4b) (see also Bar-el and Petzell 2021, 537), and a future morpheme (4c).

- (4) a. *Yakuluta*.
 ya-ku-lut-a
 SM1-NON_PST-leave-FV
 'S/he is going.' or 'S/he will go.' (Petzell 2008, 108)
- b. *Hakaluta*.
 ha-ka-lut-a
 PST-SM1-leave-FV
 'S/he went.' (Petzell 2008, 110)
- c. *Wakalima umugunda wao*.
 wa-ka-lim-a u-mu-gunda u-ao
 SM2-FUT-cultivate-FV AUP-3-farm 3-POSS.3PL
 'They shall cultivate their farm.' (3172Bsyd)

Aspect can be marked by a habitual morpheme (5a), or by AVCs (5b) (see Petzell 2008; Bar-el and Petzell 2024; Petzell and Edelsten 2024).

- (5) a. *Hakejaga*.
 ha-ka-ij-ag-a
 PST-SM1-come-HAB-FV
 'S/he came (regularly).' (Petzell and Edelsten 2024, 310)

b. *Amina yekuwa yebilima.*

Amina ye-ku-uw-a ye-bilim-a

Amina SM1-NON_PST-be-FV SM1-know-FV

‘Amina usually runs.’ (9025roz)

Note that class 1 is the only noun class that has two different subject markers in Kagulu: *ya-/ye-*⁴ (4a, 5b) and *ka-* (4b–c, 5a).

This typological profile sets Kagulu apart from other Bantu languages which exhibit rich TA paradigms. Moreover, it aligns Kagulu more closely with neighbouring Ruvu Bantu languages such as Luguru and Kami, which also rely on auxiliaries, especially for TA categories that are not morphologically expressed (Nurse 2019, 174; Bar-el and Petzell 2024, 212).

Verbs such as *uwa* ‘be’, *gendelela* ‘continue’, *genda* ‘go’, *ija* ‘come’, *leka* ‘let alone’, *fulusa* or *mala* ‘finish’, and *sowela* ‘be used to’ serve as the primary means of expressing temporal, aspectual, and modal nuances when they occur in AVCs (their co-occurrence with NG’HALI is discussed in Section 5). These verbs retain their ability to function as main verbs but are frequently deployed in periphrastic tense, aspect, and mood constructions, demonstrating the productive overlap between lexical and auxiliary uses in Kagulu.

The data that make up the Kagulu corpus referenced throughout this paper were collected by the authors during fieldwork between 2003 and 2025. The database consists of more than 3,000 sentences, as well as seven interlinearized stories (see Petzell and Jordan 2022 for detailed discussion of the Greater East Ruvu database). The speakers consulted are all first language Kagulu speakers who are bilingual in Swahili. Some Kagulu speakers also speak English. A combination of structured interviews, direct translations and back-translations, grammaticality judgements, descriptive contexts, and non-verbal stimuli were used to elicit the forms, primarily using Swahili, and at times English, as a metalanguage. The bulk of the data in this paper are from two speakers of the Nongwe variety of Kagulu.

Data from the Kagulu corpus are cited throughout the paper with their unique ID codes in the database. The codes consist of the number of the questionnaire or elicitation session, a sentence number, and speaker code(s) (Petzell and Jordan 2022, 615). The data were collected over a period of 23 years, using different questionnaires and elicitation methods, hence the spread in the usage of ID numbers. Data collected in 2024 and 2025 are in the process of being coded and have been given temporary IDs for the purpose of this paper.

3 Properties of Kagulu NG’HALI

In this section, we explore the morphophonological (Section 3.1), morphosyntactic (Section 3.2), and morphosemantic (Section 3.3) properties of Kagulu NG’HALI. This discussion sets the groundwork for the grammaticalization analysis in Section 4.

⁴Speakers alternate freely between *ya-* and *ye-*. Since their use is not phonologically predictable, we represent both alternates as underlying forms in the data. The forms are typically used with present and future constructions, as well as in dependent clauses and with auxiliaries (see Petzell 2008 and Bar-el and Petzell 2021 for discussion). *ka-*, on the other hand, is typically used in past constructions (that is, when there is no overt tense morphology). However, Bar-el and Petzell (2024) point out that when *ka-* occurs in a construction with the imperfective morpheme *-ag-*, the sentence is interpreted as a present habitual.

3.1 Morphophonological properties

As noted in Section 1, NG'HALI has three different phonological realizations, the two allomorphs *ng'hali* and *kali* (Petzell 2008) being primary. These two realizations differ only in the initial segment, which is either a voiceless velar nasal /ŋ/, orthographically represented as <ng'h>, or a voiceless velar stop. It is likely that this auxiliary consists of the Proto-Bantu persistive marker (*n*)*ka* (Güldemann 1998, 166) and a reflex of the copular Proto-Bantu **di* (Guthrie 1970, 150), as suggested by Veselinova and Devos (2021, 451). The copular Proto-Bantu **di* is realized as *li* in Swahili (Ashton 1944, 270), and in the neighbouring languages Luguru (Seidel 1898, 442) and Zalamo (Worms 1897, 305). Even though copular *li* does not occur in Kagulu (see Section 4 for discussion), we assume it is part of the reconstruction of NG'HALI.

The Proto-Bantu persistive marker *ka-* was most likely prenasalized at one point in time (Güldemann 1998, 166). In Kagulu, as in other Bantu languages, earlier prenasalized voiceless stops have developed into voiceless nasals (Maddieson 2003, 38). The voiceless nasals begin with an airstream passing through the nasal cavity during articulation, and the airflow may continue after the nasal segment ends, producing an effect similar to aspiration. Although described as 'voiceless', these nasals are often partially voiced. Furthermore, there is sometimes post-nasal aspiration, which can have a whisper-like quality (Petzell 2008, 39).

The variants *ng'hali* and *kali* are sometimes ascribed by Kagulu speakers to different dialects: *kali* is said to be the more 'correct' form of the mountain variety, while *ng'hali* is used in the more 'common' variety (Petzell fieldnotes 2004). *Ng'hali* is the more frequent realization of the persistive NG'HALI and is also the form that is used by all Kagulu speakers. The form *kali* is only used by speakers from the Nongwe (mountain) area. These speakers use *ng'hali* as well, albeit less often. Given that one speaker uses both forms in the same sentence, as in (6) below, we consider them allomorphs.

- (6) *Esta hakowa yeng'hali/yekali yamanyile.*
 Esta ha-ka-uw-a ye-**ng'hali/ye-kali** ya-many-ile
 Esta PST-SM1PST-be-FV SM1-PER/SM1-PER SM1-know-ILE
 'Esta still knew.' (1004sau)

A third variant, *ng'hati*, is documented for one of the six NG'HALI constructions in the Kagulu corpus⁵ (see Table 1 in Section 3.2 below).

3.2 Morphosyntactic properties

NG'HALI is prefixed with subject agreement markers, but not with tense or aspect marking (7a–b). Note that NG'HALI only takes the *ya-/ye-* subject marker for class 1, never *ka-* (see Section 2 above):

⁵ As for the origins of the *ng'hati* form, we posit a potential Proto-Bantu reflex of **ti* '(be/do) thus, like this/that' (Güldemann 2002, 268), preceded by a prenasalized Proto-Bantu persistive marker (*n*)*ka* (Güldemann 1998, 166). See Veselinova and Devos (2021, 458) and Bernander (2017, 199–200) for discussion. The fact that **ti* and also copular *li* lend themselves to this type of grammaticalization is not unexpected since old forms in dependent clauses "have so little semantic content on their own" (Bybee et al. 1994, 296), thus making them ideal candidates for grammaticalization.

- (7) a. *Imwana yang'hali kendeka.*
 i-mu-ana ya-**ng'hali** ka-end-ek-a
 AUP-1-child SM1-PER SM1-love-NEUT-FV
 'The child is still lovable.' (250351roz, sau)
- b. *Idimudyo dikali dikudiika.*
 i-di-mudyo di-**kali** di-ku-di-ik-a
 AUP-5-fruit SM5-PER SM5-NON_PST-eat-NEUT-FV
 'The fruit is still edible.' (6008sau)

Morphosyntactically, we group the constructions in which we find NG'HALI into three main types: (I) those in which the main verb is finite, (II) those in which the main verb is infinitival, and (III) those which exhibit further stages of grammaticalization. There are three subtypes of constructions in which the main verb is finite (Ia, Ib, Ic), and there are two subtypes of constructions exhibiting further stages of grammaticalization (IIIa, IIIb). These patterns are summarized in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Morphosyntactic properties of NG'HALI

	Subtype	Construction	Forms
I. Finite main verb	Ia	SM-NG'HALI SM-TA-V-FV	<i>ng'hali, kali</i>
	Ib	SM-NG'HALI SM-V-SBJV	<i>ng'hali, kali, ng'hati</i>
	Ic	SM-NG'HALI SM-V-ILE	<i>ng'hali, kali</i>
II. Infinitival main verb		SM-NG'HALI INF-V-FV	<i>ng'hali, kali</i>
III. Further stages of grammaticalization	IIIa	SM-NG'HALI-SM-V-ILE	<i>kali</i>
	IIIb	SM-NG'HALI-V-FV	<i>ng'hali, kali</i>

Both *ng'hali* and *kali* forms appear in each of these constructions, with the exception of IIIa, for which we have only documented the form *kali*. Furthermore, an additional form, *ng'hati*, appears with construction Ib only. We assume the absence of *ng'hali* in IIIa constructions to be an accidental gap in the corpus data (e.g., due to speaker variation, differences in data collection methods). The appearance of *ng'hati* may be semantically driven (see Section 3.3 for further discussion). The finite main verb constructions are discussed in Section 3.2.1, the infinitival main verb constructions in Section 3.2.2, and the constructions that exhibit further grammaticalization in Section 3.2.3.

3.2.1 AVCs with a finite main verb

In each of the NG'HALI constructions in which the main verb is finite, we observe a subject marker on NG'HALI and on the main verb. The two allomorphs *ng'hali* and *kali* appear in each of the subtypes of this construction. In sentences of subtype Ia (SM-NG'HALI SM-TA-V-FV), TA

morphology can appear on the main verb, as shown by the appearance of non-past *-ku-* in (8a)⁶; the main verb of Ia constructions can also surface without any TA morphology (8b):

- (8) a. *Ibalafu ing'hali ikuluguluka.*
 i-balafu i-**ng'hali** i-**ku-**luguluk-a
 AUP-9.ice SM9-PER SM9-NON_PST-melt-FV
 'The ice is still melting.' (250365roz, sau)
- b. *Yekali konela.*
 ye-**kali** ka-onel-a
 SM1-PER SM1-be/get_happy-FV
 'She is still happy.' (8316roz, sau)

In construction Ib (SM-NG'HALI SM-V-SBJV) the main verb takes a subjunctive suffix *-e*, as illustrated in (9):

- (9) a. *Amina yang'hali yamanye.*
 Amina ya-**ng'hali** ya-many-e
 Amina SM1-PER SM1-know-SBJV
 'Amina does not yet know.' (8445roz, sau)
- b. *Amina yakali yagende.*
 Amina ya-**kali** ya-gend-e
 Amina SM1-PER SM1-walk-SBJV
 'Amina has not yet walked.' (8289roz, sau)

Construction Ib is the only construction in which the form *ng'hali* is observed, as illustrated in (10) below:

- (10) a. *Amina yekusokaga*
 Amina ye-ku-sok-ag-a
 Amina SM1-NON_PST-be/get_tired-HAB-FV
lakini yang'hali yasoke.
 lakini ya-**ng'hali** ya-sok-e
 but SM1-PER SM1-be/get_tired-SBJV
 'Amina will get tired, but she is not yet tired.' (8294roz, sau)

⁶ See Petzell (2008) and Bar-el and Petzell (2021) for further discussion on tense and aspect in the Greater East Ruvu languages.

- b. *Leora konelaga*,
 Leora ka-one1-ag-a
 Leora SM1-be/get_happy-HAB-FV
lowo yang'hati yonele hambiya.
 lowo ya-**ng'hati** ya-one1-e hambiya
 but SM1-PER SM1-be/get_happy-SBJV now
 'Leora is always happy, but she is not [yet] happy now.' (8313roz, sau)
- c. *Ning'hati nilime mgunda wangu.*
 ni-**ng'hati** ni-lim-e mu-gunda u-angu
 SM1SG-PER SM1.SG-cultivate-SBJV 3-farm 3-POSS.1SG
 'I have not yet cultivated my farm.' (3153mta)

In construction Ic (SM-NG'HALI SM-V-ILE) the main verb takes the suffix *-ile*, as shown in (11). Note that unlike in other Bantu languages, where *-ile* is described as a perfect or perfective marker (see Nurse 2008; Botne 2010; Crane 2012 for discussion), in Kagulu, the appearance of *-ile* is restricted to dependent clauses, negation, and change-of-state main verbs in an AVC (see Petzell 2008; Bar-el and Petzell 2021).

- (11) a. *Nyagilisa simu na ing'hali yagilile.*
 ni-agil-is-a simu na i-**ng'hali** i-agil-ile
 SM.1SG-lost-CAUS-FV 9.phone and SM9-PER SM9-lost-ILE
 'I lost my phone, and it is still lost.' (8368roz, sau)
- b. *Isuke haidonha digulo*
 i-suke ha-i-donh-a digulo
 AUP-9.dress PST-SM9-be/get_wet-FV yesterday
na ikali idonhile.
 na i-**kali** i-donh-ile
 and SM9-PER SM9-be/get_wet-ILE
 'The dress was wet yesterday and is still wet.' (8297roz, sau)

Derived states (states derived by the neuter⁷ affix *-ik-* or its allomorph *-ek-*) appear in construction Ic, illustrated in (12) below. When the neuter morpheme *-ik-/-ek-* merges with *-ile*, it is abbreviated to *-ike* (see Petzell 2008, 126 for discussion).

- (12) *Isupa i-kali itulike.*
 i-supu i-**kali** i-tul-ike (< i-tul-ik-ile)
 AUP-9.bottle SM9-PER SM9-break-NEUT.ILE
 'The bottle is still broken.' (240331roz, sau)

Crucially, we analyse the final vowel *-e* in (12) as a phonological reduction of the suffix *-ile* after *-ik-*, and not as the subjunctive final vowel *-e* (compare (10) above and (14) below) in accordance with Kagulu morphophonology (see Petzell 2008). This is further illustrated in (13)

⁷Also labeled 'stative' (Dom et al. 2023, 134).

below. The sentence in (13a) contains a relative clause, another type of construction where *-ile* surfaces. The sentence in (13b) contains a relative clause where we expect *-ile*; however, as the verb *ben* ‘break’ takes the neuter suffix *-ek-*, the two suffixes surface as *-eke*. Note that these are not constructions in which we would expect the subjunctive; thus we analyse *-eke* in (13b) as a phonological reduction of *-ile* after *-ek-*, parallel to *-ike* in (12) above.

(13) a. *Imunhu yejile lumbu dyangu.*

i-mu-nhu ye-ij-ile lumbu di-angu
 AUP-1-person SM1-come-ILE 5.sibling_of_opposite_sex 5-POSS.1SG
 ‘The person who came is my brother.’ (3255jes)

b. *Umukono wa Komba ubeneke ukutaama.*

u-mu-kono wa Komba u-ben-eke u-ku-taam-a
 AUP-3-arm CON Komba SM3-break-NEUT.ILE SM3-NON_PST-hurt-FV
 ‘Komba’s arm, which is broken, hurts.’ (11374roz)

This reduction does not constitute imbrication (see Hyman 1995; Downing 1999; Morrison 2025) of the type attested in languages such as Nyakyusa (Persohn 2017, 144–152), where *-ile* fuses with stem-internal material and an *i*-vowel is inserted before the final root consonant (*ambilila* ‘receive; entertain guests’ > *ambili*<*i*>*l-e* > *ambiliile*). Instead, in Kagulu, *-ile* is reduced to *-e* without any root-internal alternation (see Section 3.3 for further discussion).

Derived states also appear in construction Ib (14a–b), a subjunctive construction, where the main verb is suffixed with a subjunctive *-e*.

(14) a. *Idijua ding'hali dyoneke.*

i-di-jua di-ng'hali di-on-ek-e
 AUP-5-sun SM5-PER SM5-appear-NEUT-SBJV
 ‘The sun has not yet appeared.’ (250341roz, sau)

b. *Matagi gang'hati/ng'hali gatulike.*

ma-tag-i ga-ng'hati/ng'hali ga-tul-ik-e
 6-egg SM6-PER SM6-break-NEUT-SBJV
 ‘The eggs are not yet broken.’ (240336roz, sau)

3.2.2 AVCs with an infinitival main verb

In the Kagulu corpus, when NG’HALI is followed by an infinitival main verb (construction II in Table 1 above: SM-NG’HALI INF-V-FV), we observe both variants, *ng'hali* and *kali*:

(15) a. *Hamwedu ni mndele*

hamwedu ni mu-ndele
 although COP 1-beauty

yeng'hali kutoligwa.

ye-ng'hali ku-tol-igw-a
 SM1-PER INF-be/get_married-PASS-FV

‘Although she is a beauty, she is not (yet) married.’ (3254mgu)

b. *Ning'hali kulima mgunda wangu.*

ni-**ng'hali** ku-lim-a mu-gunda u-angu
 SM.1SG-PER INF-cultivate-FV 3-farm 3-POSS.1SG
 'I have not yet cultivated my farm.' (3152mgu)

c. *Ngodi saka kahi sikali kwaka.*

ngodi si-ak-a kahi si-**kali** ku-ak-a
 10.firewood SM10-burn-FV again SM10-PER INF-burn-FV
 'The firewood has burnt and it is still burning.' (240399roz, sau)

d. *Amina yakali kwija kila siku hang'halisiku.*

Amina ya-**kali** ku-ij-a kila siku hang'halisiku⁸
 Amina SM1-PER INF-arrive-FV every 9.day early_morning
 'Amina still arrives early every morning' (9046roz)

NG'HALI followed by an infinitival main verb is not always judged felicitous, as illustrated in (16):

(16) #*Hanimanya na nikali kumanya.*

#ha-ni-many-a na ni-**kali** ku-many-a
 PST-SM.1SG-know-FV and SM.1SG-PER INF-know-FV
 Intended: 'I knew and I still know.' (8433roz, sau)

The infelicity of the sentence in (16) could be due to the speaker's interpretation of this type of construction as conveying the meaning 'not yet', which would lead to a contradiction (i.e., 'I knew and I don't yet know'). When volunteering a corrected form of (16) above, the speaker offers the main verb in finite form, with the meaning 'still', as shown in (17):

(17) *Hanimanya na nikali nimanyile.*

ha-ni-many-a na ni-**kali** ni-many-ile
 PST-SM.1SG-know-FV and SM.1SG-PER SM.1SG-know-ILE
 'I knew and I still know.' (8435roz, sau)

However, as shown in (15) above (and discussed in Section 3.3 below), NG'HALI followed by an infinitival verb can be interpreted as 'still' or 'not yet'. Thus, it may be the case that the infelicity in (16) above stems from speaker preference. This may suggest that AVCs with NG'HALI and finite main verbs are preferred over infinitival main verbs. Furthermore, this may explain why there are fewer examples of infinitival main verbs in the Kagulu corpus.

3.2.3 Constructions exhibiting further stages of grammaticalization

There are two construction subtypes that illustrate further stages of grammaticalization. Both constructions IIIa (SM-NG'HALI-SM-V-ILE) and IIIb (SM-NG'HALI-V-FV) exhibit morphological reductions that we take to indicate that NG'HALI is grammaticalizing into a TA marker. Although the examples of construction IIIa in the Kagulu corpus only appear with the form *kali*, as

⁸ We analyse *hang'halisiku* as morphologically complex, containing the locative *ha-*, NG'HALI, and the word *siku* 'day'. This points to the lexicalization of NG'HALI.

aforementioned, we assume this to be an accidental gap in the data. Examples of construction IIIb exhibit both allomorphs.

Construction IIIa is found only twice in the Kagulu corpus. In these sentences, what appears to be a reduced subject marker appears on the main verb: *a-* instead of the expected *ya-*, illustrated in (18). We take this phonological reduction to indicate that NG'HALI has been grammaticalized into a TA marker (see Section 4 for detailed discussion):

(18) a. *Ponsiano katola mwaka ulokile*

Ponsiano ka-tol-a mu-aka u-lok-ile
 Ponsiano SM1-be/get_married-FV 3-year SM3-pass-ILE

na yang'haliatolile.

na ya-**ng'hali-a**-tol-ile
 and SM1-PER-SM1-be/get_married-ILE

'Ponsiano got married last year and he is still married.' (2403182roz, sau)

b. *Amina hakowa yakaliasokile.*

Amina ha-ka-uw-a ya-**kali-a**-sok-ile
 Amina PST-SM1-be-FV SM1-PER-SM1-be/get_tired-ILE

'Amina was still getting tired.' (9021roz)

In construction IIIb sentences, the subject marker on the main verb is absent altogether. This is illustrated in the sentences in (19):

(19) a. *Igolofa ding'alipolomoka.*

i-golofa di-**ng'ali**-polomok-a
 AUP-5.building SM5-PER-break_down-FV

'The building is still breaking down. / The building is still collapsing.'
 (250355roz, sau)

b. *Chikalilonga naye.*

chi-**kali**-long-a naye
 SM.1PL-PER-speak-FV with_her/him

'We are still speaking with her/him.' (2079sau)

c. *Amina yakalisokela/ya-**ng'hali**sokela.*

Amina ya-**kali**-sokel-a/ya-**ng'hali**-sokel-a
 Amina SM1-PER-be/get_tired-FV/SM1-PER-be/get_tired-FV

'Amina is still tired.' (9006roz)

We propose that this type of construction in Kagulu is an indication that NG'HALI has undergone further grammaticalization into a TA marker (see Section 4 for details). Although it is not clear whether this construction has developed from an infinitival form (construction II, Section 3.2.2.) or from construction IIIa, it is likely that it has developed from construction IIIa, given the 'still' interpretations it yields (see Section 3.3 for discussion). We thus analyse IIIb as a single verb consisting of one subject marker, NG'HALI, and a verb.

3.3 Morphosemantic properties

Auxiliaries in East African Bantu languages commonly select a finite or infinitival verb (Gibson 2025). Variation in the finiteness of the main verb can have interpretive consequences: an infinitival main verb may signal dependency or incompleteness, while a finite main verb can mark greater integration with tense-aspect morphology. Zahran and Bloom Ström (2022) show how the form of the main verb following Swahili adverbial *bado* impacts interpretation: when followed by an affirmative infinitive, *bado* yields a conventionalized ‘not yet’ interpretation, and when followed by a finite verb, *bado* instead signals the persistence of an ongoing state or activity (‘still’). These cross-Bantu observations suggest that auxiliary-main verb constructions not only vary morphosyntactically, but that these variations have semantic effects (cf. Abe’s (2015) five patterns for Bende). In Kagulu, ‘still’ and ‘not yet’ interpretations of NG’HALI are dependent on the constructions in which this auxiliary is found. The NG’HALI patterns from Table 1 above are summarized again in Table 2 below and include the interpretations associated with each:

Table 2: Morphosemantic properties of NG’HALI

	Subtype	Construction	Forms	Meanings
I. Finite main verb	Ia	SM-NG’HALI SM-TA-V-FV	<i>ng'hali, kali</i>	‘still’
	Ib	SM-NG’HALI SM-V-SBJV	<i>ng'hali, kali, ng'hati</i>	‘not yet’
	Ic	SM-NG’HALI SM-V-ILE	<i>ng'hali, kali</i>	‘still’
II. Infinitival main verb		SM-NG’HALI INF-V-FV	<i>ng'hali, kali</i>	‘still’, ‘not yet’
III. Further stages of grammaticalization	IIIa	SM-NG’HALI-SM-V-ILE	<i>kali</i>	‘still’
	IIIb	SM-NG’HALI-V-FV	<i>ng'hali, kali</i>	‘still’

As illustrated in Table 2, there are two patterns where NG’HALI yields a ‘not yet’ interpretation. It is the only interpretation of construction Ib sentences, where the final vowel of the main verb is the subjunctive *-e* (e.g., example (9b) from above, repeated in (20) below):

- (20) *Amina yakali yagende.*
 Amina ya-**kali** ya-gend-**e**
 Amina SM1-PER SM1-walk-SBJV
 ‘Amina has not yet walked.’ (8289roz, sau)

As discussed in Section 3.2.1, the suffix *-e* has different functions in Kagulu: it occurs in subjunctive constructions (Petzell 2008, 129) and as an abbreviated form of *-ile* when it occurs together with the neuter affix *-ik/-ek-*. The homophony allows both readings of NG’HALI – ‘not yet’ (subjunctive *-e*) and ‘still’ (*-ile* abbreviated to *-e*). The ‘not yet’ reading arises when the *-e* is interpreted as the subjunctive, whereas the ‘still’ reading arises when it is interpreted as a reflex of *-ile*. The sentences below illustrate the distinction between the subjunctive *-e* and *-ile*: NG’HALI + the stative verb *tol* ‘be/get married’, suffixed with subjunctive *-e*, yields the interpretation ‘not

yet married' (21a), while NG'HALI + the stative verb *tol* suffixed with *-ile* yields the interpretation 'still married' (21b):

- (21) a. *Mugosi yakali yatole.*
 mu-gosi ya-kali ya-tol-e
 1-man SM1-PER SM1-be/get_married-SBJV
 'The man is not yet married.' (240380roz, sau)
- b. *Mugosi yakali yatolile.*
 mu-gosi ya-kali ya-tol-ile
 1-man SM1-PER SM1-be/get_married-ILE
 'The man is still married.' (240379roz, sau)

We can thus use the interpretations of NG'HALI constructions to tell us whether a final *-e* is a subjunctive or a reduced *-ile*. For sentences in which the eventuality is interpreted as not yet taking place/holding, we analyse the final *-e* as a subjunctive ((22a), repeated from (14a) above). For sentences in which the eventuality is interpreted as still taking place/holding, the final *-e* is a reduced *-ile* ((22b), repeated from (12) above):

- (22) a. *Matagi gang'hati/ng'hali gatulike.*
 ma-tagi ga-ng'hati/ng'hali ga-tul-ik-e
 6-egg SM6-PER SM6-break-NEUT-SBJV
 'The eggs are not yet broken.' (240336roz, sau)
- b. *Isupa ikali itulike.*
 i-supu i-kali i-tul-ike
 AUP-9.bottle SM9-PER SM9-break-NEUT.ILE
 'The bottle is still broken.' (240331roz, sau)

That it is the subjunctive that is used for 'not yet' interpretations in Kagulu is not unexpected. Persohn (2024b) shows that 'still' expressions without an overt negator are cross-linguistically used to express 'not yet' in several environments, one of which is "with less-than-finite and/or dependent complements" (84). Persohn suggests that the status of the subjunctive as irrealis may explain its similarities to infinitival complements where there is a "conventionalized inference from a pending situation to a persistently negative one" (102).

The other construction that yields 'not yet' interpretations of NG'HALI in Kagulu is construction II, when the main verb is infinitival (example (15b) above, repeated in (23a) below). In contrast to subjunctive complements that are only interpreted as 'not yet', infinitival complements can also have 'still' interpretations (example (15c) above, repeated in (23b) below):

- (23) a. *Ning'hali kulima mgunda wangu.*
 ni-ng'hali ku-lim-a mu-gunda u-angu
 SM.1SG-PER INF-cultivate-FV 3-farm 3-POSS.1SG
 'I have not yet cultivated my farm.' (3152mgu)

b. *Ngodi saka kahi sing'hali kwaka.*

ngodi si-ak-a kahi si-**ng'hali** ku-ak-a
10.firewood SM10-burn-FV again SM10-PER INF-burn-FV

'The firewood has burnt and it is still burning.' (240399roz, sau)

The 'not yet' interpretation with infinitival complements is in line with Persohn's (2024b) findings for Bantu languages.

NG'HALI followed by an infinitival verb is also used to express the meaning 'before', as shown in example (24) below.

(24) *Chifula kiyona ching'hali kugolosa imilimo.*

chi-ful-a ku-i-on-a chi-**ng'hali** ku-golos-a i-mi-limo
SM.1PL-finish-FV INF-REC-see-FV SM.1PL-PER INF-do-FV AUP-4-work

'We already (lit. finished) met before (starting) work.' (250351roz, sau)

This extended usage of a persistive marker is found cross-linguistically and is discussed in Veselinova and Devos (2021, 466) and Persohn (2021, 106; 2024a, 175–177), among others. 'Not yet' markers are often used in 'before' clauses in Bantu languages (van der Auwera and Veselinova 2018, as cited in Olguín Martínez 2022, 44). Since the eventuality in the main clause occurs prior to the eventuality in the 'before' clause, the eventuality in the 'before' clause has not yet taken place (Olguín Martínez 2022, 42).

Although, as suggested in Section 3.2, we take the absence of the form *ng'hali* in IIIa constructions as an accidental gap in the corpus data, the form *ng'hati* (see footnote 5) only appears in construction Ib (subjunctive), for which 'not yet' is the only interpretation (see (10c) above, repeated in (25) below):

(25) *Ning'hati nilime mgunda wangu.*

ni-**ng'hati** ni-lim-e mu-gunda u-angu
SM.1SG-PER SM.1SG-cultivate-SBJV 3-farm 3-POSS.1SG

'I have not yet cultivated my farm.' (3153mta)

Examples of the form *ng'hati* in the Kagulu corpus contrasts with Last (1886, 66–67), who documents it as *nati* and glosses it 'still, yet, again'. Last suggests *nati* occurs with infinitival main verbs (26) (glosses adapted):

(26) *Chinati kwenda.*

chi-**nati** ku-end-a
SM.1PL-PER INF-love-FV

'We are still loving.' (Last 1886, 66 67)

Last further suggests that *nati* can occur within the main verbal complex (27) (glosses adapted):

(27) *Yanaitonya.*

ya-**nati**-tony-a
SM1-PER-rain-FV

'It is still raining.' (Last 1886, 67)

Last proposes that *nati* requires negation in order for the eventuality to be interpreted as ‘not yet’ holding/taking place, as in (28):

(28) *Wasinati kwenda.*

wa-si-nati ku-end-a
SM2-NEG-PER INF-love-FV

‘They have not yet loved.’ (Last 1886, 78)

Last refers to *nati* as another “‘not yet’ tense” and asserts that it is used when “the action implied by the verb has not taken place, and is not likely to happen” (Last 1886, 76).

Last’s generalizations are not borne out by the data in the Kagulu corpus. Last’s proposed form *k’ali* ‘not yet’ formally corresponds to contemporary Kagulu *ng’hali/kali* and is usually interpreted with the meaning ‘still’. Last’s proposed form *nati* ‘still, yet, again’ formally corresponds to contemporary Kagulu *ng’hati*, which is only interpreted with the meaning ‘not yet’. Despite these different generalizations, we still consider the forms in Last’s work and the forms in the contemporary Kagulu corpus to have developed from the same source.¹⁰

4 Development into a TA prefix

In Section 3.2 above, we suggested that some NG’HALI constructions illustrate that it is undergoing further grammaticalization. In this section, we discuss these stages in more detail. We begin with an illustration of the grammaticalization of Kagulu *uwa* ‘be’, which is the most commonly used auxiliary in the language.

The auxiliary *uwa* undergoes three grammaticalization stages. This analysis is based on Nurse (2003, 93–94) and developed for Kagulu by Petzell (2008, 149). The constructions at all three stages are used in Kagulu today, which points to an ongoing grammaticalization process.

In Stage 1, *uwa* occurs separately from the main verb, and is affixed with a subject marker, non-past prefix, and final vowel *-a*:

(29) *Nikuwa nilima.*

ni-ku-uw-a ni-lim-a
SM.1SG-NON_PST-be-FV SM.1SG-cultivate-FV

‘I am cultivating.’ (Petzell 2008, 153)

In Stage 2, *uw* is phonologically reduced and merged with the non-past morpheme *-ku-*, resulting in *-koo-* or *-ko-*. Moreover, the final vowel of the auxiliary is omitted. We suggest this to be an indication that the auxiliary and main verb have fused into a single verb complex, but that the auxiliary has not yet completely grammaticalized. Consequently, we gloss *-ko(o)-* as a merged non-past (*-ku-*) and auxiliary (‘be’) morpheme. At this stage, the subject marker of the main verb is retained, and thus the verbal complex now has two subject markers. This is illustrated in (30):

⁹The other ‘not yet’ tense Last (1886, 76) refers to is *k’ali* ‘not yet’, discussed in Section 1 above.

¹⁰There is a similar auxiliary in Kagulu, *naki* (see Petzell 2008, 152), that requires negation and that may be interpreted as ‘not yet’, as well as ‘never mind’, which we assume has developed from a different source.

- (30) a. *Nikoonilima*.
ni-**koo-ni**-lim-a
SM.1SG-NON_PST.be-SM.1SG-cultivate-FV
'I am cultivating.' (Petzell 2008, 153)
- b. *Nikonilima*.
ni-**ko-ni**-lim-a
SM.1SG-NON_PST.be-SM.1SG-cultivate-FV
'I am cultivating.' (Petzell 2008, 153)

Although the subject marker from the main verb (bolded *-ni-* in (30) above) might at first glance appear to be an object marker seeing as it appears in what is typically the object marker slot in the Bantu verb template, there are two reasons to consider this a subject marker: (i) the sentences in (30) above cannot have the reflexive interpretation that might otherwise be expected with a first person object marker, and (ii) we observe examples with both the retained first person subject marker *ni-* and with an object marker (*mu-* in (31) below):

- (31) *Nikoonimuhambula chila ijuwa*.
ni-**koo-ni-mu**-hambul-a chila i-juwa
SM.1SG-NON_PST.be-SM.1SG-OM1-take_off-FV every 5-day
'I usually take the clothes off him/her every day.' (8394roz, sau)

In Stage 3, the reduced auxiliary morpheme completes its grammaticalization process. The dialectal/idiolectal vowel length variation observed in Stage 2 persists in Stage 3. The subject marker on the main verb that was retained in Stage 2 is omitted in Stage 3. The merged form *-ko(o)-* now occupies the TA slot, as in (32):

- (32) *Niko(o)lima*.
ni-**ko(o)**-lim-a
SM.1SG-NON_PST-cultivate-FV
'I am cultivating.' (Petzell 2008, 153)

The development of an auxiliary 'be' into a present tense is documented cross-linguistically (Bybee et al. 1994).

NG'HALI appears to be undergoing similar grammaticalization stages to *uwa*. The data in the Kagulu corpus primarily show NG'HALI as being in Stage 1, as an auxiliary separate from the main verb, as shown in (33) below (repeated from (2a) above).

- (33) *Mwana yang'hali yakusoma*.
mu-ana ya-**ng'hali** ya-ku-som-a
1-child SM1-PER SM1-NON_PST-read-FV
'The child is still studying.' (2403162roz, sau)

There are also a number of examples in the corpus of NG'HALI at Stage 3. As the examples in (34) illustrate, the main verb subject marker is omitted, and the auxiliary is grammaticalized into the TA morpheme slot.

- (34) a. *Ning'hali*golosa milimo.
 ni-**ng'hali**-golos-a mi-limo
 SM.1SG-PER-do-FV 4-work
 'I am still working.' (03091jes)
- b. *Ung'hali*dia.
 u-**ng'hali**-di-a
 SM.2SG-PER-eat-FV
 'You are still eating.' (03092jes)
- c. *Yeng'hali*wenda.
 ye-**ng'hali**-mu-end-a
 SM1-PER-OM1-love-FV
 'S/he still loves him/her.' (200409lem)
- d. *Chikalilong(anya)* naye.
 chi-**kali**-long(-any¹¹)-a naye
 SM.1PL-PER-speak(-SOC)-FV with_her/him
 'We are still speaking with her/him.' (2079sau)
- e. *Amina yakali*genda.
 Amina ya-**kali**-gend-a
 Amina SM1-PER-walk-FV
 'Amina is still walking.' (8290roz, sau)

While some auxiliaries can also occur as a main verb, NG'HALI never occurs as a main verb. Unlike in *uwa* constructions, when NG'HALI is separated from the main verb, it does not appear with a final vowel, which might make it difficult to determine whether or not NG'HALI is fusing with the main verb. Nonetheless, we take the parallels with *uwa* grammaticalization as evidence that NG'HALI is fusing with the main verb. Moreover, we take examples in the Kagulu corpus where NG'HALI is preceded by another auxiliary (*uw* in (35) below) as further evidence that NG'HALI is indeed undergoing grammaticalization (see Section 5 for further discussion of the co-occurrence of NG'HALI with multiple verb constructions).

- (35) *Amina kowaga yakalibilima*.
 Amina ka-**uw**-ag-a ya-kali-bilim-a
 Amina SM1-**be**-HAB-FV SM1-PER-run-FV
 'Amina still runs/is still running.' (9030roz)

There are two examples in the Kagulu corpus that may illustrate Stage 2 (or possibly Stage 3) of NG'HALI grammaticalization. In (36) below (repeated from (18) above), *-a-* intervenes between NG'HALI and the main verb (*tol* 'be/get married' and *sok* 'be/get tired', respectively). If this morpheme is considered a reduced version of the subject marker *ya-*, this may be evidence of NG'HALI at Stage 2 or 3.

¹¹ For discussion on the sociative in Kagulu, see Dom et al. (2023b, 207).

(36) a. *Ponsiano katola mwaka ulokile*

Ponsiano ka-tol-a mu-aka u-lok-ile
 Ponsiano SM1-be/get_married-FV 3-year SM 3-pass-ILE

na yang'haliatolile.

na ya-ng'hali-a-tol-ile
 and SM1-PER-SM1-be/get_married-ILE

'Ponsiano got married last year and he is still married.' (2403182roz, sau)

b. *Amina hakowa yakaliasokile.*

Amina ha-ka-uw-a ya-kali-a-sok-ile
 Amina PST-SM1-be-FV SM1-PER-SM1-be/get_tired-ILE

'Amina still became tired (again).' (9021roz)

The sentences with reduced subject markers in (35) above are also documented with the non-reduced subject marker (37), which we take as further evidence of grammaticalization in progress:

(37) a. *Ponsiano katola mwaka ulokile*

Ponsiano ka-tol-a mu-aka u-lok-ile
 Ponsiano SM1-be/get_married-FV 3-year SM3-pass-ILE

na yang'hali yatolile.

na ya-ng'hali ya-tol-ile
 and SM1-PER SM1-be/get_married-ILE

'Ponsiano got married last year and he is still married.' (2403181roz, sau)

b. *Amina hakowa yang'hali yasokile.*

Amina ha-ka-uw-a ya-ng'hali ya-sok-ile
 Amina PST-SM1-be-FV SM1-PER SM1-be/get_tired-ILE

'Amina was still getting tired.' (9021roz)

Veselinova and Devos (2021) suggest that auxiliaries such as *NG'HALI* may have historically developed into auxiliaries via grammaticalization and are now further grammaticalizing. For example, they propose that in Stage 1, the meaning 'not yet' is expressed by a bound morpheme, which could potentially be analysed as *(n)ka* in Kagulu. In Stage 2, the 'not yet' interpretation is 'reinforced' by the addition of an auxiliary, specifically copular *li* from Proto-Bantu **di* (see Nurse 2008, 173). Veselinova and Devos argue that in Stage 3, this newly formed AVC *(n)ka + li* may subsequently undergo univerbation and morphologization such that it grammaticalizes into a bound morpheme (2021, 477–480). Even though copular *li* is not attested elsewhere in Kagulu, it is attested in neighbouring Luguru (Seidel 1898, 442) and Zalamo (Worms 1897, 305), which further supports this path of development.

5 AVCs with multiple verbs

Whether or not it is grammaticalized, when *NG'HALI* interacts with other auxiliaries or verbs and aspectual morphology, it contributes to the expression of progressive and habitual aspect. *NG'HALI* co-occurs with two other verbs: *gendelela* 'continue' and the auxiliary *uwa* 'be'.

When they appear in the same construction, *gendelela* follows NG'HALI, and the main verb appears in the infinitive, as illustrated in the following schema (38):

(38) SM-NG'HALI-V-FV INF-V-FV

The constructions in (39) below are used to express events in progress with a dynamic verb (a) and with a neuter (*-ik/-ek-*) derived verb (b).

(39) a. *Amina yakaligendelela kubilima.*

Amina ya-kali-gendelel-a **ku-bilim-a**

Amina SM1-PER-continue-FV INF-run-FV

'Amina is still running.' (9037roz)

b. *Dilokelo ding'haligendelela kubeneka.*

Di-lokelo di-ng'hali-gendelel-a **ku-ben-ek-a**

5-bridge SM5-PER-continue-FV INF-break-NEUT-FV

'The bridge is still continuing to break down (right now).' (250355roz, sau)

In contrast to AVCs with *gendelela* where it appears in the same complex as NG'HALI, the auxiliary *uwa* appears in its own auxiliary construction, followed by grammaticalized NG'HALI in the main verb complex. In these constructions, structurally schematized in (40), either the habitual marker (*-ag-*) appears on the auxiliary (41), or the suffix *-ile* appears on the main verb (42)¹²:

(40) a. SM-AUX-HAB-FV SM-NG'HALI-V-FV

b. SM-AUX-FV SM-NG'HALI SM-V-ILE

(41) a. *Amina kowaga yakalibilima.*

Amina ka-uw-**ag**-a ya-kali-bilim-a

Amina SM1-be-HAB-FV SM1-PER-run-FV

'Amina still runs /is still running (usually).' (9030roz)¹³

b. *Amina kowaga yakalisoka.*

Amina ka-uw-**ag**-a ya-kali-sok-a

Amina SM1-be-HAB-FV SM1-PER-be/get tired-FV

'Amina still becomes tired (habitually).' (9007roz)

(42) a. *Esta hakowa yeng'hali/yekali yamanyile.*

Esta ha-ka-uw-a ye-ng'hali/ye-kali ya-many-**ile**

Esta PST-SM1-be-FV SM1-PER/SM1-PER SM1-know-**ILE**

'Esta still knew.' (1004sau)

¹² There is one example in the corpus that does not adhere to this generalization where the final vowel *-a* appears instead of *-ile*. We leave this for further research.

¹³ With the exception of the optional past tense prefix *ha-*, past tense is not obligatorily morphologically encoded in Kagulu. Thus, although sentences without overt past tense morphology typically yield past tense interpretations, sentences marked with *-ag-* yield present tense habitual interpretations (see Bar-el and Petzell 2024, 215).

b. *Amina hakowa yang'hali yasokile.*

Amina ha-ka-uw-a ya-ng'hali ya-sok-ile
 Amina PST-SM1-be-FV SM1-PER SM1-be/get_tired-ILE
 'Amina was still getting tired.' (9021roz)

The sentence in (43) below shows that in the absence of either *-ag-* or *-ile*, AVCs consisting of NG'HALI and *uwa* are infelicitous.

(43) #*Amina yekuwa yakalisoka.*

#Amina ye-ku-uw-a ya-kali-sok-a
 Amina SM1-NON_PST-be-FV SM1-PER-be/get_tired-FV
 Intended: 'Amina still becomes tired. (9007roz)

Finally, there is one occurrence in our corpus of both *gendelela* and *uwa* combined with NG'HALI. In this example, *uwa* appears in the auxiliary position and takes habitual *-ag-*, NG'HALI and *gendelela* form another verbal complex, and the main verb is in the infinitive. The schema of this construction is given in (44a) and illustrated in the example in (44b):

(44) a. SM-AUX-HAB-FV SM-NG'HALI-V-FV INF-V-FV

b. *Amina kowaga yakaligendelela kwija.*

Amina ka-uw-ag-a ya-kali-gendelel-a ku-ij-a
 Amina SM1-be-HAB-FV SM1-PER-continue-FV INF-come-FV
 'Amina still (usually) comes.' (9045roz)

In this section we have shown that when combined with other auxiliaries and verbs, NG'HALI appears in four different multiple verb constructions that vary according to the auxiliary/verb. NG'HALI + *gendelela* is always followed by an infinitive. Furthermore, NG'HALI + *uwa* requires specific morphology (habitual *-ag-*, or suffix *-ile*), whereas NG'HALI on its own occurs in a variety of 'simpler' constructions. With respect to morphosemantic properties, AVCs containing NG'HALI carry only the 'still' interpretation. While this is expected for finite forms (seeing as the 'not yet' interpretation is only associated with subjunctive *-e* constructions), this differs from the simpler AVC with infinitival complements that get both 'still' and 'not yet' interpretations. Despite these morphosyntactic and morphosemantic differences and similarities, the occurrence of NG'HALI with other auxiliaries shows grammaticalization stages similar to those observed in 'simpler' constructions, and specifically Stage 3 where NG'HALI becomes a TA prefix.

6 Conclusions

In this paper we have explored previously undescribed phonological, morphosyntactic, and semantic properties of the Kagulu auxiliary NG'HALI. We have shown that there are two predominant allomorphs in the Kagulu corpus: *ng'hali* and *kali*. Our study reveals that NG'HALI occurs in three main construction types: (I) constructions with finite complements, (II) constructions with infinitival complements, and (III) constructions that exhibit further grammaticalization. There are three subtypes of construction I and two subtypes of construction III, thus there are six overall constructions. We have demonstrated that 'still' is the predominant interpretation of NG'HALI across constructions, and the 'not yet' interpretation is restricted to two constructions,

and in fact is the only interpretation available for constructions with the subjunctive suffix *-e*. We have shown that there is another form of NG'HALI, *ng'hati*, which occurs in only one of the six constructions and is always interpreted as 'not yet'. We have proposed that NG'HALI is developing into a tense/aspect marker and that its grammaticalization path parallels the development of the Kagulu auxiliary *uwa* 'be'. The fact that, in its current use, NG'HALI is observed at multiple stages also confirms that grammaticalization is in progress. Finally, we have described the co-occurrence of NG'HALI and other Kagulu auxiliaries, and we have shown that auxiliaries such as *gendetela* 'continue' and *uwa* 'be' occur in different types of NG'HALI constructions which vary morphosyntactically from the simpler NG'HALI constructions.

This paper contributes to the understanding of Kagulu morphosyntax and the development of auxiliaries. The coexistence of NG'HALI at multiple stages of grammaticalization offers a current and unique snapshot of ongoing univertation processes, which parallels, but is also distinct from, the pathway of *uwa* 'be'. Given that the forms at different stages of grammaticalization are used synchronically, NG'HALI illustrates that univertation is not a linear process but one in which earlier and later stages can overlap. This challenges assumptions of unidirectionality in grammaticalization pathways and offers a comparative point of reference. This perspective enriches not only our understanding of Kagulu but also the theoretical modeling of grammaticalization processes in Bantu languages and beyond.

This study has significant typological implications given the structural profile of the Greater East Ruvu Bantu languages, which lack the rich TA paradigms characteristic of other Bantu subgroups. As a result, auxiliaries shoulder much of the functional load in expressing tense, aspect, and mood. The versatility of NG'HALI across both simpler and more complex AVCs demonstrates that such languages employ various strategies to expand functional coverage. Our findings provide a foundation for the study of auxiliaries in Greater East Ruvu and the Bantu language family.

The productivity of infinitival verbs in NG'HALI constructions requires further examination. While some examples in the corpus contain infinitival main verbs, speaker judgments point to limited acceptability, raising the question of whether infinitival forms are a stable feature of the system or a transitional stage in the grammaticalization process. Finally, while we have focused in this paper on the correlation between NG'HALI constructions and 'still' and 'not yet' meanings, we leave open the possibility that a more detailed study of actionality in Kagulu may reveal that the actional class of the main verb in NG'HALI constructions may determine whether NG'HALI contributes a 'still' or 'not yet' meaning in a given construction.

Abbreviations

1, 2, 3 ... etc.	Bantu noun class
1, 2SG/PL	person
AUP	augment prefix
AUX	auxiliary
CAUS	causative
CON	connective
COP	copula
FV	final vowel
FUT	future
HAB	habitual
INF	infinitive

ISO	International Organization for Standardization
NEUT	neuter
NON_PST	non-past
OM	object marker
PASS	passive
PER	persistent
POSS	possessive
PROG	progressive
PST	past
REC	reciprocal
SBJV	subjunctive
SM	subject marker
SOC	sociative
TA	tense and aspect
V	verb

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BE Auxiliary Verb Constructions in Kihehe

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Abstract

Kihehe (G62) has a rich inventory of auxiliary constructions (> 120) grounded in different forms of BE: copula *-li* and *-va* ‘be’. This paper addresses those constructions in which the auxiliary is marked for one of three pasts – hodiernal, pre-hodiernal, or remote – or one of two futures – near and remote – comparing the differences in use and distribution. The study investigates both single and double auxiliary constructions in which the main verb is in the simple perfective form: SM-B(ase)-*iC-e*. I describe two evolutionary paths of auxiliary forms derived from these recent and remote past forms of BE: SM-*ká-li* > SM-*ké* > *ké=* and SM-*áá-li* > SM-*eé*, all of which continue in use, although having different senses at different times. The 18 past constructions all have an English translation of ‘had VERBED’, the four future constructions a translation of ‘will have VERBED’. In addition, there are three double auxiliary constructions with *-ké/ké=* or *-eé* plus the future of *-va* that induce a modal interpretation, ‘would have VERBED’. The study analyses the differences noted above in the Domains and Regions framework (Botne 2025), elucidating the differences between these constructions in tense/tenor and the referential/indexical roles of the auxiliary verbs.

Keywords: grammaticalization, single versus double auxiliaries, modal use of auxiliary, referential index, Domains and Regions framework

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1 Introduction

Auxiliary verb constructions (AVCs) comprise one or more auxiliary components – verbal elements typically having their origins in lexical verbs and expressing some functional semantic category – “operating on a lexical predicate verb” and situated on a “diachronic form-function continuum standing between a fully lexical verb and a bound grammatical suffix” (Anderson 2011; Bernander et al. 2022 following Heine 1993; Anderson 2006). Eastern Bantu languages, and likely many other Bantu languages as well, often employ variants of the verb BE in functional roles as auxiliary verbs. Anderson (2011, 62) asserts that “a common function of ‘be’ as an auxiliary verb (...) is as a dummy stem that serves as an anchor for expressing obligatorily encoded formally realized grammatical categories.” However, as I proposed in Botne (1986) and will reiterate here, as auxiliary elements, BE verbs in Bantu are not simply ‘dummy’ verbs, but exhibit both referential and indexical functions, referring to a temporal locus of orientation – point or time span – and indexing a second (and even third) reference time as this locus. In this study, I describe and analyse a number of such constructions in Kihehe.

Kihehe (autonym *Ikíhehe*; Guthrie code G62, ISO 639-3 code *heh*) is a Bantu language spoken in south-central Tanzania, primarily in the Iringa region. The variety investigated here is centred around Kitelewasi village, southeast of Iringa. Data were obtained from conversations recorded between the primary language consultant and seven individuals from the Kitelewasi and Iringa areas, a folk tale, the Kihehe translation of the Bible (Matthew, Mark, and the Book of Exodus), and elicitation from the primary consultant.

Kihehe has an extraordinarily rich inventory of auxiliary constructions – numbering over 120 – many grounded in different forms of BE: copula *-li* or *-va* ‘be(come)’. This paper focuses on a relatively small number of those constructions, primarily those in which the auxiliary is marked for a past: hodiernal, recent, or remote past time – comparing the differences in use of the two BE types, each construction of which can be loosely translated as ‘had Ved’ – as well as several future perfective constructions. The study examines both single and double auxiliary constructions in which the main lexical verb is in the simple perfective form: SM-B-*iC-e*, *-iC-e*, representing abstractly a variety of perfective endings: *-il-e*, *-it-e*, *-i-e*, and imbricated *-iC-e* (Botne in prep).¹ In so doing, I describe two developmental paths of auxiliary forms derived from the recent and remote past forms of BE: SM-*ká-li* > SM-*ké* > *ké=* and SM-*aá-li* > SM-*eé*, all of which continue to exist in use, although in some cases differing in sense. Also addressed are several constructions in which the same auxiliary verbs occur coupled with a second auxiliary verb in a non-perfective form.

The remainder of the paper is laid out as follows:

- 2 Background basics
- 3 Contraction of basic pluprfect(ive) forms
- 4 Developmental path I: SM-*ká-li* > SM-*ké* > *ké=*
- 5 Developmental path II: SM-*aá-li* > SM-*eé*
RECAP
- 6 Auxiliary *-va*
RECAP
- 7 Auxiliary SM-T-*li* vs. SM-T-*v-e*

¹ Imbrication refers to a common process in Bantu languages in which the perfective marker *-iC* is interleaved with the ending of the verb stem, the *C*-slot being filled by the final consonant of said stem (cf. Bastin 1983). For example, the perfective form of *-lovan-a* ‘become soaked’ is *-loviin-e* (< *-lova-in-e*), with the vowel [a] being deleted preceding the compensatorily lengthened [i], and with [n] filling the *C*-slot.

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- 8 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (1a): [SM-*ké* [SM-T-*v-e* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]
 9 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (1b): [SM-*ké* [SM-*v-é* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]
 10 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (2): [SM-*aa-li* [SM-T-*v-e* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]
 11 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (3): [SM-*ee* [SM-T-*v-e* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]
 12 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (4): [SM-*ee* [SM-*aa-li* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]
 RECAP
 13 Future auxiliaries: (*sá=*)SM-*v-á* SM-T-B-*iC-e*
 14 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (5): (SM-)*ké* [SM-*v-á* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]
 RECAP
 15 Summary and conclusion

2 Background basics

Kihehe has six basic temporal constructions: three pasts, two futures, and one aspectual-like relative present (Figure 1). The latter can express a current present event or one that denotes a relevant reference time, a shifted *origo*. These temporal constructions are analysed here in the Domains and Regions (DaR) framework (see Botne and Kershner 2008; Botne 2012, 2023, 2025 for more detailed discussion), which is founded upon two complementary perspectives on the timeline. In the first perspective, imagine the timeline as a sequence of “mentally projected” cognitive worlds, labelled domains, one P(rietary) domain (including UT) and two D(issociated) domains, Preterite and Futurum. These are the realm of tense marking – remote past and remote future. In the second perspective on the timeline, the prevailing P-domain, tenor relations situate events in one of several regions: two past regions P1 and P2, one (or potentially two) tangible future regions F1 (and F2), as well as an immediate time region at utterance time. The two pasts (typically) designate Hodiernal and pre-Hodiernal regions, i.e. Proximal (PrxTR) and Distal (DisTR) time regions, respectively.

The DaR framework posits a constrained schema of the organization and limits of temporal relations in tense/tenor systems. In particular, it entails the following: if there are three distinct past forms, two will mark regions in the P-domain, one (the most remote) in the D-domain. Thus, in Kihehe, Ø- marks the PrxTR, *káa-* the DisTR in the P-domain, *aa-* the D-domain (Figure 1). More generally, a single past form in a language will typically mark the preterite D-domain, as with Kiswahili *li-*, while two forms will refer either to the two regions in the P-domain or to a region in the P-domain and to the D-domain, the analysis depending on morphological form and/or use (Botne and Kershner 2008, Botne 2012, 2023, 2025). As an example, Sibhende (F.12) has two past forms SM-*a-Ø-B-a* and SM-*a-ká-B-a* referring to the proximal (PrxTR) and distal (DisTR) time regions in the P-domain. On the other hand, Ekoti (P.30) also has two past forms, SM-*a-B-a* and SM-*aa-B-iyé*. However, in this case they refer to the P-domain and D-domain, respectively (Botne and Kershner 2008, based on Schadeberg and Mucanheia 2000). One piece of evidence for this distinction comes from the expression of the past of the proposition PORTUGUESE BUILD FORTRESS. If the Portuguese are the salient agents, the remote past is employed; when the fortress is the salient entity, as in the passive, the recent past form is employed, expressing its current extant status.²

The placement of simple Kihehe verb forms in Figure 1 indicates where, temporally, an event is predicated to occur.

²I wish to thank Thilo Schadeberg for pointing out this interesting and significant fact about Ekoti, following an incident in which a speaker used both in speaking with him.

Figure 1: Basic Kihehe tenses and tenors in the Domains and Regions (DaR) framework

In Kihehe, conjugated forms of the verb *-va* ‘be(come)’ fully fill out this framework (Figure 2). That is, *-va* behaves like any other lexical verb in its temporal marking potential. Copula *-li*, on the other hand, is deficient; it does not occur with either of the future markings or the recent pre-Hodiernal past (Figure 3). This asymmetry between the two verbs is significant for the analysis of their use as auxiliaries.

Figure 2: The verb *-va* ‘be(come)’ in the Domains and Regions framework

Figure 3: Copula *-li*

Crucial to understanding the differences in distribution is the marker *káa-* with *-va* but *ká-* with *-li*, which are best analysed as two forms of the same morpheme *ká(a)-*. Notice first that *ká-* has a short vowel before *-li*. Second, it superficially appears to have a different meaning: pre-hodiernal past with *-v-é*, hodiernal with *-li*. Upon closer inspection, however, we see that there is an analogous relationship between the unmarked forms of each verb and the two *ká(a)-* forms. That is, *SM-li* has the same relationship to *SM-ká-li* as *SM-v-e* has to *SM-káa-v-é*; the *ká(a)-* forms mark that region that immediately precedes the present *origo* – the deictic pivot of an utterance (UT), typically construed as utterance time, indexed as *R(eference) T(ime)*₀ – which is understood to be earlier today preceding UT in the case of *ká-*, but before today (pre-hodiernal) preceding the *origo* ‘today’ in the case of *káa-* (Figure 4).

Significantly, one cannot say either **tu-káa-li* or **ki-ká-v-é* (1). We can conclude, consequently, that the two markers are variants of the same morpheme. More generally, we can consider *-li* to situate an event earlier than some reference point, *RT*. On the other hand, *-v-e* situates an event within a temporal space, represented as \square , terminating in *RT*.

Figure 4: *-ká-li* vs. *-káa-v-é*

- (1) a. *Iki-koove ki-ká-li pa=meésa.* [*ki-ká-v-é]
 7-basket_for_flour SM7-P2-COP 16=9.table
 'The flour basket was on the table.' [earlier today]
- b. *Tu-káa-v-é i-pa p=liliinga.* [*tu-káa-li]
 1P-P2-be-PFV.FV DEM-16 16-Iringa
 'We were here in Iringa.' [recently]

As noted, both *-va* and *-li* can function as auxiliary elements. In this paper, we will focus first on examining those auxiliary constructions that have either copula *-li* or *-va* 'be' as an auxiliary followed by a perfective form of the main verb. Each simple past of the verb *-va* has a corresponding pluperfect(ive) form of the simple past perfectives (Table 1a), as does *-li* (Table 1b). Several illustrative examples are given in (2) and (3).

Table 1: Basic Kihehe pasts and pluperfect(ive)s

[B = verb base, SM = subject marker, *Ç* = imbricated consonant; Hodiernal = today]

a. *-va*

	<u>PAST</u>		<u>PLUPERFECT(IVE)</u>	
Hodiernal	P1/Pf	SM- ^H B- <i>iÇ-e</i>	PP1	SM- <i>v-e</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iÇ-e</i>
pre-Hodiernal	P2	SM- <i>káa</i> -B- <i>iÇ-e</i>	PP2	SM- <i>káa-v-é</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iÇ-e</i>
Remote	P _{RM}	SM- <i>aa</i> -B- <i>iÇ-e</i>	PP _{RM}	SM- <i>aa-v-é</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iÇ-e</i>

b. *-li*

	<u>PRESENT & PASTS</u>		<u>PLUPERFECT(IVE)</u>	
Present	P _R	SM- <i>li</i>	—	
Hodiernal	P _{HOD}	SM- <i>ká-li</i>	PP _{HOD}	SM- <i>ká-li</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iÇ-e</i>
Remote	P _{RM}	SM- <i>aa-li</i>	PP _{RM}	SM- <i>aa-li</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iÇ-e</i>

(2) *-va*

- a. *A-fih-it-e ama-gobóle.* b. *Á-v-e a-fih-it-e ama-gobóle.*
 1S-hide-PFV-FV 6-money 1S-be-PFV.FV 1S-hide-PFV-FV 6-money
 'S/he (has) hid(den) the money.' 'S/he had hidden the money.'
- c. *A-káa-fih-ít-e ama-gobóle.* d. *A-káa-v-é a-fih-it-e ama-gobóle.*
 'S/he hid the money.' [before today] 'S/he had hidden the money.'
- e. *Tw-aa-fih-ít-e ama-gobóle.* f. *Tw-aa-v-é tu-fih-it-e ama-gobóle.*
 'We hid the money.' [remote] 'We had hidden the money.'

(3) *-li*

- a. *A-li mu=ki-pugu.*
 1S-COP 18=7-canoe
 'He is in the canoe.'
- b. *va-ká-li mu=ki-pugu.* c. *va-ká-li v-íinj-e mu=ki-pugu.*
 1P-COP 18=7-canoe SM2-COP SM2-enter.PFV-FV 18=7-canoe
 'They were in the canoe.' [earlier today] 'They had gotten into the canoe.'

d. <i>Tw-aá-li</i>	<i>mu=kí-pugu.</i>	e. <i>Tw-aá-li</i>	<i>tw-íinj-e</i>	<i>mu=kí-pugu.</i>
1P-COP	18=7-canoe	1P-COP	1P-enter.PFV-FV	18=7-canoe
‘We were in the canoe.’ [remote]		‘We had gotten into the canoe.’		

3 Contraction of basic pluperfect(ive) forms

In addition to the five basic pluperfective auxiliary constructions shown in Table 1, we also find six similar constructions that are also translated as pluperfect(ive) ‘had Ved’ (Table 2). The auxiliaries listed there are contractions of one of the BE forms. At issue is whether they are contractions of the *-li* or the *-va* forms observed in Table 1. Botne (2023) posited that the contracted forms derive from the *-va* auxiliary constructions. Although plausible, it is not probable. There are four reasons – one semantic, three phonological – that the *-li* constructions are undoubtedly the source of the contracted forms. First, the contracted forms with *ké* refer to the Hodiernal past and not the pre-Hodiernal past. This correlates with the temporal range of *-ká* observed for the *-li* constructions. Second, phonologically, loss of [l] is common in the language. For example, the perfective of the verb *-galul-a* ‘capture’ is *-galw-e*, with loss of the final [l] before [e] and with glide formation of [u] before [e]. I do not know of any comparable loss of [v]. Third, coalescence of [á] and [i] results in a short [é], rather than a long [ée], which one would expect if the temporal marker had been *káa-*. The long vowel is exactly what we do find with contraction of *SM-aá-li* becoming *SM-eé*. Fourth, the retained high tone occurs where one would expect to find it in the coalescence of these vowels. We are led to conclude therefore that the contracted forms arise from the *-li* auxiliary constructions.

Table 2: Contracted auxiliary forms of *-li*

- a. From *SM-ká-li* *SM-^HB-iC-e*
SM-ké *SM-^HB-iC-e* > *ké=SM-^HB-iC-e*
SM-ké *SM-káa-B-iC-e* > *ké=SM-káa-B-iC-e*
- b. From *SM-aá-li* *SM-^HB-iC-e*
SM-eé *SM-Ø-^HB-iC-e*
SM-eé *SM-aa-B-iC-e*

As a graphic means of exposition of the extensive system of auxiliary constructions, various simple verb forms [grey font above] are shown in contrast with comparable auxiliary constructions below in Figure 5. The verb *-va* can occur as an auxiliary element in any of the temporal regions [upper sets] and domains, followed here by the simple perfective form of the main verb in the pasts, by either the simple or past perfective form in the non-past. Copula *-li* (lower set below dotted line) is restricted to the hodiernal or remote pasts when functioning as an auxiliary. Recall that *SM-ká-li* refers only to the hodiernal region. That is, *ká-* has a different temporal range than *káa-*, which is always interpreted as pre-hodiernal.

4 Developmental path I: *SM-ká-li* > *SM-ké* > *ké=*

Let us consider first the situation with copula *-li*. Auxiliary *-li* functions to refer to and index some reference point before which the situation named by the main verb has occurred. The full form is *SM-ká-li*, *ká-* referring to a near past in the P-domain. Note, first, that the simple copula refers to some time earlier today (4). This is also the case when it functions as an auxiliary (5a).

Figure 5: Some simple *-li* and *-va* vs. auxiliary constructions in Kihehe

However, it may also refer to an occurrence on the same day as some other event at some earlier time (5b).

- (4) *kí-koove* *kí-ká-li* *pa=meésa pé=tw-ii-vaáng-a* *ukú-haalúla*.
 7-basket_for_flour SM7-P2a-COP 16=9.table when=SM2-PRO-start-FV 15-grind
 ‘The flour basket was on the table when we started to grind.’ [earlier today]

- (5) a. *Pé=fík-it-e* *pamilaáwu va-ká-li* *va-héle* *ku=káaye.*
 when=1s.arrive-PFV-FV morning SM2-P2a-COP SM1-go.PFV.FV 17=home
 ‘When I arrived this morning, they had gone home [earlier in the day].’
- b. *Tu-ká-li* *tu-vály-e* *imi-kaate* *gí-la* *mbeé=gi-li* *pamilaáwu*
 1P-P2-COP 1P-count.PFV-FV 4-bread 4-DEM all=SM4-COP morning
pé=tw-ii-heg-a.
 when=1P-PRO-leave-FV
 ‘We had counted all those loaves of bread in the morning before [Lit. when] we left.’

The auxiliary form *SM-ká-li* at some point in time became contracted to *SM-ké*, ostensibly via a process in which the [l] was deleted – a common occurrence in Kihehe – with [á]+[i] becoming realized as [é], the high tone being retained. The contracted form has the same sense as the full form. The main verb can be either in the simple perfective form (6) or in the recent past form marked by P2 *káa-* (7). The former denotes an event that occurred earlier in the day (6a) prior to some contextually-determined reference time, for example, ‘start washing clothes’ (6b), or earlier on the same day as some other contextually-determined event (6c), but not one that is conceptually connected to it.

- (6) a. *Tu-ké* *tu-héle* *ku=boóma pamilaáwu pé=si=tu-láa-bit-á*
 1P-AUX 1P-go.PFV.FV 17=9.town morning when=NEG=1P-NEG_{YET}-go-FV
ku=mu-guúnda.
 17=3-field
 ‘We had gone to town in the morning before we went [Lit. when we had not yet gone] to the field.’ [today]
- b. *va-ké va-lím-it-e* *umu-guúnda* *pé=v-ii-vaáng-a* *uku-fuva*
 SM2-AUX SM2-till-PFV-FV 3-field when=SM2-PRO-start-FV 15-wash
imy-eénda
 3-clothes
 ‘They had tilled the field [earlier] when they started washing the clothes [at a later time the same day].’ [no connection between events]
- c. *Ava-támwa* *va-ké* *va-pám-iis-é* *ulú-piindo lw-a* *umw-eénda*
 2-sickly SM2-AUX SM2-touch-PFV-FV 11-hem 11-ASV 3-cloth
gw-ǎkwe *héla.*
 3-3S.POSS only
 ‘The sickly had touched only the hem of his clothes.’ [on that same day]

Use of the recent past *káa-* on the main verb indicates that the event must have occurred prior to today (7), the reference time RT_1 indexing a new *origo* earlier today shifted from RT_0 . The event ‘stealing’ in (7a) marked by *i-* – occurring today or before, that is, in the recent past.

- (7) a. *Tu-ké* *tu-káa-helé* *kw=liliinga* *pé=v-ii-hiis-a* *ku=káaye.*
 1P-AUX 1P-P2-go.PFV.FV 17=Iringa when=SM2-PRO-steal-FV 17=9.home
 ‘We had gone to Iringa [before today] when they were stealing from [our] home.’

- b. *A-bit-e kú=kú-saka yí-la y-é=yi-ké* .
 SM1-go-SUB RED=15-search 9-DEM 9-REL=SM9-AUX

yi-káa-yas-il-e

SM9-P2-become_missing-PFV-FV

‘He should go expressly to search for that that had gone missing.’

In sum, *SM-ké* indexes a reference *origo* RT_1 earlier in the day with respect to which the main event occurs either earlier than that on the same day or on some day preceding that day, the latter marked with the recent past P2 *káa-* (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Auxiliary *SM-ké*

A final step in the evolution of this *-li*-based auxiliary resulted in loss of the subject agreement marker and *ké=* becoming a proclitic. The proclitic form differs from the full *SM-ké* forms in that the latter are indexed to another event, as in (8a), while the former implies that the event is explanation or motive, for example, for some query concerning a state at reference time (8b-d).

- (8) a. *Tu-ké tu-lím-it-e pa-kómi pé=l-í-vaáng-a ukú-vala.*
 1P-AUX 1P-till-PFV-FV 16-large when=SM5-PRO-start-FV 15-shine
 ‘We had tilled a large area when [= before] it [sun] started to get hot [later].’
 [this morning]
- b. *Ké=tu-lím-it-e pamílaáwu.*
 AUX=1S-till-PFV-FV morning
 ‘We had tilled this morning.’ [possible response to Q: ‘Why aren’t you working?’]
- c. *Ké=ń-dy-e ili-píindigeesi héla.*
 AUX=1S-eat-PFV.FV 5-peach only
 ‘I had eaten only a peach.’ [possible response to Q: ‘Why are you hungry now?’]

This difference between the proclitic *ké=* and the other two forms can also be observed with an adjectival complement rather than a verbal one. Thus, in (9a), proclitic *ké=* denotes some generic situation in the past countenancing (and indexing) the later act of ‘buying’. With a subject marker, auxiliaries *-ké* and *-ká-li* are both grammatically correct, but not in the context of (9a). The former, for example, would indicate that the beer was good specifically at some past

time – for instance, when we were there – but that beer which is here now is no longer so (9b). The latter implies a span of time earlier in the day up to some reference time, but intimates that this point was a while back and that there is no beer now (9c).

- (9) a. *Ngoné w-eéng-e súkumwí na ngoné uwu-giimbi ké=wú-nofu*
 if 2S-brew-SUB once and if 14-beer AUX=14-good
néke wu-sil-e, u-wáan-it-e u-gúl-e ili-gunila ly-a
 then AGR14-finish-CMPL 2S-can-PFV-FV 2S-buy-SUB 5-sack 5-ASV
amá-sebele.
 6-maize
 ‘If you brew once and if the beer was good and has been completely consumed, you could buy a[nother] sack of maize.’
- b. *Uwu-giimbi wu-ké wú-nofu pamilaáwu.*
 14-beer SM14-AUX 14-good morning
 ‘The beer was good in the morning (but is no longer so).’ [there is some here now]
- c. *Uwu-giimbi wu-ká-li wú-nofu mbeé=pa-li.*
 14-beer SM14-P2a-COP 14-good all=SM16-COP
 ‘The beer was good all the time (up to reference time).’ [no beer remaining]

As described for the full SM-*ké* form previously, the main verb in the proclitic construction can also be marked for the recent past P2. The narrated event has occurred before today (10a) or before some contextually determined day (10b,c), *ké=* still implying a rationale for (and indexing) a reference event on a day preceding the main event, as described for (8) above. Thus, in (10b), grinding the flour occurred before the day on which the speaker steeped it.

- (10) a. *Kwakúva ké=mu-káa-helé néke m-loong-án-e ulú-kaani lú-la.*
 because AUX=2P-P2-go.PFV.FV then 2P-speak-REC-CMPL 11-issue 11-DEM
 ‘Because you had gone [before today] and discussed that issue.’
- b. *N-gw-éeng-a uwu-sé w-é=ké=n-gáa-twaan-z-íl-e wú-la.*
 1S-PRO-brew-FV 14-flour 14-REL=AUX=1S-P2-grind-PFV-FV 14-DEM
 ‘I steep that flour that I had ground [before that day].’
- c. *v-aákú-m-peel-ág-a g-eéki wakáti ye=ké=va-káa-hoomb-ít-e*
 SM2-HAB-OM1-give-DUR-FV 6-what while already=AUX=SM2-P2-pay-PFV-FV
ili-fuungu?
 5-brideprice
 ‘Why do they give it [money] to him when they had already paid the bride price?’

In sum, the recent past SM-*ká-li* auxiliary underwent two stages of contraction: 1) contraction of SM-*ká-li* to SM-*ké*, and 2) loss of the subject marker and cliticization to *ké=*. The main verb, originally only occurred in the simple perfective, denoting earlier in the day. Subsequently, it came to be marked as well for the pre-Hodiernal past with either the SM-*ké* or *ké=* auxiliary (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Stages in the evolution of *SM-ká-li SM-t-B-iC-e*

5 Developmental path II: *SM-aá-li* > *SM-eé*

A second path of development occurred with the auxiliary marked for the remote past, *SM-aá-li*. In this case, the auxiliary indexes a reference time (RT_1) – a shifted *origo* – temporally situated in the preterite D-domain with respect to RT_0 (UT), the main verb – in the simple perfective – interpreted as a past perfect(ive) in the same domain. Thus, *SM-aá-li* indexes *-tegwé* (11a) as RT_1 , which the predicated event precedes at some earlier time (Figure 8). Note that in (11b) the reference time is not specified (though it is likely to be interpreted as the point of forgetting), but is inferred as some point in the remote past.

- (11) a. *Aa-tegw-é* *gá-la* *amá-sebele* *g-é=nd-aá-li* *ndi-ga-póond-it-e*.
 SM1.P_{RM}-take.PFV-FV 5-DEM 5-maize 6-REL=1S-P_{RM}-COP 1S-OM6-pound-PFV-FV
 ‘She took that maize that I had pounded [at some earlier time].’
- b. *Yuúva* *aá-li* *a-n-dóonj-e;* *inó* *nd-aá*
 1.mother SM1.P_{RM}-COP SM1-1S-speak.APPL.PFV-FV now 1S-AUX
n-gw-iwúk-a *gú-mw-aáka* *swê*.
 1S-PRO-remember-FV AUG-2-year only
 ‘My mother had told me; now I remember only the year.’

Figure 8: Perfective in the Preterite D-domain; auxiliary *SM-aá-li*

Auxiliary *SM-aá-li*, like *SM-ká-li*, has undergone contraction, again through loss of [l] and coalescence of [aá] and [i], thereby becoming *SM-eé*. The original full auxiliary construction only occurred with the simple perfective form of the main verb (12). However, like the *-ké* forms, its use was extended to include the remote past form of the main verb (13), which, in this case, situates the event in an Ante-preterite D-domain. In both cases, the auxiliary still functions to

index RT_1 (Figure 9). The time gap between main event and reference event is perceived as greater in (13) where the main verb is marked for remote past.

(12) a. *Pé=gu-fik-it-e umw-aka gw-a wu-hulu, ye=w-eé*
 when=SM3-arrive-PFV-FV 3-year 3-ASV 14-independence already=2S-AUX
u-héle ukw-íkála koóno kúu-ngi lú-bali na iing'i y-a
 2S-go.PFV 15-stay 17.place 17-other 11-side with 9-land 3-ASV
vá-Hehe?
 2-Hehe

‘When the year of independence arrived, had you ever gone to stay at another place outside of Heheland?’

b. *Tw-eé tu-mu-lóonj-e we=si=a-láas-á íla*
 1P-RMCOP 1P-OM1-speak.APPL.PFV-FV while=NEG=SM1-NEG.come-FV but
a-séem-il-w-e.
 SM1-forget-PFV-PASS-FV

‘We had told him before he came, but he has forgotten.’

(13) *Iki-lo iki-mwí nd-eé nd-aa-helé kú-paána um-píla ku=ki-waánja*
 7.day 7-one 1S-AUX 1S-P_{RM}-go.PFV 15-play 3-ball 17=7-field
na vá-y-ǎngu; néke pé=v-aas-il-e ku=ki-waánja,
 with 2-EP-1S.POSS then when=SM2-P_{RM}.come-PFV-FV 17=7-field
se=tw-ii-vaáng-a ukú-paána um-píla.
 MOD=1P-PRO-start-FV 15-play 3-ball

‘One day I had gone to play soccer at the field with my friends; then, when they came to the field, we could start to play soccer.’

Figure 9: Auxiliary *SM-eé* with main verb in simple perfective (10a) in the Preterite D-domain or in the Remote Past (11) in the Ante-preterite domain

Figure 10 summarizes the stages in the evolution of SM-*aa-li*: first, a contraction of *-aa-li* to *-eé*, followed by subsequent use of the remote past perfective in addition to the simple perfective.

Figure 10: Stages in the evolution of auxiliary SM-*aa-li*

RECAP

Auxiliary *-li* refers to a locus of orientation, indexing that locus as a reference point to which the event named by the main verb is related temporally. Original near (*ka-*) and remote (*aa-*) past marking contracted with *-li* to form *-ke* and *-eé*, respectively, the former contracting further to become a proclitic *ke=*. The main event is always at some earlier time than reference time, as evident in examples (4) to (13), i.e. there is a clear temporal gap between reference time and event time. Table 3 tabulates various constructions grounded in *-li* as an auxiliary verb.³

Table 3: Compound auxiliary constructions grounded in the COPULA *-li*: *-ka-li* > *-ke* > *ke=* *-aa-li* > *-eé*

SM- <i>ka-li</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	
SM- <i>ke</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	SM- <i>ke</i> SM- <i>kaa-B-iC-e</i>
<i>ke=</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	<i>ke=</i> SM- <i>kaa-B-iC-e</i>
SM- <i>aa-li</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	
SM- <i>eé</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	SM- <i>eé</i> SM- <i>aa-B-iC-e</i>

6 Auxiliary *-va*

Turn now to the verb *-va* ‘be’, which may be marked for any of the three pasts, unlike *-li*. The Hodiernal Past has no overt temporal prefix (14a), but rather a high tone on the subject marker. The recent, or pre-Hodiernal, Past, as noted above in Figure 1, is marked with the prefix *kaa-* plus a high tone on final *-é*, as in (14b). The Remote Past (14c) has prefix *aa-* plus a high tone on final *-é*, like the pre-Hodiernal past.

- (14) a. *A-v-e* *i-pa* *iki-múuny’i* *mbe=ki-li*.
 SM1-be-PFV.FV DEM-16 7-day all=SM7-COP
 ‘She has been here all day.’

³ Johnson (2015, 2021) discusses *ke=* constructions in the Mufindi variety, which appears to be much simplified. In the first paper, she implies that *ke=* has come to mark a remote past in contrast with a proximal past SM-B-*iC-e*. She mistakenly assumes *ke=* to have been the same as *kaa-*, which seemingly has disappeared from the language. However, in Johnson (2021) she provides an example with *ka-* as a past tense, stating that *ke* is an auxiliary (p. 7). There is no discussion of the equivalent *-eé* auxiliary.

- b. *Tu-káa-v-é pála p=Iliínga.*
 1P-P2-be-PFV.FV 16.there 16-Iringa
 ‘We were there in Iringa.’ [recently]
- c. *Kú-la, ii-suúle y-aa-v-é n-gomi-n-gómi lu-dóodo.*
 17-DEM 9-school SM9-PRM-be(come)-PFV.FV 9-hard-9-hard 11-little
 ‘There, school was/became a little bit harder.’ [remote]

As an auxiliary verb, *-va* may also be marked for any of the past forms: hodiernal, pre-hodiernal, or remote. In the cases considered in (15)–(17), the main verb is in the simple perfective form, interpreted as having occurred at some earlier time within the reference time span in the hodiernal (15), pre-hodiernal (16), and remote (17) pasts. Auxiliary *-va*, as described previously, situates an event in a time span whose terminal point acts as a reference point. In each of these examples, that reference point is marked for the Relative Present *origo* (PrO). That is, in (15a) for example, ‘started to rain’ is the endpoint of the reference time span indexed by auxiliary *tú-v-e*, which began with the event ‘tilled’. Hence, the implication is that the rain didn’t interfere with the tilling.

- (15) a. *Pé=y-ii-vaáng-a ukú-toóny’a, tú-v-e tu-lím-it-e.*
 when=SM9-PRO-start-FV 15-rain 1P-be-FV 1P-tilled-PFV-FV
 ‘When it started to rain, we had tilled [earlier today].’
- b. *vá-v-e va-lím-it-e umu-guúnda, swe v-ii-vaáng-a ukú-vyála.*
 SM2-be-PFV.FV 1P-tilled-PFV-FV 3-field then SM2-PRO-start-FV 15-plant
 ‘They had tilled the field, then [in due course] they started to plant [earlier today].’
- (16) a. *Tu-káa-v-é tu-lím-it-e umu-guúnda mbeé=gu-li pé=y-ii-vaáng-a*
 1P-P2-be-FV 1P-tilled-PFV-FV 3-field all=SM3-COP when=SM9-PRO-start-FV
ukú-toóny’a.
 15-rain
 ‘We had tilled the whole field [at some earlier time before today] when it started to rain.’
- b. *N-gáa-v-é ndi-va-péel-y-e ama-gobóle i-g-ó*
 1S-P2-be-PFV.FV 1S-OM2-give-PFV-FV 6-money DEM-6-DIS
*pé=n-gú-mu-wón-a.*⁴
 when=1S-PRO-OM1-see-FV
 ‘I had given them that money [at some earlier time before today] when I saw him.’
- (17) a. *v-aa-v-é va-vyâl-it-e, pé=y-ii-vaáng-a ukú-toóny’a*
 SM2-PRM-be-FV SM2-plant-PFV-FV when=SM2-PRO-OM1-start-PFV-FV 15-rain
híilo.
 much
 ‘They had planted [at some earlier time], when it started to rain a lot.’

⁴The Relative Present *origo* marker is realized as *kú-* (*gú-* following a nasal) preceding an object marker.

- b. *Pé=l-ii-sot-a* *ilí-suwa,* *tw-aa-v-é* *tu-fis-il-e.*
 when=SM5-PRO-arrive-FV 5-sun 1P-P_{RM}-be-PFV 1P-arrive-PFV-FV
 ‘When the sun (was) set(ting), we had arrived.’

Auxiliary SM-*aa-v-é* cannot co-occur with the main verb marked for the recent past P2 *káa-* (18a); that is, *káa-* is only admissible for pre-hodiernal times expressed in the P-domain. The main verb can, however, occur with the remote past P_{RM} *aa-* (18b), which implies a relatively large interval between the event and reference time.

- (18) a. *Aa-tegw-é* *amá-sebele* *gá-la* *g-é=*nd-aa-v-é*
 SM1.P_{RM}-take.PFV-FV 5-maize 5-DEM 6-REL=1S-P_{RM}-be-FV
ndi-ká-ga-poond-ít-e.
 1S-P2-OM6-pound-PFV-FV
 ‘She took that maize that I had pounded.’
- b. *Tw-aa-v-é* *tw-aa-limít-e* *umu-guúnda* *mbeé=gu-li*
 1P-P_{RM}-be-FV 1P-P_{RM}-till-PFV-FV 3-field all=SM3-COP
gw-é=tw-aa-vyál-ít-e *amá-sebele.*
 3-REL=1P-P_{RM}-plant-PFV-FV 6-maize
 ‘We had tilled the whole field, in which we planted maize.’

Related to the *-va* auxiliary constructions described above is a similar construction in which perfective *-it* is absent. In this case, there is just a final *-e*, a completive aspect marker (Botne in prep). This construction is analogous semantically to the previous construction except that it means that the time span between the event and the reference event is short; that is, the former immediately preceded the latter (19). The auxiliary occurs with all three past tense forms.

- (19) a. *vá-v-e* *va-lím-e* *umu-guúnda* *mu-kómi,* *va-súup-it-e*
 1P-be-PFV.FV SM2-till-CMPL 3-field 3-big SM2-rest-PFV-FV
paány'i *pa=m-bíki.*
 16.under 16=3-tree
 ‘Having [just] tilled a large field, they rested under a tree.’
- b. *Tu-káa-v-é* *tu-telék-e* *tu-ká-va-peel-y-é* *va-ly-é.⁵*
 1P-P2-be-PFV.FV 1P-boil-CMPL 1P-P2-OM2-give-PFV-FV SM2-eat-SUB
 ‘Having [just] cooked, we gave them [sth.] so that they should eat.’
- c. *li-seénga* *yí-la* *y-aa-v-é* *yi-kiimbíl-e,* *y-aa-bumiil-w-é*
 9-cow 9-DEM SM9-P_{RM}-be-PFV SM9-run-CMPL SM9-P_{RM}-strike.PFV-PASS-FV
n=umú-tuka.
 by=3-car
 ‘That cow having [just] run away, it was struck by a car.’

⁵The recent past P2 *káa-* becomes *ká-* preceding an object marker.

This completive form only occurs in two contexts that I have been able to identify: (i) following an auxiliary verb, as above, and (ii) following the conjunction *néke* ‘and then’ (20). The latter is in contrast with the similar *swe* ‘then, in due course’, which does not permit the completive, but typically takes the Relative Present *origo* marker *i-*, as in (20c), where the same verb *-peel-* ‘give’ occurs in different forms following the two conjunctions.

- (20) a. ... *néke va-mém-e muú=ng'i mbeé=yi-li.*
 and_then SM2-fill-CMPL 18=9.world all=SM9-COP
 ‘... and then they filled the whole world.’
- b. *Aa-helé ku=va-ny'a-lú-kolo v-ǎkwe néke*
 SM1.P_{RM}-go.PFV.FV 17=2-of-11-clan 2-3S.POSS and_then
a-lu-loóng-ag-e ulú-gudolw-ǎwo.
 SM1-OM11-speak-DUR-CMPL11-struggle 11-3P.POSS
 ‘He went to his clan relatives and then he spoke [more] about their struggle.’
- c. ... *néke a-va-peél-e ava-ny'-i-geéndo swe ava-ny'-i-geéndo*
 and_then SM1-OM2-give-CMPL 2-of-9-journey then 2-of-9-journey
va-kú-va-peél-a v-a ma-lúgu.
 SM2-PRO-OM2-give-FV 2-ASV 6-group
 ‘... and then he gave the disciples [bread and fish] and in due course the disciples gave [them] to the crowds.’

The *-li* auxiliary forms do not occur with the completive form. Rather, they may occur with a predicative adjective that, like the completive, ends in *-e*. However, there are two differences of note. First, they follow different agreement patterns. The completive requires the usual subject agreement marker, whereas the predicative adjective requires the adjectival agreement pattern, a copy of the noun class prefix. Thus, in (21a) for example, the auxiliary takes the usual class 6 subject prefix *ga-*, while the predicative adjective takes *ma-*. Second, the tones of the two forms differ, completive having a high tone on the penultimate mora, the predicate adjective a high tone on the stem-initial mora. The full form of the auxiliary appears to highlight the process (21), while the contracted forms – with no apparent difference in sense – appear to focus on the resultant state (22).

- (21) a. *Amá-figa ga-ká-li ma-válil-e mbeé=ga-li.*
 4-cooking_stone SM4-P2-COP AGR4-COUNT-PA all=SM6-COP
 ‘All the cooking stones were [in a state of having become] counted.’
 [Focus = process]
- b. *A-ká-li mu=táambul-e híilo mu=Kítelevási.*
 SM1-P2-COP AGR1=state_of_being_known-PA much 18=Kitelewasi_village
 ‘He was [in a state of having become] well-known in Kitelewasi village.’
- (22) a. *Amá-figa ga-ké ma-válil-e mbeé=ga-li.*
 ‘All the cooking stones were already [in a state of having been] counted (by that time).’ [Focus = state]

- b. *Amá-figa ké=ma-válil-e mbeé=ga-li.*
 ‘All the cooking stones had been counted.’

The predicative adjective also occurs with the auxiliary marked for the remote past. The full form denotes a state having occurred earlier than reference time, the focus on the process that has occurred (23).

- (23) a. *Umu-guúnda gú-la gw-aá-li mu-kátul-e wé=si=va-láa-vyal-â.*
 3-field 3-DEM SM3-P_{RM}-COP SM3-harrow-PA while=NEG=SM2-NEG-plant-FV
 ‘That field was [in a state of having already become] harrowed while they had not yet planted [i.e. before they planted].’
- b. *S-aá-li m-búyap-il-e ich-uúma ch-a ii-sába.*
 SM10-P_{RM}-COP AGR10-make-APPL-PA 7-metal 7-ASV 9-copper
 ‘They were [in a state of having become] made of copper metal.’

The contracted form, like the full form, denotes a state as having occurred earlier, but the focus is on the state rather than the process. Thus, in (24a), the focus is on the process of the tree becoming uprooted, while in (24b), the focus is on the current state. A similar distinction is shown in (25).

- (24) a. *Umu-biki gw-aá-li mu-kímufu.*
 3-tree SM3-P_{RM}-COP AGR3-uprooted
 ‘The tree was [in a state of having become] uprooted.’ [Focus = process]
- b. *Umu-biki gw-eé mu-kímufu.*
 3-tree SM3-RMCOP AGR3-uprooted
 ‘The tree was already [in a state of having been] uprooted.’ [Focus = state]
- (25) a. *Umu-hiisi aá-li mu-díind-il-e.*
 1-thief SM1.P_{RM}-COP AGR1-become_closed-APPL-PA
 ‘The thief was [in a state of having become] taken into custody.’ [Focus = process]
- b. *Na-vé, eé mu-díind-il-e.*
 even-3S.PRO SM1.RMCOP AGR1-be_closed-APPL-PA
 ‘Even him, he was already [in a state of having been] taken into custody.’ [Focus = state]

RECAP

Auxiliary *-va* refers to some time span as a locus of orientation, indexing a reference time at the terminal point of that span to which the event named by the main verb is related temporally. The auxiliary may be marked for any of the three pasts, Hodiernal, pre-Hodiernal, or Remote (Table 4). It may also be followed by the main verb in a completive form lacking perfective *-it* but ending in *-e*, with a high tone on the penultimate mora. This differs from the *-li* auxiliary, which cannot co-occur with the completive, but can occur with a predicative adjective.

Table 4: Auxiliary constructions grounded in *-va*

SM- <i>v-e</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	
SM- <i>káa-v-é</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	
SM- <i>aa-v-é</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	SM- <i>aa-v-é</i> SM- <i>aa-B-íC-e</i>
SM- <i>v-e</i>	SM-B ^H - <i>e</i>	
SM- <i>káa-v-é</i>	SM-B ^H - <i>e</i>	
SM- <i>aa-v-é</i>	SM-B ^H - <i>e</i>	

7 Auxiliary SM-T-*li* vs. SM-T-*v-e*

As the reader may have noticed, there is a subtle difference between the use of *-li* and *-va* as the auxiliary verb, one that has been challenging to determine. Each can be marked with hodiernal, recent, or remote past temporal markers followed by the simple perfective form of the main verb. In (26), both auxiliary constructions refer to an event happening today, hence they are hodiernal; they appear to differ in the temporal gap implied between the reference time and the event –notionally greater with *-li*, shorter with *-va*.

- (26) a. *Tu-ká-li tu-vály-e imi-kaate gí-la mbeé=gi-li*
 1P-P2-COP 1P-count.PFV-FV 4-bread 4-DEM all=SM4-COP

pamilaáwu pé=tw-ii-heg-a.
 morning when=1P-PTP-leave-FV

‘We had counted all those loaves of bread [earlier] in the morning when we left.’

- b. *Tú-v-e tu-vály-e imi-kaate gí-la mbeé=gi-li*
 1P-be-PFV 1P-count.PFV-FV 4-bread 4-DEM all=SM4-COP

pamilaáwu pé=tw-ii-heg-a.
 morning when=1P-PRO-leave-FV

‘We had all those loaves of bread counted in the morning when [not long before] we left.’

Auxiliary *-ká-li* also contrasts with *-káa-v-é*. As noted for (26a), the former indicates that the event ‘go home’ had occurred today (27a), whereas the latter indicates that the event had occurred at some earlier time before today, but on the same day as (or before) reference time (27b). A similar distinction is observed with the remote past marker (28)–(29b), *-á-li* denoting some earlier imprecise time, while *-aa-v-é* implies that the event happened on the same day as the reference time. Note that auxiliary *-á-li* cannot cooccur with the main verb also marked with the remote past (29a); the reason for this is not clear.

- (27) a. *Pé=nd-ii-fik-a, va-ká-li va-héle ku=káaye.*
 when=1S-PRO-arrive-FV 1P-P2a-COP SM1-go.PFV 17=9.home
 ‘When I arrived, they had gone home [earlier today].’

- b. *P=ií-fík-a* *íísuusi,* *tu-káa-v-é* *tu-héle*
 when=SM1.PRO-arrive-FV two_days_ago 1P-P2-be-PFV.FV 1P-go.PFV.FV
ku-káaye.
 17-9.home
 ‘When he arrived two days ago, we had gone home.’ [same day or before that day]

- (28) a. *Yuúva* *aá-li* *a-n-dóonj-e;* *inó* *nd-aá*
 1.mother.1S.POSS SM1.P_{RM}-COP SM1-1S-tell.PFV-FV now 1S-AUX
n-gw-iíwúk-a⁶ *gú-mw-aáka swé.*
 1S-PRO-remember-FV AUG-2-year only
 ‘My mother had told me [at some earlier time]; now I remember only the year.’

- b. *Yuúva* *aa-v-é* *a-n-dóonj-e* *pé=v-íí-vaáng-a*
 1.mother.1S.POSS SM1.P_{RM}-be-PFV.FV SM1-1S-tell.PFV-FV when=SM2-PRO-start-FV
ukú-m-buúsa
 15-1S-ask
 ‘My mother had already told me when they were starting to question me.’ [same day]

- (29) a. *Aa-vyal-ít-e* *amá-sebele* *gá-la* *mu=mu-guúnda* *gw-é=*nd-aá-li*
 SM1.P_{RM}-plant-PFV-FV 6-maize 6-DEM 18=3-field 6-REL=1S-P_{RM}-COP
nd-aa-lim-ít-e.
 1S-P_{RM}-till-PFV-FV
 ‘He planted that maize in the field that I had tilled [at some earlier time].’

- b. *Aa-vyal-ít-e* *amá-sebele* *gá-la* *mu=mu-guúnda*
 SM1.P_{RM}-plant-PFV-FV 6-maize 6-DEM 18=3-field
gw-é=nd-aa-v-é *nd-aa-lim-ít-e.*
 6-REL=1S-P_{RM}-be-PFV.FV 1S-P_{RM}-till-PFV-FV
 ‘He planted that maize in the field that I had tilled.’

Figure 11: Copula *-li*

⁶The Relative Present *origo* marker *i-* is realized as *kw-* (*gw-* following a nasal) before V-initial verbs.

The schemas in Figures 11 and 12 illustrate the temporal relations between the reference times and the events expressed in (23)–(26) above for the *-li* and *-v-e* auxiliaries, respectively.

Figure 12: Auxiliary SM-t-v-e

8 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (1a): [SM-ké [SM-T-v-e SM-^HB-iC-e]]

The auxiliary constructions discussed above may occur as the complement of another auxiliary, invariably a contracted form of *-li*. The auxiliary in the complement clause is usually a form of *-va*. Although translated as ‘had Ved’, there are two reference times indexed, which in English would ostensibly be the ungrammatical ‘had had Ved’. In (30a), there is a conceptual connection between the *E(vent) -límite* ‘tilled’, which had occurred before the reference time span *RT₂*, which indexes the event *E₂ -vyale* ‘planted’, *RT₁* indexing *E₁* ‘start [to rain]’. This connection can be observed in the single auxiliary construction with *vá-v-e* (30b). On the other hand, there is no conceptual connection between *-límite* and *-iivaánga ukútoóny’a* ‘start to rain’, as illustrated for the single auxiliary with *-ké* (30c).

- (30)
- | | | | | | |
|----|---------------------------|-----------------------|---------------------|----------------------|-----------------------|
| | <i>RT₁</i> | <i>RT₂</i> | <i>E</i> | | <i>E₂</i> |
| a. | [<i>va-ké</i> | [<i>vá-v-e</i> | <i>va-lím-it-e</i> | <i>umu-guúnda</i>]] | <i>néke va-vyál-e</i> |
| | SM2-AUX | SM2-be-PFV.FV | SM2-till-PFV-FV | 3-field | then SM2-plant-CMPL |
| | <i>E₁</i> | | | | |
| | <i>pé=yi-váang-iig-é</i> | | <i>ukú-toóny’a.</i> | | |
| | when=SM9-start-DUR.PFV-FV | | 15-rain | | |
- ‘They had tilled the field and then planted [today], when it was starting to rain.’

- b. *vá-v-e* *va-lím-it-e* *umu-guúnda*, *swe* *v-íi-vaáng-a* *ukú-vyála*.
 SM2-be-PFV.FV SM2-till-PFV-FV 3-field then SM2-PRO-start-FV 15-plant
 ‘They had tilled the field, then [in due course] they started to plant.’
 [earlier in the day] [conceptual connection implied between the two events]
- c. *va-ké* *va-lím-it-e* *umu-guúnda* *pé=v-íi-vaáng-a* *ukú-fuwa*
 SM2-AUX SM2-till-PFV-FV 3-field when=SM2-PRO-start-FV 15-wash
imy-eénda.
 3-clothes
 ‘They had tilled the field [at some time earlier in the day] when they started to wash clothes.’ [no conceptual connection implied between the two events]

Figure 13: Schema of auxiliary *-ké* with complement auxiliary clause in (30a)

A second example of this construction is provided in (31). The language consultant made the comment that the event of ‘washing’ was perceived as beyond two steps back in time, i.e. as occurring prior to two reference times, as noted above. The washing and the rain occurred on the same day, but there is no conceptual connection implied between them.

- (31) [*va-ké* [*vá-v-e* *va-fúf-il-e* *imy-eénda j-áwo*]]
 SM2-AUX SM2-be-PFV.FV SM2-wash-PFV-FV 4-clothes 4-3P.POSS
néke *v-aánik-e*, *pé=yi-vaáng-iig-é* *ukú-toóny’a*.
 and_then SM2-spread_to_dry-CMPL when=SM9-start-DUR.PFV-FV 15-rain
 ‘They had washed their clothes and then spread [them] to dry before it was starting to rain.’

The *SM-ké* auxiliary may be reduced further, to a proclitic, occurring without the subject marker. There is apparently no semantic difference between this form and the *SM-ké* form of the construction.

- (32) *Ké=vá-v-e va-fúf-il-e imy-eénda j-ǎwo, pé=li-kw-éleelúk-a .*
 AUX =SM2-be-PFV SM2-wash-PFV-FV 4-clothes 4-3P.POSS when= SM5-PRO-reappear-FV
ilí-suva.
 5-sun
 ‘They had washed their clothes [at some earlier time] when the sun reappeared.’ [today]

Figure 14: Schema of auxiliary *-ké* with complement auxiliary clause in (33)

The second auxiliary, *-va*, may occur with the P2 marker *káa-*, which indicates that the event had occurred during some span of time before today. The *-ké* auxiliary indicates that the two reference times are on the same day.

- (33) RT_1 RT_2 E E_2
[Tu-ké [tu-káa-v-é tu-fís-il-e], néke tu-kí-won-e iki-lugu.
 1P-AUX 1P-P2-be-PFV.FV 1P-arrive-PFV-FV then 1P-OM7-see-CMPL 7-group
 ‘We had arrived and then we saw the crowd [before today].’

As with the *-ké* auxiliary construction in (33) above, that in (34) with complement *-káa-v-é* can also be reduced to the proclitic *ké=*. Again, the consultant was unable to articulate a difference in meaning.

- (34) *Ké= tu-káa-v-é tu-fís-il-e, p=ií-vaáng-a ukú-loóng-a.*
 AUX=1P-P2-be-PFV 1P-arrive-PFV-FV when=SM1.PRP-start-FV 15-speak
 ‘We had arrived [at some earlier time before today], when he started speaking.’ [same day]

9 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (1b): [SM-*ké* [SM-*v-é* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]

In an auxiliary construction with a complement auxiliary clause similar to that described above, the complement auxiliary *-v-e* may be marked as irrealis via the subjunctive final vowel, with commensurate shift of the high tone from stem-initial mora to final mora, hence [SM-*ké* [SM-*v-é* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]. Use of the simple auxiliary construction SM-*v-é* SM-^HB-*iC-e* (35) seems to imply a future possibility, as yet unrealized. The double auxiliary construction changes the meaning from possibility to unrealized supposition (36). Note that the verb in the main clause has either auxiliary SM-*ké* (36a) or proclitic *ké=* (36b) with the main verb marked for the future, with no apparent difference in meaning.

- (35) *Néke a-bihíl-e, swe va-kú-mu-sóp-a muu=n-diinde mbáka*
 then SM1-refuse-CMPL then SM2-PRO-OM1-relocate-FV 18=9-prison until
pé=a-v-é a-hóomb-it-e umú-kole mbeé=gu-li.
 when=SM1-be-SUB SM1-pay-FV 3-debt all=SM3-COP
 ‘Then he refused, and in due course they sent him to prison until [that time] when he would have paid the debt in full.’
- (36) a. [*Tu-ké [tu-v-é tu-fís-il-e]*], *tu-ké tu-va-taáng-a.*
 1P-AUX 1P-be-SUB 1P-arrive-PFV-FV 1P-AUX 1P-OM2-help-FV
 ‘Had we arrived [earlier today], we would have helped them.’
- b. [*va-ké [va-v-é va-lím-it-e umu-guínda]*], *ké=va-vyál-a*
 SM2-AUX SM2-be-SUB SM2-till-PFV-FV 3-field AUX=SM2-plant-FV
neéng’ino.
 today
 ‘Had they tilled the field [at some earlier time today], they would have planted today.’

In the above constructions, too, auxiliary *-ké* may be reduced to a proclitic *ké=*. In (37), the verb in the conjoined clause is marked as completive following *néke*. Again, the event in the protasis clause has not occurred. There appears to be no difference in meaning between the contracted and non-contracted forms *ké=* and *SM-ké*.

- (37) a. *Ké=va-v-é va-fís-il-e néke va-tu-loóng-el-e*
 AUX=SM2-be-SUB SM2-arrive-PFV-FV then SM2-1P-speak-APPL-CMPL
ké=tu-va-taáng-a.
 AUX=1P-SM2-help-FV
 ‘Had they arrived and then spoken to us, we would have helped them.’ [today]
- b. *Ké=tu-v-é tu-mu-lóonj-e héla úlwa á-su-pá-li,*
 AUX=1P-be-SUB 1P-OM1-tell.PFV-FV only that SM1-NEG-SM16-COP
si=ké=áas-a ndâ.
 NEG=AUX=SM1.come-FV NEG
 ‘Had we only told him that she was not here, he would not have come.’ [today]

10 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (2): [SM-*aá-li* [SM-T-*v-e* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]

The main auxiliary verb may be the full remote past form *SM-aá-li* or the contracted *SM-eé*, unlike the hodiernal past, which only occurs in the contracted form *SM-ké* or proclitic *ké=* (see Section 6 above). The [SM-*aá-li* [SM-*v-é* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]] construction denotes an event that occurred in the remote past on the same day as, and just before, the reference time. There is, in (38a), a conceptual link between ‘tilling’ and ‘planting’, denoted by *vá-v-e va-lím-it-e*, but no such link between ‘tilling and planting’ and ‘arriving’.

- (38) a. [*v-áá-li* [*vá-v-e* *va-lím-it-e* *umu-guúnda*]] *néke*
 SM2-P_{RM}-COP SM2-be-PFV.FV SM2-till-PFV-FV 3-field and_then
va-vyál-e *ama-doógi pé=nd-aa-fík-iig-é* *pála.*
 SM2-plant-CMPL 6-bean when=1S-P_{RM}-arrive-DUR.PFV-FV 16.there
 ‘They had tilled the field and then directly planted beans [remote] when I was arriving there.’
- b. [*Tw-áá-li* [*tú-v-e* *tu-fúf-il-e* *imy-eénda j-étu*]]
 1P-P_{RM}-COP SM2-be-PFV.FV SM2-wash-PFV-FV 4-clothes 4-1P.POSS
pé=y-aa-vaang-iig-é *ukú-toóny’a.*
 when=SM9-P_{RM}-start-DUR.PFV-FV 15-rain
 ‘We had washed our clothes [remote] when it was starting to rain.’

The complement auxiliary *-v-e* may occur with the remote past marker *aa-*. The two examples in (39) illustrate the difference between the two different verbal forms of *-v-e*. The remote tense marker on *-v-e* (39b) situates the specified event in the Ante-preterite D-domain, illustrated diagrammatically in Figure 15. The unrealized ‘had not yet left’ functions as E_2 , implied ‘leaving’ as the reference time indexed by *ch-áá-li*.

- (39) a. *Ifi-pigo fi-ify-o* [*fy-áá-li* [*fí-v-e* *fi-pígiik-e*]] *ku=káaye*
 6-task DEM-6-DIS SM6-PRM-COP SM6-be-PFV SM6-be_done-PFV-FV 17=home
y-áwo.
 9-3P.POSS
 ‘Those very tasks had just been done at their home.’
- b. *Ikí-pigo kí-la* [*ch-áá-li* [*ch-aa-v-é* *ki-pígiik-e*]]
 7-work 7-DEM SM7-RMCOP SM7-P_{RM}-be-PFV.FV SM6-be_done.PFV-FV
wé=si=tu-láa-wuuk-á.
 while=NEG-1P-NEG_{YET}-stand_up-FV
 ‘That work had been done [earlier] before we had left [Lit. while we had not yet left].’

The example in (39b) is significant for two reasons. First, Anderson (2011,23) states that “one salient way in which a number of languages in Africa stand out (...) is the doubled inflectional pattern of AVCs”, as, for example, with doubled subject or tense marking. This doubled subject marking, as we have observed, is found in Kihehe AVCs. However, while both auxiliary and main verb may have the same tense marking, it is not the case that this represents Anderson’s doubling in this language, and probably not in many other Bantu languages. As the example in (39) demonstrates, double *aa-* on the auxiliary verbs indicates two different tense relations – that between RT_0 (UT) and RT_1 , and a second between RT_1 and RT_2 – illustrated in Figure 15. Second, the existence of the Ante-preterite is relevant to the analysis of tense in many Bantu and even European languages, such as Portuguese and French (Botne 2023).

Figure 15: Double auxiliary SM-*á-li* SM-*t-v-e* with main verb in the simple perfective in the Preterite D-domain (38a), in the Ante-preterite D-domain (39b)

11 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (3): [SM-*e-é* [SM-*t-v-e* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]

The contracted remote copula SM-*e-é*, reduced from SM-*á-li*, occurs with the same auxiliary complements as the full form (40). The event specified by the main verb has occurred at some time earlier than two indexed reference times. Thus, in (40a), there is a conceptual connection between the event -*fúfile* ‘washed’ and the event -*ánike* ‘spread to dry’, the former preceding the latter, which is indexed at RT_1 . The event -*vaangiigé ukútoóny’a* ‘start to rain’ is indexed at RT_2 . That is, both E and E_2 have occurred at some earlier time with respect to the onset of rain. The same analysis applies to (40b). In (40c), two reference times are indexed, but the event E_2 is implied.

- (40)
- a. RT_2 RT_1 E
 a. [*v-e-é* [*vá-v-e* *va-fúf-il-e* *imy-eénda* *j-áwo*]] *néke*
 SM2-RMCOP SM2-be-PFV.FV SM2-wash-PFV-FV 4-clothes 4-3S.POSS and_then
 E_2 E_1
va-ánik-e *pé=y-aa-vaang-iig-é* *ukú-toóny’a*.
 SM2-spread_to_dry-CMPL when=SM9-PRM-start-DUR.PFV-FV 15-rain
 ‘They had washed their clothes and spread [them] to dry when it was starting to rain [at a later time].’
- b. [*v-e-é* [*vá-v-e* *va-lím-it-e* *umu-gúinda*]] *néke*
 SM2-RMCOP SM2-be-PFV.FV SM2-till-PFV-FV 3-field and_then
va-vyál-e *pé=ly-aa-vaang-iig-é* *ukú-vala*.
 SM2-plant-CMPL when=SM5-PRM-start-DUR.PFV-FV 15-shine
 ‘They had tilled the field and then directly planted, when the sun was starting to shine [at a later time].’

- c. *Pakúva imi-ítu i-j-ó [j-eé [gí-v-e gi-pígiik-e]] ku=Tiilo,*
 because 4-miracle DEM-4-DIS SM4-RMCOP SM4-be-PFV SM4-do.PFV-FV 17=Tiilo
v-eé va-v-á va-pés-il-e i-daáha iinz-ánaangífu i-s-ô.
 SM2.RMCOP SM2-be-FV SM2-stop-PFV-FV 9-long_time 10-bad_actions DEM-10-DIS
 ‘Because those miracles had happened in Tilo, they would have stopped those bad actions long ago.’

If the main auxiliary verb is in its full form, i.e. SM-*aa-li*, rather than contracted SM-*ee*, the construction indicates that the relevant event occurred just prior to reference time RT_1 , as in (41a), in contrast with the contracted form, which implies some greater gap in time (41b).

- (41) a. *Ifi-pigo fi-ify-o [fy-aa-li [fi-v-e fi-pígiik-e]] ku=káaye*
 8-task 6-6-DEM SM6-RMCOP SM6-be-PFV.FV SM6-be_done.PFV-FV 17=home
y-áwo pé=v-ii-sogól-a ulu-geéndo lw-áwo.
 9-3P.POSS when=SM2-PRO-head_out-FV 11-trip 11-3P.POSS
 ‘Those tasks had [just] been done at their home when they headed out on their trip.’
- b. *Ili-pigo li-ily-o [ly-ee [li-v-e li-pígiik-e]] ku=káaye*
 5-work DEM-5-DIS SM5-RMCOP SM5-be-PFV SM5-be_done-PFV-FV 17=home
y-áwo.
 9-3P.POSS
 ‘That work had been done at their home [at some earlier time].’

The complement auxiliary clause can occur with auxiliary *-v-e* marked with remote past *aa-*, hence [SM-*ee* [SM-*aa-v-é* SM-B-*iC-e*]]. In (42b), RT_1 – the shifted *origo* – is understood as that time at which I arrived, while RT_2 indexes the time of a non-event ‘my not yet having arrived’.

Figure 16: Auxiliary SM-*ee* marking reference time in the Preterite D-domain, auxiliary SM-*aa-v-é* marking a second reference time span RT_2 in the Ante-preterite D-domain, with the main verb marked as perfective with respect to RT_2

- (42) a. [*Tw-eé* [*tw-aa-v-é* *tu-lím-it-e* *umu-guúnda*]] *néke*
 1P-RMCOP 1P-P_{RM}-be-PFV.FV 1P-till-PFV-FV 3-field and_then
tu-vyál-e pé=y-aa-vaang-iig-é ukú-toóny'a.
 1P-plant-CMPL when=SM9-P_{RM}-start-DUR.PFV-FV 15-rain
 'We had tilled the field and then planted [very remote] when it was starting to rain.'
- b. [*J-eé* [*j-aa-v-é* *gi-píg-i-it-w-é*]] *mbeé=gi-li*
 SM4-RMCOP SM4-P_{RM}-be-PFV.FV SM4-do-PASS-PFV-PASS-FV all=SM4-COP
wé=si=ndi-láa-fik-â.
 even_though=NEG=1S-NEG-arrive-FV
 'They [tasks] had all been done even though I had not yet arrived.'

12 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (4): [SM-*eé* [SM-*aa-li* SM-^HB-*iC-e*]]

The contracted main auxiliary verb SM-*eé* can also occur with copula *-li* as the auxiliary in the complement clause. In this case, the copula must be in the remote past tense. In (43a), then, the *origo*, here RT_1 , is that implied point at which 'I' had arrived. 'He' had told everyone by some earlier point in time when I had not yet arrived (RT_2). This second reference time is located in the Ante-preterite D-domain, and preceded by the main event, 'told', as schematized in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Auxiliary SM-*eé* + auxiliary *-aa-li* with main verb in simple perfective in the Ante-preterite D-domain

- (43) a. *Ye=[eé* [*aa-li* *a-va-lóonj-e* *mbeé=va-li*]]
 already=SM1.RMCOP SM1.P_{RM}-COP SM1-OM2-speak.APPL.PFV-FV all=SM2-COP
wé=si=ndi-láa-fik-â.
 even_though=NEG=1S-NEG_{YET}-arrive-FV
 'He had already told all of them even though I had not yet arrived.'

- b. [*Tw-eé* [*tw-aá-li tu-lím-it-e umu-guúnda mbeé=gu-li*]]
 1P-RMCOP 1P-P_{RM}-COP 1P-till-PFV-FV 3-field whole=SM3-COP

pé=tw-kú-va-gusikis-â.

when=1P-PRO-OM2-sell_{to}-FV

‘We had [already] tilled the whole field [earlier] when we sold [it] to them.’

RECAP

Double compound auxiliary constructions invariably have a form of *-li* as the first auxiliary, followed by an auxiliary complement clause. However, although there is a construction with *-aá-li*, there is no full auxiliary with *-ká-li*, only the contracted form. The second auxiliary is usually constructed from one of three temporal forms of *-v-e*, but from the remote past form of *-li* in one case. These constructions index two reference times, auxiliary *ké* referring to a point, auxiliary *-v-e* to a temporal span.

Table 5: Double compound auxiliary constructions grounded in COPULA *-li*

SM- <i>ké</i>	SM- <i>v-e</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	SM- <i>ké</i>	SM- <i>káa-v-é</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>
<i>ké=SM-v-e</i>		SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	<i>ké=SM-káa-v-é</i>		SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>
SM- <i>ké</i>	SM- <i>v-é</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>			
<i>ké=SM-v-é</i>		SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>			
SM- <i>aá-li</i>	SM- <i>v-e</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	SM- <i>aá-li</i>	SM- <i>aa-v-é</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>
SM- <i>eé</i>	SM- <i>v-e</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>	SM- <i>eé</i>	SM- <i>aa-v-é</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>
			SM- <i>eé</i>	SM- <i>aá-li</i>	SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>

13 Future auxiliaries: (sá=)SM-v-á SM-T-B-iC-e

Although the focus of this study has been on auxiliary verbs marked for different pasts, it should be noted that future auxiliary constructions, based on auxiliary *-va* ‘be’ – near SM-*v-á* and remote *sá=SM-v-á* – there are two sets of auxiliary constructions based on them. As near future auxiliary, SM-*v-á* may occur with either the simple (44a) or recent *káa-* (44b) perfective form of the main verb, having the sense ‘will have Ved’ (in the future of the P-domain).

- (44) a. *Ná=l-o ulú-leénga lw-é=u-v-á u-tégw-e ukú-huma*
 even=11-DEM 11-water 11-REL=2S-be-FV 2S-take.PFV-FV 15-come_{from}

mu=mú-koga lu-v-á lu-sís-il-e.

18=3-river SM11-be-FV SM11-finish-PFV-FV

‘Even that water that you will have taken from the river will have been depleted.’

- b. *M-swámú va-ángu a-v-á a-káa-naambul-y-ê.*

1-son 2-1S.POSS SM1-be-FV SM1-P2-1S.tell-PFV-FV

‘My son will have told me.’ [the day before or earlier than reference time]

The remote future is formally like the near future but with the addition of the proclitic *sá=*. In the first instance, the main verb in the auxiliary construction is in the simple perfective (45a), in the second the remote past perfective (45b). The latter is then interpreted as occurring in the Ante-futurum D-domain, analogous to the Ante-preterite D-domain described previously above (Figure 17). Note that the dotted timeline through the Ante-futurum is for legibility.

- (45) a. *Sá=mu-teng'emál-a pamwiínga na umú-twa pé=sá=a-v-á*
 $F_{RM}=2P$ -sit-FV together with 1-chief when=FUT-SM1-be-FV
a-téng'em-e mu=ki-goda ch-a uwu-kómi.
 SM1-sit-PFV.FV 18=7-chair 7-ASV 11-power
 'You will sit together with the chief when he will have been seated in the chair of power.'
- b. *Sá=tu-v-á ye=tw-aa-hes-il-e ku=Mbigili pé=v-ii-pilúk-a.*
 $F_{RM}=1P$ -be-FV already=1P- P_{RM} -leave-PFV-FV 17=Mbigili when=SM2-PRO-return-FV
 'We will have already left from Mbigili when they return.'

Figure 18: Auxiliary *-va* in the future

Note the difference between the auxiliary construction in the subordinate clause (45a) and in the main clause (45b). In the former, reference time is marked with the remote future proclitic *sá=* in the main clause, while in the latter it is marked by the Relative Present *origo í-* in the subordinate clause. Thus, in (45a) both clauses are interpreted with respect to UT, while in (45b) the verb in the subordinate clause is construed as a ‘present origo’ indexed by RT_1 .

14 Auxiliary with complement auxiliary clause (5): (SM-)ké [SM-v-á SM-^HB-iC-e]

As described in Section 11 above, the auxiliary construction SM-v-á SM-^HB-iC-e indexes a reference time in the tangible future F1 of the P-domain. However, when the auxiliary SM-ké precedes the construction, the new construction acquires a conditional reading (46a), that is, finding us at home would have occurred but for some unspecified issue. The form with proclitic ké= differs in that it does not specify whether the event occurred immediately before reference time or much earlier today.

- (46) a. *va-ké* [*va-v-á* *va-tu-fis-il-e*] *pa=káaye*.
 SM2-AUX SM2-be-FV SM2-1P-make_contact-PFV-FV 16=9.home
 ‘They would have found us at home (but didn’t).’ [at that point today]
- b. *Ké=va-v-á* *va-tu-fis-il-e* *pa=káaye*.
 AUX=SM2-be-FV SM2-1P-make_contact-PFV-FV 16=9.home
 ‘They would have met us at home (but didn’t).’ [today; no specific time]

Note that there is no equivalent original construction SM-ká-li SM-v-á SM-^HB-iC-e, presumably because the *ká-li* specifies overtly a recent past, whereas *ké* has acquired a conditional interpretation.

The conditional sense of auxiliary -*va* use arises as well in its future form as an auxiliary verb in a complement auxiliary clause, with either contracted primary auxiliary SM-ké (47) or proclitic ké= (47). These constructions indicate that the event named in the main verb of the main clause did not occur. There is no apparent difference between the full form and the contracted ké= proclitic (48).

- (47) a. *va-ké* *va-lemw-é* *ukú-hweeleléla* [*va-ké* [*va-v-á* *va-tu-fis-il-e*]]
 SM2-AUX SM2-fail-SUB 15-be_late-FV SM2-AUX SM2-be-FV SM2-1P-arrive-PFV-FV
pa=káaye.
 16=9.home
 ‘Had they not been late [Lit. had they failed to be late], they would have found us at home.’ [today]
- b. *Ngali* [*u-ké* [*u-v-á* *yé=u-héj-e*] *ng’aani*]
 is_it 2S-AUX 2S-be-FV already=2S-leave.PFV-FV completely
uluhumamuú=ng’i]?
 11.from 18=9.country
 ‘Is it that you would have already left the land completely?’ [on that day or today]
- (48) a. *Ké=va-v-á* *va-lím-it-e* *umu-guúnda* *gú-la* *pamílaáwu* *íla*
 AUX=SM2-be-FV SM-till-PFV-FV 3-field 3-DEM morning but
y-íi-toóny’-a.
 SM9-PRO-rain-FV
 ‘They would have tilled that field in the morning, but it rained.’

- b. *Pamilaáwu, ké=tu-v-á tu-lím-it-e umu-guínda gú-la swê,*
 morning AUX=1P-be-FV 1P-till-PFV-FV 3-field 3-DEM only_that
ké=va-v-é si=v-íí-vaw-á.
 AUX=SM2-be-PFV.FV NEG=SM2-PRO-ail.PASS-FV
 ‘In the morning, we would have tilled that field only, had we not been ill.’

There is also a double auxiliary construction SM-*eé* SM-*v-á* SM-B-*iC-e*, which is understood only as not having been realized, and is hence translated as ‘would have Ved’ (49) in the remote past.

- (49) [*v-eé* [*va-v-á va-hés-it-e n=av-án-áwo mbeé=va-li*]]
 SM2-RMCOP SM2-be-FV SM2-leave-PFV-FV with=2-children-3P.POSS all=SM2-COP
 i. *íla si=v-aa-lamw-í ukú-hega.*
 but NEG=SM2-P_{RM}-decide-NEG 15-leave
 ii. *pé=v-íí-haám-a pála.*
 when=SM2-PRO-move-FV 16.there
 ‘They would have left with all their children
 i. but they decided not to leave.’
 ii. had (when) they moved there.’

RECAP

The verb *-va* also occurs in double compound auxiliary constructions with *-ké*, *ké=*, or *-eé* as the first auxiliary. In each case, the event is unrealized. The construction has a conditional sense ‘would have Ved’ (Table 6).

Table 6: Double compound auxiliary constructions grounded in *-va*

<i>WOULD HAVE VED</i>
SM- <i>ké</i> SM- <i>v-á</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>
<i>ké=</i> SM- <i>v-á</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>
SM- <i>eé</i> SM- <i>v-á</i> SM- ^H B- <i>iC-e</i>

Figure 19: Functions of the BE verb

15 Summary and conclusion

In this study, we have explored just a few of the many, many auxiliary constructions in Kihehe. The focus has been on two auxiliary BE verbs, especially when they have as a complement a perfective matrix verb or second auxiliary verb. Notably, we have seen that each functions in two ways, (i) referring to a temporal locus of orientation – a temporal point, a temporal span, or a temporal span culminating in a point; and (ii) indexing that locus as a reference time *RT*, summed up in Figure 19. Their dual nature implies that they are advantageously analysed as shifters, much like other deictic elements. As the data have shown, auxiliary BE verbs do not simply serve as ‘dummy’ hosts for grammatical inflections.

The data have shown as well that original forms of auxiliary copula *-li* have contracted into new forms *SM-ké*, *ké=*, and *SM-eé*, the contracted forms taking on new modal roles in certain contexts. These original and contracted forms occur in both single and double auxiliary constructions, the latter indexing two reference times. These double auxiliary constructions always have one of the *-li* forms as the first auxiliary. If the construction has perfective *-v-e* as the complement auxiliary, it expresses a temporal relationship in the past between some event and two reference times. On the other hand, we have observed just the contracted auxiliary with a complement auxiliary *-va* that expresses conditional modality.

As posited throughout, auxiliary *-li* refers to and indexes a point as *RT*. It has contracted in various ways so that original *-li* itself is no longer transparent. These contracted forms have come to compete with the original full forms so that there is now an inventory of auxiliary constructions grounded in one form or another of *-li*. Auxiliaries based on *-va*, on the other hand, have remained in their full forms, but unlike *-li* auxiliaries, refer to time spans with the terminal point indexed as *RT*. Thus, the two types can be used to express different relations.

One significant aspect of the double auxiliary constructions is that the primary auxiliary is invariably a form of *-li* followed, in all cases but one, by an auxiliary clause headed by a form of *-va*. It is not clear why this should be the case; presumably it has something to do with the difference in the expression of reference times as points or intervals. More research in this area is certainly warranted.

We have seen, too, that double auxiliary constructions, with a contracted form of *-li*, have come to express a conditional or deontic modality if the complement auxiliary is headed by *-vá*. Thus, these auxiliaries have acquired roles separate from the full forms.

The two auxiliary BE verbs investigated in this study do bear grammatical information, as Anderson (2011, 62) posits, in particular tense and aspect, but they also impart information about reference indices, in Kihehe as many as two, which reflect a shifted origo. What is important here is that these compound auxiliary constructions communicate relevant information about complex temporal relations among events, fruitfully analysed in the Domains and Regions framework. We have seen, for example, the difference between preterite and ante-preterite marking (D-domains), and preterite and ante-preterite perfects, construction types not overtly found in English or in many European languages (but compare Portuguese and French (Botne 2023), hence the repeated ‘had VERBED’ translation for many of these auxiliary forms. Further investigation using the DaR framework may usefully provide new insights into these or related types of constructions.

Abbreviations

AGR	agreement	FV	final vowel	PrO	relative present <i>origo</i>
APPL	applicative	HOD	hodiernal	PRE-PR.	pre-present
ASV	associative marker	IMMTR	immediate time region	PRM	remote past
AUX	auxiliary	LOC	locative	PRO	pronoun
B	verb base	NEG	negative	Q	question marker
CMPL	completive	OM	object marker	REC	reciprocal
COP	copula	P1	hodiernal past	RED	reduplicant
DEM	demonstrative	P2	recent past	REL	relative marker
DIS	distal	PA	predicate adjective	RM COP	remote past copula
DUR	durative	PASS	passive	RT	reference time
E	event	PFV	perfective	SM	subject marker
EP	epenthetic element	POSS	possessive	SUB	subjunctive
F1	near future	PP	pluperfect(ive)	T	tense
FRM	remote future	PR	present	UT	utterance time

1S, 2S, 1P, 2P = first person singular, etc.; 1, 2, ... = noun classes 1, 2, ... [with SM, OM, AGR, and DEM]

B^H = high tone on final mora of verb base; ^HB = high tone on first mora of verb base

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The Development of Negative ‘have’ Auxiliaries in the Bantu Languages of the Middle and Lower Zambezi

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Abstract

This paper studies the grammaticalization of possessive predicates into negative auxiliaries expressing main clause negation in the Bantu languages of the Middle and Lower Zambezi River region. Drawing on a convenience sample of languages from this linguistic area, the study identifies four distinct types of ‘have’ predicates that function as negative auxiliaries in a little-known pattern of asymmetric main clause negation in Bantu languages. Focusing on patterns of interlingual and intralingual variation, the paper considers the functional and conceptual homogeneity of the auxiliary constructions versus their formal heterogeneity, taking into account the sociolinguistic context of sustained language contact through migration, trade, and the movement of soldiers. The attested variation is moreover suggestive of a ‘negative possessive cycle’ highly reminiscent but still different from a better known ‘negative existential cycle’ which has been connected to long-standing contact situations among Bantu languages. The findings contribute to our understanding of negative auxiliary systems in Bantu, while at the same time offering insights into the mechanisms driving linguistic innovation in the region.

Keywords: defective verbs, light verbs, negation without negators, negative existentials

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1 Introduction

The grammaticalization of various formally divergent types of possessive predicates into auxiliaries expressing main clause negation occurs with striking frequency in the Bantu languages of the Middle and Lower Zambezi Valley. In this contact-rich region negative ‘have’ auxiliaries, as illustrated in (1) for Barwe, display considerable formal variation while maintaining consistent patterns of functional specialization.

- (1) Barwe N45, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)¹
*Dzuro, hatíná kugúrá mafígú.*²
 dzuro ha-ti-na ku-gur-a ma-figu
 yesterday NEG-SP1PL-have INF-buy-FV NCP6-banana
 ‘Yesterday, we didn’t buy bananas.’

Derived from diverse negative predicative possession constructions, these auxiliaries have been reanalyzed and grammaticalized into main clause negators, typically marking the negative perfect(ive).³ While negative constructions and auxiliary systems have received ample attention in Bantu linguistics, the development of possessive predicates into main clause negators has not yet been examined in a dedicated study. This paper addresses this gap through a comprehensive analysis of four distinct types of negative possessive predicates in the Bantu languages of the Middle and Lower Zambezi and adjacent areas. Map 1 displays the geographic locations of the languages in which a negative ‘have’ auxiliary is attested.⁴

Methodologically, the study adopts a cross-linguistic comparative approach, drawing on a diverse dataset which combines original fieldwork data with existing descriptions from the linguistic literature. Original linguistic data were collected through elicitation tasks, semi-structured interviews, and natural discourse recordings with native speakers of selected languages in the region. Secondary data were drawn from grammars and academic articles on the languages under study. Languages were chosen based on the availability of data and their relevance to the research questions.

By integrating synchronic description with historical-comparative analysis this study aims to:

- i. systematically document and analyse the four types of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries in the Bantu languages of the Middle and Lower Zambezi, identifying their morphosyntactic properties, functional roles, and distribution across the language sample.
- ii. give a typological framework for this type of asymmetric negation and see how its development (a) reflects a grammaticalization process displaying cyclical change (specifically a ‘negative possessive cycle’); and (b) is driven by external sociolinguistic factors (e.g., language contact, migration, and trade).

¹ ‘Fieldnotes’ indicates data collected by one or several of the authors.

² We present the fieldwork examples as spoken, including surface tones, in the top line, followed by the segmented morphemes below. For examples taken from published works, we present the transcriptions as they are given by the author and respect the (recurrent) absence of tone marking.

³ Throughout this paper we use perfect(ive) as a cover term for both perfect and perfective aspect. Their expression often involves the same morphosyntactic means in Bantu languages, the perfect(ive) suffix *-ile* being a notorious example (Crane and Fanego 2020, 45).

⁴ A detailed description of the entire language sample is presented in the Appendix.

Map 1: Locations of the sampled languages (created with ArcGIS Online – Map Viewer)

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 outlines the different types of affirmative and negative possessive predication attested in the sample and considers their distribution from a Bantu-wide perspective. Section 3 describes the four types of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries and their morphosyntactic properties, while Section 4 situates them within known patterns of negation in Bantu and within Miestamo’s (2005) typology of asymmetric negation. Section 5 adopts a historical-comparative lens to trace the diachronic development of these auxiliaries, exploring the role of language contact and grammaticalization patterns. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the findings and their implications for studies of grammaticalization, negation, and possession in Bantu and beyond.

2 Predicative possession

Since ‘have’ auxiliaries are the principal feature of the negative constructions under study, this section starts out by investigating the expression of predicative possession in the languages of our sample. Creissels (2024) shows that two types of possessive constructions are widespread among Bantu languages, i.e., the ‘Have Possessive’ type and the ‘Comit Possessive’ type. In the Have Possessive type, the coding of the possessor and the possessee matches that of the agent and the patient in transitive predication, whereas in the Comit Possessive Type the possessee is introduced by a comitative (‘with’) marker. The Have Possessive Type is illustrated for Tonga (M64)⁵ in (2). The ‘have’ predicate *jisi* is the perfect(ive) form of the verb *jata* ‘catch, hold’

⁵The Guthrie classification codes adopted in this paper follow Maho’s (2009) updated inventory, with the addition

(Collins 1962, 49). The Comit Possessive Type can also be illustrated with Tonga. In (3) the predicate is the copula *li* ‘be’ and the possessee is introduced by the comitative *a* ‘with’, which may apparently attach to either the copula or the possessee.⁶

- (2) Tonga M64, Zambia (Carter 1974, 9, glossing added)

Héna mujisi cilyo?
 hena mu-jisi ci-lyo
 YOU.PL SP2PL-seize.PFV NCP7-food
 ‘Do you have any food?’

- (3) Tonga M64, Zambia (Carter 2002, 69, glossing added)

Wakali anguzu / Wakalaa nguzu
 w-aka-li a-nguzu / wa-aka-li-a nguzu
 SP1-PST-COP COM-NCP9.strength
 ‘He was with/had strength.’

Predicative possession in many of the languages in our sample reflects a process referred to as ‘have-drift’ by Stassen (2009), by which possessive constructions of other types acquire characteristics of the Have Possessive type. In present tense contexts the copula is often (optionally) omitted and the comitative marker is inflected for person. In the absence of a copula, the comitative marker undergoes a categorical change from preposition/conjunction to predicate. However, it is a defective predicate at best, as it can often only take subject prefixes and negative morphology, but no other verbal morphology, such as object prefixes. The possessee can thus not be object marked on the comitative predicate, as opposed to ‘have’ predicates, which typically can take an object prefix indexing the possessee. Phimbi (N402) shows such optional omission of the copula in present tense contexts. In (4), the subject prefix attaches directly to the comitative predicate, which can only index the possessee through a referential enclitic (=ko). This morphosyntactic feature is inherited from its origin in a preposition/conjunction which can host referential enclitics, as seen in (5), where the comitative preposition is (still) preceded by the copula. In Malawian Tonga (N15) the copula is always omitted in present tense contexts. We consider (possibly) merged and shortened constructions, like the ones in (3) and (4), respectively, as belonging to the Comit Poss type.

- (4) Phimbi N402, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

Pano tina kamú:tí kadí:kí komwe tiná:ko.
 pano ti-na ka-mu-ti ka-diki ka-omwe ti-na=ko
 here SP1PL-have NCP12-NCP3-tree NAP12-small PP12-REL SP1PL-have=REF.12
 ‘Here we have the only small stick that we have.’

of new proposed codes for the previously non-inventoried varieties (N401, N402, N403, N404, N411, S101, and S102). See the Appendix for details.

⁶Note that without further phonological analysis it is unclear whether the comitative truly attaches to the copula, as suggested by Carter (2002, 69), or whether there is liaison between the copula and the following possessee introduced by the comitative. The fact that a merger between copula and comitative occurs recurrently in Bantu languages (Devos and Bernander 2022) adds some weight to Carter’s analysis.

- (5) Phimbi N402, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

Ndiri názo má:ri (...).

ndi-ri na=zo Ø-mari
 SP1SG-COP COM=REF.10 NCP10-money
 ‘I have money.’

- (6) Tonga N15, Malawi (MacAlpine et al., n.d.)

Tose tindi wabali.

ti-ose ti-ndi wá-bali
 SP1PL-all SP1PL-have NCP2-relative
 ‘All of us have relatives.’

When looking at affirmative predicative possession in the Bantu languages of the Zambezi valley, in line with Creissels’ (2024) cross-Bantu observations, we find that they overwhelmingly make use of the Comit Possessive type: 25 out of the 26 languages for which we have relevant data have the Comit Poss type, while only one Bantu Botatwe language⁷ has the Have Poss type. Three other Bantu Botatwe languages have both types, as in Tonga (M64) (2)–(3). The ‘have’ predicates used in these Bantu Botatwe languages are perfect(ive)s of verbs expressing ‘seize, grasp’, as with *jisi* in (2) above. Another example comes from Ila (M63), where *kwete*, the perfect(ive) of *kwata* ‘have, hold’ (from *kóat ‘seize’ (Bastin et al. 2002)), is used in affirmative predicative possession.

- (7) Ila M63, Zambia (Smith 1907, 185, glossing added)

Ndikwete shidyó.

ndi-kwete shi-dyo
 SP1SG-have.PFV NCP7-food
 ‘I have food.’

Negative predicative possession shows non-dedicated construction types which combine standard negative marking with the two main affirmative types and two dedicated types involving either specialized negative morphology or intrinsically negative verbs. Negative predicative possession can be rendered by the Comit Poss type in combination with standard negation, as in (8). A related dedicated type replaces the comitative marker with a specialized negative enclitic which we assume to mean something like ‘empty, without’, as in (9). We refer to this type as the Enclitic Poss type. The specialized negative enclitic, which takes forms such as =be, =be, =vye, =ve, and =je, is dedicated to negative possessive and existential constructions (for the latter see also Bernander et al. 2022, 21–22).

⁷The term Bantu Botatwe refers to a group of closely related languages, further divided into Eastern and Western Botatwe. Our sample includes languages from the eastern cluster which is composed of languages from Guthrie’s Zone M60 languages (see Bostoen 2009).

- (8) Nyanja N31a, Zambia (Lehmann 2002, 26, glossing added)

Simuli ndi ana.

si-mu-li ndi a-ana
NEG-SP2PL-COP COM NCP2-child

‘You have no children.’

- (9) Nyanja N31a, Zambia (Peace Corps 1995b, 11, glossing added)

Alibe nyumba

a-li=be ny-umba
SP1-COP=NEG NCP9-house

‘S/he does not have a house.’

In one language, Sena (N44), the predicate is an invariable particle, i.e., *nkhabe*, which contains the specialized negative enclitic =*be*. Since it is also used in existential constructions and might contain petrified locative morphology ($n < \text{class 18 locative prefix } *m\bar{v}-?$) (Meeussen 1967; Grégoire 1975), we treat this type as the Exist Poss type from Creissels’ typology (Creissels 2024).

- (10) Sena N44, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2025)

Ífe nkhábé mazái makú:lu

ife nkhabe ma-zai ma-kulu
PRO1PL NEG.EX NCP6-egg NAP6-big

‘We do not have big eggs.’

- (11) Sena N44, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2025)

Nkabépo múntú anapikwaní:sa

nkhabe=po mu-ntu a-na-pi-kwanis-a
NEG.EX=LOC16 NCP1-person SP1-PRS-OP8-manage-FV

There is no one there who is able (to lift that).’

The negative Have Poss type involves the combination of standard negation and a ‘have’ predicate derived from a verb expressing ‘seize, grasp’, as in (12). We consider the construction in Bemba as non-dedicated because it involves standard negation, defined as the basic way(s) a language has to negate a declarative main clause (Miestamo 2005). However, it does show signs of specialization, as the ‘have’ predicate *kwete* is not used in affirmative predicative possession. This type of specialization is attested in other languages of the M40–M50⁸ groups and in some Bantu Botatwe languages (see Table 1).

⁸The M40–M50 groups are primarily spoken in Zambia and neighbouring regions. Bemba (M42) is one of the country’s seven recognized regional languages, and is primarily spoken in northeastern Zambia, being widely used in both rural and urban areas, especially in the Northern, Luapula, and Copperbelt provinces. Wisa (M51) (often referred to as Bisa) is spoken in northeastern Zambia, in Muchinga Province and in parts of Luapula Province, with smaller communities in southeastern Democratic Republic of Congo. Lamba (M54) is spoken mainly in Zambia’s Copperbelt and in parts of the Democratic Republic of Congo (Haut-Katanga).

- (12) Bemba M42, Zambia (Peace Corps 1995a, 40, glossing added)

Nshikwete impiva.

n-shi-kwete i-m-piva

SP1SG-NEG-have.PFV AUG-NCP9-money

‘I have no money.’

The ‘have’ predicate may also be an intrinsically negative verb expressing ‘not have, lack’. We refer to this dedicated type as the Have_{NEG} Poss type. Three such intrinsically negative verbs are attested in our language sample: *vul-a* (from *bód ‘lack, be lacking, be lost’ (Bastin et al. 2002)), *so-a* ‘lack’ (etymology unclear), and *(ny)in-a* ‘have not, be without, be not’.⁹

- (13) Soli M62, Zambia (van Eeden 1936, 37, glossing added)

Vavula vakaši

va-vul-a va-kasi

SP2-lack-FV NCP2-woman

‘They have no wives’

- (14) Sena N44, Mozambique (Torrend 1900, 165, glossing added)

Asoa mufti.

a-so-a m-futi

SP1-lack-FV NCP9-gun

‘He has no gun.’

- (15) Tonga M64, Zambia (Collins 1962, 63, glossing added)

Bantu banyina maanu.

ba-ntu ba-nyina ma-anu

NCP2-person SP2-not.have NCP6-intelligence

‘People have no intelligence/sense.’

The negative ‘have’ verbs *nyin-a* in Tonga (M64) and *in-a* in Ila (M63) seem to be derived from a merger of *d_I ‘be’ and *na ‘with’ (Bastin 2020, 49). How they became intrinsically negative is puzzling, however. One hypothesis is that the first part, rather than being a reflex of the copula *d_I, is a petrified post-initial negative marker. Post-initial *i-* is attested in Bemba (M42), Wisa/Bisa (M51), and Lamba (M54). However, it is always used for the negation of subjunctive and related conjugations, never in negative predicative possession. Another hypothesis is that *(ny)in-a* is a negative verb like *vu-la* or *so-a*, whose etymology we do not know. However, the fact that *(ny)in-a* does not mean ‘lack’ or ‘be lost’ but rather ‘have not’, ‘be not’ does suggest an origin in a merger of *d_I and *na, even if the comitative marker has been replaced by or reduced to *a* ‘with’ in the languages in question. Bastin (2020, 49) notes that these merged forms in some languages of zone H have acquired the meaning ‘be’. In the Western Botatwe language Totela (K41), *in-a* is polysemous between ‘have’ and ‘be’ (Crane 2011, 245–246; Devos and Bernander 2022, 600–601). In affirmative possessive constructions the comitative marker tends

⁹It should be noted that intrinsically negative ‘have’ verbs like *vula* occur in other languages in our sample as well (see also Bernander et al. 2023). However, they are only included here if they present the only way or the conventional way of expressing ‘have’ in unmarked present tense contexts.

to be added to disambiguate the two senses. However, the addition of the comitative marker is not required in negative possessive constructions. A similar pattern is attested in Tswana (S31), Southern Sotho (S33), and Lozi (K21), where *na* is polysemous between ‘have’ and ‘be’. Again, affirmative possessive constructions require the insertion of an (innovated) comitative marker, whereas negative possessive constructions do not need extra marking (Creissels 2024, 208–209) (see also Fortune 1950 for similar observations). The examples below are from Southern Sotho (S33).

- (16) Southern Sotho S33, South Africa (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 309, glossing added)

Kēna lēngōana.

ke-na le-ngo-ana
 SP1SG-be COM-NCP1-child
 ‘I have a child.’

- (17) Southern Sotho S33, South Africa (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 309, glossing added)

Hakēna ngōana.

ha-ke-na ngo-ana
 NEG-SP1SG-have NCP1-child
 ‘I do not have any child.’

Pending further historical-comparative research, we suggest that such a pattern may have triggered reanalysis of *(ny)ina* or *na* as an intrinsically negative ‘have’ verb.

For negative predicative possession, the dedicated Enclitic Poss type is the most frequently attested in our sample: it occurs in 14 languages, in 11 of which it is the only strategy. The Comit Poss type occurs 11 times but mostly as an alternative to the Enclitic Poss type or the Have Poss type. The Have Poss type occurs seven times and the Have_{NEG} Poss type four times. The Exist Poss type occurs only once and is not represented in Table 1.

Table 1 summarizes the distribution of affirmative and negative predicative possession types in our sample.¹⁰ The Comit, Enclitic, Have, and Have_{NEG} types correspond to the Type A, B, C and D auxiliaries respectively, as will be seen in Section 3. Languages tend to have more competing strategies in negative than affirmative predicative possession, which is suggestive of renewal and possibly cyclical change reminiscent of a negative existential cycle (NEC) (Croft 1991; Veselinova 2016; Veselinova and Hamari 2022; Bernander et al. 2022). Only five languages in Table 1 have only a non-dedicated (either Comit or Have) negative possessive strategy (Stage A in a NEC). Moreover, in Kunda (N411),¹¹ the non-dedicated Have Poss type shows signs of

¹⁰ A dash (-) indicates that a certain type is not attested in the language in question, at least not in the available data. Strategies that belong to the same type but have different lexical input are separated by a semicolon (;). Strategies belonging to the same type but showing phonological variation are separated by an oblique stroke (/).

¹¹ N411 refers to ‘Kunda of Mambwe district’. Kunda does not appear in Maho (2009), but is subsumed under N41 by Hammarström (2019). We propose a new Guthrie Code based on divergent features identified in Zemba’s

specialization, as the ‘have’ auxiliary *kwete* is not used for affirmative possession. In the four languages which can use both non-dedicated strategies, the Have Poss Type typically shows similar signs of specialization. Four languages in Table 1 have both non-dedicated (Comit or Have) and dedicated (Enclitic or Have_{NEG}) negative possessive strategies, reminiscent of the transitional Stage A~B of a NEC, while 14 languages only have dedicated strategies (at least in present tense contexts), reminiscent of Stage B of a NEC. Bernander et al. (2022) show that Bantu dedicated negative existentials hardly ever expand into the domain of main clause negation (Stage C), and on the rare occasion that they do, language contact typically plays a crucial role. In Section 4, we describe how and to what extent both non-dedicated (Sections 4.1 and 4.3) and dedicated (Sections 4.2 and 4.4) negative possessive strategies expand to main clause negation in the Bantu languages of the Middle and Lower Zambezi.

Table 1: Affirmative and negative predicative possession types in Zambezi Bantu

Language	Affirmative types		Negative types			
	Comit	Have	Comit (Type A)	Enclitic (Type B)	Have (Type C)	Have _{NEG} (Type D)
Bemba M42	li+na; ba+na	-	li+na	-	kwete	-
Wisa/Bisa M51	li+na; wa+na	-	wa+na	-	kwete	-
Lamba M54	li+na	-	wa+na	-	kwete	-
Lenje M61	li+a	cité	li+a; ba+a	-	kwe; cité	-
Soli M62	-	kute	-	li-ya	-	vula
Ila M63	di/li+o; di/li¹²	kwete	-	-	kwete	ina; bula
Tonga M64	li+a/laa; ba+a	jisi	-	-	kwe; jisi	ina/ nyina
Mlw. Tonga N15	ndi	-	-	li-vi	-	-
Tz. Nyanja N201	li+ni	-	-	lí-je	-	-
Tumbuka N21	li+na	-	-	li-vye	-	-
Senga N21d	na	-	-	li-je	-	-
Zam. Nyanja N31a	li+ni	-	li+ndi	li-be	-	-
Chewa N31b	li+ndi	-	-	li-be	-	-
Moz. Nyanja N31d	ri+ndi	-	li+ndi	li-be	-	-
Nserero N401	na	-	-	ri-be	-	-

(2015) grammar sketch, and due to lexical similarity with Nsenga being estimated at 70% by Sawka et al. (2021, 36). Kunda (N411) is unrelated to and not to be confused with Chikunda (N42).

¹²Smith (1907, 184–185) notes that the omission of the comitative marker *o* is prevalent in relative clauses. Fowler (2000) does not mention the Comit Poss type as a possible equivalent for ‘have’, which might indicate that the Comit Poss type has become obsolete and has been replaced entirely by the Have Poss type.

Language	Affirmative types		Negative types			
	Comit	Have	Comit (Type A)	Enclitic (Type B)	Have (Type C)	Have _{NEG} (Type D)
Phimbi N402	na; ri+na	-	-	ri-be	-	-
Dema N403	na	-	-	ri-be	-	-
Guro Tonga N404	na	-	-	ri-be	-	-
Nsenga N41	ri+na; na	-	-	li-ye	-	-
Kunda N411	li+na	-	-	-	kwete	-
Chikunda N42	ri+na; na	-	-	ri-be; be	-	-
Nyungwe N43	na	-	-	ri-be	-	-
Sena N44	li+na; na	-	-	-	-	soa
Barwe N45	na	-	na; wa+na	-	-	-
Doma S101	na/ne	-	na	-	-	-
Hwesa S102	na	-	na; khara+na	-	-	-
Korekore S11	na/ne	-	na	-	-	-
Tawara S11	na	-	na	ri-be; be	-	-
Zezuru S12	na/ne	-	na	-	-	-
Manyika S13	ne	-	ne	-	-	-

3 Four types of ‘have’ predicates as negative auxiliaries

The four types of possessive predicates distinguished in Section 3 have extended uses as auxiliaries dedicated to the expression of specific categories of main clause negation. Importantly, the affirmative counterparts of these negative categories involve simplex verbal constructions, making the negative expressions structurally distinct and asymmetric. In the following subsections we look in more detail at the Comit Poss (Type A, Section 3.1), the Enclitic Poss (Type B, Section 3.2), the Have Poss (Type C, Section 3.3), and the Have_{NEG} Poss (Type D, Section 3.4) possessive predicate types in our language sample and discuss their extended uses as negative auxiliaries in main clause negation. The question of whether these extended uses are suggestive of a ‘negative possessive cycle’, reminiscent of a NEC, will be addressed in Section 5.1.

3.1 Type A: The Comit Poss type for main clause negation

Type A involves a Comit Poss type predicate which, in combination with standard negative morphology and a main verb in the infinitive, serves to express a negative perfective. Crucially, it is only the short Comit Poss predicate, i.e., the comitative predicate *na* without a preceding ‘be’ verb, which has this extended use.

Type A is attested in the S10 Shona group, as well as in certain M60 Botatwe languages and in Barwe (N45), where the NEG-SP-*na* + INF construction serves as a negative TAM auxiliary, specifically encoding perfective aspect (18). The affirmative perfective, by contrast, is marked solely by the prefix *dá-* (19). Notably, *na* does not appear as an auxiliary in affirmative contexts, nor is the perfective marker *dá-* negated through standard prefixal negation.

- (18) Barwe N45, Mozambique (Natural speech, Fieldnotes 2024)

Mai bzángú ndikhá:da, handíná kubzikwaní:sa.

mai bzi-angu ndi-kha-d-a ha-ndi-na ku-bzi-kwanis-a
but PP8-POSS.1SG SP1SG-PST.IPFV-want-FV NEG-SP1SG-have INF-OP8-manage-FV

‘But mine that I wanted, I did not manage.’ (‘I did not manage to do what I wanted’)

- (19) Barwe N45, Mozambique (Natural speech, Fieldnotes 2024)

Ndidabarirya paDú:nda.

ndi-da-bar-ir-y-a pa-Dunda
SP1SG-PFV-give.birth-APPL-PASS-FV NCP16-Dunda

‘I was born in Dunda.’

Such asymmetric negation is not categorical but rather restricted to specific TAM categories. In Barwe, for instance, the asymmetry observed in (18) and (19) contrasts with symmetric prefixal negation of the past imperfective (prefix *kha-*), illustrated in (20).

- (20) Barwe N45, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

a. *Tikhagúrá mafígú (...).*

ti-kha-gur-a ma-figu
SP1PL-PST.IPFV-buy-FV NCP6-banana

‘We were buying bananas (when you saw us).’

b. *Hatikhagúrá mafí:gu.*

ha-ti-kha-gur-a ma-figu
NEG-SP1PL-PST.IPFV-buy-FV NCP6-banana

‘We were not buying bananas (when you saw us).’

An example of *na* co-occurring with standard negation – without additional TAM marking – and encoding the nondum (‘not yet’) meaning is provided in (21) for Ila (M63). Interestingly, Ila uses Have Poss or Have_{NEG} Poss type predicates in possessive predication rather than the Comit Poss type. We return to this pattern in Section 5.2.

- (21) Ila M63, Zambia (Smith 1907, 165)

Tatuna kubona.

ta-tu-na ku-bona
NEG-SP1PL-have INF-see

‘We have not (yet) seen.’

In Zezuru (S12), the negative Comit Poss construction may further host the persistive aspectual marker *ci-*, yielding the phasal polarity concept ‘no longer’ (22). It may also occur in non-main clause negation, in which case it takes the post-initial negative marker *si-* (23). More unexpectedly, in Hwesa (S102), a Mozambican Shona variety, the future tense marker *za-* may also be incorporated into this construction (24). The ability to encode a range of negative TAM categories beyond the perfective suggests a robust expansion of the negative possessive into main clause negation in the Shona group.

- (22) Zezuru S12, Zimbabwe (Fortune 1955, 330)

Handicina kutora.

ha-ndi-ci-na ku-tor-a
 NEG-SP1SG-PERS-have INF-take-FV

‘I no longer took.’

- (23) Zezuru S12, Zimbabwe (Fortune 1955, 330)

Ndisina kutora.

ndi-si-na ku-tor-a
 SP1SG-NEG-have INF-take-FV

‘I who have not taken’ / ‘I not having taken.’

- (24) Hwesa S102, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes, 2025)

Hakuzá:ná: kuyí:tá: cinwá:nhu.

ha-ku-za-na ku-yit-a ci-nwanhu
 NEG-SP17-FUT-have INF-do-FV NCP7-ceremony

‘There will not be held any ceremony.’

Table 2 lists the languages in our sample which attest the Type A negative auxiliary construction and shows which TAM category it helps to express in the absence of further TAM marking on the auxiliary (i.e., either *nondum* or *PST/PFV*). The table further shows whether the language also uses the *Comit Poss* type for negative possessive predication and whether the language has other negative auxiliary types. It is interesting to note that Barwe, traditionally classified within the Sena cluster (see Doke 1931; Hammarström et al. 2025), is the only N40 language to exhibit Type A. With regard to this linguistic feature, Barwe demonstrates a close alignment with the Shona group.

Table 2: Distribution of the *Comit Poss* type for main clause negation

<i>Language</i>	<i>Comit Poss Type for negative possession?</i>	<i>Type A auxiliary</i>	<i>Other negative auxiliary types?</i>
Lenje M61	-	✓ (<i>nondum</i>)	✓ (Type C)
Soli M62	-	✓ (<i>nondum</i>)	✓ (Type D)
Ila M63	-	✓ (<i>nondum</i>)	✓ (Type C & D)
Barwe N45	✓	✓ (<i>PFV</i>)	-
Doma S101	✓	✓ (<i>PST/PFV</i>)	-
Hwesa S102	-	✓ (<i>PST/PFV</i>)	✓ (Type B)
Korekore S11	✓	✓ (<i>PST/PFV</i>)	-
Tawara S11	-	✓ (<i>PST/PFV</i>)	✓ (Type B)
Zezuru S12	✓	✓ (<i>PST/PFV</i>)	-
Manyika S13	✓	✓ (<i>PST/PFV</i>)	-

3.2 Type B: The Enclitic Poss type for main clause negation

Type B involves an Enclitic Poss type predicate which, in combination with a specialized negative enclitic and a main verb in the infinitive, serves to express a negative perfective. The pattern is conceptually identical to Type A but consists of different morphological material and is found mostly in languages from Guthrie’s Zone N. The construction consists of a copulative element, typically a reflex of the Proto-Bantu copula **di* and a specialized negative enclitic, which occurs in several different forms, such as =*be*, =*be*, =*vye*, =*ve*, and =*je*. The enclitic is specialized in the sense that it only occurs in negative possessive and existential constructions, including in the extended auxiliary use. It does not occur as the negator in other constructions in the languages in the sample. The distributional pattern is illustrated in examples (25)–(27) from Phimbi (N402). The negative possessive use of *dibe* – which we use as a common denominator for the Enclitic Poss type – is illustrated in (25); the auxiliary use is shown in (26); and lastly, the use of the standard negator *rini* is shown in an imperfective TAM category in (27):

- (25) Phimbi N402, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

Niriibe: má:ri.

ndi-ri=be Ø-mari
SP1SG-COP=NEG NCP10-money

‘I do not have money.’

- (26) Phimbi N402, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

Ningadakhara dzúro ndiriibe kukuwó:na...

ni-ngada-khar-a dzuro ndi-ri=be ku-ku-on-a
SP1SG-CTFL-be-FV yesterday SP1SG-COP=NEG INF-OP2SG-see-FV

‘If I had not seen you yesterday...’ (lit. ‘If I had been I did not see you.’)

- (27) Phimbi N402, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

Ticagura rini: mabaná:na.

ti-ca-gur-a rini ma-banana
SP1PL-IPFV-buy-FV NEG NCP6-banana

‘We are not buying bananas.’

Functionally, Type B constructions are mostly used for the negation of the perfective, as illustrated in (26), which typically has present state readings with stative verbs, such as the Guro Tonga (N404) verbs *tokot-a* and *ibv-a* ‘be(come) ripe/mature’ in (28):

- (28) Guro Tonga N404, Mozambique (Natural speech, Fieldnotes¹³ 2025)

Mami yáwo yariibe kutokó:ta, yariibe kwi:bva.

ma-mi ya-wo ya-ri=be ku-tokot-a ya-ri=be ku-ibv-a
NCP6-marriage PP6-POSS.3PL SP6-COP=NEG INF-ripen-FV SP6-COP=NEG INF-ripen-FV

‘Their marriages are not ripe, they are not mature.’

¹³All the Guro Tonga (N47) data comes from fieldwork conducted by Abílio Muilima together with Aron Zahran.

For past state readings, e.g., with the verb *net-a* ‘be(come) tired’ in Guro Tonga (N404), the past imperfective *kha*-¹⁴ is added to perfective-resultative *dā*- in the affirmative (29a) and to *ribe* in the negative (29b). Standard negation with the post-verbal particle *rini* is not possible, again illustrating the formal asymmetry between perfective marking in the affirmative (*dā*-) and negative (*-ribe*).

(29) Guro Tonga N404, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

a. *Íyé: akhadané:tá (*rini) mácíbése*

iye a-kha-dā-net-a ma-cíbese
 PRO.3SG SP1-PST-PFV-be(come).tired-FV NCP6-morning
 ‘S/he was tired this morning.’ (lit. ‘s/he had tired.’)

b. *Íyé akharíbé kunétá réro macíbese.*

iye a-kha-ri=be ku-net-a rero ma-cíbese
 PRO.3SG SP1-PST-COP=NEG INF-be(come).tired-FV today NCP6-morning
 ‘S/he was not tired this morning.’ (lit. ‘S/he had not tired.’)

Beyond the canonical constructions with the copula **di* and the negative enclitic in its varying forms, the Type B construction shows some variation that, from a diachronic perspective, can be interpreted as subsequent development. Leaving the diachronic analysis for later, we will simply describe the variation observed here.

First, the auxiliary constructions with *dibe* sometimes undergo univerbation and surface as contracted simplex forms. The infinitive marker on the lexical verb may be phonologically reduced or completely eroded, which results in contracted forms such as (30). When the erosion of the infinitive is further combined with the erosion of the copula,¹⁵ very little morphological material is left from the original complex construction. In example (31) from Nserero (N401), it is synchronically possible to simply analyse *be*- as a TAMP prefix encoding negative perfective (see Section 5.1).

(30) Nsenga N41 (Ranger 1928, 233, glossing added)

*Mfumu iliyolawira.*¹⁶

m-fumu i-li=ye ku-lawir-a
 NCP9-chief SP9-COP=NEG INF-speak-FV
 ‘The chief has not spoken.’

¹⁴In these complex forms, the imperfective semantics of *kha*- are overwritten by the perfective/resultative semantics of *dā*- / *-ribe*.

¹⁵This seems especially frequent in the N40 cluster when the final vowel of the subject prefix is the same as the copula, i.e., /*ri*/ → [i] / i __.

¹⁶On the surface, the infinitival prefix may be eroded, although the compound form is still synchronically available in all the sample languages. In the glossing, we indicate the full, uncontracted form unless the example is specifically meant to highlight the ongoing grammaticalization process (see examples (31), (43f), and (53), along with a more detailed discussion in Section 5.1).

- (31) Nserero N401, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

Dzuro, tibegure βibanana.

dzuro ti-βe-gur-e βi-banana
 yesterday SP1PL-PFV.NEG-buy-EMPH NCP8-banana
 ‘Yesterday, we didn’t buy bananas.’

Secondly, *dibe* may occur with additional tense-aspect marking. This was already observed in (29), where past imperfective *kha-* was shown to render past state readings, while dynamic verbs get past perfective semantics. Another TAM marker that can be added to *dibe* in most languages of the N40 cluster is the persistive *ka-*, which is used to give the construction a nondum sense typically translatable as ‘not yet’, but sometimes also as ‘never’ or ‘before’.

- (32) Chikunda N42, Zambia (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

Nikaribé: kugura mafí:gu

ni-ka-ri=βe ku-gur-a ma-figu
 SP1SG-PERS-COP=NEG INF-buy-FV NCP6-bananas
 ‘I have never bought bananas.’

- (33) Nsenga N41, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2024)

Tikariyúúgura vikó:nde

ti-ka-ri=ye ku-gur-a vi-konde
 SP1PL-PERS-COP=NEG INF-buy-FV NCP8-bananas
 ‘We have not yet bought bananas.’

Thirdly, the negative enclitic is used with other copulative elements than *di. This is the case in Nsenga (N41) and in the Tumbuka-Kamanga (N21c) variety described by Young (1932b).¹⁷ Most descriptions of Tumbuka (N21) (e.g., Turner 1952; Vail 1972; Kishindo and Lipenga 2005; Kiso 2012) do not mention the *dibe* construction as a TAM auxiliary, but Young (1932b) and also Nurse (2008a), who may have taken his data from Young, mention *lijeliv(y)e* as an alternative, more rare, negation strategy. Young (1932b, 138) writes that the *lijeliv(y)e* form means ‘be without’ and is “only found in the present indicative”. The present tense readings might be an artefact of very literal translations of his examples,¹⁸ e.g., (34), although, in other parts of his grammar, there are examples which are clearly used with more perfective-like TAM semantics, as in (35).

¹⁷ The Tumbuka varieties described by Kiso (2012) and Vail (1972) are from the Mzimba, Chitipa, and Rumphi districts of Malawi. Turner’s (1952) dictionary also appears to draw from Malawian Tumbuka, while Kishindo and Lipenga (2005) do not specify where their data is from. Young’s (1932b) description, on the other hand, is said to represent the speech of the Tumbuka-Kamanga people, which he locates just east of the Luangwa River in modern Zambia, stretching towards, and across, the Malawian border (Young 1932b, 2; 1932a, 21–22).

¹⁸ See Ranger (1928, 60), who explicitly interprets the literal and de facto meaning for Nsenga, e.g., with the verb ‘come’: “I-am-without coming, i.e. I have not come, or I did not come”.

- (34) Tumbuka-Kamanga N21c (Young 1932b, 138, glossing added)

Nilivye kuchikhumba icho wandipa.

ni-li=vye ku-chi-khumba-a icho u-a-ndi-p-a
SP1SG-COP=NEG INF-OP7-want-FV 7.DEM SP2SG-PFV-OP1SG-give-FV

‘I am without desiring the thing which you have given me.’

- (35) Tumbuka-Kamanga N21c (Young 1932b, 167, glossing added)

Chifikiro, ulije kwiza kandiwona.

chi-fikiro u-li=je ku-iz-a ka-ndi-won-a
NCP7-arrival SP2SG-COP=NEG INF-come-FV AM-OP1SG-see-FV

‘Since arrival, you have not come to see me.’

Although we differ from Young in our analysis of the TAM value of the basic form, the fact remains that for other TAM readings in both Nsenga (N41) and Tumbuka-Kamanga (N21c), the negative enclitic =je/=v(y)e occurs with the copulative verbs *w-a* ‘be’ and/or *enze*¹⁹ ‘be.PST’. When the copulative element is not *li*, the TAM semantics frequently expand beyond the domain of the perfective, e.g., the past imperfective in (36), or the ‘continuous future’ in (37).

- (36) Nsenga N41 (Ranger 1928, 84, glossing added)

Tumpwisi twenzeveumwe.

tu-mpwisi tu-enze=ve ku-mw-e
NCP13-child SP13-be.PST=NEG INF-drink-NEG

‘The kids were not drinking.’

- (37) Tumbuka-Kamanga N21c (Young 1932b, 167, glossing added)

Ndiwengevye kuchikhumba.

ndi-w-e-nge=vye ku-chi-khumba-a
SP1SG-be-FUT-IPFV=NEG INF-OP7-want-FV

‘I will not want the thing.’

In terms of geographic distribution, the Type B auxiliary construction is centred around the Zambezi River moving downstream from the confluence area with the Luangwa River. The highest concentration of languages with the *dibe* construction are found in the N40 group, where it is widespread, except in Sena (N44) and Barwe (N45). In the rest of our sample, i.e., languages closer to Lake Malawi, such as Malawian Tonga (N15), most Tumbuka N21 dialects (see Turner 1952; Vail 1972; Kishindo and Lipenga 2005; Kiso 2012), Tanzanian Nyanja (N201) (see Ngonyani 2020), and the whole Chewa-Nyanja N31 cluster, the *dibe* construction typically only exists in negative existential and possessive constructions, not in the extended auxiliary use.²⁰ The negative perfective is thus marked with standard negation, e.g., prefixation

¹⁹This is probably a spirantized form of the auxiliary *-nga* ‘be like’, caused by the perfective suffix.

²⁰We have collected our own field data on the Chewa and Nyanja varieties and we have consulted much of the rich literature that exists (e.g., Rebmann 1877; Riddel 1880; Atkins 1950; Missioários de Companhia de Jesus 1964; Harding 1966; Mchombo 1987, 2004; Peace Corps 1995b; Lehmann 2002; Kishindo and Lipenga 2003; Kiso 2012; Downing and Mtenje 2017). Only in one source (Watkins 1937, 136) have we been able to find the auxiliary construction with *dibe* mentioned. There is no convincing dialectal or chronological explanation for the attestation by Watkins. However, the phonology of a contracted simplex form suggests that it might be influence from

and final vowel *-e* in Chewa (N31), as in (39), whereas *dibe* is restricted to examples like (38). In Tumbuka Kamanga (N21c), from closer to the Luangwa River, as well as Senga (N21d), from a nearby area in Zambia, we do find *lije* as a negative perfective auxiliary (see Nkhata 2019, 105).

(38) Chewa N31, Malawi (Mchombo 1987, 17, glossing and translations added)

Tilibe chakudya.
 ti-li=be cha-kudya
 SP1PL-COP=NEG NCP7-food
 ‘We have no food.’

(39) Chewa N31, Malawi (Mchombo 1987, 22)

Sanadye kanthu dzulo
 si-a-na-dy-e ka-nthu dzulo
 NEG-SP1-PFV-eat-NEG NCP12-thing yesterday
 ‘S/he did not eat anything yesterday.’

Beyond Zone N, we also find the Type B auxiliary in the outliers of other groups such as Soli (M62), Tawara (S11), and Hwesa (S102), which all share borders and have long histories of contact with zone N languages. While considered members of the S10 Shona cluster, Tawara and Hwesa constitute border languages between the S10 and N40 clusters and speakers are thus highly multilingual and communicate with ease with both their N40 and their S10 neighbors. At least in the case of Hwesa, speakers mix freely between N40 and S10-like grammatical constructions, lexical items, and phonology. The negative ‘have’ auxiliaries are no exception, and speakers use either Type A or Type B auxiliaries with no change in meaning (40):

(40) Hwesa S102 (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2025)

- a. *Muká:dzi aríbúúphiká nyamunsi.*
 mu-kadzi a-ri-ḡe ku-phik-a nyamunsi
 NCP1-woman SP1-be-NEG INF-cook-FV today
 ‘The woman did not cook today.’
- b. *Muká:dzi hánúúḡika nási*
 mu-kadzi ha-a-na ku-ḡik-a nasi
 NCP1-woman NEG-SP1-have INF-cook-FV today
 ‘The woman did not cook today.’

For a summary of the distribution of Type B *dibe*, see Table 3.

Nsenga (N41). Watkins (1937, 136) gives *Nilidjǎ tcitá* ‘I have not done’ as a contracted form of *ni-li-djé ku-tcit-á*. The erosion of /k/ and vowel coalescence resulting in a rounded, mid, back vowel is frequent in Nsenga (N41), both with *dibe* (see example (30)) and with other grammaticalized TAM markers, e.g., the present marker *o-* from *-a+ku-* (see Ranger 1928, 48). In Chewa, the same present marker is attested as the full *ku-*. While it is possible that the *dibe* auxiliary construction is used in certain Nyanja-Chewa varieties, other forms seem to be widely and strongly preferred.

Table 3: Distribution of the Enclitic Poss type for main clause negation

Language	Enclitic Poss Type for negative possession?	Type B auxiliary	Other negative auxiliary type(s)?
M62 Soli	✓	✓ (PFV)	✓ (Types A & D)
N15 Malawian Tonga	✓	-	-
N201 Tanzanian Nyanja	✓	-	-
N21c Tumbuka-Kamanga	✓	✓ (PFV/PST; FUT)	-
N21d Senga	✓	✓ (PFV)	-
N31 Chewa-Nyanja	✓	-	-
N401 Nserero	✓	✓ (PFV)	-
N402 Phimbi	✓	✓ (PFV)	-
N403 Dema	✓	✓ (PFV)	-
N404 Guro Tonga	✓	✓ (PFV)	-
N41 Nsenga	✓	✓ (PFV; PST.IPFV; FUT)	-
N42 Chikunda	✓	✓ (PFV)	-
N43 Nyungwe	✓	✓ (PFV)	-
S102 Hwesa	✓	✓ (PFV)	✓ (Type A)
S11 Tawara	✓	✓ (PFV)	✓ (Type A)

3.3 Type C: The Have Poss type for main clause negation

In Type C a Have Poss type predicate is used as an auxiliary followed by the main verb in the infinitive to express main clause negation, either negative past resembling the negative perfectives of Types A and B, or a more deviant negative future. The negative possessive auxiliary in type C is *kwe*, most probably a shortened form of *kwete*, the perfect(ive) stem of *kwata* 'hold, have', i.e., from **kóat* 'seize' (Bastin et al. 2002). It combines with the negative marker *ta-*, which occurs pre-initially in main clauses and post-initially in relative clauses. No other TAM prefixes are included.

Type C is a minor pattern, attested only in two Bantu Botatwe languages, i.e., Lenje (M61) and Tonga (M64). The use of *kwe/kwete* in (negative) possessive constructions is more widely attested in several M40/M50/M60 languages. In Ila (M63), *kwete* seems to be largely restricted to affirmative possessive constructions, as in (41a), while negative possession instead makes use of intrinsically negative verbs like *in-a* 'not have' or *bul-a* 'lack', as in (41b) (see also Section 3.4). In Bemba (M42), Bisa/Wisa (M51), and Lamba (M54), *kwete* may occur in negative possessive constructions, alongside an alternative strategy combining the verb 'to be' with the comitative particle *na*, as seen in (42) for Lamba (Madan 1906, 72; Schoeffler 1907, 60).

Here too, *kwete* is marked with the pre-initial negative prefix *ta-*. However, in none of these languages is *kwete* used as an auxiliary for the expression of main clause negation, at least as far as the available data allow us to conclude.²¹

(41) Ila M63 (Smith 1907, 185)

a. *Ndikwete shidyo.*

ndi-kwete shi-dyo
SP1SG-have NCP7-food
'I have food.'

b. *Ndabula shidyo.*

ndi-a-bul-a shi-dyo
SP1SG-PFV-lack-FV NCP7-food
'I have no food.'

(42) Lamba M54 (Doke 1938, 328)

a. *Tawakwete mano.*

ta-wa-kwete ma-no
NEG-SP2-have NCP6-sense
'They have no sense.'

b. *Nsingawa nembusi.*

nsi-nga-w-a ne-m-busi
NEG.SP1SG-NONDUM-be-FV COM-NCP9-goat
'I have not yet got any goats.'

In Lenje (M61), just as in Lamba, *kwee* is used to express negative possession (43a).²² Unlike in M40/M50 languages, however, *kwee* in Lenje also functions as an auxiliary. When followed by the main verb in the infinitive, it expresses a negative past as in (43d), whose simplex affirmative counterparts may express either remote (43b) or immediate past (43c). The auxiliary *kwee* + infinitive is also used in past relative tenses, as in (43e). In main clause negation, the auxiliary takes the pre-initial negative marker *ta-* as in (43d), whereas it takes the post-initial *ta-* in relative clauses, as in (43e). Erosion and merger of the auxiliary and the infinitival prefix leads to univerbation, yielding a simplex form, as in (43f) (see Section 5.1).

(43) Lenje M61 (Kagaya 1987, 23, 36; Madan 1908, 51, 39–40)

a. *ta-tu-kwe*

NEG-SP1PL-have
'we do not have'

b. *tw-a-ká-bunjik-à*

SP1PL-PST-REM-gather-FV
'we gathered' (remote past)

²¹ It should be noted that handwritten notes in Smith's (1907) Ila grammar give alternatives/corrections for some negative forms which do include *kwe*. The forms with *kwe* express either a negative future or a negative past.

²² This use of *kwe(e)* is only reported by Madan (1908, 51). Kagaya mentions the Type A pattern and a pattern involving the verb *cita* 'do', either on its own or preceded by the copula *li* 'be'.

- c. tw-a-búnjik-à
 SP1PL-PST-gather-FV
 'we gathered' (immediate past)
- d. tá-tú-kwée kú-bunjik-à
 NEG-SP1PL-have INF-gather-FV
 'we did not gather' (remote/immediate past)
- e. ba-sankwa bá-tá-kwée ku-ya ku-Lusaka cíilò
 NCP2-man REL2-NEG-have INF-go NCP17-Lusaka yesterday
 'men who did not go to Lusaka yesterday'
- f. tatukwe kulima / tatukolima
 ta-tu-kwe ku-lim-a / ta-tu-ko-lim-a
 NEG-SP1PL-have INF-cultivate-FV / NEG-SP1PL-PFV.NEG-cultivate-FV
 'we did not cultivate'

Tonga (M64) shows the same usage of *kwe* for both negative possession (44a) and main clause negation. Unlike Lenje (M61), however, the tense specifications are unexpected, both in comparison to Lenje and with the other types more generally. Instead of expressing a negative perfective or past tense, the auxiliary *kwe* in Tonga is used to express negative future. The auxiliary combines with the pre-initial negative marker *ta-* but does not take any additional TAM markers, as seen in (44b).

(44) Tonga M64 (Carter 1974, 9)

- a. Pé, *tatukwé cilyo pé*.
 pé ta-tu-kwé ci-lyo pé
 no NEG-SP1PL-have NCP7-food no
 'No, we do not have any food.'
- b. Pé, *tacikwé kukonzyeka pé*.
 pé ta-ci-kwé ku-konzyek-a pé
 no NEG-SP7-have INF-be.possible-FV no
 'No, it will not be possible.'

The future reading in the absence of any additional TAM marking is surprising. Maybe the persistence of the lexical semantics of *kwata* 'hold' plays a role here. Ila (M63), where the use of *kwete* in predicative possession is restricted to affirmative possessive constructions and either *bula* or *ina* is used in the negative counterparts, has a homophonous auxiliary *kwe*, which combines with standard negation to express non-volition, as in (45). Volition is a common source meaning for future auxiliaries, but further research is needed to ascertain whether an intermediate volitive meaning triggered the use of *kwe* as a future auxiliary in Tonga (M64).

(45) Ila M63 (Fowler 2000, 325)

- Tatukwe kusinka maanda*.
 ta-tu-kwe ku-sink-a ma-anda
 NEG-SP1PL-want INF-caulk-FV NCP6-wall
 'We do not want to caulk the walls.'

Table 4 lists the languages with predicative possession of the Have Poss type and indicates whether or not they have extended uses as negative auxiliaries in main clauses.

Table 4: Distribution of the Have Poss type for main clause negation

Language	Have Poss type for negative possession?	Type C auxiliary	Other negative auxiliary type(s)?
Bemba M42	<i>kwete</i>	-	-
Bisa/Wisa M51	<i>kwete</i>	-	✓
Lamba M54	<i>kwete</i>	-	-
Lenje M61	<i>kwee</i>	✓ (PST)	✓ (Type A)
Ila M63	<i>kwete</i>	-	✓ (Type A, Type D)
Tonga M64	<i>kwe</i>	✓ (FUT)	-

3.4 Type D: The HAVE_{NEG} Poss type for main clause negation

In Type D the predicator attested in predicative possession of the Have_{NEG} Poss type is used as an auxiliary followed by the main verb in the infinitive to express main clause negation. Intrinsically negative verbs are known to be used for the expression of negation in Bantu languages. However, according to Bernander et al. (2023), which is a cross-linguistic study of Bantu negative verbs, they only rarely develop into standard main clause negators but are devoted rather to expressing specific functions either as an alternative to or in complementary distribution with standard negation. This is certainly the case in Soli (M62), where the auxiliary *vul-a* 'lack' may be used as an alternative to standard negation with pre-initial *ka-* to express a negative past. This is illustrated in (46). The past tense reading is not solely an effect of the auxiliary construction but is co-expressed by the TAM prefix *a-*.

(46) Soli M62 (van Eeden 1936, 37, 23)

- a. u-vul-a ma-no
 SP2SG-lack-FV NCP6-cleverness
 'You are not clever.'
- b. nda-vul-a ku-y-a=ko
 SP1SG.PST-lack-FV INF-go-FV=LOC17
 'I did not go there.'
- c. ka-nda-von-a
 NEG-SP1PL.PST-see-FV
 'I did not see.'

In Ila (M63) the intrinsic negative auxiliary *ina* is more widely distributed in main clause negation. The auxiliary, which is marked solely for subject, expresses a negative perfect(ive) meaning (47b) as an alternative to a simplex form with the standard negative pre-initial marker *ta-* in combination with the perfect(ive) final (47c).

(47) Ila M63 (Fowler 2000, 207, 167)

- a. n-ina tu-lyo
 SP1SG-not.have NCP13-food
 'I do not have food.'
- b. mu-ntu u-ina ku-bon-a
 NCP1-person SP1-not.have INF-see-FV
 'The person has not seen.'
- c. ta-tu-bwene
 NEG-SP1PL-see.PFV
 'We have not seen.'

However, the role of *ina* in standard negation does not stop here, as it is also used to express negative past tenses, a negative past imperfective, and also a future tense. In contrast to the negative perfect(ive), these complex tenses do not have an alternative simplex form. The TAM markers that distinguish these complex tenses from the perfect(ive) one are attached to the main verb rather than to the auxiliary. In one past tense, as well as in the future tense, the auxiliary is followed by a finite verb form rather than by the infinitive.²³

(48) Ila M63, Zambia (Smith 1907, 167, 168, 172)

- a. tw-ina u-ku-bon-a
 SP1SG-not.have NCP17-INF-see-FV
 'We were not seeing.'
- b. tw-ina u-ka-bon-a
 SP1SG-not.have INF-PST-see-FV
 'We did not see.'
- c. tw-ina ni tw-aka-bon-a
 SP1SG-not.have WHEN SP1PL-REM.PST-see-FV
 'We did not see.'
- d. tw-ina ni tu-ka-bon-a
 SP1SG-not.have WHEN SP1PL-FUT-see-FV
 'We shall not see.'

Table 5 lists the languages with predicative possession of the Have_{NEG} Poss type and indicates whether or not they have extended uses as negative auxiliaries in main clauses.

²³ The main verb is introduced by what seems to be the subjunction *ni* (Smith 1907, 447; see also Nurse (2008a), who lists it as one of the pre-initial formatives in Ila). We are not sure what its function is in this particular construction.

Table 5: Distribution of the Have_{NEG} Poss for main clause negation

Language	Have _{NEG} Poss type for negative possession?	Type D	Other negative auxiliary type(s)?
Soli M62	<i>vula</i>	✓ (PST)	Type A
Ila M63	<i>ina</i>	✓ (PRS/PERF, PST IPFV, PST, FUT)	Type A
	<i>bula</i>	-	
Tonga M64	<i>nyina</i>	-	Type C
Sena N44	<i>soa</i>	-	-

4 Typological considerations

Predicates used in predicative possession are not common sources of dedicated negative auxiliaries in Bantu main clause negation. Comitative *na* is rather known to be a source item for narrative, progressive/imperfective, future, past, and ‘not yet’ TA prefixes (Nurse 2008b, 240). Only the ‘not yet’ or nondum prefix is dedicated to negation. Veselinova and Devos (2021), in their study of nondum expressions in the Bantu domain, assume that *na-*, attested in 13 Eastern Bantu languages in their sample, was initially used in combination with standard negation to express a negative perfect/recent past meaning in more or less symmetric negation. The ‘not yet’ reading was then the result of the conventionalization of a negative inference. The authors furthermore suggest that subsequent changes in the TAMP system and the replacement of affirmative *na-* with other morphemes might have given rise to dedicated ‘not yet’ markers without a correlative in the affirmative domain, as seen in, for example, Zaramo (G33) and Shangaji (P312), where *na-* expressing negative perfect/‘not yet’ does not correlate with an affirmative perfect.

(49) Zaramo G33 (Nurse 2008a)

a. tu-gul-ile

SP1SG-buy-PFV

‘We have bought.’

b. ha-tu-na-gul-a

NEG-SP1PL-PFV-buy-FV

‘We have not bought (yet).’

(50) Shangaji P312 (Veselinova and Devos 2021, 478)

Si-náá-c-e nkaása ki-c-i ńgiisi

NEG.SP1SG-NONDUM-eat-FV NCP9.tortoise SP1SG-eat-PFV NCP9.squid

‘I have not eaten tortoise yet. I have eaten squid.’

The resulting asymmetry had already been noted by Nurse and Hinnebusch (1993) and also by Wald (1981), who confirms that in many of these Eastern Bantu languages the use of *na-* has “further deteriorated (through replacement by other markers) so that it is restricted to the negative perfect”, a label he uses to refer to ‘not yet/before’ (Wald 1981, 143). The ‘have’ predicates involved in asymmetric negation patterns in the Zambezi Bantu languages could shed further

light on these asymmetric nondums. Maybe, rather than evolving into asymmetric negative markers, they may have been asymmetric from the outset. Cross-linguistically, asymmetric negation, where the main verb is less finite in the negative than in the affirmative construction, is not unexpected. Miestamo (2005, 73–96) pays ample attention to asymmetries pertaining to finiteness distinguishing several subtypes. His A(symmetry)/Fin(ite)/Neg(ative)-F(inite) E(lement) subtype, where the negative marker attaches to the finite element (i.e., the auxiliary) of the construction, is reminiscent of our A, B, and C types. Our Type D can be subsumed under his A(symmetry)/Fin(ite)/Neg(ative)Verb subtype, where the finite element of the construction is a negative verb and the main or lexical verb loses its finiteness. Our data also show shifts between the two types. In Nserero (N401) the loss of the 'be' copula turns the negative enclitic into an inherently negative predicative element. Although the negative construction in (31) (Section 3.2) clearly derives from a Type B construction, it is synchronically a Type D one. Similarly, the Type D negative 'have' verb *ina* in Ila (M63) seems to have derived from a Type A construction through reanalysis as an inherently negative verb and loss of negative morphology.

Miestamo (2005) evokes stativity of negation as a general functional motivation for asymmetric negation pertaining to finiteness. Both the loss of finiteness of the main verb and the stativity of the auxiliary (the 'have' predicates in our sample) iconically reflect the stativity of negation. The use of 'have' predicates as auxiliaries for the expression of main clause negation is thus not unexpected from a typological perspective. However, the question remains as to why they are, at least initially, restricted to the expression of negative perfectives. In Section 5, we address this question and suggest a grammaticalization pathway from predicative possession to the negative auxiliary being involved in the expression of main clause perfectives.

5 Historical-comparative analysis

5.1 Functional expansion and grammaticalization

As already implied in Sections 3 and 4, the use of negative possessive predicates for main clause negation can be understood as the result of a grammaticalization pathway from negative possession to main clause negative perfectives, possibly reminiscent of at least some stages of what, in the literature, is known as a 'negative existential cycle' (NEC).

A 'bridging context' is considered the key step of semantic change in a grammaticalization pathway (see Heine 2002). It arises when a new inferred meaning becomes available in addition to the original meaning. In the grammaticalization of negative 'have' auxiliaries, the bridging context arises when the negative possessive predicate, which in its source construction takes nominal complements (51), starts to take nominalized verbs as its complements (52). This context is ambiguous: while (52) literally expresses a present 'lack of falling', it naturally implies a prior 'non-occurrence of fall(ing)'. In other words, event negation is inferred from the current lack of its supposed result. Although the possessive interpretation is pragmatically more strained, perhaps especially with inanimate subjects such as 'the tree' in (52), it is still compositionally available as a literal interpretation. Nonetheless, the pragmatically more plausible inference becomes conventionalized as the default interpretation.

(51) Guro Tonga N404, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2025)

Múti uríbé masámba.

mu-ti u-ri=be ma-samba

NCP3-tree SP3-COP=NEG NCP6-leaf

'The tree is without leaves.' (i.e., 'The tree does not have any leaves')

(52) Guro Tonga N404, Mozambique (Elicitation, Fieldnotes 2025)

Múti uríbé kú:g̃ba.

mu-ti u-ri=be ku-gw-a
NCP3-tree SP3-COP=NEG NCP15-fall-FV

'The tree is without falling.' (i.e., 'The tree has not fallen')

Following Heine (2002), the subsequent 'switching context' occurs when the original interpretation is not just dispreferred but becomes entirely unavailable. In the case of the negative 'have' auxiliaries, the switching context can be identified as the stage when formal grammaticalization processes start to operate. As illustrated in Section 3, different types of complex negative 'have' constructions display morpho-phonological reduction and phrasal univerbation in Lehmann's (2020) sense, i.e., the coalescence of a formerly syntagmatic string into a single grammatical word. This is attested for types A, B, and C, which may all surface as simplex forms such as *hánupezesa* < *hánakupезesa* (53); *tíbegure* < *tiríbe kugure* (31); and *tatukolima* < *tatukwe kulima* (43f). The erosion of the infinitival marker is not a regular connected speech effect but reflects a reduction process specifically associated with the grammaticalization of these auxiliaries. The contracted outcomes are best analysed as simplex verb forms with grammaticalized TAMP prefixes rather than as auxiliary constructions, as reflected in the glossing in (31), (43f), and (53) (even though the full complex auxiliary forms are synchronically available). Consequently, the univerbation marks the point where the possessive semantics are no longer compositionally recoverable and the TAMP interpretation has been fully grammaticalized along the V > AUX > TAMP path.

(53) Barwe N45, Mozambique (Natural speech, Fieldnotes 2024)

Máe hánupezesa shkó:la.

Ø-mae ha-a-nu-pezes-a Ø-shkola
NCP1a-mother NEG-SP1-NEG.PFV-finish-FV NCP9-school

'(His/her) mother did not finish school.'

When negative possessive predicates grammaticalize into negative auxiliaries for the expression of main clause negation, they typically start out by expressing negative perfectives. This can be deduced from the fact that the majority of these negative auxiliaries express negative perfectives when occurring without additional TAM morphology and it is in line with the semantic inference discussed in relation to example (52), which can be assumed to be strongly available especially in the initial stages of the grammaticalization process. The nondum or 'not yet' sense attested in some languages can be interpreted as a side effect of the grammaticalization process. Newly grammaticalized verb constructions tend to be pragmatically stronger than equivalent older expressions (Bybee et al. 1994). They are thus well fitted to carry the 'not yet' meaning, which Hyman and Watters (1984) refer to as inherently focused. In most languages the usage range of the negative auxiliaries derived from possessive predicates seems to remain restricted to the expression of negative perfectives. This could suggest that grammaticalization has happened relatively recently. It might also be an effect of the defective nature of the (shortened) Comit Poss and the Enclitic Poss type predicates, especially. In Nyanja (N31d), a language which has not developed the negative auxiliary use, the Enclitic Poss type predicate can only occur in present and perfect(ive) (54) TAM contexts, whereas other TAM categories like the future (55) must be expressed through a periphrastic Comit Poss construction. The Have_{NEG}

Poss predicate *ina* in Ila (M63), plausibly derived from a Comit Poss type predicate, retained its defective nature as a negative auxiliary. Additional TAM marking occurs on the main verb rather than on the auxiliary, as seen in (48) in Section 3.4.

(54) Nyanja N31d, Mozambique (Missioários de Companhia de Jesus 1964, 99)

Analibe nyumba.

a-na-li=be n-yumba

SP1-PFV-COP=NEG NCP9/10-house

‘S/he did not have a house.’

(55) Nyanja N31d, Mozambique (Missioários de Companhia de Jesus 1964, 99)

Sindidzakhala ndi

si-ndi-dza-khal-a ndi

NEG-SP1SG-FUT-be-FV COM

‘I will not have.’

Last but not least, the grammaticalization of negative possessive predicates into negative auxiliaries shows signs of cyclical change reminiscent of a NEC. In Section 3, we have shown that the Bantu languages of the Middle and Lower Zambezi River have non-dedicated negative possessive predicates (Comit Poss and Have Poss types) as well as dedicated ones (Enclitic Poss and Have_{NEG} Poss types), and their distribution is comparable with Stages A, A~B, and B of a NEC. Moreover, in Section 4 we have shown that all negative possessive predicate types, whether dedicated or not, have extended uses as negative auxiliaries in main clause negation, Stage C in a NEC. The data from Ila (M63) are even suggestive of a full cycle. Ila has a negative auxiliary of the Comit Poss type (TypeA). However, it does not use Comit Poss type predicates in predicative possession but rather Have Poss and Have_{NEG} Poss types. This suggests true cyclical change, whereby the usage range of an erstwhile negative possessive predicate of the Comit Poss type is expanded into main clause negation, after which the original negative possessive use becomes obsolete and is replaced by new strategies. The fact that negative possessive constructions show evidence of cyclical change typically associated with negative existential constructions should not come as a surprise, given the strong conceptual and formal connection between the two construction types. Bernander et al. (2022) suggest that further stages of the NEC in Bantu languages seem to occur only when intense language contact is involved. In the following sections we discuss this Zambezi ‘negative possessive cycle’ in the light of contact.

5.2 Spread of negative auxiliaries in different Eastern Bantu subgroups

The innovation of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries is attested in at least four different subgroups within Eastern Bantu: Bantu Botatwe, Sabi²⁴, the Sena-Nyanja cluster, and Southern Bantu. More detailed information on each language is available in the Appendix, but an overview of the relevant subgroups is shown in the tree diagram in Figure 1. The tree is generated using previous basic vocabulary-based phylogenetic studies (Bastin et al. 1999; Grollemund et al. 2015; Koile et al. 2022) with the addition of names of subgroups and additional languages from Hammarström et al. (2025) and recent fieldwork by the authors of this paper. At the highest

²⁴The Sabi languages are a group of Bantu languages classified within Guthrie’s zones M40 (Bemba group), M50 (Lala-Bisa-Lamba group), and Nsenga N41. The Sabi languages are spoken in Zambia, with its easternmost member, Nsenga, stretching into Mozambique.

level (below “Eastern Bantu”), our tree only shows the relevant four subgroups where the innovation has been attested; for a fuller picture of other Eastern Bantu subgroups, the reader is referred to the full phylogenetic studies. At the lower levels, only the relevant subgroups are fully expanded with individual languages. The languages with attested negative ‘have’ auxiliaries are marked in blue.

The partial spread of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries into relatively distant genealogical subgroups, in geographically adjacent areas, together with the typological and cross-Bantu unusualness of this innovation, strongly suggest that these auxiliary constructions have spread through language contact. Secondly, occasionally occurring archaic negative prefixal forms, e.g., *ha-* in Guro Tonga (N404), fully preserved in sister languages such as Barwe (N45) and some Sena (N44) varieties (*nkha-*), suggests that the innovation is rather recent in terms of relative chronology (i.e., in the case of N40, it must have happened after the divergence of modern languages such as Barwe, Sena, and Tonga).

In the following section, we present some historical-linguistic contact dynamics of the Middle and Lower Zambezi which we believe are responsible for the spread of negative auxiliaries.

5.3 Migration, trade, and soldiers: Historical contact dynamics and directionality of the spread

The spread of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries as an areal feature in the Zambezi must be understood in the context of centuries of intense contact where social and linguistic identities have often been flexible and subject to change (see, e.g., Lancaster 1974; Newitt 2022). In this section we draw on historical and ethnographic literature to identify the social dynamics most likely to be responsible for this areal diffusion.

While there is little doubt that these auxiliary constructions have spread through contact, the directionality of the spread remains somewhat speculative. However, the combination of historical accounts and linguistic data suggests that the innovation originated with the Shona-speaking peoples on the Zimbabwean plateau, and spread down into the Middle and Lower Zambezi valleys. Ethnically diverse migratory groups of soldiers, mercenaries, elephant hunters, and traders such as the Chikunda and the Ngoni may then have played an important part in disbursing these linguistic innovations into more distant areas.

As noted in Section 3.2, the Type B construction *dibe* is particularly widespread in the N40 group of languages, spoken in the Lower Zambezi valley. North of the river valley in this area, we find Chewa-Nyanja speaking communities, whereas the Zimbabwean Plateau south of the valley is inhabited by Shona peoples. In the ethnographic literature, the peoples of the valley, e.g., Chikunda, Nyungwe, Guro Tonga, Dema, and Barwe, are believed to have originated as a mixture of primarily Chewa-Nyanja related groups, coming from the north, and Shona groups, coming from the south (see Tew 1950, 31; Dias 1965, 15; Rosário 1989, 25; Isaacman and Peterson 2003; Isaacman and Isaacman 2004, 331; Maia 2015, 147, among others). Linguistically, these communities, together with Sena, form the rather coherent group of N40 languages, which is close in both lexicon and grammar to N30. Typically, more Shona-like linguistic features are prevalent as we move closer to the Zimbabwean Plateau. As described by Beach (1980, 155), linguistic frontiers have fluctuated in this area as Shona-speaking peoples from the plateau moved into non-Shona-speaking areas, where they were often gradually absorbed into these valley communities. This back and forth of Shona and non-Shona peoples between the plateau and the valley has been going on for the better part of the last millennium. Recalling that *dibe* as a negative possessive construction is widespread in the Chewa-Nyanja group but its extension to a TAM auxiliary is not, we are led to believe that the auxiliary

Figure 1: Genealogical tree of sampled languages (based on Bastin et al. 1999; Grollemund et al. 2015; Koile et al. 2022)

influence in the N40 group appears to have driven a Shona-like functional expansion from negative possessive to negative perfective auxiliary, using local N40 Sena-Nyanja morphological material.

The occurrence of *dibe* in the Sabi outlier Nsenga (N41) and the Botatwe outlier Soli (M62), but not in the remainder of these groups, points towards Chikunda (N42) influence. When bands of Chikunda²⁵ soldiers, hunters, and traders moved from Tete in Mozambique up to the Zambezi-Luangwa confluence area, they had long and intense contacts with the Soli and the Nsenga (see Isaacman and Isaacman 2004; Alikuleti 2021). Beyond trade, Isaacman and Isaacman (2004) describe, on the one hand, how Nsenga and Soli speakers were integrated into Chikunda groups through slave raids, exogamous marriages between Chikunda men and Nsenga women,²⁶ and also through the recruitment of Nsenga and Soli men as carriers of ivory and gold on the caravans going back to Tete (Isaacman and Isaacman 2004, 205; Langworthy 1972, 98). On the other hand, integration often happened in the opposite direction, as many Chikunda settled

²⁵ The Chikunda identity is believed to have originated as an ethnically mixed group of slave-soldiers of the Portuguese *prazo* owners in central Mozambique. The Chikunda also operated as hunters, porters, mercenaries, and tax collectors. The majority of these people are said to have originated from the Chewa-Nyanja-related peoples north of the Zambezi, mixed with Shona groups from the south and valley populations such as the Tonga, along with other enslaved peoples from more removed areas (see mainly Isaacman and Isaacman 2004).

²⁶ The role of Nsenga-Chikunda women is particularly interesting here; Alikuleti (2021, 24), writes that there was a lot of back and forth between the ethnic identities and affiliations of these women since the Chikunda identity was initially so male-dominated. The ‘women of Chikunda’ often partially or temporarily integrated into their new communities but maintained strong affiliations to their original ethno-linguistic communities.

among local communities by forging marriage alliances and acquiring land rights in exchange for military protection and/or tributary payments (see Isaacman 2000; Alikuleti 2021, 132).

In the case of Tumbuka-Kamanga (N21c) and Senga (N21d), further north, the occurrence of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries is most likely due to contact with Nsenga (N41). We have previously noted that negative ‘have’ auxiliaries have not been attested in most Tumbuka varieties, only in the Tumbuka-Kamanga (N21c) variety described by Young (1932c), spoken around the Upper Luangwa Valley, where the same construction is also used by the neighbouring and closely related Senga.²⁷ The Senga (N21d) data is unfortunately too scarce, but in Nsenga (N41) and Tumbuka-Kamanga (N21c), the form and function of the *dibe* constructions are very similar in ways that are not shared with other languages in our sample.²⁸ This suggests that this particular Tumbuka variety has been directly influenced by Nsenga. Contact between Senga and Tumbuka-Kamanga communities is known, but the extension of the contact between these communities and Nsenga is not as well documented, although see Miracle (1962) for an account of some trade relations.

One historical factor that seems to have contributed extensively to the influx of Nsenga speakers into the Upper Luangwa Valley is the famous Ngoni migrations. When Zwangendaba’s Ngoni army moved north from modern-day South Africa, they efficiently swelled their ranks with the integration of conquered peoples along the way. When crossing the Zambezi in 1835, recruits and captives from Shona populations had, according to Omer-Cooper (1978, 65), already become a “significant element” in the Ngoni composite group. The incorporated peoples referred to as ‘Shona’ here included both Kalanga and various groups from the Mutapa State in the Zambezi valley (see Young 1933, 11–12; Omer-Cooper 1978, 65–68). These valley people can only be assumed to have included groups from the linguistic border areas of S11 and N40, such as Tawara, Korekore, and Tonga clans (see Beach 1980, 114–15; Bourdillon 1987, 10; Lancaster 1977 for more details on the population of the Mutapa State). After crossing the Zambezi, the Ngoni subdued the Nsenga and settled in their territory for as long as six years before they continued marching north (Fraser 1914, 28). At this point they had, by all accounts, considerably increased their numbers through the integration of a large number of Nsenga (Elmslie 1899, 22; Omer-Cooper 1978, 67; Langworthy 1972, 85–86; Fraser 1914, 28). After another decade of migrations and conquests, the now ethnically diverse and multilingual group of Ngoni defeated the Kamanga, settled on the Nkamanga Plateau, and subjugated many Tumbuka, Kamanga, and Senga people in the area (Omer-Cooper 1978, 80; Lane-Poole 1949, 25–26, 31; Young 1933, 11). When conquering Kamanga, the original Ngoni nucleus, that had started out as around 2000 people in Natal, had, according to Langworthy (1972, 90) long become vastly outnumbered by the thousands of people from different cultures and languages who had been integrated along the way. When the Ngoni composite group in Kamanga eventually shifted to the Tumbuka-Kamanga (N21c) tongue, it seems reasonable to assume substrate influence from Nsenga and other groups that constituted a significant portion of the group.

Beyond the Zambezi-Luangwa confluence area, the impact of the Chikunda was felt further into the Middle Zambezi, reaching as far west as Kafue and Kariba in Bantu Botatwe land. Initial trading, hunting, and raiding activities of the Chikunda were followed by the establishment of

²⁷ Aspects of Senga history and their relationship to Nsenga is debated. The Senga are often treated as unrelated to Nsenga and rather as a Bisa offshoot that settled among, subdued, and linguistically assimilated to the Tumbuka through intermarriage between the male-dominated Senga, who arrived through migration, and women from the local Tumbuka population (see Lane-Poole 1949; Chondoka 2007; Chondoka and Bota 2015; Ohannessian and Kashoki 1978, 13), although see Miracle (1962, 1963) for a contrastive view.

²⁸ E.g., various forms of the negator *vye*, *ve*, *je* occurring on various copulative elements; see Section 3.2 for details.

prazos and more permanent settlements, eventually leading to the integration of Chikunda into Botatwe populations (and vice versa²⁹) such as the Soli, the Lenje, and the Gwembe Tonga during the 18th and 19th centuries (Alikuleti 2021, 102–104; de Luna 2008, 288, 309–310; Isaacman and Isaacman 2004, 180, 211; Matthews 1981; Lancaster 1974). While the influx of Chikunda might have contributed to the presence of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries in the Botatwe languages, the deep, long-lasting direct contact with the speakers of Shona languages coming from the Zimbabwean Plateau is likely to have been the strongest influence. The Type B construction *dibe*, used in Chikunda (N42),³⁰ has only been attested in Soli (M62) from the Botatwe group. The Type A construction, on the other hand, found in all the Shona varieties examined, has been attested in most members of the Botatwe group that make use of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries, i.e., Lenje (M61), Soli (M62), and Ila (M63). The Shona contact with the Botatwe groups in the Middle Zambezi dates back several centuries, e.g., through the Ingombe Ilede trading centre that arose on the Urungwe Plateau in the Middle Zambezi sometime around the 14th or 15th century (Lancaster and Pohorilenko 1977; Beach 1980, 48; de Luna 2008, 142–143), and through territorial gains made by the Shona people on the south banks of the Middle Zambezi into the land of Botatwe groups (Beach 1980, 22). With pressure coming from both the south, e.g., via Rozvi (c. 1660–1866) and Ndebele (c. 1840–1893) conquests, and from the east through Portuguese expansions led by Chikunda armies, marginalized Shona-speaking peoples continued to be pushed into the Middle Zambezi Valley and onto the Zambian highlands north of the river. The Shona people in the valley, variously referred to as Goba or lowland Korekore, often sought to improve their social status and opportunities by socially and linguistically integrating into the local Botatwe communities, especially Tonga (Lancaster 1974; Ohannessian and Kashoki 1978, 14–15; Roberts 1979, 92).

In sum, the spread of negative ‘have’ auxiliaries in the Lower and Middle Zambezi must be understood against the backdrop of centuries of mobility, intermarriage, trade, warfare, and shifting sociopolitical alliances and identities. The linguistic data, combined with the sociolinguistic landscape, suggest a south-to-north trajectory of diffusion, beginning with Shona-speaking populations on the Zimbabwean Plateau and extending into the N40 languages of the Lower Zambezi Valley through language shift and substrate influence. The spread into Botatwe and Sabi outliers may have occurred in parallel or in multiple waves, reflecting the complex and overlapping contact histories in the region. The diffusion into varieties along the Luangwa River, especially Tumbuka-Kamanga (N21c) and Senga (N21d), appears to have been a subsequent development, mediated by Nsenga and peoples from the Lower Zambezi Valley who were incorporated into the Ngoni ranks as they moved northwards. Viewed as a whole, these

²⁹ Vice versa refers to periods in which the Botatwe and Shona populations in the Middle Zambezi, opportunistically and temporarily manipulated their ethnic identities to become Chikunda in order to enjoy certain social advantages, as described by Matthews (1981, 36).

³⁰ It is important to note that the Chikunda who were active in the Kafue and Kariba areas might not have spoken exactly the same language as the modern day Chikunda (N42); their variety might have been closer to the northern Shona varieties. Besides the general presence of Shona ranks in the Chikunda groups, Lancaster (1974) writes that certain loosely affiliated Shona peoples in the Middle Zambezi, such as the Nyai and Goba, were sometimes referred to interchangeably with the Chikunda label. In his view, “all the alleged Tonga, Chikunda, and Goba of the confluence zone [Kafue and Zambezi] have in fact long comprised a single social and cultural field, intermarrying, living together, crossing the rivers, and moving freely throughout the area. They have shared much the same history, *speak the same Shona dialect in their villages*, and share the same social structure” (Lancaster 1974, 711, emphasis added).

historical dynamics and linguistic patterns point to an areal spread triggered by contact, multilingualism, and language shift rather than inheritance or multiple independent innovations.

6 Conclusions

In this study, we have examined the emergence and distribution of negative 'have' auxiliaries in the Bantu languages of the Middle and Lower Zambezi River. We have identified four structural types (A–D) (described in Sections 2 and 3) that all originate in predicative possession but extend into auxiliary use. There is a great diversity in the morphological make-up of the types, with two of them being dedicated negative types whereas the other types are formed by applying negative marking to affirmative possessive constructions. Despite the variety in form, the four types are functionally identical in their semantic expansion from possessive (stative) negation to event negation; as discussed from a grammaticalization perspective in Section 5.1, the majority of the negative 'have' auxiliaries render negative perfective readings in their unmarked base form, which has given rise to two interesting types of formal asymmetry: i) there is a perfective-imperfective split in which standard negation in the perfective domain is marked through auxiliaries, whereas imperfective TAM categories are marked through other formal means (e.g., prefixation or particles); and ii) perfective TAM categories are marked through dedicated TAM prefixes in the affirmative, but through auxiliaries in the negative.

As event negation becomes further grammaticalized, the 'have' auxiliaries may, through analogy, acquire an increased functional range through additional TAM marking. In doing so, they are no longer dedicated to the perfective domain. We have further shown that these developments are not isolated, but form part of a broader pattern of cyclical renewal reminiscent of a negative existential cycle (NEC). Several languages of the region display both non-dedicated and dedicated negative possessive predicates, corresponding to transitional NEC stages, and the extension of these predicates into main clause negation reflects further developments along the cycle.

While we have shown that these construction types are widespread around the Middle and Lower Zambezi, we note in Section 4 that the development of possessive predicates into dedicated negative auxiliaries for main clause negation is rare across Bantu and from a wider typological perspective, where there is a preference for 'do' and 'be' verbs in this role. The rarity of 'have' predicates as TAM auxiliaries highlights the Zambezian pattern as a regional exception. Given that the languages in our sample belong to different genealogical Bantu subgroups, we take these facts together as evidence for a contact-induced spread, involving calquing and structural borrowing across the region. The study then contributes to areal linguistics by exploring how contact-induced changes have influenced the spread and diversification of these auxiliaries. In Section 5.3, we discuss some of the deeply interconnected contact histories and transformative social dynamics that have characterized the region for the latter half of the last millennium.

More broadly, the negative 'have' auxiliaries and the parallels drawn to the NEC contribute to our understanding of the cyclical change and renewal of negative possessive constructions and their grammaticalization into main clause negators. The distribution of negative 'have' auxiliaries in the Zambezi area exemplifies how morphosyntactic innovation emerges not only through internal pathways of change, but also through multilingualism and language shift resulting from social processes of mobility, trade, and warfare.

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Abbreviations

1, 2, 3...etc.	Noun class 1, 2, 3... etc.
1a	Noun class 1a
1, 2, 3PL	1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd person plural
1, 2, 3SG	1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd person singular
AUG	Augment
AM	Associated motion
APPL	Applicative
CAUS	Causative
COM	Comitative
COP	Copula
CTFL	Counterfactual marker
DEM	Demonstrative
EMPH	Emphatic
EX	Existential
FUT	Future
FV	Final vowel
INF	Infinitive
IPFV	Imperfective
LOC	Locative
NAP	Nominal agreement prefix
NEG	Negation
NONDUM	Nondum
NCP	Noun class prefix
OP	Object prefix
PASS	Passive
PERS	Persistentive
PFV	Perfect(ive)
POSS	Possessive
PP	Pronominal prefix
PRO	Pronoun
REL	Relative
REM	Remote
SP	Subject prefix

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Appendix: Language sample

The Middle and Lower Zambezi region hosts an intricate cluster of Bantu languages, and the valley itself constitutes a transition zone between different Eastern and Southern Bantu sub-groups. For the study of negative auxiliaries we have considered a main sample that encompasses representatives of several different genealogical groupings, here referred to as Botatwe, Sabi, Nyasa, and Shona (see Section 5.2 in the main text for the genealogical relations represented as a tree diagram).

In this Appendix, we provide the sources consulted for each language, and we situate the languages geographically and genealogically. Among them, Dema, Doma, Guro Tonga, Hwesa, Kunda, Nserero, and Phimbi¹ are not part of the Maho’s (2009) updated version of Guthrie’s (1967) classification system. Based on existing principles on new code assignments stipulated in Maho (2001, 46), we suggest new Guthrie codes for each of these lects respecting the following two principles:

1. “If the addition is a language close to an already-classified language, then add a third digit to the language code of that latter language.”

e.g., the code N411 for Kunda means that it is a language which is close to the already-classified language Nsenga (N41)

2. “If the addition is a language with uncertain affiliation or lies close to several languages, then add a third digit to the group code.”

e.g., the code N404 for Guro Tonga means that it is a language which lies close to several languages of the N40 group (e.g., N43, N44, and N45).

Botatwe group (M60)

‘Botatwe’ is the label often given to Guthrie’s zone M60 (the Lenje-Tonga group), together with some closely related K40 (Subia, Totela) varieties. The genealogical coherence of this group has been established by authors such as Ahmed (1996), Bostoen (2007, 2009) and de Luna (2008, 2010). Geographically, the Botatwe languages are spoken primarily in south-central Africa, with a concentration in Zambia (especially the Copperbelt, Luapula, and Southern Provinces), northern Zimbabwe and Botswana, and the Caprivi in Namibia.

In this study, we focus on four languages of the Greater Eastern Botatwe subgroup, namely Lenje (M61), Ila (M62), Soli (M63), and Tonga (M64). Each of them is briefly introduced below.

M61 Lenje

Lenje is spoken to the north of Lusaka, especially in the Chibombo District of Zambia’s Central Province, with pockets in the surrounding Lukanga Swamps. It is smaller in speaker numbers than its Botatwe relatives Tonga and Ila but has been studied since the early 20th century (see

¹ Phimbi is assumed to be under Nsenga (N41) by Maho (2009) and under Nyungwe (N43) by Hammarström (2019). Based on preliminary analysis of our field data, Phimbi shows stronger affinities to Nyungwe and the rest of the Senaic group (N42-N45), rather than to Nsenga. Nevertheless, certain features in Phimbi are attested in Nsenga and/or Chewa-Nyanja (N31), but not in Nyungwe. Since Phimbi shows closest affinities to several languages in the N40 group, we have added a third digit to the group code, i.e., N402.

Madan 1908). Besides Madan (1908), we have also consulted the works of Kagaya (1987) and Chitebeta (2007).

M62 Soli

Soli is spoken mainly in the Lusaka area and adjacent parts of Central Province. It is closely related to Lenje (Chitebeta 2019). Historically, the Soli were among the earliest inhabitants of the Lusaka Plateau. As the easternmost language of the Botatwe group, Soli has been heavily influenced by contact with neighbouring groups to the east and by urban multilingualism (de Luna 2010). The main reference work for our paper is van Eeden (1936).

M63 Ila

Ila is closely related to Tonga but distinct in its own right (see, e.g., Hambizi’s (2023) comparative study of Tonga and Ila). It is spoken mainly in Zambia’s Central Province, especially in Namwala District and surrounding areas along the Kafue River. It shares significant grammatical and lexical similarities with Tonga but retains its own identity and dialects, which include Sala and Lundwe. We have consulted the works of Smith (1907), Fowler (2000), and Nurse (2019).

M64 Tonga

Tonga is the largest and most widely spoken Botatwe language, with several million speakers concentrated in Zambia’s Southern Province and extending into parts of Central and Lusaka Provinces. Tonga has a strong sociolinguistic presence in Zambia: it is used in education, media, and literature, making it one of the country’s important regional languages. The analysis in this paper is based on the works of Collins (1962) and Carter (1974, 2002).

Sabi group (M40-50 + N41)

The Sabi group of languages is a well attested genealogical subgroup within Eastern Bantu (see Ahmed 1996; Bastin et al. 1999; Grollemund et al. 2015; Koile et al. 2022; Hammarström et al. 2025). The Sabi languages are mainly spoken in Zambia, with the outlier Nsenga (N41) stretching into neighbouring Mozambique. Historically, the Sabi peoples originate from the Luba-Lunda Empires of the Upper Congo basin (see Ahmed 1996). Details about the Sabi languages included in our sample are given below.

M42 Bemba

Bemba (M42) is one of Zambia’s official languages, with many L1 and L2 speakers in the country. The highest concentrations of speakers are found in the Northern, Luapula, and Copperbelt Provinces (Kula and Marten 2008, 19). Bemba being the most well documented of the Sabi languages, we have been able to consult several sources (e.g., van Sambeek 1955; Sims 1959; Sharman 1963; Kasonde 2009; Nurse 2019).

M51 Bisa/Wisa

Bisa (Wisa) is spoken in northeastern Zambia, in Muchinga Province and parts of Luapula Province, with smaller communities in southeastern Democratic Republic of Congo (see Madan 1906, 3). Bisa has often been grouped with the neighbouring Lala lect (Maho 2009), reflecting a history of dialect continua in that region. Our reference work is Madan (1906).

M54 Lamba

Lamba is spoken mainly in Zambia’s Copperbelt, Central, and Northwestern Provinces, and parts of southeastern Democratic Republic of Congo (Haut-Katanga). It is closely related to Lala-Bisa M51/2 (see Hammarström et al. 2025). Our data comes from the works of Doke (1933, 1938).

N41 Nsenga (incl. Kunda N411)

Nsenga is spoken primarily in Zambia and Mozambique, where it is geographically situated on the central plateau that demarcates the watershed between the Zambezi and Luangwa river basins. The language’s territorial extent also encompasses the region surrounding Kachebere (Mchinji) Mountain in western Malawi. Genetically, the language is part of the Sabi² subgroup (M40–M50), but with considerable influence from the Nyanja-Sena group (N30–N40). Our analysis is based on field data from Zumbo, Mozambique, together with several published sources (e.g., Madan 1905; Ranger 1928; Miti 2001, 2004; Simango 2006), as well as Zemba (2015) for the closely related language referred to as Kunda (N411). Kunda does not appear in Maho’s (2009) updated Guthrie code classification but is subsumed under N41 by Hammarström (2019). We propose a new Guthrie code based on divergent features identified in Zemba’s (2015) grammar sketch and due to lexical similarity with Nsenga being estimated at around 70% by both Banda et al., (2013, 37-38) and Sawka et al. (2021, 36). Kunda (N411) is unrelated to and not to be confused with Chikunda (N42) (cf. Banda et al., 2013, 37).

Nyasa group (N15, N20–40)

The languages referred to here as Nyasa are spoken mainly in Malawi, eastern Zambia, and central Mozambique. The Nyanja (N201, N30) and Sena (N40) clusters constitute two closely related sister groups while the position of the Tumbuka-Tonga-Senga (N15, N21) cluster could be more distant and is in need of proper assessment. While its position as a sister branch to the Nyanja-Sena node is somewhat doubtful, most phylogenetic studies (e.g., Bastin et al. 1999; Grollemund et al. 2015; Koile et al. 2022) support this wider Nyasa group.

N21 Tumbuka group (incl. N15 Tonga, N21c Tumbuka-Kamanga, N21d Senga)

Tumbuka dominates large parts of northern Malawi and eastern Zambia. In this study we focus particularly on Tumbuka-Kamanga (N21c) as represented in Young (1932), spoken in the upper Luangwa Valley, a tributary river to the Zambezi. Senga (N21d), also spoken in the Luangwa Valley, in the Chama District of Muchinga Province (Zambia), is represented with data from Nkhata (2019). This variety is sometimes treated as a Tumbuka dialect, but its status is debated. The Senga are said to have originated from a Bisa offshoot composed mainly of migrating men who settled among the Tumbuka, married Tumbuka women, and quickly assimilated linguistically (see Section 5.3 in the paper). Sawka et al. (2021) report that Senga is generally perceived as Tumbuka-like but with heavy Bemba admixture. However, in their linguistic survey report, they argue that its 71% lexical similarity with Tumbuka justifies considering it a distinct language. As for Bemba lexical influence, its similarity is estimated at 46%, while the similarity with Bisa is 43%. For Tumbuka we have consulted the following works: Elmslie (1891); Young (1932); Vail (1972); Kishindo and Lipenga (2005); Kiso (2012). For the closely related

² Ahmed (1996, 40) estimates a split from the rest of the Sabi group some 1100–1300 years ago. In the 18th century, Nsenga communities were ruled by Undi’s Chewa Kingdom. In the 19th century, they were subjugated by the Ngoni, and for centuries they have been in contact with the Chikunda.

Malawian Tonga N15 we have consulted what little material is available (e.g., Turner 1952; Mkochi 2024; MacAlpine et al., n.d.).

Nyanja group (N201, N30)

Tanzanian Nyanja (N201) (sometimes referred to as *Mwera*³) is a Tanzanian offshoot of the larger Nyanja continuum. The language is spoken in Mbamba Bay and our reference work is Ngonyani’s (2020) grammatical sketch. Tanzanian Nyanja is the most deviant of the documented Nyanja varieties (see Ngonyani 2020, 5; Hammarström et al. 2025), which is reflected in the Guthrie code N201, whereas the rest of the Nyanja varieties are all subsumed under N31.

Chewa N31c is the largest language of Malawi and one of the key legacies of the Maravi Confederacy. From its settlement in present-day Malawi in the 16th century, its spread was tied to missionary work (Kula and Marten 2008, 5) and political expansion (Juwayeyi 2020), and it has become a lingua franca across much of Malawi, the Eastern Province of Zambia, and Mozambique (Tete Province), where it is most often referred to as Nyanja. Genealogically, Chewa-Nyanja occupies a central place among Guthrie’s (1967) zone N languages. In this paper we have novel field data from Nyanja (Zambia, N31a), and we have consulted a wide range of available publications on both Zambian (N31a), Malawian (N31c), and Mozambican (N31d) Chewa-Nyanja (the consulted works include Rebmann 1877; Riddel 1880; Watkins 1937; Atkins 1950; Missioários de Companhia de Jesus 1964; Harding 1966; Mchombo 1987, 2004; Peace Corps 1995; Lehmann 2002; Kishindo and Lipenga 2003; Kiso 2012; Downing and Mtenje 2017).

Sena group

The Sena group (sometimes Senaic) is a cluster of closely related languages (N42-N46⁴) spoken on both sides of the Zambezi River in central Mozambique, stretching from the confluence area with the Luangwa River down to the coast. A smaller number of speakers of Senaic varieties are found in neighbouring countries, e.g., Chikunda (N42) in Zambia and Zimbabwe, and Nyungwe (N43) and Sena (N441) in Malawi. Details about the varieties included in our sample are given below.

N401 Nserero

Nserero is spoken in the small villages of Chankoma, Chiwonga, Ntondo, and Ntunda, on the eastern fringe of Zumbo, along the Zambezi River. Our data comes from the latter two villages. Nserero is undocumented in major surveys. It is described by its speakers as a mix of Chikunda and Nsenga; in our preliminary analysis, similarities to both languages are observable. Geographically, the closest languages are Chikunda (N42) and Nsenga (N41) with Korekore (S11) being spoken further south across the Zambezi river. Nserero shows affinities with several languages in the N40 group, and is thus given the code N401.

N402 Phimbi

Maho (2009) places Phimbi as a Nsenga dialect under N41, while Hammarström (2019) classifies it as a Nyungwe dialect (N43). More recently, Hammarström et al. (2025) recognize it as

³ See for example Maho (2009), Hammarström (2019), and Hammarström et al. (2025). We prefer the label (Tanzanian) Nyanja, since this is the ethnonym used by the speakers themselves (Ngonyani 2020, 1) and it avoids confusion with the Rufiji-Ruvuma language commonly referred to as Mwera (P22).

⁴ We have no data on Podzo (N46)

a Senaic language on the same level as Nyungwe, Barwe, and Sena. Local speakers describe Phimbi as a mixture of Chewa and Nsenga, though affinities to Nyungwe are evident. Although more research is needed, our preliminary analysis suggests that Phimbi is most closely affiliated to the N40 group, hence it is given the code N402. The data in our paper come from fieldwork in the town of Fingoe in Tete Province, Mozambique.

N403 Dema

Dema people live in the high-mountainous regions around Songo (Tete, Mozambique), where our fieldwork data comes from. Johnston (1891, 390) refers to them as “a Nyanja people”, which Tew (1950, 32) reiterates based on their geographical position (see also Great Britain 1920, 114–115). As far as our initial fieldwork analysis can tell, the Dema lect is part of the Senaic cluster, possibly closest to Nyungwe, although it is difficult to say whether it is closer to Nyungwe than to e.g., Chikunda or Guro Tonga. It is important not to confuse this Senaic Dema with the Shonic Doma (see below). With its internal classification within the N40 group not being entirely clear, we assign it the referential code N403.

N404 Guro Tonga

Guro Tonga is spoken in the village of Guro (Manica Province, Mozambique) and its surroundings. The language is previously undocumented apart from a short wordlist by Posselt (1929), who referred to the population as “Tonga of the Ruenya Valley” (Posselt 1929, 88). The ethnonym Tonga has been in use in the Lower Zambezi Valley since at least the first half of the 16th century, although the people it referred to were not necessarily always a homogeneous linguistic unit (see Beach 1980, 158). Guro Tonga is clearly distinct from other languages referred to as Tonga, e.g., the Tonga (M64) from the Middle Zambezi described above; Malawian Tonga⁵ (N15); and the southern Bantu language GiTonga or Tonga of Inhambane (S62) from southern Mozambique, which is not included in our sample. The anthropologist Tew (1950) does not consider the Guro Tonga to be part of the Maravi peoples, but rather to be Shona immigrants from south of the Zambezi. Similar claims were also made by Bleek (1936, 10), but based on our fieldwork data we can confidently say that Guro Tonga shows its strongest affinities with languages from the N40 cluster, namely Nyungwe, Barwe, and Sena. Hence, we propose the new Guthrie code N404. The affinities of Guro Tonga with the Senaic group were recognized by Doke (1931a, 4), and also by Ngunga and Osvaldo (2012, 120) and Alfândega (2013), who both treat it as a Sena variety, whereas Ngunga (2014, 53) lists Tonga as a Nyungwe variety. A few speakers are found across the Zimbabwean border in the district of Mudzi⁶ (Hachipola 1998), but the language there is said to be highly threatened due to Shona prevalence. Our data come from fieldwork conducted in the towns of Guro and Mungari.

N42 Chikunda

Chikunda, historically linked to enslaved military communities protecting the *prazos* of the Portuguese Crown during colonial times, spread along the Zambezi as a language of mixed populations. Today, it is spoken in a small area at the confluence between the Zambezi and

⁵ Malawian Tonga (N15), also referred to as Lakeside Tonga (see Mphande 2014; Chondoka and Bota 2015), is spoken along the northern lakeshore of Malawi. Historically, Tonga speakers were among the early communities established along Lake Malawi, interacting extensively with Tumbuka and Chewa populations (Van Velsen 1964).

⁶ Hence Hachipola’s (1998) label ‘Tonga of Mudzi’.

the Luangwa Rivers, which corresponds to the border between Mozambique, Zambia, and Zimbabwe. Historically, Chikunda is believed to have been an ethnic admixture of different groups from around the Zambezi, such as Sena, Barwe, Tonga, Lomwe, Chuwabo, Chewa (Isaacman and Peterson 2003, 269), due to its mercenary origins. Linguistically, however, Chikunda is closely related to the languages from the N40 cluster. The data in our paper comes from fieldwork conducted in Bawa and Zumbo (Mozambique), Luangwa (Zambia), and Kanyemba (Zimbabwe).

N43 Nyungwe

Nyungwe is spoken in north-central Mozambique, around the city of Tete, and has long been considered a key Senaic (N40) language. Its role as a regional lingua franca has exposed it to considerable contact with Chewa/Nyanja, Sena, and certain Shona varieties. Anthropological sources portray Nyungwe as a product of “ethnic intermixtures and creolisations” (Marizane 2016, 146), including Nyungwe-speaking people, consisting of “layers of exogenous others over a core of the people who spoke chiNyungwe at Tete town and its environs” (Marizane 2016, 146). The study suggests that groups such as Afro-Portuguese or Afro-Asian traders or settlers also became part of the identity of the Nyungwe people by aligning themselves with the Nyungwe language rather than with Portuguese. The reference works consulted in this paper are Courtois (1900), van der Mohl (1904), Torrend (1907), and Martins (1991).

N44 Sena (including Malawi Sena N441)

Sena (N44) is one of the dominant Zambezi Valley languages, spoken primarily in central Mozambique, especially in Sofala Province (along the Zambezi River), and extending into Tete, Manica, and Zambézia. Malawi Sena (N441) is a northern extension of Sena, spoken mainly in the Lower Shire Valley of Malawi, particularly in Nsanje and Chikwawa Districts.

Both areas are part of the Zambezi–Shire river system, historically a key axis of trade, migration, and state-building. This geographic corridor explains much of the Sena’s historical importance. The Sena region became a frontier zone of interaction between the Maravi Confederacy (Chewa/Nyanja-speaking groups expanding from Malawi), Shona/Mutapa groups from south of the Zambezi, Portuguese prazos (land grants) along the Zambezi, and later Afro-Portuguese and Afro-Goan trading communities (Newitt 2022). This long history of multi-ethnic contact gave Sena its role as a lingua franca of the Zambezi Valley.

For both Mozambican and Malawian Sena we rely on field data collected on several occasions (2021, 2022, 2024, 2025), as well as published material (see Anderson 1897; van der Mohl 1904; Moreira 1924; Heins 2001; Kishindo and Lipenga 2007; Kiso 2012).

N45 Barwe

Barwe is usually grouped within the Sena cluster (Doke 1931a; cf. Hammarström et al. 2025), although it is claimed to be a Shona variety by Mangoya (2012, referencing Chebanne 2008). Other sources in the fields of social anthropology and history (Junod 1936, 297–311; Bleek 1936, 10; Maia 2015) describe Barwe as Shona, which might be an oversimplification based on the ruling Shona elite of the Barwe Kingdom. Although Barwe was a Shona polity or vassal state associated with Great Zimbabwe and the Mutapa Empire, a large proportion of its population were Lower Zambezi Valley (Guro) Tonga (Beach 1980; Van Dokkum 2020). Through our first fieldwork data from Catandica we are able to identify Barwe as more N40-like while

still straddling the boundary between N40 and S10 and thus exhibiting certain grammatical features more associated with the latter. Historical migrations, intermarriage, and shifting political boundaries probably account for such ambiguities.

S10 Shona group (Shonic cluster)

Shona is a major Bantu language group primarily spoken in Zimbabwe, where it holds official status alongside Ndebele and English, as well as in parts of Mozambique, Zambia, and Botswana. As a linguistic group, Shona comprises several closely related varieties, including Zezuru, Karanga, Manyika, Ndau, and Korekore, which are generally mutually intelligible (Doke 1931b). Historically, Shona traces its roots to the migration and settlement of Bantu-speaking peoples in southern Africa around 2,000 years ago, with the Shona specifically associated with the rise of the Great Zimbabwe civilization (11th–15th centuries), a powerful pre-colonial state known for its monumental stone architecture and extensive trade networks (Beach 1980; Pikirayi 2001; Huffman 2007). Genealogically, Shona is a Southern Bantu group, an early offshoot from the rest of Southern Bantu (S20–S60) (Bastin et al. 1999; Grollemund et al. 2015; Koile et al. 2022; Gunnink et al. 2025). The Shona varieties examined are described below.

S101 Doma

Doma, spoken in the villages of Mariga and Chiramba (Kanyemba, Zimbabwe), is a Shonic language with no previous Guthrie code. The data in our paper come from the fieldwork conducted in Mariga (approx. coordinates: -15.726595, 30.385938). Both Hammarström (2019) and Hammarström et al. (2025) list an ISO code (dmx) under “unclassified Shona”. While this code refers to Doma, the name given in both sources is “Dema”. This is very likely to be a confusion with the Senaic Dema of Cahora Bassa described above. The internal classification of Doma within the Shona group needs further study, but the geographical location and basic vocabulary suggest a close affiliation to the Northern Korekore group.

S102 Hwesa

Hwesa is a liminal Shonic variety with no previous Guthrie code. Doke (1931a) categorized it as a Senaic language, whereas Borland (1970) identifies it as Shona. Its distribution in eastern Zimbabwe and across the Mozambican border aligns it geographically with other liminal varieties of the Shonic-Senaic clusters. The data in our paper come from Hwesa spoken in the Mozambican villages of Nyamtongwe (-17.475397, 32.979521) and Kawiri (-17.440609, 33.007801) near the Zimbabwean border, with Borland’s (1970) work serving as an additional reference. While certain Senaic features are observable, early analysis of phonology, lexicon and grammar suggests stronger affinities with the Shonic cluster.

S11 Korekore

Korekore is the name given to the cluster of varieties constituting ‘Northern Shona’ (Doke 1931a, 8). This group contains several varieties, including Korekore proper, which is the largest

Korekore variety, spoken mainly in Darwin, Lomagundi, and Mrewa Districts (Doke 1931a, 9). The data used in our paper is fieldwork data from the Darwin District.

S11 Tawara

Tawara is part of Northern Shona group (Korekore; see above) but is heavily influenced by languages from the Lower Zambezi Valley such as a Nyungwe (N43) (Doke 1931a, 8–9). It thus represents another transitional zone between Shonaic and Senaic languages, typical of the area between the Lower Zambezi and the Zimbabwean Plateau. The data in our paper come from fieldwork conducted in Estima, a small predominantly Nyungwe-speaking city in Tete Province, Mozambique, with Tawara speakers originally from Mague. Following Maho (2009), Tawara is subsumed under the Guthire/Maho code for Korekore (S11).

S12 Zezuru

The Zezuru are a major subgroup of the Shona people, primarily inhabiting the central and northern regions of Zimbabwe, particularly Mashonaland. The Zezuru language is one of the most prominent varieties of the Shona linguistic group and serves as the foundation (along with Karanga) for Standard Shona, the official written and educational form of the language in Zimbabwe (Doke 1931b). We have used Fortune (1955) as our reference work for Zezuru.

S13 Manyika

Manyika is a group of Shona varieties spoken in Manicaland Province in central-eastern Zimbabwe and in Manica Province in central-eastern Mozambique (Doke 1931a; Borland 1970). The preliminary sources consulted for Manyika in this paper are Buck (1911), Stevick (1959), and Stevick and Machiwana (1960). Some additional notes are found in Fortune (1955).

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Southern Bantu Auxiliary Functions and Their Distributions

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Abstract

Southern Bantu languages have extensive auxiliary inventories with functions that sometimes go beyond typical tense/aspect/mood/polarity meanings. This article examines areal semantic patterns of auxiliaries in 16 Southern Bantu varieties, identifying functions that are regularly encoded by auxiliary forms. In addition to tense, aspect, modal, and negation meanings, these include sequentiality functions ('until', 'after', 'furthermore', and 'meanwhile', among others) and adverbial-like functions such as 'quickly, soon', 'do well', 'do in vain, fail', 'nevertheless', 'rather, preferably', and 'just, merely'. This article aims to give a systematic overview of auxiliary functions and where they are attested across Southern Bantu, allowing for further targeted studies and cross-linguistic investigations and leading, ultimately, to a better understanding of the origins of Southern Bantu auxiliary systems.

Keywords: Bantu Zone S, auxiliary semantics, non-TAMP functions of auxiliaries

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1 Introduction

1.1 Contextualizing the research

Southern Bantu auxiliary systems typically feature large inventories with functions that often go far beyond the temporal, aspectual, modal, evidentiality, and polarity semantics typically associated with auxiliaries.

For example, the Sesotho auxiliary *tla* (< ‘come’) can be used to indicate that the action indicated by the lexical verb was done well (1). The siSwati auxiliary *sheshe* (< ‘hurry’) indicates a quick action (2).

- (1) Sesotho S33 (Chaphole 1988, 193)

<i>A-tla</i>	<i>a-bu-a</i>	<i>Mosotho.</i>
SP ₁ .PST-AUX	SP ₁ .CSC-speak-FV	1.Sotho

‘He spoke well, the Mosotho.’

- (2) siSwati S43 (modified from Nkuna et al. 2021, 231)

<i>Lilanga</i>	<i>li-hlala</i>	<i>li-sheshe</i>	<i>li-shon-e</i>	<i>ebusika.</i>
5.sun	SM ₅ -AUX	SM ₅ .SIT-AUX	SM ₅ -set-SBJV	LOC.14.winter

‘The sun always sets quickly in winter.’

Many such auxiliary functions are attested within Southern Bantu. Some of them involve non-cognate or even totally distinct lexical sources, suggesting that these functions are significant enough within the language group that verbal resources are recurrently recruited to express them via auxiliiation.

To the best of my knowledge, there has been little to no comparative work identifying auxiliary functions and where they are attested across Southern Bantu. My aim in this article is therefore to lay out the specific auxiliary functions attested and the breadth of their attestation across Southern Bantu, showing which functions appear to be widespread, and whether these are recruited from multiple sources.

This comparative overview further aims to serve as an aid to other researchers of Southern Bantu languages and of Bantu in general, by providing a checklist, with examples, of functions known to be expressed via auxiliaries in Southern Bantu. I hope thereby to pave the way for broader cross-linguistic comparison, so that we can determine which auxiliary concepts are specific to Southern Bantu and which are more widespread in Bantu and in African languages more generally.

The article builds upon an open-source, spreadsheet-based dataset of auxiliaries in Southern Bantu (Carbo et al. 2025).

1.2 On the term ‘auxiliary’ and its use in this article

The forms chosen for inclusion in the present study have the following properties in common (3):

- (3) Criteria for identifying auxiliaries

- i. They form a single predicate with a lexical verb, modifying that verb and sharing a subject with it.
- ii. They are bound to the lexical verb they modify and cannot appear without it.

- iii. They are verbal and can – at least optionally – host subject-marking prefixes.
- iv. They take as a complement one of three subordinate or non-finite lexical verb forms: situative, subjunctive/consecutive, or infinitive.
- v. They cannot host object-marking prefixes, which are restricted to the construction's lexical verb.

These properties are described in far greater depth in Crane et al. (forthcoming).

Over the years, auxiliaries have been defined using many different and sometimes incompatible criteria, and I have not found a definition that fully captures the phenomenon discussed in this article, although Southern Bantu auxiliary forms are frequently included in cross-linguistic studies of auxiliiation and grammaticalization (e.g. Kuteva et al. 2019; Anderson 2011). The closest-fitting comparative concept is Haspelmath's (2024, 1) "retro-definition":

An auxiliary is a non-affixed bound [i.e. it cannot appear on its own – auth.] form cooccurring with a verb that expresses TAMEP (tense, aspect, modality, evidentiality, or polarity) meanings and that has person marking which indexes the verb's subject.

However, Southern Bantu auxiliary functions are not restricted to TAMEP; furthermore, excluding the auxiliaries with non-TAMEP functions would be linguistically random, excluding forms that otherwise behave identically to other auxiliaries in the same systems.¹

The defining properties listed in (3) are not without their complexities. For one thing, auxiliaries, as forms in the process of grammaticalizing, often exhibit variable behaviour (see e.g. Kuteva 2001, 6–7). For example, some of the forms I discuss in this article are losing their agreeing subject marking (thereby looking more like adverbial particles), while others can appear as either auxiliaries or prefixes. Following the criteria in (3), I include in this investigation only forms attested to host subject prefixes (even if they do not always do so)² and to appear as non-affixed forms (even if the language in question also has corresponding prefixes).

With verbs taking infinitive complements – which have extensive functional overlap with auxiliaries taking situative, subjunctive, or consecutive complement types and clearly belong to the same semantic field – it can occasionally be difficult to draw the line between auxiliary verbs and lexical verbs taking nominal complements, since infinitive forms share many properties with nouns. I included infinitive-selecting forms in the auxiliary set if their functions in these contexts differed from the reported functions of the same verb taking regular nominal complements. For example, Sesotho sa Leboa (S32) *rata* 'like, love, want' appears to be used only with these meanings, whether followed by a noun or a verb, according to the sources I drew upon, while a cognate form in Setswana (S31) and Sesotho (S33) can have the avertive or (ap)proximative meanings 'almost' or 'nearly' when used in auxiliary constructions. I therefore included the S31 and S33 forms in the analysis but not the form from S32. However, such lines are not completely straightforward to draw, as also noted by Ziervogel (1959, 150).

¹ Indeed, Haspelmath himself notes, "The particular choice of meanings is of course arbitrary, and one could have made different choices. The reason I chose TAMEP (tense, aspect, modality, evidentiality, or polarity)... is that these are the most common kinds of meanings mentioned for auxiliaries" (2024, 14).

² A few auxiliaries only appear as imperatives, which are not marked with subject prefixes, but which are clearly verbs. Regarding criteria (b) and (d), a small number of auxiliary-like forms (mostly modal, to the best of my knowledge) do allow for ellipsis of the lexical verb and/or can be prefixed with limited object markers (mostly frozen and possibly even having been reanalysed as part of the auxiliary itself; see Crane et al. 2024; Crane, Lubambo et al. 2025). I have included these in Section 5.2 to give a better overview of the modal systems and their lexical sources, also noting the classificatory challenges.

Because the auxiliary forms are drawn from descriptive literature of varied depth, I occasionally had to make judgment calls on whether forms described in the source material under the umbrella of auxiliaries (and related terms) fit these criteria perfectly, sometimes based on less-than-ideal data. I have high confidence that the great majority of forms included in the analysis belong there, based on the criteria outlined in (3). I have noted some cases of uncertainty. I also discuss some relevant forms that conform to some but not all the criteria, flagging them as not (yet) full members of the auxiliary systems.

1.3 Southern Bantu languages

Southern Bantu, also called South-Eastern Bantu, is a cluster of related languages spoken in South Africa and neighbouring countries, including Botswana, Eswatini, Lesotho, Mozambique, and Zimbabwe (Gunnink et al. 2023, 77). It is a subclade of Eastern Bantu. Southern Bantu consists of six groups, traditionally labelled with the ‘Guthrie’ (see Hammarström 2019) codes S10 (Shona), S20 (Venda), S30 (Sotho/Sotho-Tswana), S40 (Nguni), S50 (Tsonga), and S60 (Copi). See Gunnink et al. (2023) for a detailed description of these groups and their relationships to one another.

The languages examined in this study are listed in Table 1, along with approximations of the numbers of auxiliaries included in the present study.³

Table 1: Languages and approximate inventories of documented auxiliaries

Language group	Language	Number of auxiliaries considered in this study (approx.)
Shona S10	Central Shona [mostly Zezuru] (S10/S12, sna)	30
Venda S20	Tshivenda (S21, ven)	14
Sotho-Tswana S30	Silozi (K21, loz)	26
	Setswana (S31, tsn)	69
	Sesotho sa Leboa [N. Sotho] (S32, nso)	25
	Sesotho [S. Sotho] (S33, sot)	41

³Counts are unavoidably approximate for several reasons. Documentation is incomplete, and the distinction between separate auxiliaries and the same base auxiliary with different functions, derivable from its aspectual marking, is not always straightforward to make. This may result in minor overcounting, but the more likely situation, in my opinion, is undercounting due to insufficient documentation.

Nguni S40	isiNdebele [S. Ndebele] (S407, nbl)	32
	Sindebele [N. Ndebele] (S408, no ISO)	35
	isiXhosa (S41, xho)	49
	isiMpondo (S41a, no ISO)	19
	isiZulu (S42, zul)	65
	siSwati (S43, ssw)	41
	Sindebele [Ndebele of Zimbabwe] (S44, nde)	23
Tsonga S50	Xitswa (S51, tsc)	3
	Xitsonga (S53, tso)	21
Copi S60	Gitonga (S62, toh)	11

Note that S30 Sotho-Tswana also includes K21 Silozi, a mixed language spoken in Zambia and Namibia. Silozi formed after a group of mostly Sesotho speakers known as the Makololo invaded Barotseland, setting up temporary rule over the K31 Luyana speakers living there. Although the Makololo were eventually conquered in 1864, their language had already taken hold. It is still spoken in the area as a mixed language, with mostly Luyana phonology (dramatically simplified from Sotho-Tswana) and mostly Sotho morphology and vocabulary, although some typically Zone K grammatical features and locally relevant lexical items are found in Silozi (see Gowlett 1989; Gunnink et al. 2023 for discussion). Auxiliary concepts found in Silozi and Zone S languages but absent in other Zone K (or M) languages, especially those not influenced by Silozi, may therefore provide some evidence of time depth for the auxiliary forms and functions.

1.4 Data sources

The main source for this article is the body of descriptive literature on the Southern Bantu varieties, listed in Appendix B. Notes on auxiliaries from these sources are collected in Carbo et al. (2025), and I made use of this dataset in locating examples and identifying clusters of concepts. Because this article attempts to consolidate large amounts of data, I do not cite references when listing sources and functions, unless a particular reading or property is discussed at greater length. See Carbo et al. (2025) for detailed reference information.

The reference works consulted span more than a century and were written with different aims, target audiences, theoretical frameworks, and areas of focus. The depth to which auxiliaries are discussed also varies greatly: some sources merely list auxiliaries and their functions, while others discuss their sources and usage patterns in detail.

Furthermore, many descriptions of auxiliary functions, whether of a single auxiliary form, of cognates across languages, or of different forms with similar functions across languages, overlap only partially (if at all), and without further targeted investigation it is generally impossible to determine whether divergences reflect descriptive differences or distinct usage patterns. Inevitably, a study of such a complex semantic field, based on a literature survey, will engage in ‘lumping’ or ‘splitting’ of types, some of which will be due to differences in the precision of

descriptive sources (see e.g. Kuteva et al. 2019, 10–11 for some discussion of the latter issue). I represent significantly diverging descriptions as separate functions, in the absence of evidence (e.g. from comparable illustrative examples) that they are different terminology for the same function.

Although named languages are often described as if they were separable, reified entities, descriptive data are culled from doculects that do not fully represent the breadth of speaker practices. Lack of an attested auxiliary does not mean that the auxiliary does not exist in a named language, and (more rarely) an attested auxiliary may not actually be in common use. Researchers interested in the semantics of specific auxiliaries should consult the original sources – or, whenever possible, living scholars and speakers of the languages in question.

1.5 Classifications and other conventions

I have roughly classified auxiliary functions into a few major categories: aspect (Section 2), sequentiality (Section 3), tense (Section 4), mood and modality (Section 5), negation (Section 6), and a wide-ranging set of functions that do not fit neatly into these categories, but serve functions such as speaker evaluation, manner/other adverbial, and even discourse functions (Section 7). This division is a categorization of convenience rather than a theoretical claim. It is an understatement to say that the literature on tense, aspect, mood, and polarity has not always agreed on how to define and delineate these categories, and many auxiliary functions span them no matter how they are sliced. For a different approach to categorizing auxiliary functions for cross-linguistic comparison, see Schaefer and Egbokhare (2025).

The basic definitions I have used for categorizing the categories are as follows:

ASPECT relates an eventuality and its internal structure to the time being talked about (topic time); see e.g. Klein (1994).

SEQUENTIALITY relates (the times of) eventualities with respect to other eventualities (in contrast to the topic time or the reference time). It therefore has features in common with both aspect and tense, but instead of relating reference and topic times, directly relates eventualities to one another. I also classify under sequentiality causal relationships between events, which generally entail temporal relationships.

TENSE relates the time being talked about (topic time) to a reference point, usually the time of speech (or ‘utterance time’; see e.g. Klein 1994). Note that the nature of tense in Bantu languages, which often obligatorily mark multiple temporal distinction – for example, ‘today’ vs. ‘yesterday’ vs. ‘remote’ past – is debated (see e.g. Cable 2013, who argues that at least in Gĩkũyũ (E51), temporal remoteness markers relate utterance time directly to event time). Further, some forms I have categorized as ‘tense’ function more like temporal adverbials, doing something like setting the topic time itself. Examples include meanings like ‘[do something] early/first thing in the morning’. The same forms often develop more traditionally tense-like functions (see e.g. Section 4.7).

MOOD refers to illocutionary force (following Nurse and Devos 2019, 219, “optatives and directive speech acts”).

MODALITY refers to expressions of possibility and necessity (see e.g. van der Auwera and Plungian 1998).

NEGATION refers to negative polarity, i.e. reversing the truth value of the proposition (see Miestamo 2005, 42 for standard negation as a comparative concept).

The other forms (Section 7) do not fit neatly into any of these categories, although they may have features of one or more of them.

It is sometimes difficult to distinguish the functional contributions of auxiliaries from those of the (sometimes elaborate) agglutinative TAMP marking on these auxiliaries (e.g. for auxiliaries conveying tense or negation). I have made notes on problematic cases where possible. Readers should refer to the dataset and source materials for further information.

Throughout this paper, for concision and easy cross-group comparison, and to avoid ambiguity (e.g. between ‘Ndebele’ varieties), I mostly refer to languages by their Guthrie codes, as listed in Table 1. For the convenience of human readers, I also list language names when giving examples or discussing specific forms in greater depth. Proto-Bantu (PB) reconstructions, marked with a reference number and an asterisk (*), are taken from Bastin et al. (2002).

I have generally adopted the orthographic conventions of the original reference works. Most of these works use the standard orthographies of the languages in question, although the orthographies used in older works are more variable. Some sources also mark tones. See Carbo et al. (2025) for some further notes on Southern Bantu orthographies. It is important to note that many of these languages (especially in S30) have more vowel contrasts than are represented in the orthographies. Some of the older descriptive materials do mark additional vowel distinctions (e.g. S31 *fêla* represents [fɛla] but is represented as *fela* in modern Setswana orthography; see Creissels forthcoming for phonemic transcriptions of S31 data). This means that a few auxiliaries are represented inconsistently in the dataset. I do not know of any cases where these differences represent (or mask) underlying lexical differences. Vowel diacritics in this paper, included to remain faithful to the original works, can therefore safely be ignored.

All glosses (and errors therein) are my own, either modified from the original works or (in most cases) added entirely. Translations are taken directly from the original works unless otherwise indicated.

When citing auxiliaries and noting their lexical sources, I cite the auxiliary forms as given in the descriptive sources. In each subsection (aside from Section 7.12, which lists auxiliary functions attested in only one language), I include a table of auxiliary forms grouped by source meaning. I group clearly cognate forms – which may in some cases be the result of borrowing – together in these tables. I have attempted to consolidate the translations of lexical sources to core meanings for easier cross-linguistic comparison. I also give a representative example in each subsection.

A summary of forms and meanings, along with the respective section in which each is discussed, is given in Appendix A.

2 Aspectual functions

Aspect marking is a very common function of auxiliaries across Bantu and worldwide. This section describes aspectual functions associated with auxiliaries in Southern Bantu, including functions such as imperfectivity and repetition, along with a few more specific aspectual functions, including the category of ‘phasal polarity’ (Van Baar 1997). I assume that all languages in the sample have ‘aspectual’ verbs that take verbal complements and have meanings like ‘finish’, ‘start’, ‘stop’, and so forth. Unless they have developed additional functions (e.g. finish > ‘as soon as’) and otherwise meet the criteria outlined in (3), I do not discuss them here, as I consider them primarily lexical: among other properties, they can take nominal complements, they are not bound to a complement verb, and they can take object markers.

2.1 Imperfective subtypes

By far the most frequent auxiliary function in the dataset relates to one or more of what I (following Comrie 1976) consider to be subtypes of imperfectivity, with meanings described as ‘habitual’, ‘continuous’, ‘continually’, ‘progressive’, ‘often’, ‘frequently’, ‘usually’, and ‘always’, among others.

Many auxiliaries have several of these functions. For example, Oosthuysen (2016, 291) notes that the S41 (isiXhosa) auxiliary *ya*, when followed by a subjunctive marker, can mean either ‘continues to occur’ or ‘occurs from time to time’. Some descriptions draw distinctions between these meanings: for example, Creissels (forthcoming) conceptually separates a number of imperfective subtypes in S31 (Setswana), including five auxiliaries meaning ‘continuous’ (‘constantly’); two expressing ‘continuative’ (‘continue to’); and one auxiliary each with the functions ‘frequentative’ (‘often or extensively’), ‘habitual’ ‘durative’, and ‘occasionally, sometimes’ (terms mentioned are as given by Creissels).

However, not all sources are so specific, and a more precise categorization is therefore beyond the scope of this paper, even though detailed semantic maps of each marker and its functions would be of great interest. It is very important to keep in mind that English translations alone cannot be taken as analyses, and certainly cannot be used to distinguish, for example, ‘habitual’ from ‘frequentative’ from ‘occasionally’. The main lesson to take from the preliminary comparative data presented here is the importance of auxiliaries in the expression of imperfective-type meanings in Southern Bantu.

Table 2 attempts a rough classification, distinguishing at least continuous from iterative aspects. CONTINUOUS encompasses durative ‘keep doing’ and progressive ‘be doing’ (following Heine and Kuteva 2002, 19; Kuteva et al. 2019, 27–32). What I call ITERATIVE refers to various kinds of repetition, including meanings like ‘constantly’, ‘habitual’, ‘usually’, ‘often’, and ‘occasionally’. Table 2 lists the translations given in descriptive documentation. The Xs in the continuous (CONT) and iterative (ITER) columns indicate that, based on the translations and examples given in the descriptive literature, I judge that this meaning is associated with one or more lexical items derived from the (semantic) source listed in the leftmost column. The question marks indicate that examples given in the source literature suggest that this might be a plausible interpretation, but some ambiguity remains.

This categorization does not rule out the possibility that two different lexical items derived from the same source meaning might have different functions; furthermore, it is likely that not all interpretations are represented in the table.

Sources of continuous auxiliaries include at least ‘**build**’, ‘**be common**’, ‘**continue**’, ‘**copula**’, ‘**go**’, ‘**go/leave/travel/walk**’, ‘**live**’, ‘**long ago**’ [far past continuous], ‘**refuse**’, ‘**spend the day; spend time**’, ‘**sit; stay; live**’, ‘**stretch**’, ‘**travel**’, and possibly ‘**be with**’, ‘**forget; delay**’, ‘**go round**’, and ‘**stand for**’.

Iterative functions derive from ‘acquaint; be used to’, ‘build’, ‘have/be with’, copula, ‘eat’(?),⁴ ‘end’, existential(?),⁵ ‘become full’, ‘go’, ‘go; leave; travel; walk’, ‘go round’, ‘increase’, ‘know’, potential(?), ‘remain’, ‘refuse’ ‘satisfy’, ‘stand for’, ‘sit; stay; live’, ‘travel’, ‘wait for’ ‘wander about’, and possibly ‘live’.

Sources of both functions include ‘build’, copula, ‘go’, ‘go; leave: travel; walk’, ‘sit; stay; live’, ‘travel’, and possibly comitative, ‘forget; delay’, ‘go round’, ‘live’, ‘refuse’ and ‘stand for’.

A few auxiliaries have unknown sources. Some of these resemble auxiliaries with known sources and may be borrowings or have similar source material.

Although a few imperfective-related prefixes occur, such as S10 (present) progressive *khou-* (Nurse 2019, 302), Southern Bantu languages tend to lack general purpose imperfective morphology such as the habitual suffix *-a(n)g*, which is common across Bantu (Nurse 2008, 262–264). This lacuna might be one motivation for the recruitment of many auxiliaries to express habitual and related readings.

Table 2: Imperfectives

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary	CONT	ITER
already + DEM (c117)	S41 <i>sólókò</i> always; constantly; persistently; continuously; all the time		X
acquaint/be used to	S32 <i>tlwaetše</i> used to (past habitual, judging from examples) S33 <i>tlwaela</i> be accustomed to [> tend to] i.e. generic reading		X
build	S31 <i>aga/agile</i> usually; often; continuous; keep on doing; always	X	X
come	S31 <i>tlé</i> occasionally; sometimes; usually; habitually; frequently; as a matter of habit or regular custom		X
comitative (have/be with)	K21 <i>na</i> keep on; continue to (examples ambiguous) S31 <i>na (le)</i> habitual [also obligative]	?	X
be common	S42 <i>vama</i> usually S407 <i>vame, vane</i> habitual	X	

⁴I am not fully convinced by this reconstruction, proposed for S41 by Oosthuysen (2016, 311). As noted in Carbo et al. (2025), the tones of *dla* ‘usually’ may differ from the tones of *dla* ‘eat’, and the semantic pathway is not straightforward. The only semantic pathway for ‘eat’ noted in Kuteva et al. (2019) is EAT > PASSIVE.

⁵I have posited the existential and potential sources based on their morphological similarity and the plausibility of semantic change.

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Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary	CONT	ITER
copula	S33 <i>be</i> [usually even]; S62 <i>ba</i> [continuity]; S10 <i>va</i> [continuous; habitual] S62 <i>na</i> [continuity of action]; S31 <i>nê</i> [past continuous]; S33 <i>ne</i> [past continuous] S62 <i>ra</i> [continuity of action]; S10 <i>ri</i> [continuous]		
eat?	S41 <i>dla</i> usually; regularly		X
end	S31 <i>fêla</i> constantly; always; continually [examples suggest repetition] S408 <i>phele</i> just, sometimes, simply	X	
existential?	S33 <i>ke</i> sometimes, occasionally		X
forget / delay	S42 <i>libele</i> do continuously; do continually what ought not be done	?	X
get/become full	S53 <i>tála</i> likely; often; always S62 <i>talela</i> frequently		X
go	S41 <i>ya</i> progression; continuation; from time to time S33 <i>ya, ye</i> usually; habitually S43 <i>ye</i> usually	X	X
go / leave / travel / walk	S41 <i>hamba</i> all the time go / leave / travel / walk S41 <i>hamba</i> all the time S41A <i>hamba</i> all the time S42 <i>hambe</i> keep on; all the way along; all the time S43 <i>hambe</i> all the time; often S31 <i>tsamaya</i> keep on doing; usually; continuing; until; continuous; doesn't stop; constantly	X	X
go round	S10 <i>pota</i> go on; keep on; continually	?	X
increase	K21 <i>atisa</i> often S31 <i>atisa</i> often; frequently; keep on; usually; frequentative S33 <i>atisa</i> frequently; often		X
know (+APPL)	S10 <i>zivo, ziviro</i> habitually; according to custom		X
live	S31 <i>tshela</i> continuous; constantly	X	?
long ago	S43 <i>kadze</i> continuing in the far past	X	
potential?	S31 <i>ka</i> from time to time		X

Southern Bantu Auxiliary Functions and Their Distributions

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Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary	CONT	ITER
refuse	S10 <i>ramba</i> keep on; remain; constantly; continue S53 <i>phika</i> always; continually	X	X
remain	S407 <i>hle</i> no more [NEG]; usually; commonly; habitual action S408 <i>hlwe, hlwa</i> no more [NEG]; usually; commonly; habitual action S43 <i>ye</i> usually		X
spend the day / spend time	S53 <i>dzumba</i> S32 <i>hlwa</i> spend the day doing; continually S21 <i>twa</i> spend the day doing; continually S31 <i>tlhola</i> usually; (spend) the whole day through; constantly, repeatedly; always; continuous(ly); no longer [NEG] K21 <i>tola</i> continuation; never again [NEG]	X	
stand for	S41 <i>mana</i> repeatedly; continually; often S41A <i>mane</i> continually	?	X

Southern Bantu Auxiliary Functions and Their Distributions

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Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary	CONT	ITER
sit / stay / live	S32 <i>dula</i> always; continually S33 <i>dulela</i> keep doing S21 <i>dzula, dzulela</i> always; continuously S10 <i>gara</i> continuous S10 <i>garo</i> always S41 <i>hlala</i> persisting process; continu- ous; always, continuously S43 <i>hlala</i> keep on doing; continuously S44 <i>hlala</i> always S407 <i>hlale</i> from time to time; do habitually S408 <i>hlalela</i> always; continually S42 <i>hlale, hlalele</i> always; continu- ously; habitually; from time to time S42 <i>hlezi</i> always; constantly; from time to time S44 <i>hlezi</i> constantly S31 <i>nna; (n)ntse; nne; nnela</i> continue; may as well; gradually; keep on do- ing; do always; continually; occasionally; usually; customarily S53 <i>tsháma</i> always; be wont to; often	X	X
stretch	S31 <i>nama</i> continue; keep on; continuative	X	
travel	S31 <i>éta</i> do later/at that time; while; proceed, keep on; simultaneity; all the time	X	X
wait for	S53 <i>tshàmala, tshàmela</i> always (cf. <i>tsáma</i> < ‘sit / stay / live’?)		X
wander about	S42 <i>zinge</i> habitually		X

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary	CONT	ITER
unknown source	S42 <i>damane</i> / <i>damene</i> constantly; often; always S42 <i>dane</i> always S42 <i>de</i> always; repeatedly S33 <i>ěe</i> habitual S41 <i>fudula</i> ‘used to’; past habitual S53 <i>hámba</i> always; continually S407 <i>hle</i> no more [NEG]; usually; com- monly; habitual S43 <i>hle</i> frequently S408 <i>hleti</i> (< ‘stay?’) keep on; continue S41A <i>khunkqa</i> do much; often S42 <i>lokhu</i> , <i>lo</i> keep on; persistently S44 <i>lokhe</i> , <i>lokhu</i> continuous; keep on doing; still S33 <i>ne</i> (< COP?; sit/stay?) past continuous S408 <i>nja</i> continually S33 <i>nna</i> ; <i>nne</i> (< COP?; sit/stay?) con- tinue; keep on doing; occasionally S408 <i>nojwa</i> keep on; sometimes S407 <i>nonde</i> keep on; sometimes K21 <i>nze</i> continue, keep on, still S408 <i>se</i> usually, commonly S43 <i>solo</i> continuously S408 <i>swe</i> usually; commonly S53 <i>tàmà</i> always; continually S33 <i>ya</i> (< ‘go?’) usually		

2.2 ‘Again’ (S20; S30 incl. K21; S40; S50; S60)

Auxiliaries indicating that the predicate takes place ‘again’ occur in at least five subgroups, with numerous lexical items (many cognate). Known sources include ‘**add; increase**’ (K21, S53); ‘**repeat**’ (S21, S33, and most of S40);⁶ and ‘**return; come back; go back; return + APPL**’ (S10, K21, S33, S40 as a group, S53, S62). Most of these words (aside from ‘repeat’) are reconstructible to Proto-Bantu 3563 *jòng ‘add to’ or 353 *bój ‘come (or go) back; come’, but some seem to have been adopted by analogy, as with K21 *kuta* and S53 *tlhèlà*, both meaning ‘return’ (note that K21 also has *buela* ‘return’ as an auxiliary meaning ‘again’). Therefore, this function seems to be important in Southern Bantu. ‘Return’ is a common cross-linguistic source

⁶The auxiliary *phinde* (from *phinda* ‘repeat’) is not mentioned for S408. In S407, *phinda* is not listed as a lexical item in the isiNdebele dictionary (Iziko lesiHlathululi-mezwi sesiNdebele 2006), but *phinde* is noted as an auxiliary meaning (under negation) ‘never again’. The positive polarity meaning ‘again’ is not noted, and brief (translated) corpus searches (<https://app.glosbe.com/nr/en/>) for words such as *ngiphinde*, *aphinde*, and *baphinde* seem to confirm this pattern. *Phinde* may have been borrowed into S407, but only in negative contexts.

of the ‘again’ function (Kuteva et al. 2019, 476), and the other sources have obvious semantic relationships to the concept ‘again’.

- (4) Sesotho S33 (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 284)

Rē-bōèla rē-ngòl-a.
 SP_{1PL}-AUX SP_{1PL}.SIT-write-FV
 ‘We write again.’

- (5) Silozi K21 (Fortune 1977, 94)

Ne-ba-ekeza ku-bulel-a.
 PST-SP₂-AUX INF-speak-FV
 ‘They spoke again.’

- (6) isiZulu S42 (Mkhatshwa 1991, 127)

Ngi-fun-a uku-buye / uku-phinde ngi-ku-bon-e.
 SP_{1SG}-want-FV INF-AUX / INF-AUX SP_{1SG}-OP_{2SG}-see-SBJV
 ‘I want to see you again.’

Table 3: ‘again’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
increase	K21 <i>ekeza</i> ; S53 <i>èngeta, engete</i>
repeat	S21 <i>dovha</i> S33 <i>phēta</i> S41 <i>phinde</i> ; S41A <i>phinde</i> ; S42 <i>phinde</i> ; S44 <i>phinde</i> ; S43 <i>phindze</i>
return / return to	S10 <i>wiro, wiriro</i> S31 <i>boa, boela</i> ; S33 <i>boela</i> ; K21 <i>buela</i> ; S62 <i>ḃwelela</i> S408 <i>buya</i> ; S41 <i>buya</i> ; S44 <i>buya</i> ; S407 <i>buye</i> ; S42 <i>buye</i> ; S43 <i>buye, buya</i> K21 <i>kuta</i> S53 <i>tlhèlà</i>

2.3 (Ap)proximative and avertive (‘almost’ / ‘about to’) (S30 incl. K21; S40; S50; S60)

A very common auxiliary function expresses the concepts ‘almost’ or ‘about to’. This categorization conflates the categories (AP)PROXIMATIVE (on the verge of, about to, etc.) and AVERTIVE (nearly happened, but did not happen); see, for example, Kuteva et al. (2019, 26, 32). I combine these conceptually similar but distinct categories for two reasons: first, because a number of the markers can clearly have both kinds of readings, as in (7); and second, because many sources do not provide enough information to make a distinction, if such a distinction can in fact be made.

- (7) Silozi K21 (Gowlett 1967, 161)

a. *Njà i-bàtìlè i-nì-lúm-à*
 9.dog SP₉-AUX.PFV SP₉.SIT-OP_{1SG}-bite-FV
 ‘The dog almost bit me.’

- b. *Mbútùtù ú-bàtilè á-lòbézi.*
 1.baby SP₁-AUX.PFV SP₁.SIT-sleep.PFV
 ‘The baby is almost asleep.’

- (8) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 28)

Pula e-losetsa go-n-a.
 9.rain SP₉-AUX INF-rain-FV
 ‘It looks like it’s about to rain.’

- (9) siSwati S43 (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 121)

Lí-phòsè / lí-císhè kú-ngì-w-ís-à.
 SP₅-AUX / SP₅-AUX INF-OP_{1SG}-fall-CAUS-FV
 ‘It almost makes me fall.’

As noted, forms with these meanings are very common. S33 alone has five distinct approximative auxiliaries. Sources for these forms mostly come from diverse lexical items meaning ‘**want (lack; need; search for, etc.)**’ and/or ‘**want (like; love; desire, etc.)**’, or a combination of these meanings (S30 as a group, S40 as a group, S62). Other sources include ‘**extinguish**’ (S42, S43?); ‘**be greedy**’(?)⁷ (S10); ‘**come**’ (S31); ‘**throw**’ (S42, S43, S44, S53?⁸); **quotative** (K21); and an applicative causative form of ‘**struggle**’ (S31). ‘Almost’ forms mentioned in the literature without clear etymology (although similar to *pho(n)sa* ‘throw’) are S407 *pheze*, S408 *phase*, *phoswe*, *phoso*, S41 *phantsa*, *phantse*, and S41A *phantsa*.

Kuteva et al. (2019, 477, 486) list ‘come to’, ‘love’, ‘near’, ‘promise’, ‘threaten’, and ‘want’ as proximative sources, and ‘copula’, ‘fail’, ‘love’, ‘near’, and ‘want’ as avertive sources. It would be interesting to see if there are correlations between these two sets of meanings and the approximative vs. avertive functions in Southern Bantu.

Table 4: (Ap)proximative and avertive

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
come	S31 <i>tsile</i>
extinguish	S42 <i>cishe</i> ; S43 <i>cishe</i>
be greedy?	S10 <i>karo</i>
struggle	S31 <i>loetsa</i>
throw	S42 <i>phonse</i> , <i>phose</i> ; S43 <i>phose</i> ; S44 <i>phose</i> ; S53 <i>phòse?</i>

⁷Fortune (1955, 341) notes this as a possible source.

⁸S53 Xitsonga has *phòse* and the lexical verb *phòsà*, defined by Cuenod (1967, 167) as ‘use magic to attract or harm person’. While most S40 sources define *pho(n)sa* as ‘throw’, Pelling (1971, 57) defines *phosa* in S44 as ‘cast, throw, bewitch’, suggesting a link between these lexical items.

want (etc.)	K21 <i>bata</i> ; S31 <i>batla</i> ; S33 <i>batla</i> S41A <i>funa</i> ; S42 <i>funa</i> S32 <i>nyakile</i> S31 <i>rata</i> ; S33 <i>ratla</i> S31 <i>senka</i> S62 <i>haja</i> S42 <i>thanda</i>
quotative	K21 <i>li</i>
unknown source	S41A <i>phantsa</i> ; S41 <i>phantsa</i> , <i>phantse</i> S408 <i>phase</i> , <i>phoswe</i> , <i>phoso</i> ; S407 <i>pheze</i>

2.4 Experiential ('(have) ever', 'once') (S10; S20; S30; S40)

The most common experiential markers lack an obvious lexical source and take the form *k(h)V* (*h* represents aspiration): S31 (*e*)*kilê*, (also S32?); S33 *ka*, *kile*; S41(A), S407, S408 *khe*; S42 *ke*; S43 *ke/se*; S44 *ke*; S53 *khanga*.

- (10) Sesotho S33 (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 266)
N-kile *ka-'mòn-a* *Gauteng.*
 SP_{1SG}-AUX.PFV SP_{1SG}.CSC-OP₁.see-FV 1A.G
 'I once saw him in Johannesburg.' [sic.]

- (11) isiXhosa S41 (Oosthuysen 2016, 296)
Ndi-khe *nda-nenz-a* *na=buhlungu yini* *na?*
 SP_{1SG}-AUX SP_{1SG}.CSC-OP_{2PL}.do-FV COM=14.pain why Q
 'Did I ever cause you [pl.] any pain?'

Oosthuysen (2016, 296) posits the source *kha* 'to pluck [e.g. fruit], to dip up [e.g. water]', but I find this link tenuous. Similar forms are widespread in Southern Bantu: for example, S33 Sesotho has experiential *ka*, but the verb meaning 'pluck' is *kga* (see Moeketsi 1991, 81); S42 isiZulu has experiential *ke* but the verb 'pluck, dip up water (etc.)' is *kha* (see Doke and Vilakazi 1972, 372). Furthermore, the pathway of semantic change from 'pluck' to experiential is not clear to me, unless the route involves generalizing from a semelfactive-like action.

Doke and Mofokeng (1957, 266) equate the form in Sesotho S33 with a modal auxiliary, potential *ka*. Pretorius (1997, 129) and Creissels (this volume) also make this connection for Setswana. This conceptual overlap is attested in Swahili and possibly in some Great Lakes languages (Rasmus Bernander, p.c., March 30, 2026). The tone patterns of the experiential auxiliaries do seem to match those of the potential in the languages mentioned. It may be that the experiential forms in Sotho-Tswana languages have a modal source, and that their use as experientials arose via phonological similarity to the Nguni experiential forms, or vice versa, because the Nguni *k(h)a* forms do not correspond to potential prefixes and related morphemes, which take the form *nga*.

However, the sound correspondences seen in experiential forms are not the regular ones seen between these languages (for example, [k] in Sotho-Tswana corresponds to [ng] in Nguni), and with so little phonological material in these auxiliaries, it is difficult to draw firm conclusions

about their sources. Forms meaning ‘long ago’ are one additional candidate (see also S408 *kade* in Table 5), but these have similar challenges in terms of the initial consonant: the experiential form does not have the same initial consonant as the word ‘long ago’ in every language.

These markers seem to play a role in the formation of other auxiliaries as well, for example S408 *khange* ‘never (past)’ and S44 *ngeke* ‘cannot; will not; can/will never’.

Other experiential sources include **quotative** (S10), **‘return; come back’** (S21), and the adverb (likely with nominal source) *kade* ‘**long ago**’ (S408).

Table 5: Experiential

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
quotative	S10 <i>ti</i>
return	S21 <i>vhuya</i>
long ago	S408 <i>kade</i>
<i>k(h)V</i>	S33 <i>ka/kile</i> ; S53 <i>khànga</i> ; S41 <i>khe</i> ; S41A <i>khe</i> ; S42 <i>ke</i> ; S44 <i>ke</i> ; S43 <i>ke, se</i> ; S407 <i>khe</i> ; S408 <i>khe</i> ; S31 <i>kilê, ekilê</i> ; S32 <i>kilê</i>

2.5 Phasal polarity

Kramer (2017, 1) describes phasal polarity as “involv[ing] reference points at two related phases implying situations which are contrasted as opposites with different polarity values, i.e. one of the two situations in question holds (+) whereas the other does not (-)” – relevant meanings include ‘already’, ‘still’, ‘no longer’, and ‘not yet’. Phasal polarity meanings are commonly encoded in Bantu as auxiliaries or verbal affixes, and both strategies are found in Southern Bantu, although affixation is very common. The interactions of phasal polarity and negation (see e.g. Löbner 1989, 72 and Kramer 2017, 3) in auxiliary constructions, as well as their overall semantics and relationships to other auxiliary categories, are complex and beyond the scope of this paper; further targeted study is obviously called for. This section probably does not capture the full extent of the phenomenon within Southern Bantu auxiliary systems.

2.5.1 ‘Already’ (S10; S30 incl. K21; S40)

The most common markers of ‘already’ appear to be related to a verb *sala* ‘**stay, remain**’ (PB 2911 **tígad* ‘remain’) and in some languages are shortened as *se* (K21, S33, S40), often in addition to a longer form *sele*. These appear throughout S30 and S40. Many of these shortened forms are also (or even mostly) used as prefixes (12).

(12) isiXhosa S41 (Oosthuysen 2016, 289)

- a. *Isikolo sikatitshala uGoqo si-se si-vul-iwe.*⁹
 7.school of_1A.teacher 1A.Goqo SP₇-AUX SP₇-open-PASS.PFV
 ‘The school of teacher Goqo has already been opened.’

⁹ According to Oosthuysen (2016, 289), this form tends to be written as a single word with two subject markers (*sisesivuliwe*). The same pattern, with *se-* functioning both as an auxiliary and as a prefix, is found in other languages, as can be seen, for example, by searching for *base* [followed by *ba-X*] at glosbe.com.

- b. *Se-ndi-sebenz-a.*
 ALT-SP_{1SG} -work-FV
 ‘I am already working.’

Other ‘already markers’ are **quotative** *ti* (S10)¹⁰ – also an experiential marker – and the forms *biyo* (S408) and *piŋgo* (S10).

Finally, an auxiliary derived from a noun, S43 *khatsi*, from *sikhatsi* ‘time’, means something like ‘only now (not before)’. This is a common meaning of the *se-* prefix, as well (see Nichols 2011 for extensive discussion).

Table 6: ‘already’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
quotative	S10 <i>ti</i> [‘not yet’ under negation]
stay / remain	K21 <i>se</i> ; S33 <i>se</i> ; S407 <i>sele, se</i> ; S408 <i>sele</i> ; S41 <i>sele, se</i> ; S42 <i>se</i> ; S43 <i>se</i> ; S44 <i>se</i> ; S32 <i>šetše</i> ; S31 <i>sētse, setswe</i>
time	S43 <i>khatsi</i>
unknown source	S408 <i>biyo</i> [‘not yet’ under negation] S10 <i>piŋgo</i> [‘not yet’ under negation]

2.5.2 ‘Still’ (S30 incl. K21; S40)

The phasal polarity concept ‘still’ is generally expressed as a prefix in Southern Bantu and can be found as a ‘persistent’ prefix in all the languages under investigation (with cognates found widely across Bantu; see e.g. Nurse 2008, 145–148).

However, a few auxiliary forms that can express some notion related to ‘still’ are also found, including K21 *nze*, S33 *ntse*, and S44 *lokhe* and *lokhu*. All of these forms are connected to imperfective (‘continue to’, ‘keep on’, etc.) but the strength of the ‘still’ meaning is not totally clear to me, based on the descriptive literature. For example, the S44 forms are translated with ‘still’ when used with stative lexical verbs (Pelling and Pelling 1974, 198). Creissels (forthcoming, 16–17) classifies S33 *ntse* as a kind of ‘continuative’, and Fortune (1977, 97) gives both ‘keep on’ and ‘still’ as translations for K21 *nze*. Both S33 *ntse* and *nze* are optionally prefixed with the persistent ‘still’ marker *sa-*.

An example of Silozi (K21) *nze* (apparently meaning ‘no longer’ when the main verb is negated) is given in (13). Apparently, similar internally negated constructions with S44 *lokhe/lokhu* (Pelling and Pelling 1974, 198) and S33 *ntse* (Pretorius 1997, 176) give the reading ‘still not’ (i.e. ‘not yet?’) rather than ‘no longer’, suggesting interpretive complexities that may not be as simple as straightforward scope of negation. More investigation is needed.¹¹

¹⁰ Unlike what appears to be the case for the markers derived from ‘stay’, when S10 *ti* is under negation, it can mean ‘not yet’; see Fortune (1955, 353).

¹¹ On the other hand, the situation of fruit ceasing to ripen seems an odd one outside of artificial conditions, so it may be that the translation of (14b) is not the best one.

(13) Silozi K21 (Gowlett 1967, 161)

a. *Ú-nzè à-húl-à*

SP₁-AUX SP₁.SIT-grow-FV

‘He is still growing.’

b. *Misèlò í-nzè í-sà-bùzw-ì.*

4.fruit SP₄-AUX SP₄.SIT-NEG-ripen-FV.NEG

‘The fruit is no longer getting ripe.’

Skhosana (2009, 355) also lists *se* for S407 and S408, but this may be a typographical error, or it might refer to the persistive copula *sese* used with non-verbal predication (Ziervogel 1959, 103; see Oosthuysen 2016, 60 for a similar example from S41).¹²

Table 7: ‘still’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
sit	S33 <i>ntse</i>
unknown source	S44 <i>lokhe, lokhu</i> ; K21 <i>nze</i> ; S408 <i>se</i> (?)

2.5.3 ‘Not yet’ (S30; S40)

A small number of auxiliaries appear to occur under negation with the meaning ‘not yet’ (14). Some of these, such as S32 *ešo* and S31 *ise*, only occur in negated form. In at least the case of S31 *ise*, overt negation is not needed; that is, the auxiliary is (or is becoming) inherently negative (14b). Sources are posited to be ‘take’ (S31 *ise*), ‘dawn (?)’ (S32 *ešo*),¹³ and **quotative** (S408 *tjho*). Note also that at least a few auxiliaries with the meaning ‘already’ can mean ‘not yet’ under negation (see also Section 2.5.1). Note that with S408 *biyo*, the lexical verb, and not the auxiliary, is negated (16).

(14) Setswana S31

a. Setshedi (1974, 33)

Ga-kè-isé kè-is-è diaparo kogo

NEG-SP_{1SG}-AUX SP_{1SG}.SIT-take-FV.NEG s8?.clothes there

‘I have not yet taken clothes there.’

b. Setshedi (1974, 41)

Ke-robal-a ke-ise ke-j-e

SP_{1SG}-sleep-FV SP_{1SG}.SIT-AUX SP_{1SG}.SIT-eat-CSC.FUT

‘I sleep having not yet eaten, i.e. I sleep before I eat.’

¹² I suggest that this listing of *se* may be in error because all my own data for S407 show *se* to mean ‘now’, or ‘already’, with *sese* meaning ‘still’ in non-verbal predication in both S407 and S408. The prefix *sa-* is used in both S407 and S408, as in the rest of Nguni, to express ‘still’.

¹³ Lexical source meaning from Kriel (1976, 222). Poulos and Louwrens (1994, 275) state that the source of *ešo* is unknown.

(15) siNdebele S408 (Ziervogel 1959, 156)

A-ń-ká-tjhó *ń-khá:mbh-e*

NEG-SP_{1SG}-NEG.PST-AUX SP_{1SG}-go-SBJV

‘I have not yet gone.’

(16) siNdebele S408 (Ziervogel 1959, 153)

...*ú-bíyó* *á:-wáti* *kú-swáphel-a sibáyá sá:khe.*

...SP₁-AUX NEG.SP₁-AUX[know] INF-close-FV 7.kraal POSS.PRON_{7/1}

‘...he does not yet know how to close up his kraal.’

Table 8: ‘not yet’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
dawn?	S32 <i>ešo</i>
take	S31 <i>ise</i>
quotative	S10 <i>ti</i> (positive polarity ‘already’); S408 <i>tjho</i>
unknown	S408 <i>biyo</i> (positive polarity ‘already’); S44 <i>lokhe, lokhu?</i> (‘still not’; positive polarity ‘still’)

2.5.4 ‘No longer’ (S31)

To the best of my knowledge, the phasal polarity meaning ‘no longer’ is usually expressed with a persistive prefix on a negated verb in Southern Bantu, as in (17).

(17) isiNdebele S407 (Aunio et al. in prep., 44)

A-ngi-sa-fund-i.

NEG-SP_{1SG}-PERS-read-FV

‘I don’t read anymore. / I’m not reading anymore’

However, the dataset also shows an auxiliary strategy: when negated, at least some forms meaning ‘still’ (Section 2.5.2) and/or imperfective forms indicating continuing situations (Section 2.1) can mean ‘no longer’ under negation. An example is S31 Setswana *tlhola*, from ‘**spend the day somewhere**’. This may be a more general characteristic of auxiliaries meaning ‘continue to’ (depending on the scope of negation), but more data are needed before making generalizations.

(18) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 19).

Ga-ke-(sa-)thlole *ke-lem-a* *tshimo e*

NEG-SP_{1SG}-(PERS-)AUX.NEG SP_{1SG}.CSC-cultivate-FV 9.field DEM₉

‘I do not cultivate this field anymore.’

Table 9: ‘no longer’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
sit	S33 <i>ntse</i>
spend the day	S31 <i>tlhola</i>

3 Sequentiality

I classify as ‘sequentiality’ auxiliaries that express the ordering and general temporality of eventualities with respect to one another. Some of these functions might also reasonably be classified under tense, aspect, or discourse structure. Many of the meanings listed in this section are interrelated, with numerous auxiliaries described as having several of these functions. Marking sequentiality and other relationships between events appears to be an important use of auxiliaries across Southern Bantu, with many forms and many intersecting functions.

3.1 ‘Until’ (S10; S30 incl. K21; S40; S50; S60)

At least 20 auxiliaries in the dataset have a meaning including ‘until’ (19). Some ‘until’ readings are listed in their respective descriptions as part of more complex auxiliary semantics. For example, Pretorius (1997, 150) describes the auxiliary functions of *tsamaya* (from ‘walk, go (etc.)’) as ‘keep on doing, usually, continuing, until’; other auxiliaries have ‘until’ listed as their primary function. See also Section 3.10 on ‘eventually’ auxiliaries, which are sometimes noted to have an ‘until’ function.

(19) siSwati S43 (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 124)

li-té li-f-è

SP₅-AUX SP₅-die-SBJV

‘until it dies’

The most frequent source of ‘until’ is the verb ‘**come**’ (K21, S31, S32, S407, S408, S42, S43, S44), also a common source noted in Kuteva et al. (2019, 487). Interestingly, S43 Siswati *te* (the subjunctive form of ‘come’) is used, in positive polarity contexts, to mean ‘until’ (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 124), while its borrowed ‘Zunda’¹⁴ cognate *ze* is used in S43 as an alternate expression for ‘until’ but can also “express disgust or surprise” (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 160).

Other sources of auxiliaries reported to express ‘until’ include ‘**go and reach**’ (S53); ‘**arrive at**’ (applicative-marked form) (K21, S31); ‘**lack; have a scarcity of**’ (S53); ‘be(come)’ (K21); and a borrowing of the Portuguese *até* ‘until’ (S62). S41(A) *de* might come from the adjective *de* ‘long’. There are a few forms in S43 whose origin is unclear to me (*dzinwa* means ‘get tired’ but is not directly mentioned as a source): *dzine*, *dzimane*, *dzimate*, *ndzibane*, *ndzimate* (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 118–121).

Also relevant is S10 *dzimara*, from ‘**end by**’ and *dakaro*, from ‘**end up**’, both of which are characterized as meaning ‘at last, in the end, until’ and ‘end up [as a result]’ (Fortune 1955, 362–365). Forms including S10 *dzimara*, S31 *fitlhela*, K21 *fetela*, and S31 *tsamaya* have the ‘until’ reading when inflected with infinitive marking rather than agreeing subject marking,

¹⁴The ‘Zunda’ vs. ‘Tekela’ distinction is a traditional classification of Nguni languages that differentiates the varieties on the basis of their use of [t] vs. [z] in particular contexts, as well as a few other phonological variables.

thereby making their auxiliary status less clear, although they otherwise seem to function very similarly to the other ‘until’ auxiliaries. An example is given in (20).

(20) Silozi K21 (Fortune 1977, 96)

U-lu-libelezi ku-fitela lu-fit-a
 SP₁-OP_{1PL}-wait_for.PFV INF-AUX SP_{1PL}.SIT-arrive-FV
 ‘He waited for us until we arrived.’

Table 10: ‘until’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
arrive at	(S31 <i>fitlhêla</i>); (K21 <i>fitela</i>)
come	K21 <i>te</i> ; S43 <i>te</i> ; S31 <i>tla</i> ; S32 <i>tlê</i> ; S42 <i>ze</i> ; S44 <i>ze</i>
copula	K21 <i>be</i>
go / leave / travel / walk	(S31 <i>tsamaya</i>)
go and reach	S53 <i>kóndza</i>
lack	S53 <i>kála</i> ; <i>ká</i>
long?	S41A <i>de</i> ; S41 <i>de</i>
borrowing	S62 <i>ate</i>
unknown origin	S43 <i>dzine</i> , <i>dzimane</i> , <i>dzimate</i> , <i>ndzibane</i> , <i>ndzimate</i> ; (S10 <i>dzimara</i>)

3.2 ‘After’/ ‘then’ / consecutive (S20; S30; S40; S60) (cf. ‘as soon as’)

Many forms in the dataset indicate that an action took (/takes/will take) place shortly or immediately after something else occurred (or occurs); most of these have a variety of meanings surrounding this concept (e.g. ‘as a result of’; ‘rather’; ‘for the time being’; ‘even’). This meaning seems to have a close connection with the near/immediate future (Section 4.3) and it was not always straightforward to disentangle the meanings as presented in the literature; in many cases, the two readings are likely to be slightly different interpretations of the same basic concept. Lexical sources include ‘stay; remain’ (S32, S407, S408, S41, S42); ‘leave; depart’ (S31, S407, S408, S42); ‘arrive’ (S10, S31, S407, S408, S41A, S43); ‘come’ (S31, S41, S41A); ‘find’ (S10); ‘come from’ (S53) ‘hurry’ (S31) ‘return’ (S41A, S42); ‘pass; surpass’ (S31); ‘finish’ (S41, S42); ‘stretch out; extend’ (S31, S32); copula; ‘be(come)’ (S31, S32); ‘able’ (S21); ‘travel’ (S31); ‘see; appear’ (S41) and ‘not have (?)’ (S31). S10 quotative *ti* may also have this role (Fortune 1955, 346–351 describes it as ‘introductory’). Auxiliaries of uncertain origin include S21 *namba*; S32 *napa*; S41 *andula* (see Section 4.4); S41A *se* (from *sala*?); S41A *tfuba*; and S42 *nca*.

(21) Tshivenda S21 (Poulos 1990, 287)

... *a-kona u-pos-a marifhi anga.*
 SP₁.CSC-AUX INF-post-FV 6.letters POSS.PRON_{6/1SG}
 ‘[Vele went to the post office, bought stamps] and then posted my letters.’

Table 11: ‘after’ (etc.)

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
able; succeed	S21 <i>kona</i> / <i>konou</i> < <i>kona</i> + INF
appear	S41 <i>bon</i> ’
arrive	S43 <i>fika</i> , <i>efika</i> ; S41A <i>fika</i> , <i>fike</i> ; S407 <i>fike</i> ; S408 <i>fike</i> ; S31 <i>fitlha</i> (S10 <i>šiko</i> – see also Section 3.4)
copula	S32 <i>bile</i> ; S31 <i>ba</i>
come	S31 <i>tla</i> ; S31 <i>tlê</i> ; S41 <i>za</i> ; S41A <i>za</i> , <i>ze</i>
come from	S10 <i>bva</i>
finish	S41 <i>khova</i> S42 <i>qede</i>
leave	S43 <i>suka</i> , <i>esuka</i> ; S407 <i>suke</i> ; S42 <i>suke</i> ; S408 <i>suke</i> , <i>suka</i>
neg. comitative (not have)	S31 <i>se-na</i> / <i>sena</i>
pass	S31 <i>feta</i>
quotative	S42 <i>thi</i> ; S10 <i>ti</i>
remain	S32 <i>šala</i> ; S408 <i>sala?</i> ; S407 <i>sale</i> ; S41 <i>sala</i> ; S42 <i>sale</i>
return	S41A <i>buye</i> ; S42 <i>buye</i>

3.3 Subsequent contradictory process (S41)

S41 *suke* from ‘leave, depart’ (the same lexical item as used in S407, S408 for ‘after’; see Section 3.2) is described by Oosthuysen (2016, 299) as indicating a “subsequent contradictory process”. The examples given by Oosthuysen suggest deviation from a plan or the expected course of action.

(22) isiXhosa S41 (Oosthuysen 2016, 299)

Baku-ba=ke *be-nge-na-nto* *yoku-hlawul-a* *u-suke*
 SP₂-AUX=then SP₂.PST-NEG-COM-9.thing POSS₉.INF-pay-FV SP₁-AUX
wa-ba-xolel-a.
 SP₁.CSC-OP₂-pardon-FV

‘When they had nothing with which to pay, he/she pardoned them.’

Table 12: Subsequent contradictory process *ocess*

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
leave	S41 <i>suke</i>

3.4 ‘As soon as’ (S30 incl. K21; S40)

Forms with this meaning come from ‘arrive’ (S10); ‘suffice’ (S33, S407, S42, S44); ‘finish (?)’¹⁵ K21; and possibly ‘deny; object; refuse (?)’ (S33 *hana*). These auxiliary meanings are obviously connected to ‘after’ (Section 3.2) but may also have links to ‘just, merely’ (Section 7.8), especially S40 (*anela*, from ‘suffice’).

(23) isiZulu S42 (Doke 1992, 205)

Ngi-nele ngi-fik-e=nje ba-jabul-e.
 SP_{1SG}-AUX SP_{1SG}-arrive-SBJV=just SP₂-become_happy-SBJV?
 ‘As soon as I come, they become happy.’

Possibly also related are S10 *mba* ‘do at once’; S44 *hle* ‘do immediately/right away’; and S62 *jegela* ‘do immediately’, with semantics that seem to overlap at least partially with ‘as soon as’. These forms are also discussed in Section 4.3 (near future).

Table 13: ‘as soon as’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
arrive	S10 <i>siko</i>
deny / object / refuse	S33 <i>hana</i>
finish (?)	K21 <i>mana</i>
suffice	S44 <i>anela</i> ; S407 <i>nele</i> ; S42 <i>nele (anele?)</i> ; S44 <i>nela</i>
Possibly also related:	
take for	S62 <i>jegela</i>
unknown origin	S10 <i>mba</i> S44 <i>hle</i> (< sit / stay?)

3.5 ‘Furthermore’ (S20, S30, S40)

Also related to ‘after’ (Section 3.2) are a few forms described as meaning ‘furthermore’ (associated meanings mentioned include ‘also’, ‘again’, ‘even’, ‘besides’, ‘for that reason’, and ‘subsequently’, among others). An example is given in (24). S42 has forms based on ‘go’ and ‘lead; collect’. S31 has the form *bile*, possibly related to ‘be(come)’. S21 *namba* and S408 *nambha* are listed without source verbs, although these forms are somewhat reminiscent of S31 *nama* ‘stretch’, and Makwarela (1992, 55) lists ‘stretch out’ as a possible meaning for *namba* in S21 Tshivenda.

(24) isiXhosa S41 (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 249)

Ù-qòkèlè wá-tshò.
 SP₁-AUX SP₁.CSC-say_so
 ‘He further said so.’

¹⁵ *Mana* is not listed as a lexical verb in Jalla (1982), but it has the meaning ‘finish’ in other Zone K languages.

Table 14: ‘furthermore’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
copula?	S31 (<i>e</i>) <i>bile</i>
go	S41 <i>ye</i>
lead / collect	S41 <i>qokélà</i>
stretch?	S21 <i>namba</i> ; S408 <i>nambha</i>

3.6 Conditional: ‘if’ / ‘in the event of’ (S10?; S30?; S40?)

SiSwati S43 has two forms that mean ‘if’ or ‘in the event of’ and that might be considered auxiliaries. The form *na* “is occasionally still heard with a [subject prefix] although it is generally regarded as a conjunction” (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 121), and *hleze*, likely a borrowing from ‘Zunda’ Nguni languages, also means ‘in the event of’, although the example in Taljaard et al. (1991, 154) does not take a subject prefix and might also be considered a conjunction. Similarly, **quotative** *re* in S31 is cited as an auxiliary in several references (Pretorius 1997, 129, 337–339; Setshedi 1974, 70–71; Cole 1955, 302–303), and while Cole (1955, 302) notes that it is sometimes marked with agreeing subject concords, most examples (especially in Pretorius 1997) show an invariant concord *e-*, and the form can be followed by elements other than a verb, suggesting that its current status is more like a conjunction, as Cole (1955, 302) also notes. Connections between auxiliary forms and conjunctions should be explored further in Southern Bantu (see e.g. Sekhu 1994).

(25) siSwati S43 (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 121)

á-ná á-yí-bám-b-à-kó
 SP₁-AUX SP₁.SIT-OP₉-catch-FV-REL¹⁶
 ‘if he catches it’

Other **quotative** sources with meanings that seem to encode ‘if’ (/ ‘when’ / ‘while’) as well as a consecutive- and/or simultaneous-like meaning (Section 3.2) include S10, S408, and S42. The functions of quotative-derived auxiliaries are frequently so broad that it can be somewhat difficult to categorize them.

Table 15: ‘if’ (etc.)

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
comitative?	(S43 <i>na</i>)
stay? (borrowing)	(S43 <i>hleze</i>)
quotative	(S10 <i>ti</i>); (S31 <i>re</i>); (S408 <i>ri</i>); (S42 <i>thi</i>)

3.7 ‘First’ / ‘before’ (S10; S30; S40)

A number of verbs mean that the action described by the lexical verb is done ‘first’, or ‘before’ something (or anything) else. They come from sources meaning ‘begin’ or ‘start’ (S10, S41, S42, S43); ‘arrive’ (S33, S42); ‘appear’ (S41, S42); and ‘use quickly’ (S41).

¹⁶The suffix *-ko* occurs with relative clauses and with some situative forms, including after the auxiliary *na* (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 163).

(26) isiZulu S42 (Poulos and Msimang 1998, 330)

U-fike a-dl-e bese e-phuz-a
 SP₁-AUX SP₁-eat-SBJV then SP₁.SIT-drink-FV
 ‘He first eats and then drinks.’

At least S33 *fhla*¹⁷ and S41 *vela, vele* / S42 *vele* also have links to concepts of immediately / immediately after. Judging from Oosthuysen’s (2016, 305) description, S41 *phanga* may relate more to the concept of ‘before’ than to ‘first (in sequence)’.

Table 16: ‘first’ (etc.)

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
arrive	S33 <i>fhla</i> ; S42 <i>fike</i>
appear, come out	S41 <i>vela, vele</i> ; S42 <i>vele</i>
begin	S43 <i>cale</i> ; S41 <i>qala</i> ; S44 <i>qala</i> ; S42 <i>qale</i> ; S10 <i>tanga</i>
use quickly	S41 <i>phanga</i>

3.8 ‘Meanwhile’ (S30; S40; S50)

Many of the forms described as meaning ‘do meanwhile’ or ‘do in the meantime’ are also described as ‘do after; (e.g. S31 *sala*, S42 *sale* from ‘stay’; S31 *feta* from ‘pass’; S31 *nama* from ‘stretch’). These meanings are therefore rather hard to categorize, even with the help of the few examples provided in the sources. It is my impression, based on the examples, that ‘in the meantime’ tends to refer to a phase between implied other eventualities, or at least eventualities not specified in the example sentences. Example (27) from Xitsonga S53 includes the persistive ‘still’ prefix *ha-*, but this marker is not necessary for the ‘in the meantime’ meaning (see e.g. Baumbach 1987, 251).

(27) Xitsonga S53 (Lee and Hlungwani 2015, 121)

Wá-há-pfá á-khíy-á rívàntì.
 SP₁-PERS-AUX SP₁.SIT-lock-FV 11.door
 ‘He is still locking the door in the meantime.’

Lexical sources include ‘**stay; remain**’ (S31, S42); ‘**come from**’ (S53); ‘**pass; go past; surpass**’ (S31); and ‘**stretch**’ (S31). S408 *jwa* ‘meanwhile, so long’ is unclear in origin (cf. after/then).

Table 17: ‘meanwhile’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
come from	S53 <i>pfá</i>
pass	S31 <i>feta</i>
stay / remain	S31 <i>sala</i> ; S42 <i>sale</i>
stretch	S31 <i>nama</i>

¹⁷Doke and Mofokeng (1957, 287) translate S33 *fhla* as ‘act immediately, do straightaway’.

unknown origin	S408 <i>jwa</i> S10 <i>sano</i>
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3.9 Simultaneous (‘while’) (S30 incl. K21; S40)

A few markers are described as marking simultaneity. Two derive from a **quotative** (K21 *li* and S43 *tsi*). Other sources are ‘**come**’ (S31) and ‘**travel**’ (S31; cf. Section 2.1), with one unknown source (S10).

(28) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 32)

O-apay-a a-tla a-tlhatsw-a.

SP₁-cook-FV SP₁.SIT-AUX SP₁.SIT-wash-FV

‘She does the cooking, and at the same time she does the washing.’

Table 18: Simultaneous

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
come	S31 <i>tla</i>
travel	S31 <i>eta</i>
quotative	K21 <i>li</i> ; S43 <i>tsi</i>
unknown source	S10 <i>nguno</i>

3.10 ‘Eventually’ (S30, S40)

Auxiliaries described as meaning ‘eventually’ are often listed with other meanings, as well, especially (and unsurprisingly, given their multifaceted auxiliary functions in general) verbs from ‘**come**’ (S407 and S408, both translated by Skhosana 2009, 353 as ‘eventually, in order, so that, until’) or the copula ‘**be(come)**’ (S33, with the auxiliary function translated variously as ‘eventually’, ‘until’ [see also Section 3.1] ‘even’, and ‘moreover’ in Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 279; and as ‘to even do’ and ‘fully planning to do’ in Chaphole 1988, 184). I am not entirely certain whether the meanings discussed here and in Section 3.11 should be characterized as relating to tense or to sequence, or whether they should be filed under ‘other’ adverbial functions. I have tentatively put them in this section, as they seem to suggest a series of situations (including the lack of anything happening) culminating in the eventuality named by the lexical verb.

Additional sources include ‘**go and reach**’ (S53); ‘**finish**’ (S31); ‘**stretch**’ (S31; Creissels forthcoming, 17–18 describes this as ‘conclusive aspect’); and ‘**put; place**’ (S32 *bea*, translated as ‘in course of time’ in Mphasha et al. 2021, 364). S41 *hle* (< *hlala* ‘**sit; stay**’?) can also mean ‘eventually’.

(29) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 17)

Pula e-feletse e-n-a.

9.rain SP₉-AUX SP₉.SIT-rain-FV

‘It eventually rained.’

Table 19: ‘eventually’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
come	S408 <i>te</i> ; S407 <i>ze</i>
copula	S33 <i>ba</i>
go and reach	S53 <i>kóndza</i>
put / place	S32 <i>bea</i>
finish	S31 <i>fêla, felela</i>
stretch	S31 <i>nama</i>
unknown origin	S41 <i>hla, hle</i> (< ‘sit / stay’?)

3.11 ‘In the end’ / ‘at last’ / ‘end up’ (S10; S40)

As mentioned in Section 3.1, S10 *dzimara*, from ‘end by’, and *dakaro*, from ‘end up’, both mean ‘at last, in the end, until’ (Fortune 1955, 362–363). Seemingly similar is S41 *phetha*, from ‘finish off; end’, meaning ‘ultimately; at last; end up’.¹⁸ It may ultimately make sense to unify this category with auxiliaries meaning ‘eventually’ (Section 3.10).

(30) isiXhosa S41 (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 250)

Ndì-phèthà ndì-ncám-è.

SP_{1SG}-AUX SP_{1SG}-despair-SBJV

‘I ultimately despair.’

Table 20: ‘in the end’ (etc.)

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
end	S10 <i>dzimara</i> S10 <i>dakaro</i> S41 <i>phetha</i>

4 Tense

Many auxiliaries mark the relationship between a reference time (often the utterance time) and the topic time, or the time being talked about (the latter being related to the eventuality named by the lexical verb via aspect). Only in a few cases (aside from relative tense) do they mark general past or future, but more specific temporal relationships are usually referenced, including temporal remoteness distinctions, or may relate to the specific time (day, night, morning, etc.) when an eventuality occurred.

4.1 (Relative) tense (all sample languages)

All languages in the sample (with K21 Silozi forming a slight exception) use a copula-like form ‘**be(come)**’, inflected for tense, to introduce a reference time against which the lexical verb’s temporality is evaluated: for example, future (31) or past (32). The lexical verbs can also be inflected for tense and aspect; for example, a perfective marking on the lexical verb with future marking on the auxiliary could give a reading ‘I will have worked’. K21 Lozi differs in that the

¹⁸ For ‘end up’, see also <https://glosbe.com/xh/en/ndiphetha> (accessed July 17, 2025).

auxiliary *be* is restricted to future time, and another auxiliary *li* (quotative: ‘say; do’) is used without temporal restriction (Fortune 1977, 96). See Botne (1986) for extensive discussion of related forms and their semantics.

(31) Sesotho S33 (Chaphole 1988, 54)

Ke-tla-be ke-sebetsa.
 SP_{1SG}-FUT-AUX SP_{1SG}.SIT-work
 ‘I shall be working.’

(32) Sesotho sa Leboa S32 (Mphasha et al. 2021, 363)

Ba-šemane ba-be ba-tany-a inonyana.
 2-boy SP₂-AUX SP₂.SIT-catch-FV 10.bird
 ‘The boys were catching birds.’

S10 *nge/nga* ‘seem, be like’ (>potential?) may play a similar role in some contexts.

Table 21: Relative tense

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
copula / ‘be(come)’	all languages
quotative	K21 <i>li</i>
potential?	S10 <i>nge, nga</i>

4.2 Future (S30, S40)

Futures are most frequently realized as grammaticalized prefixes deriving from ‘go’ and ‘come’. However, in some languages, and in certain registers, auxiliary forms are also possible. See Savić (2020, 130–142) for discussion of S41 isiXhosa. The dataset has one other example of an apparently still active auxiliary, S32 *tla*, from ‘come’ (see Mphasha et al. 2021, 352),¹⁹ which is usually realized as a prefix *tla-* or *tlo-* (Lombard et al. 1985, 189–190). See also Section 4.7.2.

(33) Sesotho sa Leboa S32 (Mphasha et al. 2021, 352)

Ke-r-ile ga-re-sa-tla go-ithut-a Sesotho sa-Leboa.
 SP_{1SG}-say-PFV NEG-SP_{1PL}-NEG-AUX INF-learn-FV 7.Sotho POSS₇-North
 ‘I said that we will not learn Northern Sotho.’

¹⁹Note that the auxiliary vs. prefix question in this case is at least partially an orthographic decision, as is evident in Savić (2020, 130–142).

Table 22: Future

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
come	S32 <i>tla</i> ; (e.g.) S41 <i>za</i>
go	(e.g.) S41 <i>ya</i>

4.3 Near future ('(very) soon'; 'immediately') (S10; S20; S30 incl. K21; S40?; S60?)

Auxiliaries indicating that an eventuality will occur in the near future are fairly common. However, their semantics typically appear to indicate more than straightforward immediate future, many seeming to have both absolute tense and sequentiality functions, among other meanings. K21 *tuha* is described in various sources as indicating 'nearness in time, soon' (Jalla 1982), 'soon; probably' (Fortune 1977, 97), and 'to be about to' (O'Sullivan 1993, 2). S10 *fuma* (from 'rise early') indicates that an 'action will happen on the morrow or quite soon' (Fortune 1955, 359).

Sources include 'go (away)'/ 'leave' (S21, K21, S31, S31); 'rise early' (S10); and possibly 'take for' (applicativized form) (S62).

(34) Tshivenda S21 (Makwarela 1992, 59)

Ndi-nga-tuwa nda-lwal-a
 SP_{1SG}-POT-AUX SP_{1SG}.CSC-be(come)_sick-FV
 'I may soon get sick.'

Possibly also related are S10 *mba* 'do at once' and *bva* 'at once; immediately; forthwith; there-upon'; S44 *hle* 'do immediately/right away; happen suddenly', and S62 *jegela* 'do immediately', which seem to relate both to sequence ('immediately after') and to nearness in time, although more information is needed. Some of the forms expressing 'go (away)' or 'leave' may also turn out to relate to temporal sequence, with the default interpretation being near future.

S53 *vhèla*, of uncertain origin, is reported to mean 'now' (Baumbach 1987, 251; Lee and Hlungwani 2021, 135 have an example where the function is not made explicit, but the 'now'/ 'immediately' interpretation is plausible). Translated examples on glosbe.com frequently correspond to 'immediately'. One wonders whether this form may be a borrowing of S40 *vele/vela* (< *vela* 'appear; come out'), which has similar immediacy readings, among many other, related functions (see Sections 3.7 and 7.8).

Table 23: Near future

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
go (away) / leave	S31 <i>ya</i> S21 <i>tuwa</i> ; K21 <i>tuha</i> ; S31 <i>tloga</i> ; S32 <i>tloga</i> S31 <i>tsamaela</i>
rise early	S10 <i>fuma</i>
Possibly also related:	
take for	S62 <i>jegela</i>
come from	S10 <i>bva</i>

unknown origin	S10 <i>mba</i> S44 <i>hle</i> (< sit / stay?) S53 <i>vhèla</i> (< Nguni <i>vela</i> ‘come out’?)
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4.4 Immediate/recent past (S30; S40)

A few forms are described as indicating that something has just occurred or has occurred recently: S31 *tswa* and S32 *tšwa*, from ‘go out; leave’; and a series of similar forms across S40 (possibly excepting S43, and with unclear frequency in S407 and S408) that seem to be formed from the persistive (‘still’) prefix *sa-* and the root *anda* ‘increase; multiply; accumulate’ or *andula* (apparently used in S41 only as an auxiliary). S31 *ilê* (from ‘go’?) can indicate recent past or ‘at a certain time (referring to the past), then, when’ (Pretorius 1997, 269–270).²⁰

(35) isiZulu S42 (Canonici 1995, 134)

Ngi-sand’ uku-m-bon-a.

SP_{1SG}-AUX INF-OP₁-see-FV

‘I’ve just seen him.’

Table 24: Immediate past

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
go?	S31 <i>ilê</i>
go out / come out / leave	S31 <i>tswa</i> ; S32 <i>tšwa</i>
persistive + increase	S407 <i>sanda</i> ; S408 <i>sanda</i> ; S42 <i>sanda</i> S44 <i>sanda</i> ; S41 <i>sandula</i>

4.5 Distant / remote past (‘long ago’) (S10; S30; S40)

The S10 auxiliary *nguva*, noted by Fortune (1955, 358) as being used only in the Karanga variety, comes from ‘spend time’ and indicates that the situation “took place a long time ago” (Fortune 1955, 358). S31 *sa-le* (persistive ‘still’ + copula; see also Section 4.6) can also indicate that a situation took place – or started – long ago (Creissels forthcoming, 19–20). As suggested in examples (36)–(37), both forms appear to be ambiguous between ‘[happened] for a long time’ and ‘[happened] long ago’, suggesting a logical path of semantic change between the two meanings (see Figure 1).

Other forms related to the remote past are S31 *bolo* (possibly from ‘tell’); S42 *kade* (< *de* ‘long’; adv. *kade* ‘long ago’); and S43 *kadze*, a remote past continuous marker (see also Section 2.1).

(36) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 19)

Dikgomo di-sa-le di-timel-a

8/10.cow SP_{8/10}-PERS-AUX SP_{8/10}.SIT-get_lost-FV

‘The cows have been lost for a long time.’

‘The cows got lost long ago.’

²⁰These forms are negated as *aka*, e.g. *hakeaka kareka* ‘I didn’t buy’ (Chaphole 1988, 185).

(37) Karanga Shona S10 (Fortune 1955, 358)

Hoŋo, wa-ŋguva a-gar-a pamukova.
 yes SP₁.RECPST?-AUX SP₁.PST.SIT?-sit_down-FV 16.3.door
 ‘Yes, he sat down at the door a long time [ago? – Auth.]’

Table 25: Distant past

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
spend time	S10 <i>ŋguva</i>
persistent + copula	S31 <i>sa-le</i>
tell?	S31 <i>bolo</i>
long (ago)	S42 <i>kade</i> ; S43 <i>kadze</i> ; others in S40?

4.6 ‘The last time’ / ‘most recent’ (S30, S40)

Two auxiliaries in the dataset are used to refer to the last or most recent time something occurred (i.e. the event has not occurred since): S31 *sa-le* (from a persistent prefix and a **copula** form; see also 4.5), and S41 *gqibela*, the applicative form of ‘finish’.

(38) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 19–20)

Ke-sa-le ke-m-mon-a ka laboraro
 SP_{1SG}-PERS-AUX SP_{1SG}.SIT-OP₁-see-FV by Wednesday
 ‘I saw him for the last time on Wednesday.’ [i.e. ‘I last saw him on Wednesday.’ – Auth.]

The links between ‘long ago’, ‘for a long time’, and ‘the last time’ for *sa-le* are logical, since the original meaning is ‘still be’ (see Creissels forthcoming, 19), seemingly interpreted as something like ‘situation ongoing for long[er than normally expected]’. Semantic connections are schematized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: ‘long ago’ – ‘for a long time’ – ‘the last time’

S41 *gqibela* also seems to function as a main (unbound) predicate meaning ‘finish off’ (e.g. Tshabe and Shoba 2006, 621), or – in examples given by Oosthuysen (2016, 167, 311) – the last time of having seen someone (39a), this latter function suggesting a conventionalized (degrammaticalized?) use. Oosthuysen (2016, 310–311) posits such uses as “contractions” of phrases involving the verb *bona* ‘see’ (39b).

(39) isiXhosa S41 (Oosthuysen 2016, 310–311)

- a. *Nda-m-gqibel-a* *izolo.*
 SP_{1SG}.REMPST?-OP₁-last_{see}?-FV yesterday
 ‘I last saw him yesterday.’
- b. *Nda-gqibela* *uku-m-bon-a* *izolo.*
 SP_{1SG}.REMPST?-AUX INF-OP₁-see-FV yesterday
 ‘I last saw him yesterday.’

Table 26: ‘the last time’ (etc.) T

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
persistentive + copula	S31 <i>sa-le</i>
finish	(S41 <i>gqibela</i>)

4.7 ‘Early’ (S10, S30)

Several forms are reported to mean ‘early’, i.e. doing something early or first thing in the morning, not restricted to past or future tense. S33 *tsoha* is from ‘**rise; wake up**’; S31 *phakêla* is from ‘**get up early**’ (see 4.7.1).

(40) Sesotho S33 (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 295)

- Rē-tla-tsōha* *rē-lē-bōn-a* *hōsasa.*
 SP_{1PL}-FUT-AUX SP_{1PL}.SIT-OP_{2PL}-see-FV tomorrow
 ‘We shall see you tomorrow morning.’

Table 27: ‘early’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
get up early	S31 <i>phakêla</i>
rise / wake up	S10 <i>fumo</i> S33 <i>tsoha</i>

4.7.1 Hodiernal past (S31)

While S31 *phakêla* means ‘early’ (Section 4.7), it can specifically be used (as perfective *pha-*ketse**) as a hodiernal past (Creissels forthcoming, 23). Creissels (forthcoming, 23) also analyses S31 *tsoga* (as perfective *tsogile*) ‘**rise; get up**’ as a hodiernal past (the aspectual interpretation arises via the form of the lexical verb).

(41) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 23)

Ke-tsogile ke-lem-a.

SP_{1SG}-AUX.PFV SP_{1SG}.SIT-cultivate-FV

‘I’ve been ploughing today.’

Table 28: Hodiernal past

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
get up early	S31 <i>phakêla</i>
rise / get up	S31 <i>tsogile</i>

4.7.2 Crastinal future (‘tomorrow’)

The same forms that are used as hodiernal pasts in S31 are also used (without perfective marking) as crastinal futures. According to Creissels (forthcoming, 24), *tsoga* has also generalized so that it can refer to more general future time.

(42) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 24)

N-ka-se-tsoge ke-y-a toropong.

SP_{1SG}-POT-NEG-AUX.NEG SP_{1SG}.SIT-go-FV 9.town.LOC

‘I will not be able to go to town tomorrow.’

Table 29: Crastinal future

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
get up early	S31 <i>phakêla</i>
rise / get up	S31 <i>tsoga</i>

4.8 ‘At night’ / ‘spend the night’ (S20; S30 incl. K21)

Verbs meaning ‘sleep’ (S21, S30 as a group) come to mean ‘do at night’ as auxiliaries. Like ‘early’, these forms are generally not restricted to past or future. Whether the night in question is in the future or the past seems to depend on tense morphology on both the auxiliary and on the main verb (as also shown in the next two sections regarding S31 Setswana).

Table 30: ‘spend the night’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
sleep	S21 <i>lala</i> ; K21 <i>lobala</i> ; S31 <i>lala, létse</i> ; S32 <i>lala</i> ; S33 <i>lala</i>

4.8.1 ‘At night’ / hesternal past (S30)

S31 Setswana seems to have at least partially lost the ‘night’ component of *lala* ‘sleep’ / *letse* ‘(have) slept’ when used as auxiliaries. *Letse* can either refer to something that happened the previous night, or it can be used as a hesternal (‘yesterday’) past. Creissels (forthcoming, 22) notes that when the lexical verb is unmarked for tense (what Creissels labels ‘present circumstantial’, often referred to as ‘situative’ or ‘participial’ form), either an ‘at night’ or ‘yesterday past’ interpretation is possible, but when the lexical verb is also marked as perfective (what Creissels analyses as ‘perfect’, in ‘circumstantial’ form), the hesternal past reading is unambiguous (43).

- (43) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 22)
Re-letse re-m-monye kwamasimo.
 SP_{1PL}-AUX SP_{1PL}-OP₁-see.PFV.SIT LOC.6.field
 ‘We saw him in the fields yesterday’

Table 31: Hesternal past

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
sleep	S31 <i>létse</i>

4.8.2 ‘At night’ / hodiernal future (S31)

Similarly, in S31 Setswana, *lala* with future orientation (e.g. prefixed with potential *ka-*, with future *tlaa-*, or after a modal verb like *tshwanetse*) can either mean ‘at night’ or ‘later today’ (Creissels forthcoming, 23). Again, when the lexical verb is in the perfect(ive) form, the meaning is unambiguously a hodiernal (‘today’) future (44).

- (44) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 23)
Pula e-tlaa-lala e-nele.
 9.rain SP₉-FUT-AUX SP₉.SIT-rain.PFV
 ‘It will rain today.’

As Creissels (forthcoming, 22–23) indicates in his literal translations, the readings with the perfect(ive) make sense, as they indicate that something had occurred, or will have occurred, before sleep/nighttime.

Table 32: Hodiernal future

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
sleep	S31 <i>lala</i>

4.9 ‘Spend the day’ / ‘during the day’ (S20; S30)

Some verbs meaning ‘spend the day’ or ‘spend some time’ have auxiliary functions meaning ‘spend the (whole) day doing’ or ‘during the day’ (S10, S21, S31, S33); this meaning is reported in S31 for perfective *tlhôtse* (cf. Section 2.1 for imperfective readings of *tlhòla* (*thlola*) with unmarked tense and aspect). S33 *hlòla* also has imperfective readings (‘repeatedly’ and ‘permanently’; see Section 2.1). In this context, the forms seem to be more like temporal adverbials and not restricted to past or future.

- (45) Tshivenda S21 (Poulos 1990, 327)²¹
Vhatukana vha-ṭwela u-bambal-a.
 2.boy SP₂-AUX INF-SWim-FV
 ‘The boys spend the day swimming.’

²¹ See Poulos (1990, 327) for arguments for the auxiliary status of *ṭwela*.

Table 33: ‘spend the day’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
spend a/the day / spend time	S10 <i>wiro</i> , <i>wiriro</i> S21 <i>ṭwela</i> ; S31 <i>tlhôtse</i> ; S33 <i>hlòla</i>

5 Mood and modality

A few auxiliary expressions mark illocutionary mood (here, imperatives). Many more relate to modality and the expression of possibility, necessity, and adjacent concepts.

5.1 Illocutionary mood

5.1.1 Imperative / hortative (some notes)

A few auxiliaries in the dataset appear to be frequently used in the imperative, but these also express additional semantics, as with S53 *jinga* ‘nevertheless’ in (46); see Section 7.6. The imperative force comes from the form and context rather than the semantics of the auxiliary, which rather seem to add a manner element or pragmatic nuance to the command.²²

(46) Xitsonga S53 (Cuenod 1967, 60, slight illegibility of translation in source)

jinga *u-tirh-a* *hambi* *va-ku-hlek-a*
AUX.IMP SM2SG.SIT-work-FV although SM2-OM2SG-laugh-FV
‘Go on working although they laugh at you.’

For S41, du Plessis and Visser (1992, 254) note that with second-person marking and followed by a subjunctive form, *ze*, from ‘**come**’, “appears i.a. in commands”, as in (47). It is my impression, supported by discussions with expert colleagues (Onelisa Slater, WhatsApp messages, October 22, 2025), that the contribution of *ze* in this context is not imperative force but rather something temporal or directional.

(47) isiXhosa S41 (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 254)

Ú-zè *ú-búz-è* *kú-yé*.
SP_{2SG}-AUX SP_{2SG}-ask-SBJV 17-PRON₁
‘You must ask at him.’ [sic]

In summary, then, I have not found convincing support for imperative force as the primary function of any Southern Bantu auxiliaries. That said, ‘come’ is a known cross-linguistic source for imperatives (Kuteva et al. 2019, 481).

A few other forms that appear to be related to experiential auxiliaries can also be used in hortative/politeness contexts: S407 *akhe*; S408 *nkhe*; S41 *makhe* (also *maze*; cf. 47); S43 *ake*. Many of these appear to involve the hortative prefix (*m)a-*.

When used in the subjunctive mood, S31 *nê* is described by Cole (1955, 300) as hortative; Creissels (this volume) describes the same form as meaning ‘it would be better if...’.

²²The question of which auxiliaries can be used in commands is given relatively little attention in the descriptive literature, and is a topic worth pursuing further.

5.1.2 Negative imperative: ‘do not’; ‘must not’ (S40, S50)

At least S407, S41, S41A, S42, and S44 use *musa* ‘must not’ as a negative imperative. S53 has *tshùkà* ‘start in surprise; in fear’ (see Section 5.2.2), used with negation marking, as a prohibitive, usually in biblical contexts (Cordelia Nkwinika, p.c. 2024). These forms share a subject with the lexical verb, but are not themselves subject-marked, because imperative forms do not bear subject-marking prefixes. Here, too, the imperative force comes from the verb form, and it could possibly be argued that the auxiliary itself has only negative semantics, but because *musa* is *always* used in negative imperative contexts, I include it here.

(48) isiXhosa S41 (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 262)

Músà úkù-théth-à.
 AUX.IMP INF-speak-FV
 ‘Don’t talk!’ (sg.)

Oosthuysen (2016, 309) reconstructs *musa* as being derived from the causative of *muka/mka* ‘go away’ > causative *mkisa* ‘cause to go away’. This seems to me to be a plausible semantic derivation, although it is not clear to me why the *ki* is elided. I have not found other sources in the literature proposing this grammaticalization pathway. Ziervogel and Mabuza (1976, 120) suggest that *musa* in siSwati (S43) is a borrowing from isiZulu (S42). Overall, the derivation and spread of *musa* appears to be a complex matter and merits further study. Sources also note that *musa* is often realized as a prefix-like element, sometimes shortened, as in, for example, *Mùsúkùthéthà!* or *Súkùthéthà!* ‘Don’t talk!’ (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 262).²³

Also possibly relevant is the chiShona (S10) verb *rega* ‘stop; leave’, which has a meaning akin to the negative imperative (‘stop doing’ > ‘don’t do’) when followed by an infinitive complement (Fortune 1955, 363 considers this a non-auxiliary use), but a hortative-like use (‘let X do Y’) when followed by a subjunctive form.²⁴

Table 34: Negative imperative

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
stop; leave	S10 <i>rega</i>
start in surprise / fear	S53 <i>tshuki</i>
unknown origin (‘cause to go away’?)	S407 <i>musa</i> ; S41 <i>musa</i> ; S41A <i>musa</i> ; S42 <i>musa</i> ; S43 <i>musa</i> ; S44 <i>musa</i>

5.2 Modal

Modal expressions tend to be outliers in Southern Bantu auxiliary systems, with many having different syntactic properties. Some, for example, take full clausal complements; others take

²³ The plural negative imperative is *musani uku-*, which in prefix form appears as *musanuku-* or *sanuku-* (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 262).

²⁴ By this article’s criteria, *rega* + INF would at least marginally be an auxiliary use, since ‘don’t do X’ can apply to situations that have not yet started (see Carbo et al. 2025 for details), but the *rega* + SBJV hortative use is not an auxiliary function, since *rega* has a different subject from that of the subjunctive-marked verb.

object marking and can stand on their own without verbal complements. Because of these features, my impression is that many expressions of ability and necessity are at early stages in the grammaticalization process (cf. Bernander et al. 2022, 23 on East African Bantu), and their auxiliary status is questionable. Nevertheless, they also exhibit some of the properties of auxiliaries (such as their complementation patterns) and I include them for the sake of giving a more complete survey, since they form a system with other modal expressions that are clearly auxiliaries (some of which also alternate with prefixes).

5.2.1 Ability (/ possibility) (S30 incl. K21, S40, S50, S60)

All languages in the sample probably have at least one auxiliary or auxiliary-like expression for ‘ability’ (participant-internal possibility), many of which are also used with other modal flavours (see e.g. Crane, Lubambo et al. 2025). The main sources are ‘**know**’ (at least S31, S32, S40 as a group, and S53) and ‘**be able**’ (at least K21, S31, S33, S407, S408, S41?, S42?, S43, S53, and S63). Some of these forms are likely to be borrowings (e.g. ‘be able’ in S40 is probably from S30), and others may be restricted in their usage and less than fully modal (e.g. possibly ‘know’ in some S30 languages). An example of ‘be able’ is given in (49).

- (49) Sesotho S31 (Chaphole 1988, 55)
U-kgona ho-ngol-a dithoko.
 SP₁-AUX INF-WRITE-FV 10.praise_poem
 ‘He can write praise poems.’

See Crane, Savić et al. (2025) for discussion of the S41 (circumstantial) possibility auxiliary *nak(h)o*, its semantics, and its origins: we analyse *nak(h)o* as deriving from **comitative na-** and a pronominal form.

One form indicates inability. S408 *bhalelwa* ‘be unable’ is the passive form of *bhalela* ‘overcome’.

At least some auxiliaries with an ability/possibility meaning seem sometimes to allow for ellipsis of the lexical verb, when it is contextually salient, similar to English *I can’t*.

Table 35: Ability / circumstantial possibility

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
able	S407 <i>kghona</i> ; S33 <i>kgona</i> ; S62 <i>koja</i> ; K21 <i>kona</i> ; S408 <i>kxhona</i> ; S31 <i>kgôna</i>
know	S43 <i>kwati</i> ; S407 <i>kwazi</i> ; S41 <i>kwazi</i> ; S42 <i>kwazi</i> ; S53 <i>tiva</i> ; S32 <i>tseba</i> ; S408 <i>wati</i> ²⁵
unable	S408 <i>bhalelwa</i>
comitative+pronoun	S41 <i>nak(h)o</i>

²⁵ Although these forms look different, all are clearly related to PB 6209 *jǝjǝb ‘know’. The initial *kw-* on S40 reflexes is the infinitive/class 15 prefix, which has undergone (de)grammaticalization in at least some S40 languages to be analysed as part of the modal verb itself.

5.2.2 Epistemic possibility / probability (S10; S30 incl. K21; S40; S50)

Many languages also have auxiliaries that appear to relate to epistemic possibility and/or probability. A main source seems to be related to the **potential** marker (see Nurse 2008, 251–252 for discussion) (S10? K21, S32), sometimes combined with additional auxiliary material (S41 *ngaba* and *ngahle*; S42 *ngahle* and *ngase*). Other sources mentioned in the literature include ‘**be(come)**’ (S31); ‘**come**’ (S31); ‘**become full; be abundant**’ (S53); ‘**be greedy**’ (S19); ‘**resemble; be like**’ (K21, S41); and possibly ‘**start in surprise**’ (S53 *tshùkà*). Although the meaning of *tshùkà* seems to be more mirative, it is also described as ‘it may happen that’ and ‘by/per chance’ (see Cuenod 1967, 206; Baumbach 1987, 251).

(50) Silozi K21 (Gowlett 1967, 161)

Nì-tá-swànà *nì-zámày-à.*
 SP_{1SG}-FUT-AUX SP_{1SG}.SIT-leave-FV
 ‘I might go.’

Table 36: Epistemic possibility

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
copula	S31 <i>bô</i>
become full / be abundant	S53 <i>tála</i>
be greedy?	S10 <i>karo</i>
resemble / be like	K21 <i>swana</i> ; S41 <i>fana</i>
start in surprise / fear	S53 <i>tshùkà</i>
potential (+ ...)	S10 <i>nge</i> (?) ²⁶ ; K21 <i>ke</i> ; S32 <i>ka</i> S41 <i>ngaba</i> S41 <i>ngahle</i> ; S42 <i>ngahle</i> S42 <i>ngase</i> S31 (<i>e</i>) <i>kete</i>

5.2.3 ‘Apparently’ (S31)

S31 *kete* has the modal-adjacent (evidential?) meaning ‘apparently’ (51).

(51) Setswana S31 (Setshedi 1974, 42)

Ga-re-kete *re-tshab-a* *maphodisa.*
 NEG-SP_{1PL}-AUX SP_{1SG}.SIT-fear-FV 6.police
 ‘We are not apparently scared of the police.’

²⁶This form, translated as ‘seem’ (Fortune 1955, 360), is probably related to a predecessor of the potential marker; see Nurse (2008, 251–252). Some other languages (e.g. isiXhosa S41; see Oosthuysen 2016, 286) have this form meaning ‘seem (like), as if’ in auxiliary-like constructions in which the lexical verb appears in main-verb form (i.e. as an independent clause), thereby differing from the forms focused on in this paper.

Table 37: ‘apparently’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
unknown origin (?experiential + ?)	S31 <i>kete</i>

5.2.4 Bouletic possibility? (‘wish’) (S41)

S41 **potential** *nga* as an auxiliary means ‘wish’; it can also mean ‘as if’ something were the case, both meanings possibly related to the reconstructed sense of non-verbal *nga* as ‘as, like, though’ (see Nurse 2008, 252). This meaning of *nga* requires the potential *nga*- prefix on the lexical verb.

(52) isiXhosa S41 (Oosthuysen 2016, 287)

Si-nga si-nga-bon-a ukumkani,
 SP_{1PL}-AUX SP_{1PL}-POT-see-FV 1A.king
 ‘We wish to see the king.’

Table 38: Bouletic possibility

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
potential	S41 <i>nga</i>

5.2.5 Deontic possibility (S31)

Setshedi (1974, 30) mentions S31 Setswana *mma/mmê*, which can be used either to mean ‘allow (s.o.)’, or as an auxiliary (53).

(53) Setswana S31 (Setshedi 1974, 30).

Phuthego e-mmê e-ntse.
 9.congregation SP₉-AUX SP₉-sit
 ‘The congregation may be seated.’

Table 39: Deontic possibility

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
unknown origin	S31 <i>mma, mmê</i>

5.2.6 Necessity (all groups)

Necessity auxiliaries and auxiliary-like verbs are complex in their syntax and semantics (see e.g. Crane et al. 2024 for a discussion of necessity verbs in Xhosa), and a few (e.g. S40 *funeka*) may fit less neatly into the auxiliary mould, for example, taking expletive rather than agreeing subject prefixes. I include them here to give a fuller picture of the semantic field

They derive from an applicative form of ‘**resemble**’ (at least K21, S30 as a group, S40 as a group, S51, and S63); ‘**appear**’ (S43); an applicative form of ‘**be(come) straight, right (etc.)**’ (K21, S33); ‘**be desirable**’ (S407, S408, S41, S43); ‘**be bound to**’ (S32, S33, S53); ‘**need; lack; want**’ (S33, S40); an applicative (and sometimes passive) form of ‘**stand**’ (S407, S41, S42, S51?); ‘**stay; remain**’ (S42, S43); ‘**have**’ (S31); and several verbs of uncertain origin

(S407 *fuze*; S44 *sake*; S41 *nge* (< pot *nga*-?); S62 *fela* (posited *fa* ‘die’+appl.; see Lanham 1955, 180).

S31 *nama*, from ‘stretch’, may also indicate obligation.

(54) siSwati S43 (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 124)

Bà-vélé bá-m-tsétsís-è.

SP₂-AUX SP₂-OP₁-scold-SBJV

‘It is necessary that they scold him.’

Table 40: Necessity

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
appear	S43 <i>vele</i>
be bound to	S53 <i>boheka</i> S32 <i>tlamegile</i> ; S33 <i>tlameha</i>
die for (?)	S62 <i>fela</i>
comitative (+ cop.) (have)	S31 <i>na (le)</i>
need / lack / want	S33 <i>hloka</i> S40 (e.g. S42) <i>dinga</i>
remain	S42 <i>sale</i> ; S43 <i>sale</i>
resemble / be suitable	K21 <i>swanela</i> ; S31 <i>tšhwanêla</i> ; S32 <i>swanetše</i> ; S33 <i>tšhwanela</i> ; S407 <i>fanele</i> ; S408 <i>fanele</i> ; S42 <i>fanele</i> ; S43 <i>fanele</i> ; S41 <i>fànèlè</i> ; S51 <i>fanela</i> ; S62 <i>yela</i>
be(come) straight / right	K21 <i>lukela</i> ; S33 <i>lokela</i>
be needed / wanted	S407 <i>funeka</i> ; S408 <i>funeka</i> ; S41 <i>funeka</i> ; S43 <i>funeka</i>
stand for (?)	S407 <i>mele</i> ; S41 <i>mel(w)e</i> ; S42 <i>mele</i> ; S51 <i>yimelwa?</i>
unclear origin	S407 <i>fuze</i> S44 <i>sake</i> S41 <i>nge</i> (< potential?)

5.2.7 ‘Intend to’ (S40)

Several S40 languages have auxiliaries indicating intent. They derive from ‘go/be straight; understand; decide’ (S42, S43); ‘hate’ (S42 *zondelele*, from *zonda* ‘hate’; S43 *jinge*); ‘hunt; pursue’ (S42) and ‘stand’ (S408 *jamisela*, from *jama* ‘stand’).

(55) isiZulu S42 (Poulos and Msimang 1998, 332)

Ba-zondelele uku-m-dubul-a.

SP₂-AUX INF-OP₁-shoot-FV

‘They are bent on shooting him.’

Table 41: ‘intend to’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
hate	S42 <i>zondelele</i>
hunt / pursue	S42 <i>zingela, zingele</i>
stand	S408 <i>jamisela</i>
go / be straight; understand; decide	S43 <i>condze</i> ; S42 <i>qonde</i>

5.2.8 ‘Insist on’ / ‘persist’? (S43)

S43 *jinge*, likely from ‘**follow closely, continue**’, is used as an auxiliary to mean ‘insist on’, but also to indicate that something “will happen eventually or that it happens continually or insistently” (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 156; see Section 3.10). The few examples I have found suggest a situation eventually or inevitably brought about through insistence or persistence.²⁷

(56) siSwati S43 (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 119)

Ù-jìngè á-m-àng-è.

SP₁-AUX SP₁-OP₁-kíSS-SBJV

‘He insists on kissing her.’

Table 42: ‘insist on’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
follow closely, continue	S43 <i>jinge</i>

6 Negation**6.1 General negation (S30)**

A few auxiliaries mark straightforward negation. The main source is ‘**refuse**’ (S31, S32). S31 also has *bisa* and *nke*, with unclear origin.

(57) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 30)

Pula e-gana go-w-a.

9.rain SP₉-AUX INF-fall-FV

‘It is not raining.’

‘It refuses to rain.’

Table 44: General negation

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
refuse	S31 <i>gana</i> ; S32 <i>gana</i>
unknown origin	S31 <i>bisa</i> ; S31 <i>nke</i>

²⁷ For example, <https://glosbe.com/ss/en/wajinge> (accessed July 17, 2025).

6.2 ‘never’ (S10, S30, S40, S50)

More common than negation by auxiliary is the combination of negation and temporality, with the meaning ‘never’. Some auxiliaries specifically mark future ‘never’ (i.e. ‘will never’, often also meaning ‘cannot’); others mark past/experiential ‘never’; and others are either underspecified for time, or temporal information is not given in the descriptive literature. Most of these include some kind of negation marker, either integrated as part of the auxiliary, or as a prefix.

6.2.1 Future negative / future ‘never’ (S30, S40)

Many of these forms are built on what appears to be a negated version of the **potential** marker *nga-/ka-*, followed by a marker reminiscent of the **experiential** (*kelkhe*) (S407, S42, S43, S44) or by ‘**come**’ (S407, S43, S44). These markers also commonly convey the negated modal meaning ‘cannot’. Other forms seem to be built on the **persistentive** (‘still’) *sa-* prefix with ‘**come**’ (S41, S42, S43, S44). One form is argued to come from ‘**strike with an object**’ (S31), although it also includes morphology reminiscent of the other forms noted here. It is very common for these forms also to express (future / general) impossibility (58).

(58) Sindebele (Pelling and Pelling 1974, 197)

Si-ngeke si-qed-e lumsebenzi
 SP_{1Pl.}-AUX SP_{1Pl.}-finish-SBJV this.3.work
 ‘We cannot finish this job.’

S31 *lala*, from ‘**sleep**’, also a hodiernal future (Section 4.8.2), has a future ‘never’ reading (along with a hodiernal future negative reading) when used with the potential negative (Creissels forthcoming, 29).

Table 45: Future negative / ‘never’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
comitative (+ COP) + NEG	S31 <i>na (le)</i> + negation
neg. potential + experiential?	S407 <i>ngekhe</i> ; S42 <i>ngeke</i> ; S43 <i>ngeke</i> ; S44 <i>ngeke</i>
neg. potential + come	S43 <i>ngete, (k)a(SC)te</i> ; S407 <i>ngeze</i> ; S44 <i>ngeze, ngaze</i>
persistentive + come	S43 <i>sete</i> ; S41 <i>soze</i> ; S42 <i>soze</i> ; S44 <i>soze</i>
sleep	S31 <i>lala</i>
strike with an object?	S31 <i>kitla, ketla</i>

6.2.2 Past negative / experiential ‘never’ (S30, S40, S50)

Most of these forms seem to be built from experiential *k(h)a* plus a negative or potential marker²⁸ (S31, S407, S41), or ‘come’ plus *nge/nga* (found in at least S407, S41, S41A, S42,

²⁸At this time, I am not sure how to differentiate the two.

S44, S53, with past specified or implied in S41(A)²⁹ and S53). S43 also has *mange*, with *ma* possibly related to ‘stand’. There may be subdistinctions in this group regarding whether the past negation refers to ‘not within a certain past period of time’ and ‘never in the past’: see, for example, Pelling and Pelling (1974, 195–196), who claim that *zange* in S44 Sindebele means only the former; however, the matter is not straightforward, even based on the examples given in the same reference, such as (59). Note that at least some of these auxiliaries, including the one in (59), are also marked for negation prefixally.

- (59) Sindebele S44 (Pelling and Pelling 1975, 196)
Ka-si-zanga si-bon-e inyoka lapha.
 NEG-SP_{1PL} -AUX SP_{1PL} -see-SBJV 9.snake here
 ‘We have never seen a snake here.’

Table 46: Past / experiential ‘never’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
experiential + neg. / pot.?	S31 <i>ke</i> S407 <i>khange</i> ; S41 <i>khanga, khange</i>
come + neg. / pot.?	S41 <i>zange</i> ; S41A <i>zange</i> ; S44 <i>zanga, zange</i> ; S53 <i>zanga</i>
stand? + neg. / pot.?	S43 <i>mange</i>

6.2.3 General ‘never’ (or time unspecified in the dataset) (S10, S30, S40, S50)

This section deals with forms that are either unspecified for time (to the best of my understanding), or where the time is not specified in the references I accessed. Many of the latter may in fact have past or future orientation. A few forms have somewhat clear lexical sources: ‘die’ (S10) and ‘come’ (S408), ‘sit (down); stay’ (S31), while others seem to have similar components to future and past ‘never’, e.g. S31 (negated) *ka*; S408 *tákhe, tékhe, tjokhe*; S42 *bange, bonange, bonaze, kaze, vange*; S53 *kanga, zà*, among others.

S407 *phinde* is used after a negative auxiliary to mean ‘never again’ (see footnote 6).

- (60) SiNdebele S408 (Ziervogel 1959, 156)
A-ń-tjho·ke ndí-ń-món-e.
 NEG-SP_{1SG} -AUX SP_{1SG} -OP₁ -see-SBJV
 ‘I have never seen him.’

- (61) SiNdebele S408 (Ziervogel 1959, 156)
A-ń-te ń-gú:l-e.
 NEG-SP_{1SG} -AUX SP_{1SG} -be(come)_sick-SBJV
 ‘I never get sick.’

²⁹Oosthuysen (2016, 296) describes S41 *khange* as indicating ‘will not even once or never at all’, but Oosthuysen’s examples (and the examples I found in a brief survey of the glosbe online corpus of translations) all seem to have past orientation.

Table 47: General / unspecified ‘never’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
come (+ NEG / POT?)	S408 <i>takhe, tékhe, te, tjhokhe</i> ;
die	S10 <i>fa</i>
experiential + NEG / POT?	S408 <i>khange</i> ; S53 <i>kanga</i>
sit / stay	S31 <i>nne</i> + negation
various / unknown origin	S42 <i>bange, bonange, bonaze, kaze, vange</i> ; S53 <i>zà</i> S407 <i>phinde</i>

7 Evaluative / other adverbial meaning

This category includes meanings that (debatably) do not fit clearly into tense, aspect, modality, and polarity categories. The auxiliaries discussed here have, as what seems to be their primary function, an element of speaker evaluation of the situation referenced (suggesting that it was surprising, it was good, and so forth) or have other adverbial-like meanings (e.g. ‘quickly’). As noted above, some of the TAMP-related auxiliaries mentioned above also have additional meanings, and some of the meanings here also relate to TAMP.

7.1 Mirative / ‘suddenly’ / ‘unexpectedly’ (S10; S30 incl. K21; S40; S50)

A number of auxiliaries in the dataset express a notion of surprise, conveying that something happened suddenly or unexpectedly. Most come from a verb with a meaning along the lines of ‘**fear; take fright; get a start**’ (S31, K21, S33 [with reciprocal marking], S407, S408, S53). Other sources include ‘**leave; go away; depart**’ (S33, S53) and ‘**meet with by chance, suddenly**’ (S10). Kuteva et al. (2019, 483) list mostly grammatical sources for miratives (adversative, inferred evidential, and perfect), but the Southern Bantu lexical sources seem logical, and in any case, these cannot be considered fully fledged grammatical miratives.

Also found are S41 *hle* and S43 *ze*, the latter of which is a borrowing and can indicate surprise or disgust (see Section 3.1). Cole (1955, 299) also notes that S31 *nama* (from ‘**stretch**’) “implies condescension or rather unexpected action” (Setshedi 1974 gives examples with similar readings).

(62) Silozi K21 (Jalla 1917, 43)

Lu-suhane ku-ba-bon-a.
 SP_{1PL}-AUX INF-OP₂-see-FV
 ‘We chanced to see them.’

(63) Setswana S31 (Cole 1955, 299)

Ó-namilê a-kgôn-a ditlhatlhobô.
 SP₁-AUX.PFV SP₁.SIT-succeed-FV 10.exam
 ‘He actually managed to pass the examinations.’

Table 48: Mirative

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
fear	K21 <i>suha, suhana</i> ; S31 <i>tshogana</i> ; S407 <i>thuke</i> ; S408 <i>thuke</i> ; S33 <i>tshoha (tšōha)</i>
leave	S33 <i>tlōha</i> S53 <i>tshika</i>
meet with by chance	S10 <i>yerekana</i>
stretch	S31 <i>nama, namile</i>
come (borrowing)	S43 <i>ze</i>
potential (PFV)	K21 <i>kile</i>
unknown origin	S411 <i>hle</i> (< ‘sit / stay’?)

7.2 ‘Quickly’ / ‘soon’ (S21; S30 incl. K21; S40; S50)

Eleven auxiliaries in the dataset mean ‘quickly’, and sometimes also ‘soon’, making this an important auxiliary function in Southern Bantu. All of those with clear sources come from verbs meaning ‘**hasten**’, ‘**be fast**’, ‘**hurry**’, or similar (K21, S33, S41, S42, S43, S53), although the auxiliaries themselves take many different forms (e.g. S33 *phakisa* vs. S43 *sheshe*). Others are of unclear origin: S408 *tjh(w)e*; S41 *ṭavhanya*; S41 *behle*. Some languages have several auxiliaries with this function (e.g. S41 *khawuleza, tshetsha, and behle*).

(64) siSwati S43 (modified from Nkuna et al. 2021, 231)

Lilanga li-hlala li-sheshe li-shon-e ebusika.
 5.sun SM₅-AUX SM₅-AUX.SBJV SM₅-set-SBJV LOC.14.winter
 ‘The sun always sets quickly in winter.’

Table 49: ‘quickly’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
hurry / be fast	S10 <i>cimbidzo</i> S53 <i>hàtla</i> S41 <i>khawuleza</i> K21 <i>pakisa</i> ; S33 <i>phakisa</i> S43 <i>phange</i> S43 <i>sheshe, shesha</i> ; S41 <i>tshetsha</i> ; S42 <i>sheshe</i>
unknown origin	S41 <i>behle</i> S21 <i>ṭavhanya</i> S408 <i>tjhwe, tjhe</i>

7.3 ‘Do the right thing’ (S20; S40)

A few auxiliaries indicate ‘do the right thing’. Putative sources are ‘**work**’ (S21); ‘**make; do**’ (S21); and ‘**satisfy**’ (S41). These auxiliary constructions are mostly translated as ‘**did well to do X**’, in that the situation turned out well because of that action.

- (65) isiXhosa S41 (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 258)
U-kholisile u-hamb-e kwangonyezi namhlanje...
 SM_{2SG}-AUX.PFV SM_{2SG}-go-SBJV early today
 ‘It is a good thing you left very early today...’

Table 50: ‘do the right thing’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
do / make	S21 <i>ita</i>
satisfy	S41 <i>kholisa</i>
work	S21 <i>shuma</i>

7.4 ‘Do well’ (S30; S40)

Another occasional auxiliary meaning is ‘do well’. One auxiliary has ‘come’ as a source (S33), one comes from ‘improve’ (S10), and one form is of unclear origin (S42 *ive*, which also means ‘do very much’).

- (66) Sesotho S33 (Chaphole 1988, 193)
A-tla a-bu-a Mosotho.
 SP₁.PST-AUX SP₁.CSC-speak-FV 1.Sotho
 ‘He spoke well, the Mosotho.’

Table 51: ‘do well’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
come	S33 <i>tla</i>
improve	S10 <i>natso, nyatso</i>
unknown origin	S42 <i>ive</i>

7.5 ‘Do in vain (fail)’ (S10; S30; S40)

Some auxiliaries indicate that something was attempted but failed, done in vain, or done futilely. This category might be related to ‘almost’ (Section 2.3). Sources include ‘come from’ (S33); ‘resemble’ (S41, S41A); ‘find’ (S41); and a quotative (S10).

S43 *sa* (< ‘dawn’?) is reported to imply continued effort without success. Another form, S43 *batse*, has the same meaning, but does not have the typical complementation patterns of the auxiliaries, although Ziervogel and Mabuza (1976) discuss it under the umbrella of auxiliaries. S43 *sa* has a pattern typical of necessity auxiliary(-like) forms (see Crane et al. 2024), which often take expletive (class 17) subject marking, followed by a subject-agreeing subjunctive-marked lexical verb.

- (67) isiXhosa S41 (Oosthuysen 2016, 293)
Ukuba abafundi a-ba-phulaphul-i u-fumana e-theth-a utitshala.
 if 2.student NEG-SP₂-listen-NEG SP₁-AUX SP₁.SIT-speak-FV 1A.teacher
 ‘If the pupils do not listen the teacher speaks in vain.’

Table 52: ‘do in vain’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
come from	S33 <i>tswa</i>
find	S41 <i>fumana</i>
resemble	S41 <i>fana</i> ; S41A <i>fana</i>
quotative	S10 <i>ti</i>
unclear origin	S43 <i>sa</i> (< dawn?) (S43 <i>batse</i> (< copula?))

7.6 ‘Nevertheless’ (S30; S40; S50)

Three auxiliaries are described as meaning ‘nevertheless’. S42 *dlula* derives from ‘**pass; surpass**’, while other examples are of unclear origin. One of these is S33 *mpa*, meaning “do nevertheless withstanding opposition” (Chaphole 1988, 142, 185, 201). Chaphole notes several related forms, with descriptions suggesting that these other forms might be used more like conjunctions than like auxiliaries proper. The other relevant form is S53 *jinga* ‘nevertheless’ (Baumbach 1987, 250), also used in hortative or imperative contexts to mean ‘make an effort and...; take it upon you to’ (Cuenod 1967, 60).³⁰

(68) isiZulu S42 (Poulos and Msimang 1998, 330)

Wa-m-qand-a wa-dlula wa-yi-shay-a ingane.

SP₁.PST-OP₁-stop-FV SP₁.CSC-AUX SP₁.CSC-OP₉-beat-FV 9.child

‘She stopped him but he beat the child nevertheless.’

Table 53: ‘nevertheless’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
pass / surpass	S42 <i>dlula</i>
unknown origin	S33 <i>mpa</i> S53 <i>jinga</i>

7.7 ‘Rather’ / ‘preferably’ (S10; S30; S40)

Four forms are described as indicating ‘rather’ or ‘preferably’. One is from ‘**spoil**’ (S10), while the others are of unclear origin (S33 *mpa*,³¹ S408 *swe*, S42 *ngamane*).

(69) chiShona S10 (Fortune 1955, 358)

Ndi-nga-ise nda-f-a zangu.

SP_{1SG}-POT-AUX SP_{1SG}.CSC-die-FV indeed?

‘I would rather die.’

³⁰ Perhaps related is S43 *jinge*; see Section 5.2.8.

³¹ Setshedi (1974, 29) translates *mpa* as ‘rather’; see Section 7.6 on ‘nevertheless’ for what is possibly a conjunction built on *mpa*.

Table 54: ‘rather, preferably’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
spoil	S10 <i>iša</i>
unknown origin	S33 <i>mpa</i> S42 <i>ngamane</i> S408 <i>swe</i>

7.8 ‘Just, merely (etc.)’ (S30; S40)

Many auxiliaries are described as meaning ‘just’ or ‘merely’, although these terms are somewhat ambiguous, and most descriptions also include additional senses. I will therefore list the auxiliaries along with their described meanings here. Sources include ‘find’ (S41); ‘resemble’ (S41, S43); ‘finish; end’ (S31, S32, S33?, S407, S408); ‘appear; be born (etc.)’ (S407, S41, S42); ‘go’ (S41); ‘leave; move off’ (S41, S42); ‘refuse; deny’ (S44) ‘suffice’ (S33, S42); and ‘stand’ or ‘stop; halt’(?) (S407, S42, S43, S44). Several auxiliaries are of unclear origin (S10, S32, S407, S41A, S42), although some of these contain components seen in other auxiliaries (e.g. markers reminiscent of the potential or the experiential). Like the range of imperfective meanings seen in Section 2.1, these functions need to be studied in more detail to see to what extent they overlap and to what extent they represent distinct concepts; however, descriptive sources do not provide enough data to do so, and a closer look at (for example) corpus uses is beyond the scope of the present article.

(70) isiZulu S42 (Poulos and Msimang 1998, 333)

U-mane a-khal-e uma si-m-buz-a lokho.
 SP₁-AUX SP₁-CRY-SBJV if SP_{1PL}-OP₁-ask-FV that
 ‘She simply cries if we ask her that.’

(71) Attested meanings (compilations of descriptions across sources):

S33 *anela*: only just be able to do; S42 *anela*, (*a*)*nele*: do nothing but; as soon as
 S10 *bango*: just; precipitately, rashly, without thought; neg: even think of, even begin to
 S41 *fumana*, *fana*: just; merely; carelessly; in vain; irresponsibly; at random³²
 (NB: S41A *fana* ‘do at random’)
 S43 *fane*: simply; merely; might as well
 S31 *fela*: merely; without reason; simply; finally; at last
 S32 *fela*: only [in order to?]
 (S33 *fela*: in fact do; end up doing; do indeed; do in reality)
 S41A *hle*: just
 S42 *hle*, *se*: just; merely
 S407 *je*: just; motivational; meanwhile; so long
 S32 *ke* a little; just³³

³²Oosthuysen (2016, 293) and du Plessis and Visser (1992, 256) are in agreement that a situative complement gives the reading ‘in vain’ (see Section 7.5), but their descriptions of the meanings with subjunctive complements differ slightly, with du Plessis and Visser emphasizing ‘just, merely’, while Oosthuysen highlights the “irresponsible, arbitrary or careless fashion”. These seem to me to be different aspects of the same meaning.

³³This use, described in Lombard et al. (1985, 188), seems to be directly related to the experiential (‘once; at all’ meaning).

- S407 *mane*: just; only; simply; rather
 S42 *mane*: simply; just; intensifies commands or desires; merely
 S43 *mane*: simply; for no reason; merely
 S44 *mane*: just; simply
 S42 *ngake*: just
 S408 *phela*: just; sometimes; simply
 S407 *phele*: just; sometimes; simply
 S42 *phike*: merely
 S42 *simze*: simply; merely
 S41 *suka*: just; merely; (and) then; without reason³⁴
 S42 *suke*: simply; merely; just
 S44 *suke* [with *nje*]: simply; without cause
 S41 *vela*: without any reason; just; start with; do immediately/from the outset; heedlessly, carelessly
 S407 *vele*: of course; just
 S42 *vele*: from the outset; simply; just; merely; of course; naturally
 S41 *ye*: just; merely

Table 55: ‘just, merely’ (etc.)

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
appear	S407 <i>vele</i> ; S42 <i>vele</i> ; S41 <i>vela</i>
finish	S31 <i>fêla</i> ; S32 <i>fêla</i> ; S33 <i>fela</i> (?); S408 <i>phela</i> ; S407 <i>phele</i>
go	S41 <i>ye</i>
leave / move off	S41 <i>suka</i> ; S42 <i>suke</i> ; S44 <i>suke</i>
refuse	S42 <i>phike</i>
resemble	S41A <i>fana</i> ; S43 <i>fane</i>
stand / finish (?)	S407 <i>mane</i> ; S42 <i>mane</i> ; S43 <i>mane</i> ; S44 <i>mane</i>
suffice	S33 <i>anela</i> ; S42 <i>anela</i> , <i>anele</i> , (<i>nele</i>)
unknown origin	S41A <i>hle</i> ; S42 <i>hle</i> / <i>se</i> ; S407 <i>je</i> ; S32 <i>ke</i> ; S42 <i>ngake</i> ; S42 <i>simze</i>

7.9 Emphatic; ‘certainly’ (S30, S40)

A small number of auxiliaries are described as representing something like emphatic certainty. S42, S44 *vele* may be derived from ‘**come forth; appear**’, or, perhaps more likely, may be a borrowing from the Afrikaans emphatic adverb *wel*, which has similar functions; *vele* is also used as an adverb meaning ‘of course; naturally’ in isiZulu (isiZulu.net).³⁵ Other relevant forms include S31 *nta* and S33 *hle/hla*, the latter of which Chaphole (1988) describes as having both emphatic and habitual meaning. These forms have significant form overlap with those in Section 7.8, and the meanings are also likely to be linked. There are also links to modal (necessity) concepts (Section 5.2.6).

³⁴ Du Plessis and Visser (1992, 248) additionally note that *suka* “denotes an element of surprise in the action”.

³⁵ Thanks to Hilde Gunnink (p.c. November 20, 2025) for pointing out this connection.

(72) Sesotho S33 (Chaphole 1988, 53)

O-hle o-se-rek-a sefofane seo?
 SP_{2SG}-AUX SP_{2SG}.SIT-OP₇-buy-FV 7.aircraft DEM₇
 'Are you certainly buying that aircraft?'

Table 56: 'certainly'

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
appear / Afrikaans <i>wel</i>	S42, S44 <i>vele</i>
unclear origin	S31 <i>nta</i> S33 <i>hle, hla</i>

7.10 'Extremely' / 'excessively' / 'completely' (S40)

S41 *shiya* from 'leave behind' has the adverbial meaning 'extremely, to a great extent'. Along the same lines, S41 quotative *tsho* can mean 'to such an extent; excessively', and S41 *betha* (from 'beat') can mean 'excessively' as well as 'at last'.

S42 *shaya/shaye* 'completely' apparently comes from 'strike'. Doke (1992, 207) describes the meaning as "to do a thing completely, with full energy". S10 has *nyanyo* from 'exceed' and *išo* from 'spoil'.

(73) isiZulu S42 (Doke 1992, 207)

U-shaye wa-shantshul-a.
 SP₁-AUX SP₁.CSC-go_off?-FV
 'He went off at full speed.'

Table 57: 'extremely, excessively, completely'

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
exceed	S10 <i>nyanyo</i>
leave behind	S41 <i>shiya</i>
quotative	S41 <i>tsho</i>
beat, strike	S41 <i>betha</i> ; S42 <i>shaya/shaye</i>
spoil	S10 <i>išo</i>

7.11 'At the right time' (S30)

S31 and S33 both have auxiliaries meaning something like 'opportunistically' or 'at the right time'. S31 *jafilê* may be related to *jafa* 'act speedily; do quickly', while S33 *nyafa* and *phaka* are of unknown origin.

(74) Sesotho S33 (Chaphole 1988, 190, typo corrected)

Mosadi a-nyafa a-fihl-a.
 SP₁.WOMAN SP₁-AUX SP₁.SIT-arrive-FV
 'His wife arrived at the right moment.'

Table 58: ‘at the right time’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
quickly	S31 <i>jafilé</i>
unknown origin	S33 <i>nyafa</i> S33 <i>phaka</i>

7.11.1 ‘In someone’s absence’ (S10; S30)

S31 *sala*, from ‘**stay; remain**’, indicates that something took place or will take place in someone’s absence. Creissels (forthcoming, 32) notes that usually “the person in question is not designated explicitly, and his/her identity is inferred from the context”. S10 *sara* (also from ‘**stay; remain**’) seems to have a similar function, although Fortune (1955, 360) describes it as meaning ‘after a separation’.

(75) Setswana S31 (Creissels forthcoming, 32)

Ba-sadile ba-bets-a ngwana wame.
 SP₂-AUX.PFV SP₂.SIT-beat-FV 1.child POSS.PRON_{1/1SG}
 ‘They beat my child during my absence.’

Table 59: ‘in someone’s absence’

Source Meaning	Language / Auxiliary
remain	S10 <i>sara</i> ; S31 <i>sala</i>

7.12 Functions attested for only one lexical item

In this final subsection, I include non-TAMP meanings that were described for only one language in the dataset. Some of these involve one the several meanings of multifunctional auxiliaries, some of which have already been discussed in previous sections. The functions listed here are interesting and merit further investigation, both to better understand their properties and to see whether they are, in fact, more widespread in Southern Bantu (and beyond).

7.12.1 ‘Do further’ / ‘do more than expected’ (S31)

S31 *eketsa* (from ‘**add; increase**’) means ‘do further; act besides’ (cf. Section 3.5) (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 286), as well as ‘do over and above what was expected’ (Chaphole 1988, 86).³⁶

(76) Setswana S31 (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 286)

N-ka-eketsa ka-bu-a.
 SP_{1SG}-POT-AUX SP₁.CSC-speak-FV
 ‘I may speak more.’

7.12.2 ‘At the wrong time’ / ‘inopportunistly’ (S33)

S33 *haba* is described as meaning ‘do inopportunistly’ (Chaphole 1988, 192).

³⁶Doke and Mofokeng give examples like ‘We shall write more’ (1957, 286); Chaphole gives the example ‘Phakwane further hacked his wife with a matchet [sic]’ (1988, 190).

(77) Setswana S31 (Chaphole 1988, 192)

Seka-haba o-bu-e.

NEG.IMP-AUX SP_{2SG}-speak-SBJV

‘Do not speak yet.’ [i.e. it is not yet the right time – Auth.]

7.12.3 ‘Repetition (of undesirable process)’ (S41)

S41 *phikela*, the applicative form of *phika* ‘**contradict**’, indicates that “a usually undesirable process occurs repeatedly” (Oosthuysen 2016, 311).

(78) isiXhosa S41 (Oosthuysen 2016, 311)

UMpayipheli wa-phikela uku-tshay-a endlwini

1A.M SP₁-AUX INF-smoke-FV LOC.9.house.LOC

e-m-qumb-is-a umkakhe

SP₁-SIT-OP₁-get_angry-CAUS-FV 1.his_wife

‘Mpayipheli repeatedly smoked in the house, angering his wife.’

7.12.4 ‘A little’ (S42)

S42 **quotative** *thi* can mean ‘a little’. Canonici (1995, 133) lists the function but does not appear to give an example.

7.12.5 ‘In desperation’ (S33)

S33 *tena* means ‘do in desperation’ as well as ‘to do tiresomely, inappropriately’ (Chaphole 1988, 186, 191). Its source is ‘**annoy**’.

(79) Sesotho S33 (Chaphole 1988, 191)

Ke-tena ke-o-shap-a tjena ka botlokotsebe bona bahao

SP_{1SG}-AUX SP_{1SG}-SIT-OP_{2SG}-lash-FV so about 14.crime PRON₁₄ POSS.PRON_{14/2SG}

‘I end up lashing you in this manner because of your delinquency.’

7.12.6 ‘Be inclined to’ (S43)

S43 *cinetele*, from *cina* ‘**be strong**’, is used to express “an inclination” (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 151) (i.e. ‘she is inclined to do X’).

(80) siSwati S43 (Ziervogel and Mabuza 1976, 151)

U-cinetele ku-phik-a=nje...

SP₁-AUX INF-deny-FV=just

‘He is inclined to deny it...’

7.12.7 ‘Contrary to expectation or right usage’ (S10)

S10 *dzoka*, from ‘**return**’, expresses the sense that “the action indicated by its complement is contrary to expectation or right usage” (Fortune 1955, 359; cf. Section 3.3).

(81) chiShona S10 (Fortune 1955, 359)

Panzimbo poku-p-a muviri wedu vitamins,
16.instead 16.INF-give-FV 3.body POSS.PRON_{3/1PL} vitamins

ti-no-dzoka to-p-a tupukanana.

SP_{1PL}-PRES-AUX SP_{1PL}.OP₃.SIT-give-FV 14.microbes

‘Instead of giving our body vitamins, we instead give them microbes.’ [sic]

7.12.8 ‘Approximately’ (S31)

S31 *nê* (**copula**) is used with a potential (*ka*) prefix to mean ‘about’ or ‘approximately’, followed by another copula (*le*) in the participial form and a number (with a seeming literal meaning of ‘it can/might be [that] it is [this many]’) (see Cole 1955, 300).

(82) Setswana S31 (Cole 1955, 300)

Ò-ka-nê o-le dinyaga di-le mašomê amararo.
SP_{2SG}-POT-AUX SP_{2SG}.SIT-be 10.year SP₁₀.REL-be thirty

‘You are about thirty years of age.’

7.12.9 ‘Always be ready to?’ (S41)

S41 *hlalele/hlelele*, the applicative form of ‘**sit; stay**’ is reported to mean ‘always be ready to’ (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 261). This meaning seems to be clearly derived from the imperfective function of *hlala* ‘sit; stay’.

(83) isiXhosa S41 (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 261)

Bá-hlálélé úkú-mk-à.

SP₂-AUX INF-leave-FV

‘They are always ready to leave.’

7.12.10 ‘For that matter’ (S31)

Setshedi (1974) gives examples of S31 *tswa* (from ‘**go out**’) meaning ‘as it is’ or ‘for that matter’ (1974, 73) and ‘in the meantime’ (1974, 74).

(84) Setswana S31 (Setshedi 1974, 73)

O-tswa o-tshab-a bankane bagago.

SP_{2SG}-AUX SP_{2SG}-fear-FV 2.fellows POSS.PRON_{2/2SG}

‘As it is or for that matter, you are afraid of your equals.’

7.12.11 ‘What else’ (S408)

This meaning is mentioned for *swa* in S408.

(85) Sindebele S408 (Skhosana 2009, 356)

Kwa-swa kwa-yent-w-a njani?

SP₁₇.CSC?-AUX SP₁₇.CSC-do-PASS-FV what

‘What else was done?’

7.12.12 'Whatever, whenever' (S41)

Oosthuysen (2016, 292) mentions this meaning for S41 *sukuba*, apparently the grammaticalization of *suka* 'leave; move off' and the complementizer *ukuba*.

(86) isiXhosa S41 (Oosthuysen 2016, 292)

Ndi-ya ku-ku-xhas-a entweni yonke o-sukuba
 SP_{1SG}-AUX INF-OP_{2SG}-support-FV LOC.9.thing.LOC all₉ SP_{2SG}.REL-AUX
u-y-enz-a.
 SP_{2SG}.SIT-OP₉-do-FV
 'I will support you in whatever thing you do.'

7.12.13 'Even though; although' (S10 + S31?)

S10 has an auxiliary *nyango* that often appears in prefix-like form, with the meaning 'although' or 'even though'. S31 has a form (*e*)*ntswa* with similar function, analysed by Pretorius (1997, 129, 342) as an auxiliary; Cole (1955, 389–390) describes it rather as a "conjunctive possibly of verbal origin", and this analysis seems to me to best match the data as I understand it. Further investigations may uncover more auxiliary-like uses, however.

(87) chiShona S10 (Fortune 1955, 342)

U-ka-nyango=wan-a pfuma dzose
 SP_{2SG}-PST-AUX=find-FV 10.riches all₁₀
 'Even if you have got all riches'

8 Conclusion

Auxiliaries in Southern Bantu are used to express a wide range of meanings, almost certainly wider even than the survey in this article. The most significant recurring auxiliary functions identified in this article are summarized in (88), which lists functions attested in three or more subgroups in the dataset.

(88) Widespread auxiliary functions in Southern Bantu (3+ subgroups)

- i. **aspectual**: 'again'; approximative/avertive; continuous; experiential; phasal polarity (esp. 'already' and 'not yet', possibly 'still'); repeated/habitual
- ii. **sequentiality**: 'until'; 'after, then, consecutive'; 'furthermore'; conditional ('if, in the event of'), 'first, before, begin'; 'meanwhile'
- iii. **tense/time**: relative tense; near future; 'spend / during the day'
- iv. **modality**: ability/ circumstantial possibility; epistemic possibility; necessity
- v. **negation**: never (future / past / general)
- vi. **other**: mirative ('suddenly, unexpectedly'); 'quickly, soon'; 'do well'; 'do in vain' / 'fail'; 'nevertheless'; 'rather, preferably'; 'just, merely'

Table 60 lists the generalized meanings attested in more than one subgroup. It additionally notes whether these meanings are expressed by auxiliaries deriving from more than one lexical source, suggesting an auxiliary concept widespread enough that diverse sources are recruited

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to fill it; and whether, within lexical sources with (roughly) the same translation, non-cognate forms are found, suggesting a recurring cognitive process from source meaning > auxiliary function.

Table 60: Meanings by subgroup and multiplicity of expressions

Meaning	# of subgroups attested	>1 lexical source	Non-cognate forms (with same source translation)
again	6	Y	Y
imperfective (continuative or habitual)	6	Y	Y
relative tense	6	Y	-
approximative, avertive	5	Y	Y
experiential	5	Y	-
quickly	5	Y	Y
until	5	Y	-
ability	4+	Y	-
necessity	4+	Y	Y
after, then, consecutive	4	Y	Y
as soon as	4	Y	-
epistemic possibility	4	Y	-
meanwhile	4	Y	-
mirative	4	Y	Y
near future	4	Y	Y
never	4	Y	-
already	3	Y	-
do in vain	3	Y	-
do well	3	Y	-
first	3	Y	Y
furthermore	3	Y	-
just, merely	3	Y	-
nevertheless	3	Y	-
not yet	3	Y	-
preferably	3	Y	-
spend the day	3	-	Y?
future	2+	Y	-
at night	2	-	-
certainly	2	Y	-
distant past	2	Y	-
do the right thing	2	Y	-

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Meaning	# of subgroups attested	>1 lexical source	Non-cognate forms (with same source translation)
eventually	2	Y	-
immediate/recent past	2	Y	-
in someone's absence	2	-	-
in the end	2	-	Y
last (most recent) time	2	Y	-
neg. imperative	2	Y	-
simultaneous	2	Y	-
still	2	-	Y
conditional	(3)	Y	-

The Eastern Bantu clade to which Southern Bantu belongs appears to have much more constrained auxiliary systems outside of Southern Bantu, both in terms of the number of auxiliaries and in their functions. For example, Gibson (2025) reports that Rangi (F33, Tanzania) has just two auxiliary forms and (citing Guérois 2015) that Cuwabo (P34, Mozambique)³⁷ has three. Much typological work remains to be done (see Gibson 2025, 315–316; Gibson 2019; Bernander et al. 2022), but assuming that descriptions of Eastern Bantu languages are not massively underreporting auxiliary forms,³⁸ this situation raises the question of how the Southern Bantu auxiliary systems came to be: are they retentions from Proto-Bantu (and wider Niger-Congo) – with other Eastern Bantu languages having subsequently simplified their auxiliary inventories – or are they innovations, possibly influenced by historical interactions with speakers of Khoisan languages?

Auxiliary systems in Northwest Bantu languages and other Niger-Congo languages (as well as other languages of Africa) are reported to have many of the properties seen in Southern Bantu auxiliary systems (Creissels et al. 2008, 105–106), including large inventories and functions that go beyond tense, aspect, modality, and polarity.

Table 61 lists functions noted in Southern Bantu and compares them with the brief survey of Emai (Edoid) and several other African languages given in Schaefer and Egbokhare (2025). Omitting from consideration very basic and widespread auxiliary functions such as imperfective (progressive, habitual) aspect, common modal expressions, negation, or tenses such as

³⁷ Cuwabo belongs to the Makhuwa subclade, which is sometimes categorized as Southern Bantu, due to some similarities with Sotho languages. However, the linguistic phylogeny in Gunnink et al. (2023, 96–97) does not support this grouping.

³⁸ Auxiliary systems are understudied across Africa, and perhaps especially in Bantu languages, where elaborate agglutinative verbal systems have received far more attention than have multiverb constructions, so it seems possible that many auxiliary forms have simply been overlooked, underreported, or not considered ‘auxiliaries proper’ and therefore not dealt with extensively in grammatical descriptions. Auxiliary systems in other Eastern Bantu languages may, in fact, be more extensive than is commonly believed. The kinds of auxiliaries described in this paper are extremely common and constitute salient features of Southern Bantu languages, so I find it somewhat unlikely that they would have been totally overlooked in other Eastern Bantu languages. However, areal descriptive traditions can be surprisingly powerful in predetermining what is considered a phenomenon worthy of treatment in a grammar, and we should not take anything for granted.

present or future, about a third of the auxiliary functions attested for Southern Bantu are also found even in Schaefer and Egbokhare's small survey of auxiliaries in Africa.

Table 61: Comparison of attested functions with those mentioned in Schaefer and Egbokhare's (2025) brief survey

Function found in Southern Bantu	Mentioned in Schaefer and Egbokhare (2025)
again	Emai (Edoid) and others
avertive / approximative	Yoruba and others 'almost, nearly'
experiential	Emai (Edoid) <i>mò</i> 'once in past'
already	
still	Nupe and others
not yet (under negation)	(mentioned)
no longer (under negation)	
until	
in the end / at last / end up	Yoruba <i>jàjà</i> 'at last, finally'
after / then / consecutive	Dinka (Nilo-Saharan) <i>look</i> 'do afterwards' <i>jaal</i> 'do next'
subsequent contradictory process	
as soon as	
furthermore	Yoruba <i>túbò</i> 'further, more'?
if / in the event of	
first / before / begin	Nupe and others
meanwhile	
the last time	
simultaneous /while	Emai <i>ghe</i> 'simultaneous'
future, near / soon / immediately	Dinka <i>gwoor</i> 'immediately' <i>daac/laac</i> 'soon'
past, immediate / recent	Dinka <i>pyaac</i> 'have done recently'
past, distant / long ago	
early	Yoruba <i>tètè</i> 'early'
past, hodiernal	
future, crastinal	
at night	
past, hesternal	(mentioned)
future, hodiernal	
eventually	
spend /during the day	
apparently	
possibility, bouletic/wish	
certainly	

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intend to	
insist on / persist	
imperative	Emai
imperative, negative / must not	Emai
mirative	Yoruba <i>dédé</i> ‘suddenly, by chance’
quickly / soon	(very common)
do the right thing	
do well	Dinka <i>nyeek</i> ‘do properly’
do in vain / fail	Yoruba <i>wulè</i> ‘in vain’
nevertheless	
rather / preferably	Emai <i>wòò</i> ‘preferably’
just / merely	Yoruba <i>kòn</i> ‘merely, just’
at the right time	
in s.o.’s absence	
do further	Yoruba <i>túnbò</i> ‘further’
at the wrong time	
repetition (undesirable)	
a little	Emai <i>zèzè</i> ‘a bit, not quite’
completely	
extremely	Emai <i>tótóbò</i> ‘great intensity’?
in desperation	
happen by chance	Yoruba <i>dédé</i> ‘by chance’
be inclined to	
be pleased to	
randomly	Yoruba <i>sáà</i> ‘for no purpose’
contrary to expectation or right usage	
approximately	
always ready to	
for that matter	
what else?	
whatever, whenever	

It may therefore be that the Southern Bantu systems are at least partially retentions from Proto-Bantu and even from broader Niger-Congo, and that the systems in many other East Bantu languages have diminished over the years. Such a scenario would probably have required multiple processes of loss and simplification over the years, since Eastern Bantu as a group is significantly more diverse than is its Southern subclade. That is, ‘unusual’ auxiliary functions seem to be common across Africa, and rather than asking why they are present in Southern Bantu, the more pertinent question might turn out to be why they seem to be absent in some other Bantu subgroups.

Another scenario is that extensive auxiliary systems are common innovations across Africa, including in Southern Africa, possibly supported in Southern Africa by contact with speakers of Khoisan languages, which also make extensive use of multiverb constructions (Güldemann and Fehn 2017; Fehn and Phiri 2022), although their semantics are underdescribed. Contact with speakers of Khoisan languages played a role in the development of many distinctive Southern Bantu features (see e.g. Pakendorf et al. 2017). Although many Southern Bantu auxiliaries seem to be traceable to Proto-Bantu origins in their forms (Gunnink 2023; Carbo et al. 2025), and there is little evidence for the direct borrowing of auxiliaries, the importance of multiverb constructions in these languages may have contributed to the retention or (re)introduction of certain auxiliary constructions in Southern Bantu. This article provides a basis for comparing auxiliary concepts found in Southern Bantu with those found in other languages in the area, to determine the plausibility of this scenario.

This article is meant to be an initial step in the bigger project of understanding why and how elaborate auxiliary systems arose and are maintained in Southern Bantu languages, with this comparative overview of Southern Bantu auxiliary semantics enabling more precise comparison with other systems. I hope this work can be used to spur further study of the Southern Bantu systems, refining and correcting the data and generalizations presented here, and testing for the presence of auxiliaries and their functions in languages where they are not yet attested, making use of the known forms and their lexical sources as possible hints. I also hope that it will aid in future studies that aim to disentangle some of the more complex semantic fields (e.g. the imperfective in Section 2.1 and ‘just, merely’ in Section 7.8), as well as studies tracing semantic pathways between lexical sources and auxiliary functions.

Glosses and abbreviations

1A noun class 1a; 7 noun class 7 (etc.); 1PL first person plural; 1SG first person singular; ALT alterative; ASSC associative; AUX auxiliary; COM comitative; CONJ conjunction; CSC consecutive; DEM demonstrative; FUT future; FV final vowel; IMP imperative; INF infinitive; LOC locative; NEG negative; OP₁ object prefix, class 1 (etc.); PASS passive; PB Proto-Bantu; PERS persistent; PFV perfective; POSS possessive; PRON pronoun; POSS.PRON_{7/1} possessive pronoun, class 7 possessee, class 1 possessor; POT potential; PST past; RECPST recent past; REL relative; SBJV subjunctive; SIT situative; SP_{1SG} subject prefix, first person singular (etc.); TAMP tense, aspect, mood and polarity

Glossing conventions

I have occasionally used rough English equivalents for grammatical categories when doing so made the examples easier to follow and the grammatical specifics were not central to understanding the example (or, a few times, if I was not certain about the underlying grammatical structures). For verbal complements of auxiliaries, I gloss the infinitive form on the infinitive prefix. In general, consecutive, situative, and subjunctive forms concern the whole verb form and not a specific morpheme, raising the conundrum of where to mark them, especially when the forms themselves are not segmentally distinct from main-clause indicative forms. For the consecutive and situative forms, I gloss them on the subject prefix, since this is where segmental changes, if any, occur. For subjunctive forms, I gloss them on the final vowel (usually *-e*), as this is the most consistent segmental indicator of subjunctive mood.

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Editorial note

Thera Marie Crane is currently serving as an Editor-in-Chief of the *Nordic Journal of African Studies* and as an editor of this special issue. This article was subject to the same double-blind review process as all other articles in this issue, and the author had no access to reviewer information.

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Appendix A: Table with functions and corresponding auxiliaries.

This table omits S51, which has only three auxiliaries in the dataset, and S41A, which does not have much documentation and is generally rather similar to – although not identical to!– S41).

Function	S10	S21	K21	S31	S32	S33	S407	S408	S41	S42	S43	S44	S53	S62	Sect.
Imperfective (various senses)	<i>gara garo pota ramba zivo, ziviro</i>	<i>dzula dzulela ɟwa</i>	<i>atisa na nze swala tola</i>	<i>(n)ntse aga agile atisa êta fêla ka na (le) nama nê nê nna; (n)ntse nne nnela tlê tlhôla tsamaya tshela</i>	<i>dula hlwa tlwaetše</i>	<i>atisa be dulela ëe ke ne nna nne ya ye</i>	<i>hlale hle nonde vame vane</i>	<i>hlalela hleli hlwe, hlwa nja nojwa phele se swe</i>	<i>dla hamba hlala kholisa mana sólókò ya</i>	<i>damane /damene dane de hambe hlale hlalele helzi kholisa libele lokhu (P&M; Doke); lo: (Doke) vama zinge</i>	<i>hambe hlala hle kadze solo ye</i>	<i>hlala hlezi</i>	<i>hámba phika tála támà tshàmala / tshàmela</i>	<i>ba na ra talela</i>	2.1
again	<i>wiro, wiriro</i>	<i>dovha</i>	<i>buela ekeza kuta</i>	<i>boa/ boela</i>		<i>boela phêta</i>	<i>buye</i>	<i>buya</i>	<i>buya phinde</i>	<i>buye phinde</i>	<i>buye, buya phindze</i>	<i>buya phinde</i>	<i>èngeta, engete tlhèlà</i>	<i>òwelela</i>	2.2
almost / about to	<i>karo</i>		<i>bata li</i>	<i>batla loetsa rata senka tsile</i>	<i>nyakile</i>	<i>batla ratla</i>	<i>pheze</i>	<i>phase, phoswe, phoso</i>	<i>phantsa, phantse</i>	<i>cishe funa phonse, phose thanda</i>	<i>cishe phose</i>	<i>phose</i>	<i>phòse</i>	<i>haja</i>	2.3
experiential	<i>ti</i>	<i>vhuya</i>		<i>kilê, ekilê</i>	<i>kilê</i>	<i>ka</i>	<i>khe</i>	<i>biyo kade khe</i>	<i>khe</i>	<i>ke</i>	<i>ke, se</i>	<i>ke</i>	<i>khànga</i>		2.4
already	<i>piŋgo</i>		<i>se</i>	<i>sêtswe, setswe</i>	<i>šetše</i>	<i>se</i>	<i>se sele</i>	<i>sele biyo</i>	<i>se sele</i>	<i>se</i>	<i>khatsi se</i>	<i>se</i>			2.5.1
still			<i>nze</i>	<i>ntse</i>				<i>se?</i>				<i>lokhe, lokhu</i>			2.5.2
not yet (under negation)	<i>ti</i>			<i>ise</i>	<i>ešo</i>			<i>biyo tjho</i>				<i>lokhe, lokhu?</i>			2.5.3
no longer				<i>tlhole</i>		<i>ntse</i>									2.5.4

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Function	S10	S21	K21	S31	S32	S33	S407	S408	S41	S42	S43	S44	S53	S62	Sect.
(under negation)															
until	<i>dzimara</i> <i>dakaró</i>		<i>be</i> <i>fetela</i> <i>te</i>	<i>fitlhêla</i> <i>tla</i> <i>tsamaya</i>	<i>tlê</i>		<i>ze</i>	<i>te</i>	<i>de</i>	<i>ze</i>	<i>dzine,</i> <i>dzimane,</i> <i>dzimate,</i> <i>ndzibane,</i> <i>ndzimate</i> <i>te</i> <i>za</i>	<i>ze</i>	<i>kála, ká</i> <i>kóndza</i>	<i>ate</i>	3.1
eventually				<i>fêla, felela</i> <i>nama</i>	<i>bea</i>	<i>ba</i>	<i>ze</i>	<i>te</i>	<i>hla, hle</i>						3.10
in the end / at last / end up	<i>dzimara</i> <i>dakaró</i>								<i>phetha</i>						3.11
after / then consecutive	<i>bva</i> <i>ti</i> <i>wana</i> <i>(šiko)</i>	<i>kona</i> <i>namba</i>		<i>ba</i> <i>feta</i> <i>fitlha</i> <i>se-na, sena</i> <i>tla</i> <i>tlê</i>	<i>bile</i> <i>nama</i> <i>napa</i> <i>šala</i>		<i>fike</i> <i>sale</i> <i>suke</i>	<i>fike</i> <i>sala?</i> <i>suke,</i> <i>suka</i> <i>ri?</i>	<i>andula</i> <i>khova</i> <i>sala</i> <i>za</i>	<i>buye</i> <i>nce</i> <i>qede</i> <i>sale</i> <i>suke</i> <i>thi</i>	<i>fika, efika</i> <i>suka, esuka</i>				3.2
subsequent contradictory process									<i>suke</i>						3.3
as soon as	<i>šiko</i> <i>mba?</i>		<i>mana</i>			<i>hana</i>				<i>nele</i> <i>(anele?)</i>		<i>anela</i> <i>nela</i> <i>hle?</i>	<i>jegela?</i>		3.4
furthermore		<i>namba</i>		<i>bile</i>		<i>eketsa</i>		<i>nambha</i>	<i>qokélà</i> <i>ye</i>						3.5
conditional: if / in the event of	<i>(ti)</i>			<i>(re)</i>				<i>(ri)</i>		<i>(thi)</i>	<i>(hleze)</i> <i>(na)</i>				3.6
first / before / begin	<i>tanğa</i>					<i>fihla</i>	<i>phanga</i> <i>qala</i>		<i>vela, vele</i>	<i>fike</i> <i>gale</i> <i>qale</i> <i>vele</i>	<i>cale</i>	<i>qala</i>			3.7
meanwhile	<i>sano</i>			<i>nama</i> <i>sala</i>				<i>jwa</i>		<i>feta</i> <i>sala</i>			<i>pfâ</i>		3.8
simultaneous / while			<i>li</i>	<i>tla</i> <i>eta?</i>							<i>tsi</i>				3.9
relative tense	<i>ŋge, ŋga</i>		<i>li</i>												4.1

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Function	S10	S21	K21	S31	S32	S33	S407	S408	S41	S42	S43	S44	S53	S62	Sect.
(besides 'be(come)')															
future (incomplete list)					<i>tla</i>				<i>ya</i>						4.2
future, near / soon / immediately	<i>bva?</i> <i>fuma</i> <i>mba?</i>	<i>ɬuwa</i>	<i>tuha</i>	<i>tloga</i> <i>tsamaela</i> <i>ya</i>	<i>tloga</i>									<i>jegela?</i>	4.3
past, immediate / recent				<i>ilê</i> <i>tswa</i>	<i>tšwa</i>		<i>sanda</i>	<i>sanda</i>	<i>sandula</i>	<i>sanda</i>		<i>sanda</i>			4.4
past, distant / long ago	<i>ɱguwa</i>			<i>sa-le</i>						<i>kade</i>	<i>kadze</i>				4.5
the last time				<i>sa-le</i>					<i>ggibela</i>						4.6
early	<i>fumo</i>			<i>phakêla</i>		<i>tsoha</i>									4.7
past, hodiernal				<i>phaketse</i> <i>tsogile</i>											4.7.1
future, crastinal				<i>phakêla</i> <i>tsoga</i>											4.7.2
at night		<i>lala</i>	<i>lobala</i>	<i>lala</i>	<i>lala</i>	<i>lala</i>									4.8
past, hesternal				<i>letse</i>											4.8.1
future, hodiernal				<i>lala</i>											4.8.2
spend / during the day	<i>wiro</i> , <i>wiriro</i>	<i>ɬwela</i>		<i>tlhotse</i> <i>(tlhola)</i>		<i>hlôla</i>									4.9
imperative, negative / must not	<i>rega</i>						<i>musa</i>		<i>musa</i>	<i>musa</i>	<i>musa</i>	<i>musa</i>	<i>tshuki</i>		5.1.2
possibility, ability			<i>kona</i>	<i>itse</i> <i>kgôna</i>	<i>kgona</i> <i>tseba</i>	<i>kgona</i>	<i>kghona</i> <i>kwazi</i>	<i>kxhona</i> <i>wati</i>	<i>kwazi</i> <i>nak(h)o</i>	<i>kwazi</i>	<i>kwati</i>		<i>tiva</i>	<i>koja</i>	5.2.1
possibility, epistemic / probability	<i>karo</i>		<i>swana</i>	<i>bô</i> <i>e kete, ekete</i> <i>ka-tla</i>	<i>ka</i>				<i>fana</i> <i>nga+ba</i> <i>ngahle</i>	<i>ngahle</i> <i>ngase</i>			<i>tála</i> <i>tshùkà</i>		5.2.2
apparently				<i>kete</i>											5.2.3
possibility, bouletic / wish									<i>nga</i>						5.2.4
possibility, deontic				<i>mma</i> <i>mmê</i>											5.2.5
necessity			<i>lukela</i> <i>swanela</i>	<i>na (le)</i> <i>tšhwanêla</i>	<i>swanetše</i> <i>tlamegile</i>	<i>hloka</i> <i>lokela</i> <i>tlameh</i> <i>a</i> <i>tshwanela</i>	<i>fanele</i> <i>funeka</i> <i>fuze</i> <i>mele</i>	<i>fanele</i> <i>funeka</i>	<i>fânèlè</i> <i>funeka</i> <i>mel(w)e</i> <i>nge</i>	<i>dinga</i> <i>fanele</i> <i>mele;</i> <i>melwe</i> <i>sale</i>	<i>fanele</i> <i>funeka</i> <i>sale</i> <i>vele</i>	<i>sake</i>	<i>boheka</i>	<i>fela</i> <i>yela</i>	5.2.6

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Function	S10	S21	K21	S31	S32	S33	S407	S408	S41	S42	S43	S44	S53	S62	Sect.
intend to								<i>jamisela</i>		<i>qonde zingela, zingele zondelele</i>	<i>condze</i>				5.2.7
insist on / persist											<i>jinge?</i>				5.2.8
negation				<i>bisa gana nke</i>	<i>gana</i>										6.1
never, future (some forms involve additional morphology)				<i>kitla, ketla lala na (le) +negation</i>			<i>ngekhe ngeze</i>		<i>soze</i>	<i>ngeke soze</i>	<i>ngete, (ka)(SC)te →kasite, asite, kete, ete sete</i>	<i>ngeke ngeze, ngaze soze</i>			6.2.1
never, past / experiential (some forms involve additional morphology)				<i>ke</i>			<i>khange</i>		<i>zange</i>				<i>zanga</i>		6.2.2
never (general / unspecified) (some forms involve additional morphology)	<i>fa</i>		<i>ke nne + neg.</i>				<i>zange</i>	<i>khange táke, tékhe te tjhokhe</i>	<i>khange (etc.)</i>	<i>bange bonange bonaze kaze vange zange</i>	<i>mange ngeke</i>	<i>zanga, zange</i>	<i>kanga zà</i>		6.2.3
mirative (suddenly, by chance, etc.)	<i>yerekana</i>		<i>kile suha, suhana</i>	<i>nama, namilê tshogana</i>		<i>tlôha tshoha (tšôha)</i>	<i>thuke</i>	<i>thuke</i>	<i>hle</i>		<i>ze</i>		<i>tshika</i>		7.1
quickly / soon	<i>cimbidzo</i>	<i>javhany a</i>	<i>pakisa</i>			<i>phakis a</i>		<i>tjhwe, tjhe</i>	<i>behle khawulez a tshetsha</i>	<i>sheshe</i>	<i>phange sheshe, shesha</i>		<i>hàtla</i>		7.2
do the right thing		<i>ita shuma</i>							<i>kholisa</i>						7.3
do well	<i>natso, nyatso</i>					<i>tila</i>				<i>ive</i>					7.4
do in vain / fail		<i>ti</i>				<i>tswa tswats wa</i>			<i>fumana, fana</i>		<i>batse sa</i>				7.5

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Function	S10	S21	K21	S31	S32	S33	S407	S408	S41	S42	S43	S44	S53	S62	Sect.
nevertheless						<i>mpa</i>				<i>dlule</i>			<i>jinga</i>		7.6
rather / preferably	<i>iša</i>			<i>mpa</i>				<i>swe</i>		<i>ngamane</i>					7.7
just / merely	<i>bangō</i>			<i>fēla</i>	<i>fēla ke (kê)</i>	<i>anela fela?</i>	<i>je mane phele vele</i>	<i>phela</i>	<i>fana fumana suka vela ye</i>	<i>anela, anele, (nele) hle / se mane ngake phike simze suke vele</i>	<i>fane mane</i>	<i>mane suke</i>			7.8
emphatic / certainly				<i>nta</i>		<i>hla</i>				<i>vele</i>		<i>vele</i>			7.9
extremely / excessively / completely	<i>išo nyanyo</i>								<i>betha shiya tsho</i>	<i>shaya, shaye</i>					7.10
at the right time				<i>jafilê</i>		<i>nyafa phaka</i>									7.11
in s.o.'s absence	<i>sara</i>			<i>sala</i>											7.11.1
do further						<i>eketsa</i>									7.12.1
for that matter				<i>tswa</i>											7.12.10
what else?								<i>swa</i>							7.12.11
whatever, whenever									<i>sukuba</i>						7.12.12
although	<i>nyango</i>			<i>((e)ntswa?)</i>											7.12.13
at the wrong time						<i>haba?</i>									7.12.2
repetition (undesirable)									<i>phikela</i>						7.12.3
a little										<i>thi</i>					7.12.4
in desperation						<i>tena</i>									7.12.5
be inclined to											<i>cinele</i>				7.12.6
contrary to expectation or right usage	<i>dzoka</i>														7.12.7
approximately				<i>nê</i>											7.12.8
always ready to									<i>hlalele, hlelele</i>						7.12.9

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Appendix B: Data sources

Language	References
Central Shona [mostly Zezuru] (S10/S12, sna)	Fortune (1955)
Tshivenda (S21, ven)	Makwarela (1992); Netshisaulu et al. (2021); Poulos (1990); Ziervogel et al. (1972)
Silosi (K21, loz)	Burger (1960); Fortune (1977); Gowlett (1967); Jalla (1917, 1936, 1982); O’Sullivan (1993)
Setswana (S31, tsn)	Cole (1955); Creissels (forthcoming); Pretorius and Berg (2019); Pretorius (1997); Setshedi (1974)
Sesotho sa Leboa [N. Sotho] (S32, nso)	Kriel (1976); Lombard et al. (1985); Mphasha et al. (2021); Poulos and Louwrens (1994); Ziervogel and Mokgokong (1985)
Sesotho [S. Sotho] (S33, sot)	Chaphole (1988); Doke and Mofokeng (1957)
isiNdebele [S. Ndebele] (S407, nbl)	Crane, Lubambo et al. (2025); Iziko lesiHlathululi-mezwi sesiNdebele (2006)
Sindebele [N. Ndebele] (S408, no ISO)	Skhosana (2009); Ziervogel (1959); author’s fieldnotes
isiXhosa (S41, xho)	Crane et al. (2024); Crane, Savić et al. 2025); du Plessis and Visser (1992); Oosthuysen (2016); Tshabe and Shoba (2006); Mini et al. (2003); Pahl et al. (1989)
isiMpondo (S41a, no ISO)	Cantrell (1946)
isiZulu (S42, zul)	Canonici (1995); Doke and Vilakazi (1972); Doke (1992 [1927]); https://isizulu.net ; Mkhathshwa (1991); Poulos and Msimang (1998)
siSwati (S43, ssw)	Gibson and Marten (2016); Gibson and Riedel (2021); Rycroft (1981); Taljaard et al. (1991)
Sindebele [Ndebele of Zimbabwe] (S44, nde)	Pelling (1966, 1971); Pelling and Pelling (1974); Pietraszko (2017)
Xitswa (S51, tsc)	Persson (1932)
Xitsonga (S53, tso)	Baumbach (1987); Crane, Lubambo et al. (2025); Cuenod (1967); Lee and Hlungwani (2015)
Gitonga (S62, toh)	Lanham (1955)

Dedicated Auxiliaries in Tswana (Bantu S31)

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Abstract

This article discusses the subclass of Tswana auxiliaries that cannot be analysed as resulting from the grammaticalization of regular forms of verbs also used predicatively in the present state of the language. It describes the general characteristics of the dedicated auxiliaries, their individual properties and their possible etymologies. No generalization is possible about the way dedicated auxiliaries may depart morphologically from the regular inflection of synthetic verb forms, and there is a sharp contrast between a group of three auxiliaries occurring in a variety of tense forms each, and the other ones, which have a very limited number of possible tense forms. Each of the auxiliaries selects particular forms of the lexical verb (either infinitive, circumstantial, sequential, or subjunctive). The negation of the analytic tenses formed by means of auxiliaries can often be obtained by putting the lexical verb in the negative form without modifying the auxiliary, but never by putting the auxiliary in the negative form without modifying the lexical verb.

Keywords: Bantu, Tswana, ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions, dedicated auxiliaries, negation

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1 Introduction

Some of the auxiliary verbs found in Tswana coincide with regular inflected forms of a verb also attested with predicative uses, i.e., a verb found in clauses in which it determines the type of event denoted by the clause and assigns semantic roles to NP referents. For example, (1a) is a clause projected by the verb *aga* [áχá] ‘build’, in which the noun phrases *batho ba* [bà^hò bá] ‘those people’ and *lesaka* [lisàká] ‘kraal’ express the semantic roles ‘builder’ and ‘thing being built’ that constitute the argument structure of this verb. By contrast, in (1b), the same verb occurs in a construction in which its contribution is limited to adding an aspectual specification to the event denoted by another verb.

(1) a. *Batho ba ba aga lesaka.*

bà-t^hò bá 'bá-áχá lí-sà:ká
 PL-person(2) CL2.DEM SI:CL2-build.PRS SG-cattle.kraal(5)
 ‘Those people are building a cattle kraal.’

b. *Mhero o aga o tlhoga.*

m-hèrò ó-áχà ó-t^hò:χà
 SG-weed(3) SI:CL3-build.PRS SI:CL3-grow.PRS.CIRC
 ‘Weeds don’t stop growing.’

However, ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions syntactically and semantically comparable to (1b) may also involve ‘dedicated auxiliary verbs’, whose forms do not coincide with those of verbs used predicatively in the present state of the language.

This article describes the dedicated auxiliary verbs of Tswana. It complements an article on auxiliarization in Tswana (Creissels forthcoming 2026) in which I discuss in detail the Tswana verbs that can by themselves project clauses in which they assign semantic roles to the referents of noun phrases, but are also used as auxiliaries in some of their regularly inflected forms, like *aga* [áχá] in (1).¹

The discussion in Sections 3 to 12, which constitute the main body of the article, is limited to dedicated auxiliaries, but Section 2 summarizes the necessary background information already presented in Creissels (forthcoming 2026) about the ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ construction, and the complete list of Tswana auxiliaries (including those discussed in Creissels forthcoming 2026) is summarized in the Appendix.

The data analysed in this article were either provided to me directly by five Tswana consultants, or taken from a variety of written sources and checked (and sometimes adapted) with the help of the same consultants, who are native speakers of the Ngwaketse and Ngwato varieties of Tswana. In all cases, the phonetic transcription reflects the pronunciation of the consultants with whom they were elicited. Among my consultants, I observed no variation that might have an impact on the analyses presented in this article, but in written sources I also came across forms or constructions that are not actively used by my consultants. They are presumably

¹ For an overall presentation of Tswana morphosyntax, see Cole (1955), Creissels (2003), and Krüger (2006, 2013a, 2013b). For a systematic presentation of the inflection of the synthetic verb forms of Tswana, see Creissels (2006), for a detailed discussion of the tonal morphology of Tswana verbs, see Creissels et al. (1997), and for details on the conjoint vs. disjoint contrast in Tswana, see Creissels (2017a). Pretorius (1997) is the main reference on Tswana auxiliaries.

specific to other dialects, and would require further investigation with speakers of the relevant Tswana varieties.

As regards the presentation of the examples, given the complexity of the tonal morphology of Tswana verbs and the pervasiveness of fusion and multiple exponence at segmental level (Creissels 2006), a decomposition of verb stems into morphs would not be of much help for the readers (and could even be confusing) in the absence of a detailed discussion of multiple exponence and of the role played by tonal variations that cannot be analysed in terms of tonal interaction between morphs. This is the reason why, in the glossing of the examples presented in this article, verb stems are not segmented into morphs, and the grammatical meanings expressed morphologically that have no straightforward concretization as prefixes or post-finals are simply enumerated after the lexical gloss of the verb form, separated from the lexical gloss and from each other by dots.

2 General properties of Tswana auxiliary verbs

In this article, as in Creissels (forthcoming 2026), the term ‘auxiliary verb’ without further specification refers to a class of Tswana words whose distinctive property is that they occupy the first position in two-word sequences meeting the following conditions:

1. The first word of the sequence (the ‘auxiliary verb’) does not necessarily display full regular verb inflection, but it shows at least one of the regular paradigms of obligatory subject indexes that characterize Tswana verbs.
2. The second word of the sequence (the ‘lexical verb’) is a regular inflected form of a verb that can also be found in monoverbal constructions.
3. The auxiliary verb and the lexical verb cannot be analysed as acting separately as clause nuclei; taken together they project a single clause whose structure is not different from that of clauses projected by synthetic verb forms.

Moreover, Tswana has several derivational suffixes encoding valency operations (reciprocal, decausative, causative, applicative, and passive), but does not have voice auxiliaries, which means that all Tswana auxiliaries form with the lexical verb a construction whose valency properties, both formally and semantically, are exactly the same as those of the lexical verb. In the ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ construction, the auxiliary plays no role in the selectional restrictions on the nominal terms of the clause; it does not contribute to participant structure (or ‘argument structure’) and cannot have its own modifiers. In particular, the subject NP that may precede the auxiliary and the subject index that constitutes an obligatory element of the auxiliary represent a participant whose semantic role is fully identical to that expressed by the subject of the lexical verb in monoverbal constructions.

The general type of construction ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ as defined above shows variation as regards the following two properties:

- depending on the auxiliary, the lexical verb may be in one of the following forms: infinitive, circumstantial,² subjunctive, or sequential;³

²For a detailed analysis of the specificity of the circumstantial mood (aka situative) and of the relationship between indicative, circumstantial and relative verb forms in Tswana, readers are referred to Creissels (2024b).

³The forms of the sequential mood mark non-initial clauses in clause chains referring to sequences of events in which the verb of the first clause is in a form of the indicative mood. The sequential mood consists of two tenses,

- some auxiliary verbs (those discussed in this article) are dedicated auxiliaries that do not coincide with regularly inflected forms of a verb with the ability to project clauses by itself, whereas some others (those discussed in Creissels forthcoming 2026) are identical to inflected forms of a verb that has the ability to act by itself as the predicative nucleus of a clause.

Moreover, as will be described in detail in Sections 3 to 12, morphologically, some of the dedicated auxiliaries have a morphological structure fully identical to that of regular verb forms acting as the predicative nucleus of clauses, whereas some others variously depart from the regular structure of the verb forms that lend themselves to a predicative use.

Readers are referred to Creissels (forthcoming 2026) for a detailed discussion of the following points: the dual behaviour of the verbs that can be used both predicatively and as auxiliaries (Creissels forthcoming 2026, Section 3.2), the distinction between synthetic verb forms and ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions (Creissels forthcoming 2026, Section 3.3), the distinction between monoclausal constructions involving auxiliaries and biclausal constructions (Creissels forthcoming 2026, Section 3.4), subject indexation in the ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ construction (Creissels forthcoming 2026, Section 3.5), object indexation in the ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ construction (Creissels forthcoming 2026, Section 3.6), the auxiliary as the syntactic head of the ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ construction (Creissels forthcoming 2026, Section 3.7), and recursivity of the ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ construction (Creissels forthcoming 2026, Section 3.8).

3 General properties of the dedicated auxiliaries

As already mentioned, Creissels (forthcoming 2026) discusses in detail the auxiliaries that coincide with regular inflected forms of verbs that can also be used predicatively in the present state of Tswana. The remainder of this paper is devoted to a systematic description of the dedicated auxiliaries and to a discussion of their possible etymology.

3.1 Subject indexation

The only aspect of verb morphology shared by all the auxiliaries, including those that do not have the ability to project clauses by themselves, is the obligatory subject index prefixed to the stem. Moreover, the subject indexes prefixed to auxiliaries are always perfectly regular, both at segmental and tonal level. Consequently, the selection of a particular set of subject indexes is essential for the identification of the morphological nature of auxiliary forms.

3.2 Irregularities and defectiveness in the inflection of dedicated auxiliaries

Irregularities in the tone pattern and the final vowel of the stem are common among dedicated auxiliaries, and do not have obvious historical explanations.

In particular, the final vowel of several dedicated auxiliaries is invariably realized with a L tone, even in contexts in which the general rules of tone spreading would predict the spreading of a preceding H tone. However, the tone pattern of auxiliary forms is often essential to ensure the distinction between the different possible forms of a given dedicated auxiliary.

As regards the final vowels of the dedicated auxiliaries, they often do not show the alternations that help to identify the morphological nature of verb forms in regular verb inflection.

labeled here sequential past (used with reference to past or conditional events) and sequential future (used with reference to future or habitual events).

Moreover, the auxiliaries *bo* [bò] and *ne* [nè] have the particularity that their vowel may undergo regressive assimilation. However, this assimilation is generally optional, and in the examples quoted in the following sections, it is only taken into account in the contexts where it has a regular character.

As regards the range of their possible inflected forms, all dedicated auxiliaries are defective. However, they show important variation in their inflectional potential, and from this perspective, they can be divided into two groups: *bo* [bò] (§4), *ne* [nè] (§5) and *ka* [ká] (§6) occur in a relatively wide variety of tense forms each, whereas the auxiliaries examined in Sections 7 to 12 have a very limited number of possible tense forms.

3.3 Dedicated auxiliaries and the inflectional expression of syntactic dependencies between clauses

Although this will not be systematically illustrated in the following sections, whenever a dedicated auxiliary occurs in independent assertive clauses in the indicative mood, it can also occur in the corresponding circumstantial and relative forms in the relevant syntactic contexts.

3.4 Dedicated auxiliaries and negation

Comparison with the regular inflection of Tswana verbs makes it possible to identify as either positive or negative the inflected forms in which the dedicated auxiliaries occur. However, as will be apparent in the following sections, it is striking that the negative counterpart of the analytic tenses involving positive forms of dedicated auxiliaries can never be obtained by putting the auxiliary in the negative form without modifying the lexical verb, and can often (but not always) be obtained by putting the lexical verb in the negative form without modifying the auxiliary. More precisely, the following two regularities can be observed:

- When the auxiliary is in a positive form and the lexical verb in a circumstantial form (which constitutes a particularly common configuration) or in the subjunctive (see Sections 6.7.1–2), negation can generally be expressed by putting the lexical verb in the corresponding negative form, never by putting the auxiliary in a negative form. By contrast, expressing negation by means of a negative form of the lexical verb is never possible when the lexical verb is in a sequential form or in the infinitive.
- ‘Auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions with a dedicated auxiliary in a negative form, when possible, are never the negative counterpart of a construction with a positive form of the same auxiliary and the same form of the lexical verb. Either they express meanings that have no exact positive counterpart (as for example the construction expressing ‘never’ presented in Section 6.2.1), or they have no straightforward morphological relationship with their positive counterpart (which may be a synthetic verb form, or an ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ construction involving another auxiliary, as for example in the case of the narrative past; see example (38) in Section 6.4).

Moreover, in two cases (see Sections 5.2–5.3 and Section 6.3.4), it is possible to combine a positive and a negative form of a dedicated auxiliary with the same form of the lexical verb, but semantically, the construction with the auxiliary in the negative form is not the negative counterpart of the construction in which the auxiliary is in the positive form.

The situation observed in Tswana is much more complex than that described by Pietraszko (2018) for Ndebele, and apart from the fact that, in constructions with the lexical verb in a

circumstantial form, negation is expressed in the lexical verb, the straightforward generalizations she proposes for Ndebele clearly do not apply to Tswana.

3.4 The contraction of ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions

In Southern Bantu languages, it may happen that ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions involving dedicated auxiliaries have contracted forms in which the subject marker of the auxiliary is dropped, converting the stem of the auxiliary into an invariable proclitic particle. For example, in Southern Sotho, *ke ne ke bua* [kì-nè kí-búá] ‘I was speaking’ (equivalent of Tswana *ke ne ke bua* [kì-nè kí-bùá]) has a contracted variant *ne ke bua* (Doke and Mofokeng 1985, 253; tones added with the help of a Sotho consultant). In this respect, a remarkable property of Tswana is the total lack of such contracted forms of auxiliary verb + lexical verb constructions.

4 The auxiliary *bo* [bò]

4.1 General remarks on the auxiliary *bo* [bò]

The inflected forms taken by the auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the various constructions in which it occurs can be identified as present, future, potential, subjunctive, sequential future, and sequential past. However, its vowel does not show the alternations that contribute to identifying the inflected forms of the verb in the regular inflection of Tswana verbs. It is not invariably *o* [o], but when it occurs as [e] or [a], this is due to assimilation to the vowel of the subject index, and has nothing to do with the alternations that affect the final vowel of verbs in the regular inflection of Tswana verbs. Moreover, *o* [o] does not occur as a final vowel in the regular inflection of Tswana verbs.

This auxiliary is probably a reflex of *bá ‘be’, although nothing in the system of present-day Tswana and in the regular correspondences between Proto-Bantu and Tswana can explain how the original *a may have become [o], nor how the original high tone may have been lost.

The regular reflex *ba* [bá] of *bá ‘be’ can be found as a copular verb in some Tswana dialects and in the other Sotho-Tswana languages, but not in the dialects that constitute the basis of Standard Tswana, where the copular verb ‘be’ is *nna* [ńná] (also used predicatively with the meaning ‘stay’).

4.2 The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the disjoint form of the present

In the disjoint form of the present, marked by -à- (glossed DJ) immediately after the subject index, the auxiliary *bo* [bò] can combine with the circumstantial present and circumstantial perfect forms of the lexical verb. Semantically, these combinations can be viewed as emphatic variants of the synthetic forms of the present and the perfect, whose precise meaning varies according to the conditions in which they are uttered. According to Cole (1955, 291), they may express “impatience, annoyance, curiosity, surprise and benevolent interest”, i.e., shades of meaning expressed in English either by intonation, or periphrastically.

Given the general distribution of disjoint verb forms, auxiliaries are not expected to take the disjoint form, but I have no explanation to offer for this anomaly.

4.2.1 *bo* [bò] in the disjoint form of the present, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial present

(2) *O a bo o tshega nna ke utlwa botlhoko.*⁴

ò-à-bò ó-ts^héχá ñná kí-ùtlwá bò-t^hò:kò
 SI:2SG-PRS.DJ-AUX SI:2SG-laugh.PRS.CIRC 1SG SI:1SG-feel.PRS.CIRC SG-pain(14)
 ‘You are LAUGHING when I am in pain!’

The corresponding non-emphatic form of the present positive would be *ò a tshega* [ò-à-ts^hèχà] ‘you are laughing’.

4.2.2 *bo* [bò] in the disjoint form of the present, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial present

(3) *Ò a bo o sa tshege lefa o kgatlhega.*

ò-à-bò ó-sá-ts^hèχí 'lífá ó-q^hàtl^hê:χà.
 SI:2SG-PRS.DJ-AUX SI:2SG-NEG-laugh.PRS.CIRC even.if SI:2SG-be.amused.PRS.CIRC
 ‘You are NOT LAUGHING even though you are amused!’

The corresponding non-emphatic form of the present negative would be *ga o tshege* [χà-ó-ts^hèχí] ‘you are not laughing’.

4.2.3 *bo* [bò] in the disjoint form of the present, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial perfect

(4) *Re a bo re etile re sa tshola sepe.*

rì-à-bò rì-ètílé rì-sà-ts^hòlà
 SI:1PL-PRS.DJ-AUXSI:1PL-travel.PRF.CIRC SI:1PL-NEG-take.away.PRF.CIRC
 sî:-pè
 CL7-none
 ‘We DID NOT TRAVEL without taking anything.’

The corresponding non-emphatic form of the perfect negative would be *re etile* [rì-ètílé] ‘we travelled’.

⁴In the presentation of the examples, the first line is in the current Tswana orthography, whereas the second line is a broad phonetic transcription. Given the topic of this article, it is important to emphasize that the current orthography of Sotho-Tswana languages gives a distorted view of word division, since many affixes are written as if they were independent words, which in particular blurs the distinction between synthetic and analytical verb forms. In fact, Sotho-Tswana languages are as agglutinative as the other Bantu languages. The correct grouping of morphemes into words is given on the second line, and is reflected in the glosses.

4.2.4 *bo* [bò] in the disjoint form of the present, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial perfect

(5) *Re a bo re sa eta ka taletso ya bone.*

rì-à-bò **rí-sá-ètá** 'ká Ø-'tálétsò
 SI:1PL-PRS.DJ-AUX SI:1PL-NEG-travel.PRF.CIRC INS SG-invitation(9)
 já-bò:né
 CL9.GEN-CL2.PRO
 'We DID NOT TRAVEL at their invitation.'

The corresponding non-emphatic form of the perfect negative would be *ga re a eta* [χà-rí-á-ètá] 'we did not travel'.

4.3 The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the future

The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the future combines with the circumstantial present and circumstantial perfect forms of the lexical verb to express the meaning of future progressive and future perfect.

4.3.1 *bo* [bò] in the future, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial present

(6) *Ó a bo a sa reke bojalwa, mme kgantele ó tlaa bo a bo batla.*

ó-á-bò á-sà-rékí bó-dzálwá mmí 'q^hántilé
 SI:CL1-PRS.DJ-AUX SI:CL1-NEG.buy.PRS.CIRC SG-beer(14)but soon
ó-tláá-bò **á-bò-bâ:tlà**
 SI:CL1-FUT-AUX SI:CL1-OI:CL14-want.PRS.CIRC
 'As it happens s/he is not buying beer now, but s/he will be wanting some soon.'

The corresponding synthetic form of the future would be *o tlaa bo batla* [ó-tláá-bó-bâ:tlà] 's/he will want'.

4.3.2 *bo* [bò] in the future, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial present

(7) *Ka dikgomo di tlaa bo di sa tsala ka nako eo, ke tlaa bo ke sa tlhoke modisa.*

ká dí-q^hòmś 'dí-tláá-bò dí-sá-tsálà
 since PL-cow(8/10) SI:CL8/10-FUT-AUX.CIRC SI:CL8/10-NEG-give.birth.PRF.CIRC
 ká Ø-nákò éś **kì-tlàà-bò** **kí-sá-tl^hòkí**
 INSSG-time(9) CL9.DEM SI:1SG-FUT-AUX SI:1SG-NEG-need.PRS.CIRC
 mò-dí:sà
 SG-herdsman(1)
 'Since the cows will not have calved by then, I will not be needing a herdsman.'

The corresponding synthetic form of the future negative would be *ke tlaa se tlhoke* [kì-tlǎà-sì-tʰòkí] ‘I will not need’.

4.3.3 *bo* [bò] in the future, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial perfect

(8) *Metsi a tlaa bo a fokotsegile mo molapong kgantele.*

mètsí 'á-tlǎá-bò á-fókótséχilé 'mó mó-làpó-ḡ
 PL.water(6) SI:CL6-FUT-AUX SI:CL6-decrease.PRF.CIRC LOC SG-river(3)-LOC

qʰántì:lé

soon

‘The water in the river will have decreased soon.’

The corresponding synthetic form of the future would be *a tlaa fokotsega* [á-tlǎá-fókótséχà] ‘it will decrease’.

4.3.4 *bo* [bò] in the future, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial perfect

(9) *Re tlaa bo re sa roba ka Seetebosigo.*

rì-tlǎà-bò rí-sá-ròbá 'ká síètíbòsì:χò
 SI:1PL-FUT-AUX SI:1PL-NEG-harvest.PRF.CIRC INS June

‘We will not have harvested by June.’

The corresponding synthetic form of the future negative would be *re tlaa se robe* [rì-tlǎà-sì-ròbí] ‘we will not harvest’.

4.4 The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the potential

The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the potential combines with the circumstantial present and circumstantial perfect forms of the lexical verb to express the meanings of potential progressive and potential perfect. As illustrated by the following examples, these forms are mainly found in conditional sentences.

4.4.1 *bo* [bò] in the potential, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial present

(10) *Nka bo ke rekisa dikgomo fa dikabo di nonne.*

ḡ-ká-bò kí-rèkísá dí-qʰòmó 'fá 'dí-ká-bò
 SI:1SG-POT-AUX SI:1SG-sell.PRS.CIRC PL-COW(8/10) if SI:CL8/10-POT-AUX

dí-nònnè

SI:CL8/10-be.fat.PRF.CIRC

‘I would be selling the cows if they were fat.’

The corresponding synthetic form of the potential would be *nka rekisa* [ḡ-ká-rèkísá] ‘I can sell’.

4.4.2 *bo* [bò] in the potential, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial present

(11) *Nka bo ke sa rekise dikgomo fa go ne go se leuba.*

ḡ-ká-bò **kí-sà-rékísí** dí-q^hòmó 'fá 'χó-né
 SI:1SG-POT-AUX SI:1SG-NEG-sell.PRS.CIRC PL-COW(8/10) if SI:CL17- AUX
 'χó-sí lí-ù:bà
 SI:CL8/10-not.to.be.PRS.CIRC SG-drought(5)
 'I would not be selling cows if there had not been drought.'

The corresponding synthetic form of the potential negative would be *nka se rekise* [ḡ-ká-sì-rékísí] 'I cannot sell'.

4.4.3 *bo* [bò] in the potential, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial perfect

(12) *Fa a ka bo a sa reka poo ele, nka bo ke e rekile.*

fǎ 'á-ká-bò á-sà-réká Ø-pòó 'élé
 if SI:CL1-POT-AUX SI:CL1-NEG-buy.PRF.CIRC SG-bull(9) cl9.DEM
ḡ-ká-bò **kí-ì-rékî:lè**
 SI:1SG-POT-AUX SI:1SG-OI:cl9-buy.PRF.CIRC
 'If s/he had not bought that bull, I would have bought it.'

The corresponding synthetic form of the potential would be *nka e reka* [ḡ-ká-ì-réká] 'I can buy it'.

4.4.4 *bo* [bò] in the potential, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial perfect

(13) *Fa ba ne ba sa thoga, ba ka bo ba sa sia.*

fǎ 'bá-né 'bá-sá-ts^hòχá **bá-ká-bò**
 if SI:CL2-AUX.PRF.CIRC. SI:CL2-NEG-be.scared.PRF.CIRC **SI:CL2-POT-AUX**
bá-sà-sî:à
 SI:CL2-NEG-run.PRF.CIRC
 'If they had not been scared, they would not have run away.'

The corresponding synthetic form of the potential negative would be *ba ka se sie* [bá-ká-sì-sî] 'They cannot run'.

4.5 The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the subjunctive

The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the subjunctive combines with the circumstantial perfect of the lexical verb to express the meaning of subjunctive perfect. Note that the HL tone pattern of this form is essential to identify it as a subjunctive form, since it does not show the final vowel [ε] that characterizes the subjunctive in the regular inflection of Tswana verbs.

(14) *Ke batla gore o bo o feditse tiro e kamoso.*

kǐ-bàtlǎ χòrǐ **ó-bò** **ó-fédítse** Ø-tírò
 SI:1SG-want.PRS that SI:2SG-AUX.SBJV SI:2SG-finish.PRF.CIRC SG-work(9)

é kámò:só
 CL9.DEM tomorrow
 ‘I want you to have finished this work by tomorrow.’

The corresponding synthetic form of the subjunctive would be *o fetse* [ó-fétsé] ‘you should finish’.

4.6 The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the sequential future

The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the sequential future combines with the circumstantial present of the lexical verb into an analytical verb form which is semantically a mere emphatic variant of the synthetic form of the sequential future of the lexical verb. Note that the LH tone pattern of this form is essential to identify it as a sequential future form, since it does not show the final vowel [-i] that contributes to the identification of the sequential future in the regular inflection of Tswana verbs.

(15) ... *ke bo ke lema tshimo e.*
 kì-bò k'í-límá Ø-ts'ímò: é
 SI:1SG-AUX.SEQ.FUT SI:1SG-cultivate.PRS.CIRC SG-field(9) CL9.DEM
 ‘... and I certainly will cultivate this field.’

The corresponding non-emphatic form of the sequential future would be *ke leme* [kì-límí] ‘and I will cultivate’.

4.7 The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the sequential past

The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the sequential past can be identified as such by the presence of the prefix that characterizes the sequential past. The tonal behaviour of this form is also similar to that of the sequential past in the regular inflection of Tswana verbs.

The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the sequential past can combine with three different forms of the lexical verb: the circumstantial present, the circumstantial perfect, and the sequential past.

4.7.1 *bo* [bò] in the sequential past, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial present

This combination expresses the progressive aspect in the contexts that require the use of a sequential past form.

(16) ... *ka bo ke bua le Mpho.*
 k-à-bò k'í-bùá lí-m̀:phó
 SI:1SG-SEQ.PST-AUX SI:1SG-speak.PRS.CIRC COM-PRN
 ‘... and then I happened to be speaking with Mpho.’

The corresponding synthetic form of the sequential past would be *ka bua* [k-à-bùà] ‘and I spoke’.

4.7.2 *bo* [bò] in the sequential past, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial perfect

This combination expresses the meaning of perfect in the contexts that require the use of a sequential past form.

(17) ... *ka bo ke lemile tshimo e.*

k-à-bò **kí-límílé** Ø-ts^hímò: é
 SI:1SG-SEQ.PST-AUX SI:1SG-cultivate.PRF.CIRC SG-field(9) CL9.DEM
 ‘... and then it happened that I had cultivated this field.’

The corresponding synthetic form of the sequential past would be *ka lema* [k-à-limà] ‘and I cultivated’.

4.7.3 *bo* [bò] in the sequential past, lexical verb in the sequential past

Semantically, this combination is a mere emphatic variant of the synthetic form of the sequential past of the lexical verb. In this form, the vowel of the initial syllable of both the auxiliary and the lexical verb is invariably the [a] that represents the characteristic marker of the sequential past, which may explain why, in this combination, the final vowel of the auxiliary is not [o], but [a].

(18) ... *ka ba ka ya ko Gauteng.*

k-à-bá **k-á-jà** kó χàútê:ŋ
 SI:1SG-SEQ.PST-AUX SI:1SG-SEQ.PST-go LOC PRN
 ‘... and finally I went to Johannesburg.’

The corresponding synthetic form of the sequential past would be *ka ya* [k-à-jà] ‘and I went’.

4.8 The auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the infinitive

The paradigm of the synthetic inflected forms of Tswana verbs does not include a perfect positive form of the infinitive. This gap is filled by an analytical form consisting of the auxiliary *bo* [bò] in the infinitive and the positive form of the circumstantial perfect of the lexical verb.

In this form, *bo* [bò] shows a high tone which has no possible explanation in a synchronic perspective, since, as a rule, low-toned stems do not undergo tonal modification in the infinitive. However, diachronically, this H tone can be analysed as the retention of the H tone of *bá, which has been lost in the other forms of this auxiliary.

(19) *Go bo o re thusitse go siame.*

χò-bó **ó-rì-t^húsítsé** χó-siâ:mì
 INF-AUX SI:2SG-OI:1PL-help.PRF SI:CL17-be.good.PRF
 ‘It’s good that you helped us.’ lit. ‘For you to have helped us is good.’

Note that the synthetic forms of the infinitive do not include a subject index (the slot occupied in the other verb forms by the subject index being filled in the infinitive by the infinitival prefix, which coincides with the nominal prefix of class 17). For example, the present form of the infinitive ‘to help us’ would be *go re thusa* [χò-rí-t^húsá]. By contrast, in this analytical form of

the infinitive, a subject index is obligatorily present in the circumstantial perfect form of the lexical verb.

4.9 Summary of the functions of the auxiliary *bo* [bò]

The auxiliary *bo* [bò] can take a number of inflections and different complements. It can be used to form emphatic variants of some synthetic verb forms (Sections 4.2, 4.6, and 4.7.3), or to form analytical tenses expressing aspectual meanings: progressive if the lexical verb is in the circumstantial form of the present, perfect if the lexical verb is in the circumstantial form of the perfect (Sections 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, 4.7.1, 4.7.2, and 4.8).

5 The auxiliary *ne* [nè]

5.1 General remarks on the auxiliary *ne* [nè]

The auxiliary *ne* [nè] is most likely to be cognate with the defective and irregular verb *na* [nà] ‘have’, found not only in Tswana but also in the other Sotho-Tswana varieties, itself a reflex of the Bantu comitative preposition **na* ‘with’ (Creissels 2024a). Note that, in Sotho-Tswana languages, **na* as a comitative preposition has generally been replaced by *le* [lí]. In some varieties (for example, Southern Sotho), **na* does not subsist at all as a preposition, whereas in some others (including Tswana), **na* is still found as a preposition, but only in a very marginal way.

5.2 The auxiliary *ne* [nè] in the disjoint form of the present

With a marker identical to that characterizing the disjoint form of the present inserted between the subject index and the stem, this auxiliary combines with the circumstantial present of the lexical verb. The meaning expressed is ‘sometimes’, ‘from time to time’.

5.2.1 *ne* [nè] in the disjoint form of the present, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial form of the present

(20) *Ó a ne a rekisa kgomo go bona madi.*

ʃ-á-nè á-rékísá Ø-q^hòmó χò-bóná mà:-dí
 SI:CL1-PRS.DJ-AUX SI:CL1-SELL.PRS.CIRC SG-COW(9) INF-SEE PL-money(6)
 ‘S/he sometimes sells a cow to get money.’

5.2.2 *ne* [nè] in the disjoint form of the present, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial form of the present

(21) *Ó a ne a sa rekise kgomo.*

ʃ-á-nè á-sà-rékísí Ø-q^hò:mó
 SI:CL1-PRS.DJ-AUX SI:CL1-NEG-SELL.PRS.CIRC SG-COW(9)
 ‘Sometimes s/he does not sell any cow.’

5.3 The auxiliary *ne* [nè] in the negative form of the present

In the regular inflection of Tswana verbs, this form of the auxiliary *ne* [nè] would be the negative counterpart of the form described in Section 5.2. However, the meaning it expresses is not the negation of ‘sometimes’, but the negation of the future.

(22) *Ga ke ne ke rekisa kgomo.*

χà-kí-né kí-rèkísá Ø-q^hò:mó
 NEG-SI:1SG-AUX.PRS SI:1SG-sell.PRS.CIRC SG-COW(9)
 ‘I will not sell any cow.’

Note that the same meaning (future negative) can be expressed by the synthetic verb form *ke tlaa se rekise* [kì-tlàà-sì-rékísí] combining the future marker *tlaà* and the negative marker *sì*, by the analytical forms presented below in Sections 7.2.2 and 7.5, and by an analytical form in which the auxiliary is a regular form of *na* [ná] ‘have’ (Creissels forthcoming 2026, Section 5.1).

5.4 The auxiliary *ne* [nè] in the perfect

The perfect form of the auxiliary *ne* [nè], whose uses are described in this section, and the subjunctive form, described in Section 5.5, have the same segmental form, both consisting of a subject index and the stem *ne* [nè]. In the regular inflection of Tswana verb, the perfect and the subjunctive have distinct final vowels, but this is not the case for the auxiliary *ne* [nè].

However, these two forms do not involve the same paradigm of subject markers. The form described in this section has low-toned subject markers in the first and second person, and a subject marker *o* [ó] in class 1, whereas the form described in Section 5.5 has high-toned subject markers in all persons, and a subject marker *a* [á] in class 1, and this justifies identifying the former as a perfect form, and the latter as a subjunctive form.

With the auxiliary *ne* [nè] in the perfect, the lexical verb may be in one of the following forms: sequential past, circumstantial present, circumstantial perfect, circumstantial future, and circumstantial potential.

5.4.1 *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the sequential past

This combination, designated as past tense in Cole’s (1955) grammar, is very frequent in texts. It can be characterized semantically as narrative past, since it constitutes the usual way of referring to past events viewed as disconnected from the situation in which the sentence is uttered (in contrast to the meaning of current relevance implied by the synthetic form of the perfect).

(23) *Ngogola ke ne ka etela ko Aforika Borwa.*

ηòχólá kí-nè k-à-ètèlà kó áfòríká bò:rwá
 last.year SI:1SG-AUX.PRF SI:1SG-SEQ.PST-travel LOC PRN
 ‘Last year I visited South Africa.’

5.4.2 *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial present

This combination, designated as past continuous tense in Cole’s grammar, is used to represent events as ongoing or habitual with reference to some point in the past.

(24) *Ba ne ba nna mmogo sentle.*

bá-nè bá-ñná òmmóχó sín:tìè
 SI:CL2-AUX.PRF SI:CL2-stay.PRS.CIRC together well
 ‘They lived well together.’

5.4.3 *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial present
This combination is the negative counterpart of that presented in Section 5.4.2.

(25) *Re ne re sa dire sepe.*

ri-nè rí-sá-dìrí 'sî:-pè
SI:1PL-AUX.PRF SI:1PL-NEG-do.PRS.CIRC CL7-none
'We were not doing anything.'

5.4.4 *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial perfect

This combination expresses a meaning similar to that expressed by the forms traditionally labeled 'pluperfect' in the grammars of European languages (reference to events presented as having occurred prior to some point in the past).

(26) *Tshimo e ne e lemilwe.*

Ø-tshímó í-nè í-lìmî:lwè
SG-field(9) SI:CL9-AUX.PRF SI:CL9-cultivate.PASS.PRF.CIRC
'The field had been cultivated.'

5.4.5 *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial perfect

This combination is the negative counterpart of that presented in Section 5.4.4.

(27) *Tshimo e ne e sa lengwa.*

Ø-tshímó í-nè í-sá-lì:ŋwá
SG-field(9) SI:CL9-AUX.PRF SI:CL9-NEG-cultivate.PASS.PRF.CIRC
'The field had not been cultivated.'

5.4.6 *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial future

This combination expresses a counterfactual meaning: the event could have occurred in the past under some conditions, but did not occur. Note that in (28), the second part of the sentence includes the circumstantial form of the combination '*ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial perfect' described in Section 5.4.4.

(28) *Lo ne lo tlaa tsamaya le bone fa lone lo tsile ka nako.*

lò-nè lò-tláá-tsàmàjà lí-bòné 'fá 'lò-né
SI:2PL-AUX.PRF SI:2PL-FUT-go.FUT.CIRC COM-CL2.PRO if SI:2PL-AUX.CIRC
lò-tsilé 'ká Ø-nâ:kò
SI:2PL-COME.PRF.CIRC INS SG-time(9)
'You could have left with them if you had come in time.'

5.4.7 *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial future

This combination is in principle possible as the negative counterpart of that presented in Section 5.4.6, and it is not rejected in elicitation, but it is not mentioned in the literature on Tswana and does not occur in my data of spontaneous discourse.

5.4.8. *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial potential

This combination expresses a counterfactual meaning very similar that presented in Section 5.4.6, with an additional nuance of potentiality. In (29), as in (28), the second part of the sentence includes the circumstantial form of the combination ‘*ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial perfect’ described in Section 5.4.4.

(29) *Dikgomo di ne di ka nona fa pula e ne e nele.*

dì-q^hòmó **dí-nè** **dí-ká-nónà** fá 'Ø-púlá
 PL-COW(8/10) SI:CL8/10-AUX.PRF SI:CL8/10-POT-grow.fat.CIRC if SG-rain(9)
 'í-né í-nì:lé
 SI:cl9-AUX.PRF.CIRC SI:cl9-rain.PRF.CIRC

‘The cows could have grown fat if it had rained.’

5.4.9 *ne* [nè] in the perfect, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial potential

This combination is semantically the negative counterpart of that presented in Section 5.4.8.

(30) *Dikgomo di ne di ka se none fa pula e ne e sa na.*

dì-q^hòmó **dí-nè** **dí-ká-sì-nòní** 'fá
 PL-COW(8/10) SI:CL8/10-AUX.PRF SI:CL8/10-POT-NEG-grow.fat.CIRC if
 'Ø-púlá 'í-né í-sà:-ná
 SG-rain(9) SI:cl9-AUX.CIRC SI:cl9-rain.PRF.CIRC

‘The cows could not have grown fat if it had not rained.’

5.5 The auxiliary *ne* [nè] in the subjunctive

The auxiliary *ne* [nè] in the subjunctive combines with the lexical verb in the circumstantial present (positive or negative). The meaning expressed can be glossed as ‘it would be better if...’. As in the case of *bo* [bò] (see Section 4.5), the tone pattern of this form of the auxiliary *ne* [nè] is essential to identify it as a subjunctive form.

5.5.1 *ne* [nè] in the subjunctive, lexical verb in the positive form of the circumstantial present

(31) *O ne o re gopola fa o le ko Makgoeng.*

ó-nè ó-rì-χópólá 'fá 'ó-lí kó
 SI:2SG-AUX.SBJV SI:2SG-OI:1PL-think.PRS.CIRC when SI:2SG-be.PRS.CIRC LOC
 mà-q^hóê:-ìj
 PL-European(6)-LOC

‘You should think of us when you are in Europe.’

5.5.2 *ne* [nè] in the subjunctive, lexical verb in the negative form of the circumstantial present

(32) *O ne o se re lebale fa o le ko Makgoeng.*

ó-nè ó-sì-rí-libáli 'fá 'ó-lí
 SI:2SG-AUX.SBJV SI:2SG-NEG-OI:1PL-forget.PRS.CIRC when SI:2SG-be.PRS.CIRC

kó mà-q^húê:-ìj
 LOC PL-European(6)-LOC
 ‘You should not forget us when you are in Europe.’

6 The auxiliary *ka* [ká]

6.1 General remarks on the auxiliary *ka* [ká]

The auxiliary *ka* [ká] is most likely to be cognate with the prefix *-ká-* marking the potential tense in the inflection of the synthetic forms of Tswana verbs (as in *re ka simolola* [rì-ká-simólólà] ‘we can begin’), and in spite of the irregular tonal correspondence, both are probably reflexes of *ngà ‘be like’. On the one hand, Sotho-Tswana *k* is the regular reflex of Bantu *ng, and on the other hand, as discussed in Creissels (2017b), evidence that verbs originally expressing similarity between two concrete entities may get involved in the expression of non-epistemic modalities can be found in quite a few language families.

The auxiliary *ka* [ká] is mainly used in negative forms, in ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions that are functionally the negative counterparts of synthetic verb forms. Some of the analytic negative tenses formed by means of the auxiliary *ka* [ká] are in competition with a synthetic negative form, whereas others constitute the sole possibility of expressing the negation of the corresponding positive form.

In fact, the construction described in Section 6.7 is the only one in which the auxiliary *ka* [ká] occurs in a positive form. This suggests a relatively recent grammaticalization of *ngà ‘be like’ into an auxiliary verb, and further into a verbal prefix, the grammaticalization process being more advanced for the positive forms than for the negative ones.

In contrast to *bo* [bò] and *ne* [nè], most of the forms of the auxiliary *ka* [ká] are morphologically regular. This can be viewed as additional evidence that the grammaticalization of this auxiliary is relatively recent in the history of Tswana.

6.2 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the negative form of the present

6.2.1. *ka* [ká] in the present negative, lexical verb in the circumstantial present

The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the present negative combines with the circumstantial present of the lexical verb to express ‘never’. In this combination (and only in this combination), its stem can optionally be expanded by a nasal. A possible explanation is put forward below.

(33) *Ga o (n)ke o re etela.*

χà-ú-(í)kí ú-rì-étê:là
 NEG-SI:2SG-AUX.PRS SI:2SG-OI:1PL-visit.PRS.CIRC
 ‘You never pay us a visit.’

Example (34) illustrates the same combination with the auxiliary in the circumstantial form of the present negative (which mainly differs from the indicative form in the use of a distinct negative marker).

(34) *Ka o se ke o re etela, ga o tsala ya rona.*

ká 'ú-sí-kí ú-rì-étê:là χà-ú
 since SI:2SG-NEG-AUX.PRS.CIRC SI:2SG-OI:1PL-visit.PRS.CIRC NEG-SI:2SG

Ø-tsàlà já-rò:ná
 SG-friend(9) CL9.GEN-1PL.PRO
 ‘Since you never pay us a visit, you are not our friend.’

Note that exactly the same meaning can be expressed by using the present negative of the dedicated auxiliary *ka*, as in (33), or the present negative verb *nna* [ńná] ‘stay, be’ in auxiliary function, as in (35).

(35) *Ga ba nne ba nthusa.*

χà-bá-ńńí bá-ń-t^hû:sà
 NEG-SI:CL2-stay.PRS SI:CL2-OI:1SG-help.PRS.CIRC
 ‘They never help me.’ lit. ‘They don’t stay helping me.’

This synonymy may have been the cause of the development of a nasalized variant of the auxiliary *ka* [ká] in its use to express ‘never’ (and only in this use).

6.2.2 *ka* [ká] in the present negative, lexical verb in the sequential future

In the present negative, the auxiliary *ka* [ká] can combine not only with the circumstantial present of the lexical verb to express ‘never’, but also with the sequential future of the lexical verb to express the meaning of future negative.

(36) *Ga re ke re leme tshimo e.*

χà-rí-kí rí-lìmí Ø-tshímò: é
 NEG-SI:1PL-AUX.PRS SI:1PL-cultivate.SEQ.FUT SG-field(9) CL9.DEM
 ‘We will not cultivate this field.’

6.3 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the perfect positive

The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the perfect positive combines with the sequential past of the lexical verb to express the meaning of experiential perfect, i.e., to denote that an event has taken place at least once in the past.

(37) *Re kile ra etela ko Makgoeng .*

rì-kilè r-à-ètèlà kó mà-q^hóê:-ń
 SI:1PL-AUX.PRF SI:1PL-SEQ.PST-travel LOC PL-European(6)-LOC
 ‘We once travelled to Europe.’

6.4 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the negative form of the perfect

Contrary to what the formal relationship between these two forms might suggest, the combination of the auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the perfect negative with the sequential past of the lexical verb, illustrated in (38b), does not express the negation of the meaning of experiential perfect expressed by the analytical verb form presented in Section 6.3. Semantically, it constitutes the negative counterpart of the narrative past described in Section 5.4.1 above, i.e., an analytical form involving the auxiliary *ne* [nè], as in (38a).

- (38) a. *Ba ne ba duelwa ka madi.*
bá-nè **b-à-dúélwà** ká mà:-dí
 SI:CL2-AUX.PRF SI:CL2-SEQ.PST-pay.PASS INS PL-money(6)
 ‘They were paid in money.’
- b. *Ga ba a ka ba dulewa ka madi.*
χà-bá-à-ká **b-à-dúélwà** ká mà:-dí
 NEG-SI:CL2-PRF-AUX SI:CL2-SEQ.PST-pay.PASS INS PL-money(6)
 ‘They were not paid in money.’

6.5 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the negative form of the future

In the negative form of the future, the auxiliary *ka* [ká] combines with the sequential future of the lexical verb to express the meaning of future negative (which can also be expressed by an analytical verb form involving another form of the same auxiliary – see Section 6.2.2 – or by a synthetic verb form, in this case *re tlaa se leme* [rì-tlàà-sì-lìmí]).

- (39) *Re tlaa se ke re leme tshimo e.*
rì-tlàà-sì-kí **rì-lìmí** Ø-ts^hímò: é
 SI:1PL-FUT-NEG-AUX SI:1PL-cultivate.SEQ.FUT SG-field(9) CL9.DEM
 ‘We will not cultivate this field.’

6.6 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the negative form of the potential

In two forms that can be identified as two variants of the potential negative, the auxiliary *ka* [ká] combines with the sequential past of the lexical verb to express the meaning of potential negative.

- (40) a. *Ò ka se ka wa tsaya podi wa tlogela potsana.*
ò-ká-sì-ká **w-à-tsájá** Ø-^lpódí w-á-tlòχèlà
 SI:2SG-POT-NEG-AUX SI:2SG-SEQ.PST-take SG-goat(9) SI:2SG-SEQ.PST-leave
 Ø-pótsà:ná
 SG-kid(9)
 ‘You cannot take the goat and leave the kid.’
- b. *Ga o ka ke wa tsaya podi wa tlogela potsana.*
χà-ó-kà-kí **w-à-tsájá** Ø-^lpódí w-á-tlòχèlà
 NEG-SI:2SG-POT-AUX SI:2SG-SEQ.PST-take SG-goat(9) SI:2SG-SEQ.PST-leave
 Ø-pótsà:ná
 SG-kid(9)
 ‘You cannot take the goat and leave the kid.’

These two ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions are synonymous, not only between themselves, but also with the synthetic form of the potential negative, which in this case would be *ò ka se tsee* [ò-ká-sì-tséí] ‘you cannot take’.

Formally, it must be noted that, in the variant illustrated in (40a), the auxiliary has the morphological structure of the potential negative in the regular inflection of synthetic verb forms, with the negation expressed by means of the negative marker *se* [sì] following the potential marker. By contrast, the combination of the negative marker *ga* [χà] preceding the subject index

and the potential marker *ka* [ká] that characterizes the auxiliary in the variant illustrated in (40b) does not occur in the regular inflection of synthetic verb forms.

6.7 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the positive form of the subjunctive

The subjunctive form of the auxiliary *ka* [ká] is irregular, since instead of the [ɛ] ending that characterizes the subjunctive in regular verb inflection, its ending is [o] or [e] depending on the vowel of the subject index ([o] if the vowel of the subject index is [ɔ], otherwise [e]). It combines with the subjunctive of the lexical verb (positive or negative) to express the same meaning as the synthetic form of the subjunctive, with some additional emphasis, as illustrated in (41a–b) and (42a–b).

6.7.1 *ka* [ká] in the subjunctive positive, lexical verb in the subjunctive positive

(41) a. *A re thuse!*

á-rì-t^hû:sè

SI:2SG-OI:1PL-help.SBJV

Let him/her help us!’ (synthetic form of the subjunctive positive, non-emphatic)

b. *A ke a re thuse!*

á-kè

á-rì-t^hû:sè

SI:2SG-AUX.SBJV SI:2SG-OI:1PL-help.SBJV

‘Just let him/her help us!’

6.7.2 *ka* [ká] in the subjunctive positive, lexical verb in the subjunctive negative

(42) a. *O se ba thuse!*

ó-sì-bá-t^hû:sì

SI:2SG-NEG-OI:CL2-help.SBJV

‘Stop helping them!’ (synthetic form of the subjunctive negative, non-emphatic)

b. *O ko o se ba thuse!*

ó-kò

ó-sì-bá-t^hû:sì

SI:2SG-AUX.SBJV SI:2SG-NEG-OI:CL2-help.SBJV

‘Do stop helping them!’

6.8 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the negative form of the subjunctive

In the negative form of the subjunctive, the auxiliary *ka* [ká] combines with the sequential past of the lexical verb to express the meaning of subjunctive negative. The fact that the vowel of the auxiliary is [a] instead of the [ɪ] normally found in the subjunctive negative may be due to the assimilation to the vowel of the first syllable of the lexical verb, which in the sequential past can only be [a].

(43) *Re tlaa tswela ko ntle gore re se ka ra go tlhodia.*

rì-tlàà-tswèlà

kó

ntlé

χóti

rì-sì-ká

SI:1PL-FUT-go.OUT.APPL LOC outside so.that SI:1PL-NEG-AUX.SBJV

r-á-χò-t^hódî:à

SI:1PL-SEQ.PST-OI:2SG-disturb

‘We will go out so as not to disturb you.’

This form is synonymous with the synthetic form of the subjunctive negative, which in this case would be *re se go tlhodie* [rí-sí-χò-t^hódî].

6.9 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the negative form of the sequential future

In a form that does not exist in the regular inflection of synthetic verb forms but can be described as resulting from the addition of the negative marker *se* [sì] to the sequential future, the auxiliary *ka* [ká] combines with the sequential future of the lexical verb to express the negation of the sequential future, which cannot be expressed by means of a synthetic verb form.

(44) ... *ba se ke ba dire sepe.*

bà-sì-kí

bá-dìrì

!sî:-pè

SI:CL2-NEG-AUX.SEQ.FUT

SI:CL2-do.SEQ.FUT

CL7-none

‘... and they won’t do anything.’

6.10 The auxiliary *ka* [ká] in the negative form of the sequential past

In a form that does not exist in the regular inflection of Tswana verbs but can be described as resulting from the addition of the negative marker *se* [sì] to the sequential past, the auxiliary *ka* [ká] combines with the sequential past of the lexical verb to express the negation of the sequential past, which cannot be expressed by means of a synthetic verb form.

(45) ... *ka se ka ka bona mekoti ya gauta.*

k-à-sì-ká

k-à-bóná

mí-kòtí

jà-Ø-χâ:tà

SI:1SG-SEQ.PST-NEG-AUX

SI:1SG-SEQ.PST-see

PL-mine(4)

CL4.GEN-SG-gold(9)

‘... and I didn’t see the gold mines.’

7 The auxiliary *tle* [tlé]

This auxiliary, cognate with the verb *tla* [tlà] ‘come’, can be used in two different but synonymous forms to express the aspectual meaning ‘occasionally, sometimes’. In both cases, the lexical verb is in the sequential future. What justifies analysing these two forms as a dedicated auxiliary, instead of *tla* [tlà] ‘come’ in auxiliary function, is their irregular ending [e] and irregular tone pattern. They differ in the presence or absence of the prefix that marks the disjoint form of the present positive in regular verb inflection. With the auxiliary *tle* [tlé], the presence of this prefix is purely optional, and has nothing to do with the conjoint vs. disjoint contrast. It could be freely suppressed in (46), and added in (47), without any change in the acceptability and the meaning of these two examples.

(46) *Ba a tle ba re etele ka Kereseiose.*

bá-à-tlé

bá-rì-étéli

ká

'kírísímò:sì

SI:CL2-PRS.DJ-AUX

SI:CL2-OI:1PL-visit.SEQ.FUT

at

Christmas

‘They sometimes visit us for Christmas.’

(47) *Ke tle ke ye morakeng ka thsipi.*

kì-tlé kì-yí m'ò-ràké-ṅ ká Ø-'tshî:pi
 SI:1SG-come.PRS SI:1SG-go.SEQ.FUT SG-cattle.post(3)-LOC by SG-sunday(9)
 'I sometimes go to the cattle-post on Sundays.'

8 The auxiliary *tshogana* [ts^hòχàná]

Morphologically, the auxiliary *tshogana* [ts^hòχàná] could be the reciprocal form of *tshoga* [ts^hòχà], an intransitive verb that can be glossed as 'experience a feeling of fear'. However, this reciprocal form does not exist as such, which justifies analysing *tshogana* [ts^hòχàná] as a dedicated auxiliary, whatever its etymological relationship with *tshoga* [ts^hòχà] 'experience a feeling of fear' may be.

In combination with the present circumstantial or perfect circumstantial of the lexical verb, *tshogana* [ts^hòχàná] expresses the meaning 'unexpectedly'. It can occur in various forms, all perfectly regular, for example the perfect in (48) and the future in (49).

(48) *Re tshoganye re utlwa lentswe la gagwe.*

rì-ts^hòχàpì rì-ùtlwá lí-ṅtswí 'lá-χâ:χwè.
 SI:1PL-AUX.PRF SI:1PL-hear.PRS.CIRC SG-voice(5) CL5.GEN-CL1.PRO
 'All of a sudden, we heard his voice.'

(49) *Fa o sa dire thata ko sekolong, o tlaa tshogana o paletswe ke dithuto.*

fâ 'ó-sá-dirí 't'átá kó sì-kóló-ṅ
 if SI:2SG-NEG-work.PRS.CIRC much LOC SG-school(7)-LOC
 ò-tlàà-ts^hòχàná ó-pàlétswí kí dì-t'û:tò
 SI:2SG-FUT-AUX SI:2SG-be.too.difficult.APPL.PASS.PRF.CIRC by PL-study(10)
 'If you don't work much at school, you will have the unpleasant surprise of having failed.'

9 The auxiliary *bolo* [bòl'ó]

This auxiliary is only used in a form identifiable as present negative, with the lexical verb in the infinitive. The meaning expressed is that the event denoted by the lexical verb did not occur recently, or occurred long ago.

(50) *Kgomo ga e bolo go swa.*

Ø-q^hòm'ó χà-í-bòl'ó χ'ò:-swá
 SG-cow(9) NEG-SI:CL9-AUX.PRS INF-die
 'The cow has long been dead.'

(51) *Ga ke bolo go etela Kitso.*

χà-kí-bòl'ó χ'ò-ètèlà kí:tsò
 NEG-SI:1SG-AUX.PRS INF-visit PRN
 'I visited Kitso long ago.'

A plausible etymology (which is consistent with the tonal contour of this auxiliary, its irregular ending [ɔ̃], and the selection of the infinitive form of the lexical verb) is that it was originally a form of the auxiliary *bo* [bò] followed by the comitative proclitic *le* [lí] ‘with’, whose vowel [ɪ] assimilated to the [ɔ̃] of the infinitive prefix.

10 The auxiliary *ise* [ísí]

This auxiliary, which has a tonal variant [ísí] in some Tswana varieties, occurs only in an indicative form and its circumstantial counterpart. The indicative form, which can be identified as present negative, combines with the sequential future of the lexical verb to express a nondumitive meaning (‘not yet’).

(52) *Dijo ga di ise di rekwe.*

di-dzó ɣà-dí-ísí dì-rê:kwì
 PL-food(8/10) NEG-SI:CL8/10-AUX SI:CL8/10-buy.SEQ.FUT

‘The food has not been bought yet.’

The circumstantial form of the auxiliary *ise* [ísí] is irregular, since it expresses the same nondumitive meaning as the indicative form but includes no negative marker corresponding to the negative prefix *ga* [ɣà] found in the indicative form (normally, the auxiliary in (53) should not be *ke ise* [kí-ísí], but **ke se ise* [kí-sì-ísí], with the negative marker *se* [sì]).

(53) *Kitso o tsamaile ke ise ke goroge.*

kítsó ɔ̃-tsamáílè kí-ísí kí-ɣòrô:ɣì
 PRN(1) SI:CL1-leave.PRF SI:1SG-AUX.PRS.CIRC SI:1SG-arrive.SEQ.FUT

‘Kitso left before I arrived (lit. I not having arrived yet).’

I have nothing to propose about a possible etymology of this auxiliary.

11 The auxiliary *kitla* [kítlá]

This auxiliary, which occurs as *ketla* [kítlá] in some Tswana varieties, is only found in forms that can be identified as irregular forms of the present negative. Followed by the circumstantial form of the present positive of the lexical verb, it gives one of the variants of the future negative. It is probably cognate with *tla* [tlà] ‘come’, but its first syllable and its tonal contour have no obvious explanation.

(54) *Ga ba kitla ba tla kwano.*

ɣà-bá-kítlá 'bá-tlá 'kwâ:nò
 NEG-SI:CL2-AUX.PRS SI:CL2-come.PRS.CIRC here

‘They will not come here.’

Example (55) illustrates the circumstantial form of this auxiliary.

(55) *Ke tlaa ya ko toroppong lefa ke se kitla ke reka.*

kì-tlàà-jà kó Ø-tòròpó-ŋ lífá 'kí-sí-kítlá
 SI:1SG-FUT-go LOC SG-town(9)-LOC although SI:1SG-NEG-AUX.PRS.CIRC

kí-rè:ká

SI:1SG-buy.PRS.CIRC

‘I’ll go to town although I am not going to buy anything.’

12 The auxiliary *sena* [síná]

This auxiliary only occurs in syntactic contexts requiring the use of the circumstantial mood (for example in clauses introduced by the conjunction *fa* [fá] ‘if, when’, as in (56)), in combination with the infinitive of the lexical verb. It selects the paradigm of subject indexes used for the circumstantial in the regular inflection of Tswana verbs, but the tone pattern of the stem (LH) is not the regular tone pattern of verb stems in the circumstantial. Its meaning can be glossed as ‘having finished’. Note that it cannot be cognate with *fela* [félá], which is the regular predicative verb expressing ‘finish’ in Tswana.

(56) *Fa o sena go kwala, o balolole se o se kwadileng.*

fá	ʔ-síná	χò-kwálá	ʔ-bálòlòlé	ʔsé
when	SI:2SG-AUX.PRS.CIRC	INF-write	SI:2SG-read.OVER.SBJV	CL7.REL

ʔ-sì-kwádílè:-ń

SI:2SG-OI:CL7-write.PRF-REL

‘After writing, you must read over what you have written.’

A plausible hypothesis is that this auxiliary is cognate with *se na* [-sí-ná], the negative form of the circumstantial of the defective and irregular verb *na* [nà] ‘have’ (i.e., a form that can be glossed as ‘not having’). Semantically, it is not difficult to imagine a shift from ‘not having to V’ to ‘after V-ing’. However, the tonal difference between these two forms has no obvious explanation. Moreover, the negative form of the circumstantial of *na* [nà] ‘have’ itself is irregular (since, in principle, the negative marker in circumstantial forms is not *se* [-sí-], but *sa* [-sà-]), which further complicates attempts at explanation.

13 Conclusion

In this article, I have described the uses of the dedicated auxiliaries of Tswana and tried to analyse their etymology. The question that arises is to what extent the data described in Sections 4 to 15 lend themselves to generalizations.

A first observation, which certainly has to do with the fact that there is no reason to think that these auxiliaries share a common history, is the lack of obvious generalizations in the way many dedicated auxiliaries depart morphologically from the regular inflection of synthetic verb forms.

As regards the inflectional potential of dedicated auxiliaries, there is a sharp contrast between a group of three auxiliaries that occur in a variety of tense forms each (*bo* [bò], *ne* [nè] and *ka* [ká]), and the other ones, which have a very limited number of possible tense forms, sometimes just one. Among the auxiliaries that occur in a relatively wide variety of inflected forms, *ka* [ká] has the particularity that it mainly occurs in negative forms in ‘auxiliary verb + lexical verb’ constructions that are the negative counterparts of positive synthetic verb forms that include the cognate potential marker *-ká-*.

Among the auxiliaries with relatively rich tense inflections, it is also remarkable that most of the inflected forms of *bo* [bò] and *ne* [nè] select circumstantial forms of the lexical verb, whereas with *ka* [ká], the lexical verb is predominantly in a sequential form.

Finally, as discussed in Section 3.4, the negative counterpart of analytic verb forms involving positive forms of the auxiliary can often be obtained by putting the lexical verb in the negative form without modifying the auxiliary, but never by putting the auxiliary in the negative form without modifying the lexical verb, and in the two cases in which the latter is possible, the construction with the auxiliary in the negative form is not the semantic counterpart of the construction in which the auxiliary is in the corresponding positive form.

Abbreviations

APPL = applicative, AUX = auxiliary, CIRC = circumstantial, CL = class, in the sense of gender-number agreement marker, COM = comitative, DEM = demonstrative, DJ = disjoint, FUT = future, GEN = genitival linker, INF = infinitive, INS = instrumental, LOC = locative, NEG = negative, OI = object index, PASS = passive, PL = plural, POT = potential, PRF = perfect, PST = past, PRN = proper name, PRO = pronoun, PRS = present, REL = relative, SI = subject index, SEQ = sequential, SG = singular, SBJV = subjunctive

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Appendix: Summary of Tswana auxiliaries and the meanings they express

This appendix consists of two parts. The first part lists the verbs that can by themselves project clauses in which they assign semantic roles to the referents of noun phrases and that can also be found in auxiliary function, whose detailed description constitutes the topic of Creissels (forthcoming 2026). The second part lists the dedicated auxiliaries dealt with in this article.

In general, when the same auxiliary is mentioned as expressing two or more meanings, each of the possible interpretations is bound to particular tense forms of the auxiliary and/or the lexical verb. For the auxiliaries listed in the first part of the appendix, see Creissels (forthcoming 2026) for details. For those listed in the second part, the details can be found in the relevant sections of this article.

A/ Verbs that can project clauses by themselves and that are also used in auxiliary function

	LEXICAL MEANING	MEANING IN AUXILIARY FUNCTION
<i>aga</i> [áχá]	‘build’	continuous aspect (‘not to stop doing something’)
<i>akofa</i> [àkòfà]	‘hurry up’	immediate sequentiality
<i>atisa</i> [àtisà]	causative of <i>ata</i> [àtà] ‘increase (intr.)’	frequentative aspect (‘do something often’)
<i>batla</i> [bàtlà]	‘look for, want, need’	approximative (‘almost, nearly’)
<i>boa</i> [bóá]	‘return’	duplicative aspect (‘again’)
<i>dika</i> [díká]	‘surround’, ‘revolve’	(1) ‘in the past year’ (2) ‘later the same year’
<i>eta</i> [ètà]	‘travel’	simultaneity
<i>fela</i> [fêlá]	‘become finished’	conclusive aspect (‘eventually’)
<i>feta</i> [fità]	‘pass’	sequentiality
<i>fitlha</i> [fitlhà]	‘arrive’	(1) sequentiality (2) associated motion; occur/do upon arrival

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<i>gana</i> [χáná]	‘refuse’	negation
<i>lala</i> [lálá]	‘spend the night somewhere’	(1) hesternal past (‘the day before’) (2) hodiernal future (‘later the same day’) (3) ‘never’
<i>losetsa</i> [lòsètšà]	causative-applicative form of <i>lwa</i> [lwà] ‘struggle’	approximative (‘almost, nearly’)
<i>na (le)</i> [nà lí-]	‘have’	(1) habitual aspect (2) obligative modality (3) future negative
<i>nama</i> [nàmà]	‘stretch’	(1) continuative aspect (‘continue to do something’) (2) conclusive aspect
<i>nna</i> [ńná]	‘sit, stay, be’	(1) continuative aspect (2) durative aspect (3) potential modality (4) ‘never’
<i>nnela</i> [ńnélá]	applicative of <i>nna</i> [ńná] ‘sit, stay, be’	continuous aspect
<i>phakela</i> [p ^h àkèlà]	‘get up early in the morning’	(1) hodiernal past (‘earlier the same day’) (2) crastinal future (‘next day’)
<i>rata</i> [rátá]	‘love, like, want’	approximative (‘almost, nearly’)
<i>sala</i> [sálá]	‘remain somewhere’	(1) iamitive aspect (‘already’) (2) ‘in the absence of someone’
<i>sa le</i> [sà-lí]	‘still be’ (persistence form of the copular verb <i>le</i> [lí] ‘be’)	(1) ‘for a long time’ (2) remote past (‘long ago’)
<i>senka</i> [síńká]	‘look for’	approximative (‘almost, nearly’)
<i>simolola</i> [símolólà]	‘begin (tr.)’	inchoative aspect
<i>tla</i> [tlà]	‘come’	(1) ‘occasionally, sometimes’ (2) approximative (‘almost, nearly’) (3) sequentiality (4) simultaneity (5) associated motion: occur/do during movement towards the deictic centre
<i>tlhola</i> [tl ^h òlà]	‘spend the day somewhere’	(1) continuous aspect (2) cessative aspect (‘not anymore’)
<i>tloga</i> [tlòǰà]	‘leave’	imminent future

<i>tsamaya</i> [tsàmàjà]	‘go’	continuous aspect
<i>tsamaela</i> [tsàmàèlà]	applicative form of <i>tsamaya</i> [tsàmàjà] ‘go’	imminent future
<i>tshela</i> [ts ^h ílá]	‘live’	continuous aspect
<i>tshwanela</i> [ts ^h wánélá]	‘suit’, ‘fit’	obligative modality
<i>tsoga</i> [tsóǰá]	‘get up’	(1) hodiernal past (‘earlier the sameday’) (2) crastinal future (‘next day’)
<i>tswa</i> [tswà]	‘go out’, ‘come from’	(1) ‘for a long time’ (2) remote past (‘long ago’) (3) recent past
<i>ya</i> [jà]	‘go’	imminent future

B Dedicated auxiliaries

<i>bo</i> [bò]	(1) emphatic variants of the following tenses: present, positive (§5.2.1) and negative (§5.2.2); perfect, positive (§5.2.3) and negative (§5.2.4); sequential future (§5.6), sequential past (§5.7.3) (2) future progressive, positive (§5.3.1) and negative (§5.3.2) (3) future perfect, positive (§5.3.3) and negative (§5.3.4) (4) potential progressive, positive (§5.4.1) and negative (§5.4.2) (5) potential perfect, positive (§5.4.3) and negative (§5.4.4) (6) subjunctive perfect (§5.5) (7) sequential past progressive (5.7.1) (8) sequential past perfect (§5.7.2) (9) infinitive perfect (§5.8)
<i>bolo</i> [bòlò]	‘not recently’, or ‘long ago’ (§10)
<i>ise</i> [ísí]	nondumitive (‘not yet’) (§11)
<i>ka</i> [ká]	(1) ‘never’ (§7.2.1) (2) future negative (§7.2.2, §7.5) (3) experiential perfect (§7.3) (4) narrative past negative (§7.4) (5) potential negative (§7.6) (6) emphatic variant of the subjunctive, positive (§7.7.1) and negative (§7.7.2) (7) subjunctive negative (§7.8) (8) sequential future negative (9) sequential past negative
<i>kitla</i> [kítlá]	future negative (§12)

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<i>ne</i> [nè]	(1) ‘sometimes’ (§6.2) (2) future negative (§6.3) (3) narrative past positive (§6.4.1) (4) past continuous, positive (§6.4.2) and negative (§6.4.3) (5) pluperfect, positive (§6.4.4) and negative (§6.4.5) (6) counterfactual (§6.4.6, §6.4.8, §6.4.9) (7) ‘it would be better if...’ (§6.5)
<i>sena</i> [siná]	‘after’ (§13)
<i>tle</i> [tlé]	‘sometimes’ (§8)
<i>tshogana</i> [ts ^h òχàná]	‘unexpectedly’ (§9)

The Pragmatic Functions of the Auxiliary Verbs *za* ‘come’ and *ya* ‘go’ in isiXhosa

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Abstract

This study focuses on the syntactic and pragmatic functions of the isiXhosa auxiliary verbs *za* ‘come’ and *ya* ‘go’ when followed by subjunctive or past consecutive lexical verbs. Analysis of the auxiliaries’ occurrence in a 60,000-word database reveals that both auxiliaries introduce new predicates into the discourse. *Za* links a new predicate to a discourse old predicate in coordinated clauses. By contrast, *ya* introduces new predicates involving discourse old constituents. The study presents new insights into the grammaticalization paths of itive and ventive semantics of verbs of movement within the area of information structure.

Keywords: isiXhosa, motion verbs, grammaticalization, focus, coordination

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1 Introduction

The grammaticalization of deictic verbs of movement into tense and aspect markers is well documented across a vast number of languages. Ventive ‘come’ and itive ‘go’ are known to develop into future, completive and progressive markers (cf. Bybee and Dahl 1989; Bybee et al. 1994). More recently they have also been recognized as sources of other grammatical meanings (e.g., modality and voice) as they can function as imperative and passive markers (see Giacalone Ramat and Sansò 2014; Mocciaro 2014; Dragomirescu and Nicolae 2014; Kuteva et al. 2019, 12). In addition, *come* and *go* may develop various pragmatic roles, such as focus markers or indicators of new events being introduced into the discourse, functions which remain understudied despite a growing interest (see Ebert 1987, 2003; Nicolle 2002, 2007; Bourdin 2008; Devos and van der Wal 2010; Bravo 2014; Daniels 2014; Carlson 2014; Devos 2014; Kuteva et al. 2019).

The same tendency is found in the literature on the grammaticalized meanings of the isiXhosa verbs *za* ‘come’ and *ya* ‘go’ as auxiliary¹ verbs. In compound verbs, *za* and *ya* do not refer to deictically specified movements with goal complements (see Kuteva et al. 2019, 12), which is the meaning they exhibit as lexical verbs. Instead, as the first element of the biverbal construction, they encode grammatical meaning (tense, aspect, mood),² whereas lexical information about the predicate is specified by a complement lexical verb (inflected or non-finite). The type and function of the compound verb with the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* are determined by the grammatical form of the lexical complement, i.e., infinitive, situative, subjunctive, past consecutive (for a detailed explanation of these verb forms in isiXhosa, see Savić 2020; an account of these complement types in Southern Bantu languages is found in Crane et al. forthcoming).

The auxiliaries *za* and *ya* form the following types of compound verbs, which express:

- i. the **future tense** (see Section 1.1) with the auxiliary *za* or *ya* and an infinitive (class 15) complement; see (1–2);
- ii. the **imperfective, perfect/anterior, or prospective aspects** (see Section 1.1) in the remote past tense with the auxiliary *ya* exhibiting a suffix *-e* (or *-é*) followed by a situative (participial or circumstantial)³ complement that indicates the aspectual category; see (3);
- iii. **directives** (see Section 1.2) with the subjunctive auxiliary *za* followed by a subjunctive complement; see (4);
- iv. **gradual processes** (see Section 1.2) with the auxiliary *ya* and a situative complement; see (5).
- v. various **pragmatic functions** (see Section 1.3) with the auxiliary *za* or *ya* and a subjunctive or a past consecutive (narrative past or past subjunctive) complement,⁴ as it has been termed in many studies on isiXhosa and the other Nguni languages), exemplified in (6–7).

¹ For a detailed discussion on the definition of auxiliary verbs, see Haspelmath (2024).

² Auxiliary verbs in isiXhosa express a number of grammatical categories such as tense, aspect, lexical aspect/actionality/aktionsart, polarity, and evidentiality. However, in compound verbs with the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* marking tense and aspect (Section 1.3), the latter is primarily expressed in the lexical complement, although this view depends on the analysis of the tense and aspect system of isiXhosa. In compound verbs that denote gradual processes (Section 1.2), the auxiliary *ya* can also be said to express lexical aspect (Persohn 2020).

³ Cf. Rose et al. (2002, 59–60, 80), Bearth (2003).

⁴ Louw and Jubase (1963, 159–163), Davey (1973, 102–106), Oosthuysen (2016, 223–224); cf. Rose et al. (2002, 19–20, 54), Nurse (2008, 120–124).

- (1) *Ba-z-a* *ku-phek-a*.
SM.2-come-FV 15-cook-FV
‘They will cook.’ (constructed example)
- (2) *Ba-y-a* *ku-phek-a*.
SM.2-go-FV 15-cook-FV
‘They will cook.’ (constructed example)
- (3) *Nd-â-y-e* *ndi-phek-a*.
SM.1SG-REMPST-go-PST SIT.SM.1SG-cook-FV
‘I was cooking / I used to cook (IMPF).’ (constructed example)
- (4) *Ni-z-e* *ni-zam-el-e* *u-xolo*.
SM.2PL-come-SBJV SM.2PL-try-APPL-SBJV AUG-11.peace
‘You must strive for peace.’ (Oosthuysen 2016, 225)
- (5) *U-Gobizembi* *w-â-hamb-a* *w-a-y-a*
AUG-1A.Gobizembi SM.1-REMPST-walk-FV SM.1-CONS-go-FV
e-sondel-a *kwi-nyoka* *leyo*.⁵
SIT.SM.1SG-approach-FV 17-9.snake DEM.MED.9
‘Gobizembi walked, **coming nearer and nearer** to that snake’
(Oosthuysen 2016, 291)
- (6) *Mhlawumbi* *u-makhulu* *wa-kho* *w-â-xelex-a*
maybe AUG-1A.grandmother POSS.1-2SG SM.1-REMPST-tell-FV
u-mama *wa-kho* *w-a-z-a* *u-khokho*
AUG-1A.mother POSS.1-2SG SM.1-CONS-come-FV AUG-1A.ancestor
wa-kho *w-a-xelex-a* *u-makhulu* *wa-kho*.
POSS.1-2SG SM.1-CONS-tell-FV AUG-1A.grandmother POSS.1-2SG
‘Perhaps your grandmother told this (about the benefits of breastfeeding) to your mother, **and** your (older female) ancestor **had told** this to your grandmother.’
(Roux et al. 2001⁶)
- (7) *Ú-th-é* *emva* *ko-kuba* *e-tsh-ilo* *w-a-phakam-a*
SM.1-do-PST after POSS.17-that SIT.SM.1-say-PST SM.1-CONS-get_up-FV
w-a-y-a *e-wodrobh-ini* *ya-khe* *w-a-khuph-a*
SM.1-CONS-go-FV LOC-9.wardrobe-LOC POSS.9-1 SM.1-CONS-take_out-FV
e-nye *i-hempe*. *Ú-y-é* *w-a-yi-khulul-a*
ADJ.9-one AUG-9.shirt SM.1-go-PST SM.1-CONS-OM.9-take_off-FV

⁵In all the examples from other sources I added the glossing.

⁶Citations of corpus data used in this paper refer to published descriptions of the respective corpora, which themselves do not include page or sentence numbering.

le *bendi-fik-é* *e-yi-nxib-ile*
 DEM.PROX.9 SM.1SG.PST-arrive-ANT REL.9-OM.9-put_on-ANT.DJ

w-a-z-a *w-a-nxib-a* *le.*
 SM.1-CONS-come-FV SM.1-CONS-put_on-FV DEM.9.PROX

‘After he said that, he stood up and went to his wardrobe and took out one of his shirts. **He took off** the one he was wearing when I arrived and put on another one.’
 (Roux et al. 2001)

The auxiliary *za* differs not only semantically but also formally from its lexical counterpart. Unlike the auxiliary verb forms *baza* in (1) and *waza* in (6), as a lexical verb of movement, *za* contains a so-called ‘latent vowel’ /i-/ before the root,⁷ which does not surface as a phoneme but alters the vowel in the preceding morpheme. Thus, vowel /a/ in class 2 subject marker *ba-* in (8) and in the remote past *-â-* in (9) transforms to /e/.

(8) *Á-bá-fàzì* *bé-z-à* *námhlánjé.*⁸
 AUG-2-woman SM.2-come-FV today

‘The women **will come** today.’ (Riordan et al. 1969, 178)

(9) *A-ba-fazi* *b-ê-z-a* *ku-theng-a i-nyama* *e-si-larh-eni.*
 AUG-2-woman SM.2-REMPST-come-FV 15-buy-FV AUG-9.meat LOC-7-butcher’s-LOC

‘The women came to buy meat at the butcher’s.’ (Oosthuysen 2016, 306)

The aim of this paper is to investigate the morphosyntactic functions of the isiXhosa auxiliary verbs *za* and *ya*, as well as their role in structuring discourse. The comparative analysis will provide insights into the grammaticalization paths of itive and ventive motion verbs into the domain of information structure.

As already indicated, the formal and functional characteristics of the different types of compound verbs with auxiliary *za* and *ya* are outlined in Sections 1.1–1.3. The methodology of this study is presented in Section 2. The results are discussed in Section 3, followed by a conclusion in Section 4.

1.1 Auxiliary verbs *za* and *ya* in the tense and aspect system of isiXhosa

Auxiliary *za* and *ya* play an important role in the tense and aspect system of isiXhosa. Following Comrie (1976, 1985), I define ‘tense’ as the location of an event relative to the moment of speech, indicating whether an event is located in the past, present, or future (see Dahl 1985; Rose et al. 2002). Besides the present tense (10), isiXhosa has two past (11–12) and two future tenses.⁹

⁷Cf. McLaren (1936, 134), Davey (1973, 63), Bryant (2007, 179), and Oosthuysen (2016, 294, 253).

⁸Unless stated otherwise, isiXhosa examples from other sources are quoted with the tonal marking in the original, e.g., in (7) from Riordan et al. (1969).

⁹Note that the number of tenses in isiXhosa may vary between individual studies. In some studies the recent past is referred to as the ‘perfect’ (Louw and Jubase 1963, 41; Oosthuysen 2016, 188–190) or ‘perfective’ (Crane and Persohn 2019). Furthermore, McLaren (1936) and Nxopo (1993) do not view the two future tenses as semantically or conceptually distinct.

- (10) *Ndi-phek-a* *i-dinala.*
 SM.1SG-cook-FV AUG-9.dinner
 ‘I **cook** dinner / I **am cooking** dinner.’ (constructed example)
- (11) *Ndi-phek-é*¹⁰ *i-dinala.*
 SM.1SG-cook-PST AUG-9.dinner
 ‘I **cooked** dinner / I **have cooked** dinner.’ (constructed example)
- (12) *Nd-â-phek-a* *i-dinala.*
 SM.1SG-REMPST-cook-FV AUG-9.dinner
 ‘I **cooked** dinner.’ (constructed example)

The semantic difference between the two past tenses has often been described as one of remoteness. While the remote past expressed by the prefixed *-â-* in (11) is indeed specialized for more distant parts of the past (the ‘discontinuous past’ in Plungian and van der Auwera (2006); cf. D-domain past in Botne 2006), the recent or near past, marked by the suffix *-é* with a high tone,¹¹ is temporally and semantically less restricted and may refer to any past point (cf. Savić 2020, 404–405). In disjoint verb forms, which primarily reflect the syntactic properties of the predicate, the recent past is marked with the suffix *-ile*.¹² Note that tone marking is not part of the orthography of isiXhosa and it is used here only to distinguish homographic grammatical morphemes.

Unlike the present and the past tenses, which are expressed solely with morphological markers, the future is expressed in compound verbs in which auxiliary *za* or *ya* has an infinitive lexical verb as a complement, as already shown in the previous section. In the spoken and/or less formal registers, *za* and *ya* tend to be contracted with the infinitive marker *ku-* of the lexical verb, forming the new prefixes (between the subject marker and the root) *-zo-* (13) and *-yo-* (14).

- (13) *Ndi-z-a* *ku-phek-a.* > *Ndi-zo-phek-a.*
 SM.1SG-come-FV 15-cook-FV SM.1SG-FUT-cook-FV
 ‘I **will cook.**’ (constructed example)
- (14) *Ndi-y-a* *ku-phek-a.* > *Ndi-yo-pheka.*
 SM.1SG-go-FV 15-cook-FV SM.1SG-REMFUT-cook-FV
 ‘I **will cook.**’ (constructed example)

Similarly to the two past tenses, the distinction between the two future tenses has also traditionally been characterized as one of remoteness. However, the near or immediate future *za ku-* can be regarded as the unmarked future marker, which can refer to any future point in time without any semantic restrictions. By contrast, the remote future *ya ku-* can be understood as a discontinuous future (by analogy with the ‘discontinuous past’ in Plungian and van der Auwera 2006; cf. ‘D-domain future’ in Botne 2006), which is restricted to future events that can only be

¹⁰I gloss the recent past only as PST, whereas remote past is glossed as REMPST.

¹¹Du Plessis and Visser (1992, 19), Riordan et al. (1969, 154), and Davey (1973, 50) describe the tone of the suffix as falling (high-low), i.e., *-é*, whereas Cassimjee (1998, 201–207) and Oosthuysen (2016, 197) point out that the suffix may be realized with both tones.

¹²The conjoint/disjoint distinction in isiXhosa is found in both the present and the recent past (Savić 2020, 113).

actualized if a condition that is not met at the moment of speech is fulfilled at some point in the future (Savić 2020, 399–405). Thus, *úza kufuna* ‘he will need’ in (15) refers to a traumatized victim who already needs counselling at present, whereas *baya kugqiba* ‘they will decide’ in (16) refers to a hypothetical procedure that will only take place if the reader suffers a serious workplace injury.

- (15) *Ú-z-a ku-fun-a ii-ngcebiso i-xesha*
 SM.1-come-FV 15-want-FV AUG-10.advice AUG-5.time
eli-de kwi-Masisukumeni.
 ADJ.5-long 17-Masisukumeni
 ‘He will need counselling at Masisukumeni (Crisis Centre) for a long time.’
 (adapted from Snyman et al. 2012)¹³

- (16) *Emva k-oko um-Komishinala na-ba-nye oo-qgirha*
 after 17-DEM.17.MED AUG-1.commissioner COM-ADJ.2-one AUG-1A.doctor
ba-y-a ku-qgib-a ekubeni u-ku-khubazeka oko
 SM.2-go-FV 15-decide-FV LOC.that.LOC AUG-15-be_disabled DEM.15.MED
ku-nzima okanye ku-nzulu kangakani na.
 COP.ADJ.15-difficult or COP.ADJ.15-deep to_what_extent Q
 ‘After that, a commissioner and other doctors **will decide** on how severe (lit. the difficulty or the depth of) your disability is.’ (Eiselen and Puttkammer 2014)

Unlike tense, which temporally locates an event on the timeline, aspect specifies the perspective from which an event’s temporal structure is viewed, e.g., as a single completed event, as an ongoing event, a series of repetitive events, etc. (Comrie 1976). These perspectives are entailed in aspectual categories such as the perfect/anterior, perfective, imperfective, progressive, or the habitual. Following this definition, the isiXhosa present, past, and future verb forms in (10–16) do not exhibit overt aspectual markers.

The imperfective, perfect/anterior, and prospective aspects are expressed in the past and future tenses in compound verbs which consist of the auxiliary verbs *ba* ‘be’ or *ya* with a suffixed *-e/-é*.¹⁴ While the auxiliary specifies the tense, its complement, the situative lexical verb, specifies the aspectual category. Auxiliary *ba* is used in the near past (17), near future (18), and remote future tenses, although it can also occur in the remote past (Davey 1973, 86), whereas *ya* is typically restricted to the remote past (19–22). The situative expresses aspect with the same morphemes that are used to mark the present, recent past, and future tenses in main¹⁵ (simplex) indicative verbs: the final vowel *-a* indicates the imperfective aspect (18–19), the recent past suffix *-é* or *-ile* indicates the perfect/anterior (20), and *za ku-* (or *-zo-*) or *ya ku-* (or *-yo-*) before the lexical verb root indicates the prospective aspect (21–22).

¹³ Example adapted to correct typographical errors in the original.

¹⁴ The tone of the auxiliary suffix in uncontracted forms of these compound verbs may depend on the tense of the auxiliary. In the recent past, the suffix has the same tone as the recent past marker in non-compound verbs, i.e., *-é* (or *-ê*). In the remote past and future tenses the suffix either exhibits varying tones or its tone is subject to different interpretations (cf. Du Plessis and Visser 1992, 19, 186; Davey 1973, 50, 87, 90; Riordan et al. 1969, 154).

¹⁵ i.e., non-situative and non-consecutive verbs.

- (17) *Ú-b-é* *e-phek-a.* > *Ebe-phek-a.*
 SM.1-be-PST SIT.SM.1-cook-IPFV SM.1.PST-cook-IPFV
 ‘She/He was cooking / She/He used to cook (IMPF).’ (constructed example)
- (18) *Ndi-z-a* *ku-b-e* *ndi-phek-a* > *Ndi-zo-b-e* *ndi-phek-a*
 SM.1SG-come-FV INF-be-AUX SIT.SM.1SG-cook-FV SM.1SG-FUT-be-AUX SIT.SM.1SG-cook-IPFV
 ‘I will be cooking (IMPF).’ (constructed example)
- (19) *W-â-y-e* *e-phek-a.* > *Waye-phek-a.*
 SM.1-REMPST-go-AUX SIT.SM.1-cook-IPFV SM.1.REMPST-cook-IPFV
 ‘She/He was cooking / She/He used to cook (IMPF).’ (constructed example)
- (20) *S-â-y-e* *si-phek-ile.* > *Sasi-phek-ile.*
 SM.1PL-REMPST-go-AUX SIT.SM.1PL-cook-ANT.DISJ SM.1PL.REMPST-cook-ANT.DISJ
 ‘We were cooking / We used to cook (ANT).’ (constructed example)
- (21) *Nd-â-y-e* *ndi-za ku-phek-a* > *Ndandi-zo-phek-a*
 SM.1SG-REMPST-go-AUX SIT.SM.1SG-PRO-cook-FV SM.1SG.REMPST-PRO-cook-FV
 ‘I was going to cook (PRO).’ (constructed example)
- (22) *Nd-â-y-e* *ndi-ya ku-phek-a .* > *Ndandi-yo-phek-a*
 SM.1SG-REMPST-go-AUX SM.1SG-PRO-cook-FV SM.1SG.REMPST-PRO-cook-FV
 ‘I was going to cook (PRO).’ (constructed example)

Note that the recent and remote past auxiliary verbs often merge together with the subject marker of the lexical verbs to form contracted prefixes. The phonological contractions they undergo follow different patterns, some of which are less transparent than others, e.g., *úbe* (SM.1.PST) + *e-* (SIT.SM.1) > *ebe-* for 1.PST in (17), *wâye* (SM.1.REMPST) + *e-* (SIT.SM.1) > *waye-* for 1.REMPST in (19), *sâye-* (SM.1PL.REMPST) + *si-* (SIT.SM.1PL) > *sasi-* for 1PL.REMPST in (20), or *ndâye-* (SM.1SG.REMPST) + *ndi-* (SIT.SM.1SG) > *ndandi-* for 1SG.REMPST in (21–22).

1.2 Modal and actional uses of the auxiliaries *za* and *ya*

The auxiliary *za* in the subjunctive, followed by a subjunctive lexical verb, expresses deontic modality, as in the directive in (4), repeated here as (23).

- (23) *Ni-z-e* *ni-zam-el-e* *u-xolo.*
 SM.2PL-come-SBJV SM.2PL-try-APPL-SBJV AUG-11.peace
 ‘You must strive for peace.’ (Oosthuysen 2016, 225)

Another construction with the auxiliary *ya* (with the final vowel *-a*) followed by a situative lexical verb ending in *-a* has been characterized by Persohn (2020) as denoting ‘gradual developments’ (cf. Bennie 1939, 105, 133; Oosthuysen 2016, 291). In example (24), *ya* together with its situative complement *sondela* ‘approach’ refers to the subject’s successive steps towards the snake.

- (24) *U-Gobizembi* *w-â-hamb-a* ***w-a-y-a***
 AUG-1A.Gobizembi SM.1-REMPST-walk-FV SM.1-CONS-go-FV

e-sondel-a *kwi-nyoka* *leyo*.
 SIT.SM.1SG-approach-FV 17-9.snake DEM.MED.9

‘Gobizembi walked, coming nearer and nearer to that snake’ (Oosthuysen 2016, 291)

1.3 Pragmatic functions of the auxiliaries *za* and *ya*

The auxiliaries *za* and *ya* followed by subjunctive or past consecutive complements have received limited attention in the literature, leaving their semantic and syntactic properties largely understudied. Regarding this type of compound verb with the auxiliary *za*, Du Plessis and Visser (1992, 254–255) observe that it “occurs in successive clauses followed by a complement clause in either the Subjunctive or the Consecutive mood depending on the circumstances”, as exemplified in (25–26) with a subjunctive and a past consecutive lexical verb, respectively.

- (25) *Khà-wù-phùlaphùl-è* ***ù-z-è*** ***ù-vùl-è*** *îi-ndlèbè*.
 IMP-2SG-listen-SBJV SM.2SG-come-SBJV SM.2SG-come-SBJV AUG-10.ear

‘You must please listen **and** open your ears’ (Du Plessis and Visser 1992, 255)

- (26) *W-â-shíy-w-á* *ké* *ló* *m-ntwánà*,
 SM.2SG-REMPST-leave-PASS-FV SO DEM.PROX.1 1-child

w-á-z-à *ké* ***w-á-khùlél-à*** *áphà*.
 SM.2SG-CONS-come-FV SO SM.2SG-CONS-grow-FV here

‘The child was left behind **and then** grew up here’ (Du Plessis and Visser 1992, 255)

In both examples *za* does not refer to a motion event, but marks coordination between the preceding predicate (*khawuphulaphule* ‘listen’, *wáshiywa* ‘(she/he) was left’) and the predicate it is part of (*uze uvule* ‘and open’, *waza (ke) wakhulela* ‘and then grew up’). In (26), auxiliary *za* may also indicate a temporal subsequence between the predicates.

In line with this observation, Einhorn and Siyengo (1993, 47) specify the meaning of the auxiliary verb *za* as ‘(and) then’. Similarly, Oosthuysen (2016, 294) claims that “*ukuza* (to come) is extensively used with a predicate in the subjunctive mood as complement to indicate a consecutive or subsequent process”, a view he illustrates in examples (27–28). It should be noted that Oosthuysen (2016) regards the past consecutive in (28) as part of the subjunctive mood, whereas it is analysed here as a relative past tense (cf. Rose et al. 2002, 74) within the indicative mood.

- (27) *Yi-ya-ni*, *ni-li-hlol-e* *i-li-zwe*, ***ni-z-e***
 IMP-go-2PL SM.2PL-OM.5-spy-SBJV AUG-5-country SM.2PL-come-SBJV

ni-buy-el-e *ku-m.*
SM.2PL-return-APPL-SBJV 17-OM.1SG

‘Go and spy out the country **and then** return to me.’ (Oosthuysen 2016, 294)

- (28) *U-kumkani* *w-â-b-a*¹⁶ *no-m-sindo* *kunene,*
AUG-1A.king SM.1-REMPST-be-FV COM-3-anger really
- w-a-z-a* *w-a-thumel-a,* *w-a-ba-bulal-a*
SM.1-CONS-come-FV SM.1-CONS-send-FV SM.1-CONS-OM.2-kill-FV
- b-onke* *a-ba-ntu* *ba-loo* *lali.*
2-all AUG-2-people PP.2-DEM.9.MED 9.village

‘The king was very angry, **so he sent** and killed all the people of that village.’ (Oosthuysen 2016, 294)

The corpus example (6), repeated here as (29), confirms that the auxiliary *waza* overtly signals coordination between two similar events, i.e., the already introduced remote past *wâxelela* ‘she told’ and the discourse new past consecutive *waxelela* ‘she told’.

- (29) *Mhlawumbi* *u-makhulu* *wa-kho* *w-â-xelex-a*
maybe AUG-1A.grandmother POSS.1-2SG SM.1-REMPST-tell-FV
- u-mama* *wa-kho* *w-a-z-a* *u-khokho*
AUG-1A.mother POSS.1-2SG SM.1-CONS-come-FV AUG-1A.ancestor
- wa-kho* *w-a-xelex-a* *u-makhulu* *wa-kho.*
POSS.1-2SG SM.1-CONS-tell-FV AUG-1A.grandmother POSS.1-2SG
- ‘Perhaps your grandmother told this (about the benefits of breastfeeding) to your mother, **and** your (older female) ancestor **had told** this to your grandmother.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

However, the coordinated events are presented in the reverse-chronological order, thus showing that temporal subsequence or causality between the two events does not represent the inherent part of the pragmatic function of auxiliary *za*, but frequent contextual interpretations of predicate coordination. Since the subjunctive and the past consecutive already entail coordination after another predicate, the question remains whether the function of the auxiliary *za* is to signal additional pragmatic properties of the coordinated events.

With respect to *ya* as an auxiliary verb followed by a subjunctive or a past consecutive complement, Du Plessis and Visser (1992, 257) observe that it indicates the speaker’s surprise, which I interpret as the expression of mirativity; see (30):

- (30) *Ló* *m-fó* *ú-y-é* *w-é-mk-à.*
DEM.1.PROX 1-man SM.1-go-PST SM.1-CONS-leave-FV
- ‘This man **just merely left** (sic!).’ (Du Plessis and Visser 1992, 257)

¹⁶I added the tone to distinguish the remote past verb from the homograph past consecutive.

Einhorn and Siyengo (1993, 47) describe only the auxiliary *ya* with the past consecutive complement. They observe that it emphasizes the event denoted by the predicate¹⁷; see (31):

- (31) *Ú-y-é* *w-a-fik-a*.
 SM.1-go-PST SM.1-CONS-arrive-FV
 ‘He **did arrive**.’ (Einhorn and Siyengo 1993, 47)

The auxiliary *ya* in example (31) can be interpreted as the expression of *verum*, i.e., an overt affirmation that the proposition holds true (cf. Gutzmann et al. 2020; Bloom Ström and Zeller 2023).

Although the accounts of the auxiliary *ya* with a past consecutive complement may seem inconsistent, the expression of surprise in (30) and *verum* in (31) imply that this compound verb functions as a marker of information structure, indicating which piece of information is known to both the speaker and the hearer.

In the corpus example (7), repeated here as (32), the events are chronologically ordered. Yet, unlike the other verbs in the example, the auxiliary verb *úyé* does not refer to a specific event. If the above accounts of this construction hold, *ya* in (32) may signal something about the information structure of the sentence, e.g., the way the event of taking off the shirt is linked to the events mentioned in the preceding discourse.

- (32) *U-th-é* *emva* *ko-kuba* *e-tsh-ilo* *w-a-phakam-a*
 SM.1-do-PST after POSS.17-that SIT.SM.1-say-PST SM.1-CONS-get_up-FV
w-a-y-a *e-wodrobh-ini* *ya-khe* *w-a-khuph-a*
 SM.1-CONS-go-FV LOC.9.wardrobe-LOC POSS.9-1 SM.1-CONS-take_out-FV
e-nye *i-hempe.* *Ú-y-é* *w-a-yi-khulul-a*
 ADJ.9-one AUG.9.shirt SM.1-go-PST SM.1-CONS-OM.9-take_off-FV
le *bendi-fik-é* *e-yi-nxib-ile*
 DEM.PROX.9 SM.1SG.PST-arrive-ANT REL.9-OM.9-put_on-ANT.DJ
w-a-z-a *w-a-nxib-a* *le.*
 SM.1-CONS-come-FV SM.1-CONS-put_on_FV DEM.9.PROX
 ‘After he said that, he stood up and went to his wardrobe and took out one of his shirts. **He took off** the one he was wearing when I arrived and put on another one.’
 (Roux et al. 2001)

Du Plessis and Visser (1992, 257) mention another compound verb with the auxiliary *ya* plus a situative verb¹⁸ as its complement. According to them, this construction denotes “successive actions in the past and is translated with ‘further’ or ‘and further’”, which can be understood as expressions of coordination and additivity, as demonstrated in (33). In the domain of syntax, Du Plessis and Visser (1992, 257) stress that, unlike the other types of compound verbs with

¹⁷In addition, Einhorn and Siyengo (1993, 47) suggest that the auxiliary *ya* semantically corresponds to the adverbs ‘then’ and ‘usually’, but without providing examples that illustrate this use.

¹⁸Du Plessis and Visser (1992, 257) add that this compound verb type with auxiliary *ya* may alternatively have a non-situative indicative complement; however they do not provide examples illustrating this use.

the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* discussed in this section, an overt NP subject separates the auxiliary *ya* from its situative complement.

- (33) *Bá-y-è* (*ábò* *bà-fó*) *bé-sí-tshò*.
 SM.2-GO-SBJV DEM.2.MED 2-man SM.2-SIT-say
 ‘Further those men said (sic!).’ (Du Plessis and Visser 1992, 257)

In summary, one syntactic property seems to distinguish the auxiliary *za* from both types of compound verbs with the auxiliary *ya* irrespective of their complements. While the auxiliary *za* with the subjunctive or past consecutive complement seems to occur only after another predicate¹⁹ (25–29), the auxiliary *ya* introduces sentence-initial predicates (30–33). With respect to these auxiliary verbs’ functions, the auxiliary *za* has been associated with predicate coordination, whereas *ya* has received more varying analyses, including mirativity and verum with a past consecutive complement, and coordination and/or additivity with a situative complement.

Since auxiliary *za* and *ya* with subjunctive, consecutive, and stative complements have not been systematically compared in the literature, the question is raised as to whether their functions (predicate coordination, mirativity, verum, and additivity) overlap, i.e., how they relate to each other. Furthermore, it remains to be explored whether the two auxiliary verbs differ with respect to the type of information they introduce into the discourse. Having developed pragmatic functions from two lexical deictic motion verbs that are relational antonyms, the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* may provide novel insights into the understudied grammaticalization paths into information structure. The goal of this study is therefore to provide an account of the two auxiliary verbs’ semantic and syntactic properties.

2 Methodology

This study investigates auxiliary *za* and *ya* with pragmatic functions occurring in a sample from three corpora of isiXhosa (henceforth: corpus sample) that were used in the study of tense and aspect of isiXhosa by Savić (2020): the AST (African Speech Technology) Text Corpus compiled by Roux et al. (2001), the Genre Classification Corpus compiled by Snyman et al. (2012), and the NCHLT Text Corpus compiled by Eiselen and Puttkammer (2014). The corpus sample contains about 60,000 words. Approximately one third of the corpus sample used in Savić (2020) consists of original isiXhosa literature, whereas the remaining two thirds include magazine articles (including readers’ letters and cartoons), public announcements and speeches, forms and guidelines which have been translated into isiXhosa. The text excerpts selected by Savić (2020) varied in length and they contained at least one of the target verb forms which exhibited specific tense and aspect categories that were relevant for the study. As has been pointed out in the study of modal necessity in isiXhosa by Crane et al. (2024), an important advantage of using the corpus sample from Savić (2020) is that the texts have already been verified for quality and (at least partly) translated by consultants who are L1 isiXhosa speakers. Furthermore, the corpus sample was initially designed to investigate tense and aspect; hence the

¹⁹ The only example of auxiliary *za* with a pragmatic function provided by Einhorn and Siyengo’s (1993, 47) is *waza wathi* ‘and then he said’. However, they do not provide a description of the construction’s semantics. Therefore it is not possible to conclude whether they suggest that this compound verb can be the main predicate in a sentence.

distribution of other grammatical features across the (parts of) texts selected is randomized. For more details about the corpus sample, see Savić (2020, 26–29) and Crane et al. (2024).

For this study, I extracted all sentences containing auxiliary *za* or *ya* with a subjunctive or a past consecutive complement, including several sentences from the preceding context. No sentences were found with either auxiliary *ya* or auxiliary *za* and a situative complement. In order to understand the semantic properties and distributions of the pragmatic functions of *za* and *ya* described in Section 1.3, I coded the following properties in the corpus extracts:

1. Morphosyntactic properties:

- i) subject agreement, tense, aspect, and mood of the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* and their complements;
- ii) syntactic environment, i.e., preceding syntactic units in the sentence;
- iii) new subject indexing (agreement) or shifts in subject indexing;

2. Semantic and information structural properties:

- iv) temporal and causal relation with the preceding predicates in the sentence or the preceding sentence;
- v) information structure of the predicate: old vs. new information of the event participants and the predicate of the sentence, i.e., the status of the predicate and the arguments based on the preceding context.

My hypothesis was that the results should show whether the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* (and their complements) differ with respect to the syntactic units that precede them in the sentence. Furthermore, the data should shed light on the two auxiliaries’ ability to introduce a new subject discourse referent, i.e., whether they allow a change of subject agreement in relation to the preceding verbs or sentences. In those examples where auxiliary *za* or *ya* marks predicate coordination the results should reveal whether they also imply temporal subsequence and/or a causal relation with the preceding event.

The expression of mirativity can be expected to represent new information, whereas verum focus in emphasized events can be expected to be part of the contrastive focus (e.g., old lexical information about the predicate, whereas its verum constitutes new information). Information structure may also reveal the motivation for emphasizing coordination before a predicate.

The advantage of coding the data for the observable, objective properties listed above is that it offers insights that minimize subjective interpretations. The amount of data is limited and the corpus is not balanced. Therefore, the frequencies of the different types of syntactic environments and the interpretations of each auxiliary are not meant to be viewed as statistically significant (in part due to the limited quantity of data), but should only provide occasional weak implications (whenever they are relevant) about the different productivity levels of the analysed forms and their functions.

3 Results and discussion

As shown in Table 1, in the corpus sample auxiliary *za* occurs more than three times as often as auxiliary *ya*. The two auxiliary verbs differ significantly with respect to their morphological structure, and more precisely their tense, aspect, and mood. Whereas most instances of *za*

include the past consecutive and subjunctive, *ya* is most frequent as a recent past main clause (non-consecutive and non-situative) indicative verb. The tense-aspect marking on the lexical complements (excluded from Table 1) is rather predictable: if the auxiliary verb *za* or *ya* is in the subjunctive, so is the following lexical verb, with only one exception in the database, in which the auxiliary subjunctive is followed by the past consecutive of the lexical verb. In all other cases, the lexical verb is a past consecutive, which is the case with almost all those that are introduced by auxiliary *ya*.

Table 1: The tense and aspect marking (TAM) of the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* (excluding their lexical complements) in the corpus sample.

AUX	Total	RECPST	REMPST	PST.CONS	REMFUT	SBJV	No TAM (CLITIC)
<i>Za</i>	139	-	-	78	-	52	8
					PERF 1		
<i>Ya</i>	41	36	2	-	-	2	-
		REL 1					

As will be shown in the following paragraphs, this distinction is directly linked to the syntactic environment in which the auxiliary verbs and the following lexical verbs occur. In the corpus sample, *za* is much more common mid-sentence (after at least one indicative main verb form), a position typical of coordinated and subordinated predicates, such as the past consecutive (34) and the subjunctive (35), as opposed to the main indicative verb of the clause. By contrast, *ya* mostly introduces the first predicate in the sentence, which is where main (non-consecutive and non-situative) indicative verbs tend to occur (36).

- (34) *U-Constance* *ú-ya-tsho* *ukuba* *ú-pas-é*
 AUG-1A.Constance SM.1-PRS.DISJ-say that SM.3SG-pass-PST
ku-m-sebenzi *wo-ku-coc-a* ***w-a-z-a***
 17-3-job POSS.3-15-clean-FV SM.1SG-CONS-come-FV
w-a-pas-a *na-ko-wo-ku-qhub-a.*
 SM.3SG-CONS-pass-FV COM-15-POSS.3-15-drive-FV
 ‘Constance says that she got (lit. passed at) a cleaning job **and then she got (lit. passed at)** a job as a driver.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

- (35) *Xa* *ii-nyanga* *zi-li-15* *ú-gaq-a*
 when 10-month SM.10-COP.10-fifteen SM.1-crawl-FV
a-nyuk-e *i-zi-tepsi* ***a-z-e***
 SBJV.SM.1-climb-SBJV AUG-10-stairs SBJV.SM.1-come-SBJV
a-ze-hl-e *e-hamb-a* *ngomva.*
 SBJV.SM.1.-OM.10-descend-SBJV SIT.SM.1-walk-FV backwards
 ‘When (the baby is) 15 months old, it crawls up the stairs **and walks down** the stairs backwards.’ (Snyman et al. 2012)

- (36) *Emveni k-oko* *si-y-é* *s-a-hlaziya*
 after POSS.17-DEM.17.MED SM.1PL-go-PST SM.1PL-CONS-renovate-FV
u-m-zi *ng-ee-njongo* *zo-ku-wu-coc-a*.
 AUG-3-house INSTR-10-objective POSS.10-15-OM.3-clean-FV
 ‘After that we **tidied up** (lit. **renovated**) the house with the intention of cleaning it’.
 (Roux et al. 2001)

3.1 Syntactic environment

As shown in the previous section and in Table 2, auxiliary *za* typically introduces coordinated predicates, which follow other (main indicative, subjunctive, or past consecutive) predicates in the sentence. By contrast, *ya* tends to introduce main predicates, often at the beginning of a sentence. Although subordinate predicates do not seem to be particularly frequent with either auxiliary, *ya* shows higher frequencies than *za*.

Table 2: Distribution of the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* across main indicative (non-consecutive and non-situative) predicates and coordinated and subordinate clauses.

AUX	Total	Main indicative clause (excl. coordination)	Coordinated clause	Subordinate clause
<i>Za</i>	139	8 (5.76%)	126 (90.65%)	5 (3.6%)
		----- sentence-initial: 3 (2.16%)		
<i>Ya</i>	41	30 (73.17%)	2 (4.88%)	9 (21.95%)
		----- sentence-initial: 32 (78.05%)		

In all the five instances of auxiliary *za* occurring in subordinate clauses, the compound verb expresses modal semantics rather than exhibiting pragmatic functions. Although auxiliary *za* in the corpus example (37) denotes a request and not a directive, this use seems to be more closely related to the function of deontic modality of the subjunctive auxiliary *za* with subjunctive complements, as described in Section 1.2. Therefore, corpus data with this auxiliary in subordinate clauses will not be elaborated on further in this discussion.

- (37) *Ú-m-ceng-ile* *u-Khuselwa* *u-Nambitha* *ukuba*
 SM.1-OM.1-beg-PST.DISJ AUG-1A-Khuselwa AUG-1A-Nambitha that
a-z-e *a-man-e* *e-nxibelelan-a* *na-ye*
 SBJV.SM.1-come-SBJV SBJV.SM.1-often_do-SBJV SIT.SM.1-be_connected-FV COM-OM.1
ngo-m-nxeba *xa* *e-na-lo* *i-thuba* *lo-ko*.
 INSTR-3-telephone when SIT.SM.1-COM-OM.5 AUG-5.opportunity POSS.5-DEM.17.MED
 ‘Nambitha asked Khuselwa **to keep in touch** with her on the phone whenever she had the opportunity’ (Roux et al. 2001)

With respect to the shift in subject indexing, both auxiliaries introduce a high number of new subjects relative to the preceding context. However, auxiliary *ya* exhibits this feature twice as

often (relative to its total number of occurrences) as auxiliary *za*. Consistently with the two auxiliary verbs’ distribution across main, coordinated, and subordinate clauses (see Table 2), *za* tends to shift to new subject marking in coordinated predicates relative to subject marking in the preceding predicate of the same clause, whereas *ya* typically (re)introduces a subject in a new sentence.

Table 3: Subject indexation shift in auxiliary *za* and *ya* across main indicative (non-consecutive and non-situative) predicates and in coordinated and subordinate clauses.

AUX	Total	New subject indexation	In main clauses (excl. coordination)	In coordinated clauses	In subordinate clauses
<i>Za</i>	139	48 (34.53%)	7 (14.59% of all aux. <i>za</i> with subject shift)	37 (77.08% of all aux. <i>za</i> with subject shift)	4 (8.33% of all aux. <i>za</i> with subject shift)
<i>Ya</i>	41	28 (68.29%)	22 (78.57% of all aux. <i>ya</i> with subject shift)	1 (3.57% of all aux. <i>ya</i> with subject shift)	5 (17.86% of all aux. <i>ya</i> with subject shift)

Another striking contrast between the two auxiliaries is that no examples have been found in which the auxiliary *ya* is separated from its lexical complement, while it is common for one or more constituents (in 19 out of 48 instances), most often the subject (16 out of 48 instances), to be inserted between the auxiliary *za* and its lexical complement; see (38).

- (38) *“Bendi-fun-a u-ku-khul-a e-ku-sasaz-eni*
 SM.1SG.PST-want-IPFV AUG-15-grow-FV LOC-15-broadcast-LOC
w-a-z-a u-Andile w-a-ndi-vul-el-a
 SM.1-CONS-come-FV AUG-1A.Andile SM.1-CONS-OM.1SG-open-APPL-FV
ii-ngcango,” ú-tsh-ilo u-Bonang.
 AUG-10.door SM.1-say-PST AUG-1A.Bonang
 ‘‘I wanted to pursue a career as a presenter (lit. grow in presenting) and then Andile opened the doors for me,’’ said Bonang.’ (Snyman et al. 2012)

The auxiliary verb *ya* frequently refers to a different subject (relative to the preceding discourse) at the beginning of a sentence (39), or in a subordinate clause (40). However, it can also occur as the first verb in or after direct speech (41), or even at the beginning of a text (42), without a subject reference from the preceding discourse.

- (39) *Aku-zange ku-b-e-kho no-m-nye u-m-ntu*
 SM.15-never_do SM.15-be-PST-EXIST COM-1-one AUG-1-person
o-z-e ku-si-buz-a i-nto esi-yi-hamb-el-e-yo.
 REL.1-come-PST 15-OM.1PL-ask-FV AUG-9.thing REL.1PL-OM.9-walk-APPL-PST-REL.DISJ
I-y-é y-a-phel-a i-yure si-ku-le shedi.
 SM.9-go-PST SM.9-CONS-finish-FV AUG-hour SIT.SM.1PL-17-DEM.9.PROX 9.shed
 ‘No one came (lit. there was no one who came) to ask what we were there for. We spent an hour (lit. an hour went by) sitting in that shed.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

- (40) *A-nga-ma-doda* *a-soloko* *e-rhan-el-wa* *ngokuba*
 SM.6-COP.6-6-man SM.6-always_do SIT.SM.6-suspect-APPL-PASS-FV that
a-ne-AIDS *kangangokuba*
 SM.6-COM-9.AIDS so_much_so
a-y-e *a-xilong-el-w-e* *le*
 SM.6-go- SBJV SM.6-diagnose-APPL-PASS-SBJV DEM.9.PROX
ntsholongwane *e-ng-azi-s-w-anga.*
 9.virus SIT.SM.1-NEG-know-CAUS-PASS-NEG.PST
 ‘(Gay) Men (lit. **those who are men**) are always suspected of having AIDS to the extent that **they get diagnosed** without knowing.’ (Roux et al. 2001)
- (41) “*W-edwa nje qha Bra_Ciks?*”
 2SG-alone just only 1A.Bra_Ciks
w-a-y-a *w-a-buz-a* *u-Spokes.*
 SM.1-CONS-go-FV SM.1-CONS-ask-FV AUG-1A.Spokes
 “‘Were you alone, Bra Ciks?’ Spokes **asked.**’ (Roux et al. 2001)
- (42) *Ii-ndaba* *ezi-vel-a* *kwi-FIT*
 AUG-10.news REL.10-come_from-FV 17-9.FIT
I-FIT *i-y-é* *y-a-khuph-a* *i-ngxelo*
 AUG-9.FIT SM.9-go-PST SM.9-CONS-take_out-FV AUG-9.statement
e-y-a *ku-ma-jelo* *ee-ndaba*
 REL.9-go-FV 17-6-source POSS.6-10.news
apho *ibi-s-enz-a* *i-s-aziso (...)*
 REL.THERE SM.9.PST-SIT-do-IPFV AUG-7-announcement
 ‘News by FIT
 FIT **has issued** a press release announcing (...)’ (Snyman et al. 2012)

Although the numbers in Tables 2 and 3 are not meant to indicate statistical significance (see Section 2) about the morphosyntactic properties of *za* and *ya*, they point towards the functional domains in which the two auxiliary verbs differ. *Za* seems to require a preceding predicate as in most cases it signals coordination. However, this explanation might not hold true in those instances where *za* occurs in subordinate clauses. The functional properties of *ya* are even less transparent and they can be better understood with insights about the information structure in the sentences in which auxiliary *ya* occurs. These information structural properties are discussed in Section 3.2.

3.2 Information structure

In this section I discuss the **discourse new** and **discourse old** information provided by the auxiliary *za*, the auxiliary *ya*, and their lexical complements in the corpus data. The temporal and causal relation between the events denoted by these compound verbs and the preceding discourse will only be addressed when relevant for the discussion.

Both auxiliary *za* and *ya* introduce discourse new information about predicates by linking them to discourse old referents. Thus, in the numerous examples in which auxiliary *za* retains

the same subject indexation as in the preceding clause, the new discourse information comprises the predicate, e.g., *waza wapasa nakowokuqhuba* ‘(and then she) got the job as a driver’ in (34), repeated here as (43). The event denoted by the second clause with auxiliary *za* occurs after the event from the first clause, thus implying that the two propositions are temporally related.

- (43) *U-Constance* *ú-ya-tsho* *ukuba* *ú-pas-é*
 AUG-1A.Constance SM.1-PRS.DISJ-say that SM.3SG-PASS-PST
ku-m-sebenzi *wo-ku-coc-a* ***w-a-z-a***
 17-3-job POSS.3-15-clean-FV SM.1SG-CONS-COME-FV
w-a-pas-a *na-ko-wo-ku-qhub-a.*
 SM.3SG-CONS-PASS-FV COM-15-POSS.3-15-drive-FV
 ‘Constance says that she got (lit. passed at) a cleaning job **and then she got** (lit. passed at) a job as a driver.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

Even when the auxiliary *za* exhibits subject indexation shift, the subject can be discourse old. Thus, in the first sentence in (44), *ikhompyutha* ‘computer’ is a locative argument, but it becomes the subject in the following sentence. Similarly, in example (45), auxiliary *za* agrees with the subject (*yena* ‘she/he’) that has been mentioned for the first time in the preceding clause (*umntu ongaziwayo* ‘unknown person’) within the same sentence.

- (44) *Apho,* *oo-nobhala* *ba-wa-fak-a* *kwi-ikhompyutha loo* *ma-nani.*
 there AUG-2A.clerk SM.2-OM.6-put_in-FV 17-9.computer DEM.6.MED 6-number
I-z-e *i-ikhompyutha* ***i-khuph-e*** *i-mali*
 SM.9-COME-SBJV AUG-9.computer SM.9-take_out-SBJV AUG-9.money
eku-funek-a *u-yi-hlawul-e.*
 REL.17-be_necessary-FV SM.2SG-OM.9-pay-SBJV
 ‘There (at Eskom or the municipal offices), the clerks enter those numbers (from the electricity meters) into a computer. **And then** the computer **generates** the amount you have to pay.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

- (45) *Le* *ncwadi* *y-a-thunyel-el-w-a* *u-m-hleli*
 DEM.9.PROX 9.letter SM.9-CONS-send-APPL-PASS-FV AUG-1-editor
we-phepha_ndaba *ngu-m-ntu* *o-ng-az-iw-a-yo,*
 POSS.1-5.newspaper COP.1-1-person REL.1-NEG-know-PASS-FV-REL.DISJ
w-a-z-a *yena* ***w-a-yi-thumel-a***
 SM.1-CONS-COME-FV PRON.1 SM.1-CONS-OM.9-send-FV
ku-Mongameli_Mandela *ngaphambi* *ko-kuba* *a-yi-shicilel-el-e*
 17-1A.President_Mandela before 17-that SM.1-OM.9-publish-APPL-SBJV
e-phepha_ndab-eni *la-khe.*
 LOC -5.newspaper-LOC POSS.5-1
 ‘The letter was sent to a newspaper editor by an unknown person, **who** (in turn) **sent it** to President Mandela before publishing it in his newspaper.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

Although temporal subsequence and/or causation can be interpreted as the link enabling the coordination between auxiliary *za* and the preceding predicates in (44–45), they cannot be viewed as the invariable part of this compound verb’s function. In Section 1.3, the same conclusion was drawn about auxiliary *za* in example (6=29), repeated here as (46). Similarly, in the description of a prison building in (47), *zazakhiwe* (*ngqindilili*) (lit. ‘were built thick’) and the subsequent auxiliary *za* with the past consecutive *kwafakwa* (*iintsimbi ezikwangqindilili*) (lit. ‘there were (bars) put in (that were also thick)’) do not refer to chronologically ordered events of building the prison. Instead, *kwaza* merely encodes the information about the qualities of the walls and the barred windows in the form of two coordinated predicates.

- (46) *Mhlawumbi* *u-makhulu* *wa-kho* *w-â-xelexela*
 maybe AUG-1A.grandmother POSS.1-2SG SM.1-REMPST-tell-FV
u-mama *wa-kho* ***w-a-z-a*** *u-khokho*
 AUG-1A.mother POSS.1-2SG SM.1-CONS-COME-FV AUG-1A.ancestor
wa-kho ***w-a-xelexela*** *u-makhulu* *wa-kho*.
 POSS.1-2SG SM.1-CONS-tell-FV AUG-1A.grandmother POSS.1-2SG
 ‘Perhaps your grandmother told this (about the benefits of breastfeeding) to your mother, **and** your (older female) ancestor **had told** this to your grandmother.’
 (Roux et al. 2001)

- (47) *Ii-ndonga* *za-le* *ndawo* *zaz-akh-iw-é*
 AUG-10.wall POSS.10-DEM.9.PROX 9.place SM.10.REMPST-build-PASS-ANT
ngqindilili ***kw-a-z-a*** ***kw-a-fak-w-a***
 thick SM.15-CONS-COME-FV SM.15-CONS-put_in-PASS-FV
ii-ntsimbi *ezi-kwa-ngqindilili* *na-se-zi-festile-ni*.
 AUG-10.iron REL.15-ADD-thick COM-LOC-10-window-LOC
 ‘The walls in this place were thick (lit. built thick) **and** the windows were also **barred** with thick iron (lit. **and** bars **were put** in the windows that were also thick)’
 (Roux et al. 2001)

Auxiliary *za* may introduce discourse new subjects, such as the non-specific referent *ukhokho* ‘ancestor’ in (46), where the old information refers to the non-specific *umakhulu* ‘grandmother’, as well as the type of event, *xelela* ‘tell’, repeated from the preceding clause. Similarly, the impersonal subject *kwaza* in (47) cannot constitute old information and the object (*iintsimbi ezikwangqindilili* ‘thick bars’) has not been mentioned before, yet the locational reference to the prison walls has been implicitly transferred from the preceding clause.

Auxiliary *za* does not require the arguments in the predicate it introduces to have a specific discourse status. Instead it builds on another proposition from the preceding discourse, with which it establishes a semantic link based on any elements (same event participant, location, event sequence, type of event, etc.) they may have in common. At the discourse level, two propositions connected by the auxiliary *za* exhibit an additive relation (see Ferrari et al. 2008, 125; Forker 2016; De Cesare 2017, 3) in that both point to the same conclusion.

Unlike auxiliary *za*, auxiliary *ya* links discourse new predicates to discourse old constituents. In (7=32), repeated here as (48), *ya* introduces a new event that involves a discourse old subject, while preparing the readers for information about the scars on the subject’s body that were

revealed while he was changing the shirt. In (41), repeated here as (49), auxiliary *ya* links the utterance in direct speech to a discourse old subject (Spokes).

- (48) *Ú-th-é emva ko-kuba e-tsh-ilo w-a-phakam-a*
 SM.1-DO-PST after POSS.17-that SIT.SM.1-say-PST SM.1-CONS-get_up-FV
w-a-y-a e-wodrobh-ini ya-khe w-a-khuph-a
 SM.1-CONS-go-FV LOC-9.wardrobe-LOC POSS.9-1 SM.1-CONS-take_out-FV
e-nye i-hempe. Ú-y-é w-a-yi-khulul-a
 ADJ.9-one AUG-9.shirt SM.1-go-PST SM.1-CONS-OM.9-take_off-FV
le bendi-fik-é e-yi-nxib-ile
 DEM.PROX.9 SM.1SG.PST-arrive-ANT REL.9-OM.9-put_on-ANT.DJ
w-a-z-a w-a-nxib-a le.
 SM.1-CONS-come-FV SM.1-CONS-put_on_FV DEM.9.PROX
 ‘After he said that, he stood up and went to his wardrobe and took out one of his shirts. **He took off** the one he was wearing when I arrived and put on another one.’
 (Roux et al. 2001)

- (49) “*W-edwa nje qha Bra_Ciks?*”
 2SG-alone just only 1A.Bra_Ciks
w-a-y-a w-a-buz-a u-Spokes.
 SM.1-CONS-go-FV SM.1-CONS-ask-FV AUG-1A.Spokes
 ‘“Were you alone, Bra Ciks?” Spokes **asked**.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

The old information that links the auxiliary *ya* to the preceding discourse need not be the subject. In (42), repeated here as (50), the subject *iyure* ‘(an) hour’ is a discourse new specification of the time spent in the waiting area, whereas the situative *sikule shedi* (‘us being in the shed’) is a subordinate clause that provides old information.

- (50) *Aku-zange ku-b-e-kho no-m-nye u-m-ntu*
 SM.15-never_do SM.15-be-PST-EXIST COM-ADJ.1-one AUG-1-person
o-z-é ku-si-buz-a i-nto esi-yi-hamb-el-e-yo.
 REL.1-come-PST 15-OM.1PL-ask-FV AUG-9.thing REL.1PL-OM.9-walk-APPL-PST-REL.DISJ
I-y-é y-a-phel-a i-yure si-ku-le shedi.
 SM.9-go-PST SM.9-CONS-finish-FV AUG-hour SIT.SM.1PL-17-DEM.9.PROX 9.shed
 ‘No one came (lit. there was no one who came) to ask what we were there for. We spent **an hour** (lit. **an hour went by**) sitting in that shed.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

As already shown in Section 3.1, auxiliary *ya* can introduce the first predicate in a text; see (51–52). Therefore, similar to auxiliary *za*, auxiliary *ya* does not entail that there is a temporal or causal relation with the preceding discourse. Likewise, in (51–52) the subjects cannot be described as discourse old. However, they can be interpreted as the topic, as implied by the text title in (51). Similarly, in (52) the possessor noun phrase within the ‘heavy constituent’ subject, *wenkqubo yosasazo ethandwayo e-US* ‘of a popular talk show in the US’, helps identify the talk show host Oprah Winfrey as the topic of the text. Thus, auxiliary *ya* describes topic constituents

in overtly marked discourse new, focus predicates (cf. the development of isiXhosa *ya* as a predicate focus marker in Heine et al. (1993, 110)).²⁰

- (51) *Ii-ndaba ezi-vel-a kwi-FIT*
 AUG-10.news REL.10-come_from-FV 17-9.FIT
I-FIT i-y-é y-a-khuph-a i-ngxelo
 AUG-9.FIT SM.9-go-PST SM.9-CONS-take_out-FV AUG-9.statement
e-y-a ku-ma-jelo ee-ndaba
 REL.9-go-FV 17-6-source POSS.6-10.news
apho ibi-s-enz-a i-s-aziso (...)
 REL.THERE SM.9.PST-SIT-do-IPFV AUG-7-announcement
 ‘News by FIT
 FIT **has issued** a press release announcing (...)’ (Snyman et al. 2012)

- (52) *U-Oprah_Winfrey we-nkqubo yo-sasazo*
 AUG-1A.Oprah_Winfrey POSS.1-9.programme POSS.9-1A.broadcast
e-thand-w-a-yo e-U.S. ú-y-é w-a-zam-a
 SIT.SM.1-love-PASS-FV-REL.DISJ LOC-U.S. SM.1-go-PST SM.1-CONS-try-FV
u-ku-wa-diliz-a a-ma-nqatha a-se-m-zimb-eni wa-khe
 AUG-15-OM.6-break_down-FV AUG-6-fat REL.6-LOC-3-body-LOC POSS.3-1
ku-ma-shumi a-ma-bini e-mi-nyaka.
 17-6-ten AUG-6-two POSS.6-4-year
 ‘Oprah Winfrey, a talk show host from US **tried** to shed body fat for 20 years.’
 (Roux et al. 2001)

In subordinate clauses, auxiliary *ya* provides new information about topic constituents from the main clause; see (53–54). In the adverbial clause in (53), the secret diagnoses referred to in the adverbial clause constitute focused information emphasizing the extent of the discrimination against gay men, which is provided as old information in the preceding main clause. In the relative clause in (54), even though the first person singular subject cannot be considered discourse old information, the predicate can be viewed as focused information which identifies the antecedent noun phrase from the main clause, *olona tshintsho* ‘the change’.

- (53) *A-nga-ma-doda a-soloko e-rhan-el-wa ngokuba*
 SM.6-COP.6-6-man SM.6-always_do SIT.SM.6-suspect-APPL-PASS-FV that
a-ne-AIDS kangangokuba
 SM.6-COM-9.AIDS so_much_so
a-y-e a-xilong-el-w-e le
 SM.6-go-SBJV SM.6-diagnose-APPL-PASS-SBJV DEM.9.PROX

²⁰ A similar grammaticalization of the Shangaci verb *entta* ‘go’ as a predicate focus marker has also been described by Devos and van der Wal (2010).

ntsholongwane e-ng-azi-s-w-anga.
9.virus SIT.SM.1-NEG-know-CAUS-PASS-NEG.PST

‘(Gay) Men (lit. those who are men) are always suspected of having AIDS to the extent that **they get diagnosed** without knowing’ (Roux et al. 2001)

(54) *O-lona tshintsho ndi-y-é nd-a-lw-enz-a*
SUPERL-11.PRON 11.change SM.1SG-go-PST SM.1-CONS-OM.11-do-FV
lo-lu-ngo-ko-moya, ú-tsh-ilo.
COP.11-DEM.11.PROX-INSTR-POSS.15-3.spirit SM.1-say-PST

‘‘The change **that I have made** is a spiritual one’’, she said.’ (Roux et al. 2001)

The focused information from the predicate introduced by the auxiliary *ya* need not introduce lexical information. The corpus data confirm the observation from Section 1.3 that focus can also consist only of the verum, i.e., the truth-conditionality of the proposition (cf. Gutzmann et al. 2020; Bloom Ström and Zeller 2023). This is demonstrated in (55). In the last clause the discourse old noun phrase *iziprofeto zale ndoda* ‘the prophecy of that man’ refers to the preceding utterance in direct speech, whereas the new information (and focus) in the predicate only pertains to the confirmation that the prophecy has come true.

(55) ‘‘*U-nyana wa-kho aka-sokuze*
AUG-1A.SON POSS.1-2SG NEG.SM.1-never_do
a-phumelel-e e-si-kolw-eni.’’
SBJV.SM.1-succeed-SBJV LOC-7-school-LOC
‘‘Nge-nene i-zi-profeto za-le ndoda
INSTR-9.truth AUG-8-prophecy POSS.8-DEM.9.PROX 9.man
zi-y-é z-a-yi-nyani.’’
SM.8-go-PST SM.8-CONS-COP.9-9.truth

‘‘Your son will never succeed in school.’’ Indeed the prophecy of that man **came true**.’ (Snyman et al. 2012)

A focus predicate with auxiliary *ya* can also indicate a contrastive topic.²¹ In example (56), the main clause *uye ucinge* ‘you think’ and the following subordinate clause *ukuba awunako ukwenza into* ‘that you cannot do something’ refer to beliefs presumed to be held by the hearers and can therefore not be regarded as new information. Instead, they are contradicted in the following clauses, *kodwa usuke uzibone ukwimeko ekunyanzelisa* ‘but then you find yourself in a situation that forces you’ and *ukuba ume ngeenyawo* ‘that you stand in your feet’.

(56) ‘‘*U-y-e u-cing-e ukuba awu-nako*
SM.2SG-go-SBJV SM.2SG-think-SBJV that NEG.SM.2SG-POSS
u-kw-enz-a i-nto, kodwa u-suk-e
AUG-15-do-FV AUG-9.thing but SM.2SG-suddenly_do-SBJV

²¹ For a discussion on the distinction between contrastive topic and contrastive focus, see Neeleman et al. (2009).

u-zi-bon-e *u-kwi-meko* *e-ku-nyanzelis-a*
 SM.2SG-REFL-see-SBJV SM.2SG-17-9.situation REL.9-OM.2SG-force-FV

ukuba u-m-e *ng-ee-nyawo.*”
 that SM.2SG-stand-SBJV INSTR-10-foot

‘**You think** you cannot do something, but then you find yourself in a situation that forces you to stand on your feet.’ (Snyman et al. 2012)

In (56), the topic is the predicate of the first subordinate clause *ukuba awunako ukwenza into* ‘that you cannot do something’. In this case, the auxiliary *ya* does not mark a focused predicate but a contrastive topic of the proposition, which is contradicted in the upcoming discourse.

4 Conclusion

Auxiliary *za* introduces a predicate that combines with the preceding predicate to create a shared implication, irrespective of the discourse status of the individual constituents. The semantic link between the two propositions is based on the temporal-causal relation between the events, or on other similar properties such as location, event participants, or event type. While semantically resembling the functions of an additive marker (see Forker 2016), auxiliary *za* still behaves like a coordinating marker between two overtly expressed propositions (see De Cesare 2017, 3–4).

Auxiliary *ya* either introduces focused information in a new predicate that pertains to a topic constituent, or marks contrastive topic in a predicate which will be contradicted in the upcoming discourse; see Table 4.

Table 4: The different information structures encoded in the auxiliaries *za* and *ya*

Preceding discourse	Information encoded by the auxiliary verb	AUX
proposition	new (coordinated) predicate	za
topic constituent	focused predicate (incl. verum) or contrast	ya

This study shows the grammaticalization path of motion verbs in the domain of information structure. In isiXhosa, both *za* and *ya* introduce a new proposition into the discourse. Their functions differ with respect to the discourse status of the predicate. Thus, ventive *za* indicates that the predicate is semantically related to another predicate. As equal syntactic structures, the two predicates are connected through coordination without implying a specific discourse status of any elements. By contrast, itive *ya* provides new information about a topic constituent which includes a new predicate, proposition verum, or contrast.

The potential link between the pragmatic and temporal properties of the auxiliaries *za* and *ya* is noteworthy. In the domain of tense, *za* functions as the default, unmarked future auxiliary, whereas *ya* denotes discontinuous future. In past and future tense compound verbs marking aspect, *ya* is also the auxiliary which is usually restricted to the remote past, i.e., the discontinuous past. Similarly, at the information structural level, *ya* differs from *za* in that it indicates that the clause contains new information about topicalized constituents.

Abbreviations

1A, 2A, 1–17	noun classes 1A, 2A, 1–17
1SG, 2SG	1st and 2nd person singular
1PL, 2PL	1st and 2nd person plural
ADD	additive
ADJ	adjective
ANT	anterior
APPL	applicative
AUG	augment
CAUS	causative
COM	comitative
CONS	past consecutive
COP	copula
DEM	demonstrative
DISJ	disjoint
DIST	distal
EXIST	existential
FUT	near future
FV	final vowel
HORT	hortative
INSTR	instrumental
IMP	imperative
IMPF	imperfective
LOC	locative
MED	medial
NEG	negation
OM	object marker
PASS	passive
PERF	perfect
POSS	possessive prefix
PRO	prospective
PROX	proximal
PST	recent past
REL	relative
REMFUT	remote future
REMPST	remote past
SBJV	subjunctive
SIT	situative
SM	subject marker
SUPERL	superlative

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Auxiliary Stacking in Southern Bantu Languages

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Abstract

Auxiliary constructions in Southern Bantu exhibit a feature in which two or more auxiliaries appear alongside a single lexical verb. We term this construction ‘auxiliary stacking’. The goal of the paper is to outline the phenomenon of auxiliary stacking in Southern Bantu and raise questions about its features and limits. We focus on what we currently know in terms of features of variation associated with auxiliary stacking, namely a) ordering of stacked auxiliaries, b) number of auxiliaries permitted, c) subject marking properties, and d) the semantics of these auxiliary stacking constructions. We also look at other features such as tense-aspect-mood, as well as modality and negation. The article then sets out areas for further investigation via a systematic study of auxiliary stacking constructions in Southern Bantu and serves as a call for future targeted research on these constructions.

Keywords: multiple-auxiliary constructions, auxiliary chains, Bantu Zone S, auxiliary order

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1 Introduction

Auxiliary constructions are an important feature of Bantu languages. However, these constructions are often under-documented and under-described. This may in part be due to focus on the complex agglutinative morphology of single-verb forms. It may also be due to the more complex and often subtle nuances associated with the interpretations of compound constructions. It is also naturally part of the under-described nature of the Bantu languages more broadly.

This paper examines the co-occurrence of auxiliary forms in a single construction, found commonly across Southern Bantu, which we term ‘auxiliary stacking’ (following Gibson 2025). In these construction types, two or more auxiliaries can appear alongside a single-verb form. An example of this from siSwati is shown in (1) below, where the verb *shona* ‘set’ is preceded by two auxiliary forms *hlala* and *sheshe*.

- (1) siSwati (Nkuna et al. 2021, 231; example and glosses adjusted)¹
Lilanga li-hlala li-sheshe li-shon-e ebusika.
5.sun SM₅-AUX[HAB] SM₅.SIT-AUX[quickly] SM₅-set-SBJV LOC.14.winter
‘The sun always sets quickly in winter.’

Another example of auxiliary stacking can be seen in (2), from Sesotho sa Leboa, where a construction of two auxiliaries preceding a perfective-marked verb expresses the meaning ‘had already X-ed’.

- (2) Sesotho sa Leboa (Mphasha et al. 2021, 364)
Ba-be ba-šetše ba-sepetš-e.
SM₂-AUX[be(PST)] SM₂.SIT-AUX[already] SM₂.SIT-leave-PFV
‘They had already left.’

We define auxiliaries as verbal forms that modify a lexical verb, share its subject, and form a single predicate with it. They are ‘bound’ to the lexical verb (see Haspelmath 2024) and cannot appear without it when used with their auxiliary (grammatical) functions.² A set of stacked

¹ We have added glosses when none were given, and in all cases have adjusted authors’ original glossing to match our conventions, as listed in the abbreviations section at the end of this article. Sometimes, our morphological analyses differ from those of the original works (e.g., what we gloss as PFV is sometimes described as PERF or PST, based on our typological understanding of the category; see Crane and Persohn 2019). We adopt the orthographic conventions of the original works, but we adjust word boundaries to represent (to the best of our ability) linguistic rather than orthographic words where necessary. Our orthographic representations do not represent an analysis. We have attempted to characterize the functions of the auxiliaries in our examples, putting their functions in square brackets. These should be understood as rough approximations, because many auxiliaries are multi-functional and context-dependent, or have meanings that are difficult to pin down. For multifunctional auxiliaries, we attempt to indicate the contextually relevant function, so the function given in brackets for a specific auxiliary form may differ from example to example. We repeat some examples across sections when they best illustrate the phenomena under discussion, and because the examples are used to illustrate different phenomena, we do not always explicitly note these repetitions. We note that one of the most illustrative examples, for which we do not currently have an alternative example, refers to gender-based violence in a problematic manner (see Kotek et al. 2021 for more discussion of these issues and on how to avoid biased and stereotyping examples).

² Some auxiliaries also function as lexical verbs with meanings distinct from their grammatical functions. For example, the isiZulu lexical verb *buya* ‘return’ has a corresponding auxiliary form *buye* ‘[do] again’ (Mkhatshwa 1991, 126). A few, mostly modal, auxiliaries are less obligatorily bound to the following lexical verb, in that they can appear on their own in cases of ellipsis (as with English *I can [do it]*).

auxiliaries also forms a single predicate with a main verb. Auxiliaries are nearly always followed in Southern Bantu languages by one or more of three verb forms: situative (often called ‘participial’), subjunctive (a type that is closely related to and frequently alternates with past ‘consecutive’ verb forms), or infinitive-marked verbs. A full description of the formal properties of auxiliaries as a class in Southern Bantu languages is beyond the scope of this paper. For extensive details of how these systems can play out, see, for example, Creissels (forthcoming, this volume) on Setswana.

Auxiliary stacking constructions are common in Southern Bantu. This article draws on data from eleven major Southern Bantu varieties, all of which exhibit extensive auxiliary stacking, as evidenced in the descriptive literature and in our own investigations: Tshivenda (‘Guthrie’ code S21, ISO 639-3 ven), Silozi (K21, loz), Setswana (S31, tsn), Sesotho sa Leboa (S32, nso), Sesotho (S33, sot), isiNdebele (Southern Ndebele, S408, nbl), isiXhosa (S41, xho), isiZulu (S42, zul), siSwati (S43, ssw), Ndebele (Ndebele of Zimbabwe, S44, nde), and Xitsonga (S51, tsc).³ There are comparable constructions in languages of the North-West Bantu zone (Mark Van de Velde, conversation with authors, September 23–24, 2025; Van de Velde 2008) and in African languages outside of Bantu, such as Dinka (Western Nilotic; see Andersen 2007). However, auxiliary stacking constructions do not appear to be widespread in Eastern Bantu languages, Southern Bantu’s nearest relatives.

This article provides an overview of auxiliary stacking in Southern Bantu. We introduce the phenomenon, locate it within the broader context of auxiliary constructions in Bantu more widely, and describe regularly occurring features and potential points of variation. Systematic, in-depth data on auxiliary stacking constructions are lacking for most of Southern Bantu, so an additional goal of this paper is to lay out a set of investigative questions we believe are important for understanding auxiliary stacking in Southern Bantu and beyond.

The article is structured as follows. Section 2 describes morphosyntactic properties of auxiliary stacking constructions, including the possible orderings of auxiliaries, whether it is possible for intervening elements to occur within stacking constructions, the number of auxiliaries that can co-occur in a stacking construction, subject-marking properties, selectional properties, and tense/aspect/mood/polarity (TAMP) inflections. Section 3 briefly addresses other relevant topics for which we have little comparative data, but which seem likely to be significant for the understanding of auxiliary stacking constructions. These include semantic (non-)compositionality, the co-occurrence of auxiliaries with similar meanings, and the morphophonology and prosody of auxiliary stacking constructions. Section 4 constitutes a concise summary and summarizes avenues for future research.

The examples in this paper come from published descriptions, from corpora (often based on translated texts), and from personal communications with collaborators.

2 Morphosyntactic properties of stacked auxiliaries in the languages of the study

This section lays out the morphosyntactic properties of auxiliary stacking constructions as they occur in the descriptive literature and online data we consulted. As noted, these include the potential limits of stacking constructions in terms of the number of auxiliaries (Section 2.1), the ordering of auxiliaries (Section 2.2), whether intervening elements can occur (Section 2.3), subject-marking properties of auxiliaries (Section 2.4), complement selecting properties (Section 2.5), and how elements can be inflected for TAMP (Section 2.6), all with a focus on

³For more information on these languages and their historical relationships, see, e.g., Gunnink et al. (2023).

- (8) Sesotho (Gowlett 2003, 635)
ǎ-nè *á-k'è* *à-láli*
 SM₁-AUX[PST] SM₁.SIT-AUX[occasionally] SM₁.CSC-AUX.HAB[at_night]
á-ithút'-à
 SM₁.SIT-study-FV
 'He used occasionally to spend the night studying.'

An example with four auxiliaries is given in (9). In our data, stacking constructions with four auxiliaries are attested in isiNdebele, isiXhosa, and Setswana.

- (9) isiNdebele (M. P. Mabena, email, January 28, 2025)
A-ngekhe *a-be* *a-sa-kwazi*
 SM₁-AUX[NEG.FUT/POT] SM₁-AUX.SBJV[be] SM₁.SIT-PERS-AUX[POSSIBILITY]
uku-buya *a-sebenz-e.*
 INF-AUX[again] SM₁-work-SBJV
 'S/he will never be able to work again.'

For Setswana, there is a published example with five auxiliary forms in a construction (10). We do not know how common such constructions are in natural contexts, but this example shows that stacking constructions with five auxiliaries are possible, at least in Setswana.

- (10) Setswana (Setshedi 1974, 51)
Monna yola *o-nê* *a-bile* *a-ise*
 1.man DEM₁ SM₁-AUX[PST] SM₁.SIT-AUX[furthermore] SM₁.SIT-AUX[NEG]
a-ke *a-bo* *a-tsene* *mo-moweng*
 SM₁.SIT-AUX[POT/never] SM₁.SIT-AUX[impatience] SM₁.SIT-enter.PFV LOC-1.air.LOC
wame.
 POSS.PRON_{1/1SG}
 'For that matter, that man had never really appealed to my feelings.'
 More literal translation: 'That man has never even got into my spirit.' (Kearabetswe Rammala, email to authors, December 8, 2025)

We suggest the following questions for a future systematic, dedicated study of the number of auxiliaries that can co-occur in stacking constructions:

1. Do all languages exhibit the same distribution in terms of the number of auxiliaries permitted in a stacking construction? That is, is it possible to have two, three, four, and five auxiliaries combined in a single complex in all Southern Bantu languages?
2. What is the relative frequency of the number of auxiliaries in auxiliary constructions (both single-auxiliary constructions and stacking constructions), within varieties and in Southern Bantu as a group?
3. Can all auxiliary forms combine with the same number of other auxiliaries or are there any restrictions by auxiliary type or by specific auxiliary?

2.2 Order of auxiliaries

Little appears to have been written about restrictions, or lack thereof, on the ordering of auxiliaries within these stacking constructions in Southern Bantu. In at least some languages, varying orders are attested, but there is also evidence for restricted (or at least preferential) ordering with certain collocations.

Pietraszko (2018) proposes a distinction between auxiliaries in Ndebele (Zimbabwe) that select for subjunctive complements and those that select for situative (which she terms *participle*) complements. She proposes that the latter “realize functional heads” (2018, 315) and are bound by the same ordering constraints that apply to these heads, so that *se* ‘already’ (which Pietraszko 2018, 315 analyses as PerfP) cannot appear before *hlezi* ‘constantly’ or *lokhe* ‘still’, both of which Pietraszko (2018, 315) analyses as realizing AspP (Aspectual Phrase). Pietraszko (2018, 315) also notes that the order of *hlezi* and *lokhe* with respect to one another is not fixed.⁴

Lee and Hlungwani (2015) note cases in Xitsonga where the order of two auxiliaries is variable and affects their relative scopes, and therefore also the utterance’s interpretation (11). In (11a), *hatla* ‘quickly’ takes scope over *engeta* ‘again’, and the utterance refers to the quick recurrence of the drinking situation. In (11b), on the other hand, the drinking itself is done quickly.

(11) Xitsonga (Lee and Hlungwani 2015, 131–132)

- a. *Ndzi-hàtlà* *ndzi-éngétá* *ndzi-nw-à* *màti*.
 SM_{1SG}.SIT-AUX[quickly] SM_{1SG}.SIT-AUX[again] SM_{1SG}.SIT-drink 6.water
 ‘I quickly drink water again.’
- b. *Ndzi-èngètà* *ndzi-hátlá* *ndzi-nw-à* *màti*.
 SM_{1SG}.SIT-AUX[quickly] SM_{1SG}.SIT-AUX[again] SM_{1SG}.SIT-drink 6.water
 ‘I again quickly drink water.’

Lee and Hlungwani (2015) further note that in at least some constructions involving three auxiliaries, several orders are possible, although there are also ordering restrictions. For example, *tlhèlà* ‘once, again, also’ cannot appear in the last position, as in (12e) and (12f). This restriction may be caused by the interactions of ‘again’ and the ‘once’ reading of *tlhèlà*. According to Lee and Hlungwani, the licit orders shown in (12) do not affect the interpretation of the utterance. Since both *hatla* and *engeta* are also involved in (11), where the interpretation is not clearly affected by their relative ordering, we assume that the involvement of a third auxiliary (*thela* ‘once [again]’) either changes the interpretive calculus or renders the distinction between the different orderings too subtle to straightforwardly elicit, or to convey in English translation.

(12) Xitsonga (Lee and Hlungwani 2015, 132)

- a. *ndzi-tlhèlà* *ndzi-hátlá* *ndzi-èngètà*
 SM_{1SG}-AUX[once_again] SM_{1SG}.SIT-AUX[quickly] SM_{1SG}.SIT-AUX[again]

⁴Pietraszko (2018, 316) further predicts that situative-selecting auxiliaries cannot follow subjunctive-selecting auxiliaries, a point we return to in Section 2.5. Pietraszko does not discuss the relative ordering of subjunctive-selecting auxiliaries or the behaviour of situative-selecting auxiliaries beyond *se*, *hlezi*, and *lokhe*. The other generalizations she proposes for situative-selecting auxiliaries (they cannot be inflected for tense or negation; see Pietraszko 2018, 316–317) do not hold for situative-selecting auxiliaries across Southern Bantu, although they may well apply to specific auxiliaries. We have not investigated Ndebele (Zimbabwe) further in this regard.

ndzì-nw-à *màtì*
SM_{1SG}.SIT-drink-FV 6.water
‘Once again, I quickly drink water again’

- b. *ndzì-hàtlà ndzì-tlhéla ndzì-éngétà ndzì-nwà màtì*
- c. *ndzì-tlhèlà ndzì-éngétá ndzì-hàtlà ndzì-nwà màtì*
- d. *ndzì-èngètà ndzì-tlhéla ndzì-hàtlà ndzì-nwà màtì*
- e. **ndzì-hatla ndzì-engeta ndzì-tlhela ndzì-nwa mati*
- f. **ndzì-engeta ndzì-hatla ndzì-tlhela ndzì-nwa mati*

Other auxiliary combinations appear to have fixed (or at least preferred) orders, possibly related to semantic restrictions on scope, but also to conventionalized collocations, perhaps akin to adjective ordering in many varieties of English (see, e.g., Wulff 2003), where *the beautiful old grey mare* is licit, but **the grey beautiful old mare* sounds odd, at best. For example, auxiliaries expressing negation frequently appear as the first element in auxiliary stackings, as in (13) (but cf. (14), where an auxiliary with negation semantics appears in the third position). Both *buye* and *phinde* are often translated as ‘again’ when used as auxiliaries. We are not sure how each of these contributes to the meaning here.

- (13) isiXhosa (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 247)
- | | | |
|----------------------------------|--|---------------------------------|
| <i>Ló mfázi wám</i> | <i>à-ká-zángè</i> | <i>á-bè</i> |
| DEM 1.wife | ASSC ₁ .POSS _{1SG} | NEG-SM ₁ -AUX[never] |
| | | SM ₁ -AUX.SBJV[be] |
| <i>á-bùyé</i> | <i>á-phíndè</i> | <i>á-béth-w-è.</i> |
| SM ₁ -AUX.SBJV[again] | SM ₁ -AUX.SBJV[again] | SM ₁ -beat-PASS-SBJV |
- ‘This wife of mine was never again given a hiding.’

Setshedi (1974) suggests two tendencies in Setswana. First, temporal auxiliaries precede what Setshedi terms *modal* auxiliaries (Setshedi uses *modal* as a cover term for non-temporal uses, including negation, manner, and attitude, among other functions; see Setshedi 1974, 20). Second, within the ‘modal’ domain, there is a “preferential sequence” of “(i) co-ordination, (ii) negation, (iii) potentiality and (iv) impatience or surprise” (Setshedi 1974, 52). This proposed order is based on examples such as those in (14) below, where *nê* indicates the past tense; *bile* means ‘furthermore’ or ‘for that matter’; *ise* is a negative auxiliary meaning ‘not yet’ or ‘never [before]’; *ke* is a potential (possibility) marker; and *bo* marks impatience or surprise.

- (14) Setswana (Setshedi 1974, 51)
- | | | | |
|-------------------------------|--------------------------------------|--------------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| <i>Monna yola</i> | <i>o-nê</i> | <i>a-bile</i> | <i>a-ise</i> |
| 1.man | DEM ₁ | SM ₁ -AUX[PST] | SM ₁ .SIT-AUX[furthermore] |
| | | | SM ₁ .SIT-AUX[NEG] |
| <i>a-ke</i> | <i>a-bo</i> | <i>a-tsene</i> | <i>mo-mow-eng</i> |
| SM ₁ .SIT-AUX[POT] | SM ₁ .SIT-AUX[impatience] | SM ₁ .SIT-enter.PFV | 18-1.air-LOC |
- wame.*
ASSC₁.POSS_{1SG}
‘For that matter, that man had never really appealed to my feelings.’
More literal translation: ‘That man has never even got into my spirit.’ (Kearabetswe Rammala, email to authors, December 8, 2025)

Some Setswana data suggest that the auxiliaries in question do tend to occur in the order noted by Setshedi (1974).⁵ Creissels (forthcoming) gives an example where *bo* appears before *ne* (15), but this may not constitute a counterexample, since the function of *bo* appears to be different from the “impatience” function in (14).⁶

(15) Setswana (Creissels forthcoming, 13)⁷

Re ka bo re ne re lema tshimo.

rí-ká-bò rí-né 'rí-límá 'tshî:mò

SM_{1PL}-POT-AUX[be] SM_{1PL}.SIT-AUX[PST] SM_{1PL}.SIT-cultivate-FV 9.field

‘We might have been cultivating the field.’

Example (16) shows *bo* with an impatience reading preceding a different set of auxiliary verbs, the functional status of which is not entirely clear to us in this context.⁸

(16) Setswana (Setshedi 1974, 43)

O-bo o-tla-ne o-sale

SM_{2SG}-AUX[impatience] SM_{2SG}.SIT-FUT-AUX[CONT?] SM_{2SG}.SIT?-AUX[when?]

o-bots-a motho.

SM_{2SG}.SIT-ask-FV 1.person

‘You take a long time asking a person questions.’

⁵The data in question come from the website glosbe.com, which describes itself as an “online dictionary” and includes a searchable corpus of parallel sentences in many languages, based on a large set of human-translated texts. The corpus does not show context beyond the sentence level, but most of the source material can be found on the internet. Searches for combinations of the auxiliaries in (14) (e.g. *ne*, *ise*, and *ke*) show results that correspond with Setshedi’s (1974) ordering.

⁶The contribution of *bo* in this latter context is not clear, because the possibility meaning can be traced to the potential prefix *ka-*, and *bo* might be semantically bleached (and probably traceable to a verb meaning ‘be’). Rather than suggesting evaluative meaning, as in (14), the main function of *bo* in (15) seems to be hosting the potential prefix and fixing the time (here, present) against which the following auxiliary is evaluated. That is, from the present perspective, it is possible that we have (earlier) been cultivating the field. If *bo* has a different meaning, it may not represent a true counterexample to Setshedi’s (1974) generalization. It may also be that the location of *bo* in a stacking construction at least partly affects its interpretation. Whatever the semantics of *bo*, a modal meaning seems to precede a temporal reference (past [imperfective] ‘have [been]’) in this example, suggesting at least some flexibility beyond the broader generalizations Setshedi gives. Thanks to Denis Creissels (email to authors, September 22, 2025) for discussing this example with us. Any misinterpretations remain our own.

⁷When citing examples from Creissels, we follow his practice of reproducing the first line in the official orthography of Setswana and the interlinearized line phonemically and with tone marking.

⁸In particular, the function of future-marked *-ne* is unclear to us, as it seems to differ from past *-né* (represented in standard orthography as *-ne*, as in (15)) and may be an alternate spelling of *-nne* (continuative/habitual; see, e.g., Creissels forthcoming 17).

Checking all possible orderings of all auxiliary forms in languages with 20 or more auxiliary forms quickly becomes challenging from a combinatorial perspective. In future work, AI-assisted corpus-based research might be a fruitful avenue to explore, where reliable corpora are available.

We suggest several general research questions with respect to the ordering and semantics of stacked auxiliaries in Southern Bantu:

1. Are there any restrictions or tendencies related to semantic macro-type? For example, auxiliaries might be grouped based on whether they primarily express temporal (including sequentiality), aspectual, modal, negation, or other (e.g., manner, evaluative, epistemic/mirative) contrasts. Do these – or other possible – macro-types have ordering preferences, or do ordering restrictions apply at a more specific lexical level?
2. What scope effects can be seen with auxiliary stacking, and when can these be overridden? For example, this section showed scope differences in at least one language corresponding to orderings like QUICKLY AGAIN (i.e., the repetition happened promptly) versus AGAIN QUICKLY (i.e., the action itself was executed quickly); what about contrasts like TRULY NEVER VERSUS NEVER TRULY? Under what circumstances can preferred orderings take precedence over scopal effects?
3. Are any specific auxiliaries or classes of auxiliaries prohibited from certain positions in auxiliary chains due to their nature, i.e., not being able to take certain inflectional morphology, appear in infinitive form, etc.?

2.3 Intervening elements

There is evidence that at least some Southern Bantu languages allow intervening elements between the auxiliary and the lexical verb (e.g., Lee and Hlungwani 2015, 118 for Xitsonga; Setshedi 1974, 54 for Setswana). An example of the phenomenon in Xitsonga is shown in (17). The comitative phrase *na munghana* ‘with a friend’ can appear after the auxiliary construction, as in (17a), or it can appear between the auxiliary and the main verb, as in (17b). A pause after the comitative phrase renders the utterance with the intervening comitative phrase ungrammatical, as in (17c).

(17) Xitsonga (Lee and Hlungwani 2015, 118)

- a. *ndzi-hàtlà ndzi-nw-à byàlwà nà múnghá:nà*
 SM_{1SG}-AUX[quickly] SM_{1SG}.SIT-drink-FV 14.beer with 1.friend
 ‘I quickly drink beer with a friend’
- b. *ndzi-hàtlà ná múnghá(:)nà ndzi-nwá byàlwà*
- c. **ndzi-hatla na mungha:na // ndzi-nwa byalwa*

We propose the following questions for future research:

1. Which languages allow intervening words and phrases between the auxiliary and the main verb?
2. What kinds of intervening elements (adverbials, objects, obliques...?) are allowed in these constructions?
3. Can the same elements that intervene between auxiliaries and lexical verbs also appear between stacked auxiliaries, and if so, what restrictions or tendencies exist?

2.4 Subject marking

To the best of our knowledge, subject (or infinitive) marking on stacked auxiliaries is determined by the general selectional properties of the preceding auxiliary. As illustrated with data from Sesotho in (18) below, multiple stacked auxiliaries can all be inflected for an agreeing subject (which is not lexically expressed in (18)). In (19), agreement on all verbal elements is with the expletive class 17 rather than the subject *bafana* ‘boys’. The difference in the agreement pattern observed here is due to the position of the subject with respect to the verbal complex: the subject appears in the ‘Immediately After Verb’ (IAV) position in (19). When subjects occur in IAV position, subject agreement on the verb is not possible in Nguni languages (see Halpert 2019; Zeller 2006, 2008, but cf. Bloom Ström 2017). Thus, the subject marking pattern observed here is not caused by the auxiliary but by general syntactic rules.

(18) Sesotho (Gowlett 2003, 635)

<i>ó-nè</i>	<i>á-k’è</i>	<i>à-láli</i>
SM ₁ -AUX[PST]	SM ₁ .SIT-AUX[occasionally]	SM ₁ .CSC-AUX.HAB[at_night]
<i>á-ithút’-à</i>		
SM ₁ .SIT-study-FV		
‘He used occasionally to spend the night studying.’		

(19) siSwati (Thwala 2006, 332)

<i>Ku-ngeke</i>	<i>ku-phindze</i>	<i>ku-hamb-e</i>	<i>bafana</i>
SM ₁₇ -AUX[NEG]	SM ₁₇ -AUX[repeat].SBJV	SM ₁₇ -go-SBJV	2.boy
‘The boys will not leave/go again.’			

Regarding subject marking in auxiliary stacking constructions, we propose the following research question:

1. What patterns of subject marking are attested in each variety? Specifically, are there any restrictions on subject markers, such as whether infinitive-marked auxiliaries can be followed by subject-marked auxiliaries (see Section 2.5)?

2.5 Selectional properties

Auxiliaries in Southern Bantu typically select the form of the following verb, which, while inflected for the subject, is generally less finite or non-finite, including subjunctive (SBJV, also including consecutive [CSC], as explained in the next paragraph), infinitival (INF), and situative (SIT) forms. The restriction to a single fully finite form is similar to what is reported for sequences of auxiliaries in Spanish (Bravo et al. 2015), where all auxiliaries except for the leftmost are marked as infinitival or participial forms. It might be possible in some cases for a finite/indicative verb to follow the auxiliary in Southern Bantu (as is common beyond Southern Bantu; see Nurse 2008, 29–30, 167–177), but this possibility seems to be limited to a relatively small subset of auxiliaries (see the data in Carbo et al. 2025).

In this section, we examine the ordering of subjunctive, infinitival, and situative complements in stacked auxiliary constructions. We treat subjunctive and consecutive forms together because – amongst other functions, which do not always overlap (see, e.g., Savić 2020, §7.4) – both are used in narrative sequences (clause chains) to describe sequences of events, where consecutives typically have past orientation and subjunctives have non-past orientation (see

Riedel and Gibson 2024). The same auxiliaries often select for both subjunctive and consecutive forms, depending on the overall temporal orientation of the clause. We treat subjunctives and consecutives as interchangeable for this question, until further data are available, as our relatively constrained dataset has not allowed us to find both subjunctive and consecutive examples for each ordering possibility.

We looked for examples of all logically possible orders of inflectional categories for the second and third elements in verbal complexes with at least two auxiliaries and one main verb. For example, in (13), repeated as (20), the first auxiliary *àkázàngè* ‘never’ selects a subjunctive second element *ábè* (roughly, ‘was’), which in turn selects a subjunctive third auxiliary element *ábùyé* ‘again’. This construction has two more elements, the auxiliary *àphindè* ‘again’ and, finally, the lexical verb *ábéthwè* ‘beaten’, both of which are also subjunctive-marked; however, for the current purposes, we only consider the first three elements in a stacking construction, whether they be three auxiliaries or two auxiliaries and a lexical verb. In the examples in this section, we also mark the relevant glosses (SBJV, CSC, INF, SIT) in bold to make them easier for readers to locate.

- (20) AUX–SBJV–SBJV: isiXhosa (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 247)
- Ló mfázi wám à-ká-zàngè á-bè*
 DEM 1.wife ASSC₁.POSS_{1SG} NEG-SM₁-AUX[never] SM₁-AUX.SBJV[be]
á-bùyé à-phindè á-béth-w-è.
 SM₁-AUX.SBJV[again] SM₁-AUX.SBJV[again] SM₁-beat-PASS-SBJV
 ‘This wife of mine was never again given a hiding.’

We have so far found examples of seven of the nine combinatorial possibilities. As auxiliaries select for complement type, they are not sensitive to the form of the first auxiliary in a stacking construction, although in most cases it will be a main-clause indicative verb.

Table 1: Inflectional form of verb by position

First aux	Second aux	Main verb/Third aux	Example language (example number)
Main clause indicative	SBJV/CSC	SBJV/CSC	isiXhosa (20), Setswana (21)
	SBJV/CSC	SIT	Setswana (22), Sesotho (23)
	SBJV/CSC	INF	<i>none found</i>
	SIT	SBJV/CSC	siSwati (24)
	SIT	INF	isiNdebele (25)
	SIT	SIT	Xitsonga (26)
	INF	SBJV/CSC	<i>none found</i>
	INF	SIT	Xitsonga (27)
	INF	INF	Tshivenda (28)

Examples of each of the constructions corresponding with those in Table 1 are given below. Example (21) shows a consecutive-marked second auxiliary followed by a consecutive-marked lexical verb (see also example (20) above, with subjunctive forms). Examples (22) and (23) show a consecutive-marked second auxiliary followed by a situative-marked lexical verb.

- (21) AUX–CSC–CSC: Setswana (Creissels forthcoming, 39)
Tshenyo e ka nna ya se ka ya felela foo.
tshínó í-kà-ínà jà-sì-ká já-fêlél-à fô:ò
 9.harm SM₉-POT-AUX[stay] SM₉.CSC-NEG-AUX[never] SM₉.CSC-end.APPL-FV here
 ‘The harm may not stop here.’
- (22) AUX–CSC–SIT: Setswana (Creissels forthcoming, 29)
Ga ba ka ke ba lala ba feditse tiro ya bone.
χà-bá-kà-kí bà-lálà bá-fédítsé
 NEG-SM₂-POT-AUX[never] SM₂.CSC-AUX[HOD.FUT] SM₂.SIT-finish.PFV
tírò jábò:né
 9.work POSS.PRON_{9/2}
 ‘They won’t be able to finish their work today.’
 ‘They are never able to finish their work.’
- (23) AUX–CSC–SIT: Sesotho (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 247)
Ke-ile ka-batla ke-e-shw-a.
 SM_{1SG}-AUX SM_{1SG}.CSC-AUX SM_{1SG}.SIT-EPEN-die-FV
 ‘I nearly died.’

Examples (24), (25) and (26) show a situative-marked auxiliary followed by an auxiliary or lexical verb marked for the subjunctive, infinitive, and situative, respectively.

- (24) AUX–SIT–SBJV: siSwati (modified from Nkuna et al. 2021, 231)
Lilanga li-hlala li-sheshe li-shon-e e-busika
 5.sun SM₅-AUX[always] SM₅.SIT-AUX[quickly] SM₅-set-SBJV LOC-14.winter
 ‘The sun always sets quickly in winter’
- (25) AUX–SIT–INF: isiNdebele (M. P. Mabena, email, January 28, 2025)
Ilanga lebusika li-hlala li-rhaba uku-tjhing-a.
 5.sun POSS₅.14.evening SM₅-AUX[always] SM₅.SIT-AUX[quickly] INF-set-FV
 ‘The evening sun always sets quickly.’
- (26) AUX–SIT–SIT: Xitsonga (Lee and Hlungwani 2015, 132)
Ndzì-tlhèlà ndzì-hátlá ndzì-èngètà ndzì-nw-à
 SM_{1SG}-AUX[once] SM_{1SG}.SIT-AUX[quickly] SM_{1SG}.SIT-AUX[again] SM_{1SG}.SIT-drink-FV
màtì.
 6.water
 ‘Once again, I quickly drink water again’ [sic]

Finally, examples (27) and (28) show infinitival forms followed by a situative-marked form and a second infinitive, respectively.

(27) AUX–INF–SIT: Xitsonga (Hlungwani et al. 2021, 173)
Ndzi-dzumbela ku-hatla ndzi-nw-a mati.
 SM_{1SG}-AUX[always] INF-AUX[quickly] SM_{1SG}.SIT-drink-FV 6.WATER
 ‘I always quickly drink water’

(28) AUX–INF–INF: Tshivenda (Netshisaulu et al. 2021, 113)
Ndi-dzulela u-tavhanya u-nw-a maḍi.
 SM_{1SG}-AUX[always] INF-AUX[quickly] INF-drink-FV 6.water
 ‘I always quickly drink water’

Our present data give rise to the following questions:

1. Are any selectional orderings more common across Southern Bantu, or within particular varieties?
2. Are any selectional orderings prohibited across Southern Bantu, or within particular varieties?
3. Are certain auxiliaries unable to take part in particular selectional orderings due to their defective nature (i.e., are they unable to take particular morphological forms; see also Section 2.6)?

2.6 Inflectional possibilities (tense, aspect, mood/modality, negation/polarity)

In Southern Bantu, most tense, mood/modality, and negation (TMP) morphology is hosted by the first element in an auxiliary construction, probably because the TMP value often has scope over the whole construction. Aspect marking is a slightly more complex case, as we discuss in Section 2.6.2. However, T(A)MP morphology does not seem to be completely restricted to the first element in an auxiliary construction. We discuss the different categories of inflection in the subsections below.

2.6.1 Tense marking

In most auxiliary constructions, tense marking appears on the auxiliary, while the lexical verb is marked for aspect (although the prevalence of the perfective form, which often doubles as a near-past and frequently appears both on auxiliary forms and on the lexical verb, complicates this assertion). That said, there are cases in which both the auxiliary and the lexical verb are marked for tense, as in (29), where both forms are marked with future tense to give a future prospective reading. According to Ziervogel and Mabuza (1976, 98), *ta-* and *tawu-* are stylistic variants of the same marker.

(29) siSwati (Nichols 2011, 58)
Ngi-ta-be ngi-tawu-nats-a.
 SM_{1SG}-IMM.FUT-AUX SM_{1SG}.SIT-IMM.FUT-drink-FV
 ‘I shall be about to drink.’

There are also cases where tense marking appears on only the lexical verb, as in (30), where the first auxiliary, *phinda*, is marked with an aspectual marker *se* (persistive) and a modal marker *noku* (possibility), but the subsequent lexical verb *suleleka* ‘be infected’ has a future-marking prefix.

(30) isiXhosa (Eiselen and Puttkammer 2014, cited in Crane et al. 2025)

<i>... u-se-noku-phinda</i>	<i>w-o-sulelek-e</i>	<i>futhi</i>
SM _{2SG} -PERS-POSSIB-AUX	SM _{2SG} -FUT-be_infected-SBJV	again
<i>ku-funeka u-phinde</i>	<i>wa-nyang-w-a.</i>	
SM ₁₇ -AUX	SM _{2SG} -AUX.SBJV	SM _{2SG} .CSC-treat-PASS-FV

‘...as you can [lest you] get infected again and need to be re-treated.’

The question, then, is what restrictions, if any, are found on stacked auxiliaries. In most of the auxiliary stacking examples in our collected data, tense marking appears on the first auxiliary, as in (31).

(31) Sesotho (Creissels forthcoming, 20)

<i>Ke tlaa bo ke ntse ke bereka</i>		
<i>ki-tlâà-bò</i>	<i>ki-ńtsi</i>	<i>ki-bêrê:k-à.</i>
SM _{1SG} -FUT-AUX	SM _{1SG} .SIT-AUX[DUR]	SM _{1SG} .SIT-work-FV

‘I will be working.’

However, there is some evidence that future marking can also appear on the second auxiliary (31). (As mentioned in Section 2.1, where it first appears as example (16), we do not fully understand the compositional semantics of this example.)

(32) Setswana (Setshedi 1974, 43)

<i>O-bo</i>	<i>o-tla-ne</i>	<i>o-sale</i>
SM _{2SG} -AUX[impatience]	SM _{2SG} .SIT-FUT-AUX[CONT?]	SM _{2SG} .SIT?-AUX[when?]
<i>o-bots-a</i>	<i>motho.</i>	
SM _{2SG} .SIT-ask-FV	1.person	

‘You take a long time asking a person questions.’

Note that in (32), the future marker (assuming we are correct in analysing it as such) appears on a situative form, which, as Creissels (forthcoming, 4) notes, “express[es] temporal subordination”. That is, its temporality is evaluated against some other reference time – in auxiliary constructions, the time provided by the preceding element. Situatives can have imperfective (26) or perfective (22) aspect. In at least some languages, there is also a past situative form (see Savić 2020, 176–179 on isiXhosa). We do not know whether this form ever participates in auxiliary constructions.

Further in-depth examination of these constructions would seek to address the following questions:

1. Where in auxiliary stacking constructions can tense morphology appear?
2. What tenses are available in non-initial position?
3. If tense marking appears in non-initial position, what are its semantic effects?

2.6.2 Aspect marking

This section deals with aspect marking beyond basic perfective and imperfective contrasts. Many auxiliaries seem themselves to be derived from perfective-marked verb forms (see the

data in Carbo et al. 2025),⁹ and, while it may be possible to identify the effects of perfective marking on an auxiliary in a particular language or construction (see, e.g., Creissels forthcoming), auxiliaries derived from perfective forms of lexical verbs often develop idiomatic readings, and we do not know of a foolproof way, based on current data, of distinguishing perfective-marked from perfective-derived auxiliaries when looking at Southern Bantu as a whole.¹⁰ Perfective morphology is mostly suffixal and often ‘imbricated’, changing the verb stem itself. In a language like Tshivenda, where perfective-like morphology is prefixal rather than suffixal (33), the difference between productive perfective marking on auxiliaries and frozen perfective-like auxiliary morphology might be easier to distinguish.

- (33) Tshivenda (Heine 1993, 38)
- | | |
|----------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| <i>Ndo-vha</i> | <i>ndo-vhon-a.</i> |
| SM _{1SG} .PFV-AUX | SM _{1SG} .PFV.SIT-see-FV |
| ‘I had seen.’ | |

In any case, it is common across Bantu that more than one verb in an auxiliary construction can be marked with the perfective (see Nurse 2008, 96, who refers to the relevant aspect as “anterior”, which he contrasts with “perfective”).

Other forms related to aspectuality, such as the persistive (meaning roughly ‘still’), have at least some flexibility regarding where they appear in auxiliary stacking constructions; that is, they are not restricted to the first element. For example, persistive *sa-* in (34) appears on the third auxiliary. However, the possibility auxiliary *kwazi* falls at the less grammaticalized end of the spectrum of Southern Bantu auxiliaries (it is arguably still a lexical verb rather than an auxiliary; see Crane et al. 2025). Note that the negation of persistive *sa-* generally has a ‘no longer’ reading in isiNdebele and other Nguni languages, and this sense seems to carry across the auxiliary stacking construction in (34).

- (34) isiNdebele (M. P. Mabena, email, January 28, 2025)
- | | | |
|--|-------------------------------|--|
| <i>A-ngekhe</i> | <i>a-be</i> | <i>a-sa-kwazi</i> |
| SM ₁ -AUX[NEG.FUT/POT] | SM ₁ -AUX.SBJV[be] | SM ₁ .SIT-PERS-AUX[POSSIBILITY] |
| <i>uku-buya</i> | <i>a-sebenz-e.</i> | |
| INF-AUX[again] | SM ₁ -work-SBJV | |
| ‘S/he will never be able to work again.’ | | |

We propose the following research questions regarding aspect marking in auxiliary stacking constructions:

1. How can we characterize the role of perfective and imperfective morphology in auxiliary stacking constructions?
2. What other aspectual morphology can appear in auxiliary stacking constructions, and what are its restrictions?

⁹For discussion of the term ‘perfective’, see Crane and Persohn (2019, 314) and Crane and Persohn (2021). These forms are referred to variously across descriptions and are often given labels such as ‘anterior’, ‘perfect’, or ‘past’.

¹⁰Perhaps a criterion could be whether a corresponding imperfective (usually zero-marked) form is also available for the same auxiliary, and whether the perfective meaning is transparently derivable from it, i.e., if the semantic difference is one that corresponds to general perfective–imperfective semantics in the language.

2.6.3 Negation marking

Some auxiliaries encode negation meanings directly, and these tend to appear at or towards the beginning of auxiliary stacking constructions in our data (see Section 2.1). Other auxiliaries host negation morphology, either optionally or obligatorily. An example of a negation-marked auxiliary is given in (35).

(35) Setswana (Cole 1955, 293)

Ga-ke-bolo *go-rêk-a*
NEG-SM_{1SG}-AUX[REM.PST] INF-buy-FV
‘I have not recently bought.’ (i.e., ‘I bought [only] quite some time ago.’)

In at least some cases (some of which are likely to be marginal), negation marking can appear both on an auxiliary and its lexical complement (36).¹¹

(36) isiXhosa (O. Slater, email, November 26, 2024)

A-ndi-soloko *ndi-nga-bhal-i*.
NEG-SM_{1SG}-AUX[always] SM_{1SG}.SIT-NEG-write-NEG
‘I don’t always not write.’ [i.e., sometimes / usually I *do* write]

Our dataset includes at least a few examples where the second auxiliary in a stacking construction is marked for negation (37).

(37) Setswana (Setshedi 1974, 42)

Re-ka-bo *re-sa-ka* *ra-robal-a*.
SM_{1PL}-POT-AUX[perhaps?] SM_{1PL}.SIT-NEG-AUX[POT?] SM_{1PL}.SIT-sleep-FV
‘We, in a way, should not have slept.’

We propose the following questions:

1. What are the restrictions on negation marking within auxiliary stacking constructions, and do they vary according to variety, specific auxiliary, auxiliary type, position, or some other factor?
2. How does negation marking in auxiliary stacking constructions interact with semantic compositionality?
3. What do the properties of negation marking in auxiliary stacking constructions show about their clausal structures?

¹¹ The number of negation markers allowed is sometimes taken as a test for whether auxiliary constructions are monoclausal or biclausal. We do not take a stance on the clausal status of auxiliary constructions in Southern Bantu here (though see Creissels forthcoming, this volume for arguments for their monoclausality), despite monoclausality sometimes being seen as a criterion for auxiliary status (as in Anderson 2006, 2011, who also includes Southern Bantu auxiliary constructions in his analysis). As noted, we believe the more relevant issues to be boundedness (i.e., the auxiliary not appearing on its own with grammatical meaning) and the fact that all auxiliaries and the lexical verb form a single predicate together.

2.6.4 Mood marking proper

The subjunctive can occur at any point in an auxiliary chain. For imperative mood, we have only seen a few examples, and in these, imperative (lack of) morphology appears on the first verb in the auxiliary construction (38). We expect this property also to hold for stacking constructions. For the infinitive, we expect it to require licensing by a finite verb but otherwise to be able to appear in various places in an auxiliary chain.

- (38) Xitsonga (Cuenod 1967, 60)
- | | | | |
|--------------|--------------------------------|--------------|--|
| jinga | <i>u-tirh-a</i> | <i>hambi</i> | <i>va-ku-hlek-a</i> |
| AUX.IMP | SM _{2SG} .SIT-work-FV | although | SM ₂ -OM _{2SG} -laugh-FV |
- ‘Go on working although they laugh at you.’

We propose the following research question:

1. Are there any plausible scenarios in which imperative mood would be marked on a non-initial verb in an auxiliary (stacking) sequence? (For example, could an imperative form be preceded and modified by another auxiliary with manner semantics?) If the scenarios are plausible, are such constructions, in fact, licit?

2.6.5 Modal markers (possibility)

In all the examples we have found so far, inflectional possibility markers (potential *ka-/nga-*, isiXhosa possibility prefix *noku-/nako-*) are found on the first element of a stacking construction (39)–(40), even when, as in (40), one of the auxiliaries itself marks possibility.

- (39) Setswana (Creissels forthcoming, 13)
- | | | | |
|---------------------------------------|---------------------------------|-------------------------------------|-----------------|
| <i>re ka bo re ne re lema tshimo.</i> | | | |
| <i>ri-ká-bò</i> | <i>ri-né</i> | <i>ʹri-límá</i> | <i>ʹtshî:mò</i> |
| SM _{1PL} -POT-AUX[be] | SM _{1PL} .SIT-AUX[PST] | SM _{1PL} .SIT-cultivate-FV | 9.field |
- ‘We might have been cultivating the field.’

- (40) isiXhosa (Eiselen and Puttkammer 2014, cited in Crane et al. 2025)
- | | | |
|--|--|-----|
| <i>a-ka-naku-ze</i> | <i>a-kwazi</i> | |
| NEG-SM ₁ -POSSIB.NEG-AUX[eventually?] | SM ₁ -AUX[POSSIBILITY].SBJV | |
| <i>ku-phinda</i> | <i>a-sebenz-e</i> | ... |
| INF-AUX[again] | SM ₁ -work-SBJV | |
- ‘...s/he will/might never be able to work again...’

However, there are examples of single-auxiliary constructions where both the auxiliary and the main verb are marked with potential *ka-* (41), a construction Doke and Mofokeng (1957, 263) describe as “potential emphatic”. It is unclear to us whether such constructions are possible with anything other than the semantically ‘empty’ auxiliary *be*, which usually serves to mark a point against which the temporality of the subsequent verb is evaluated.

(41) Sesotho (Doke and Mofokeng 1957, 263)

N-ka-be *n-ka-rek-a.*
 SM_{1SG}-POT-AUX[be] SM_{1SG}-POT-buy-FV
 ‘I might possibly buy.’

We propose the following research question:

1. Can inflectional modal marking appear on non-initial elements in auxiliary stacks, either with *be* or with other auxiliaries?

3 Other topics

This section briefly introduces a few other topics for which we do not have extensive data, but which we believe to be of importance for fully understanding auxiliary stacking constructions. Section 3.1 raises the issue of compositional vs. non-compositional semantics. Section 3.2 notes that, sometimes, several auxiliaries with similar English translations can appear in the same stacking constructions and asks how such cases should be analyzed. Section 3.3 brings up the need for incorporating tone and prosody into investigations of auxiliary stacking constructions.

3.1 Semantics: compositional vs. non-compositional

In most of the auxiliary constructions presented in this short overview, the contribution of each auxiliary is relatively clear, and utterance semantics are compositional, although some constructions and their semantics are quite complex. We have not yet found any examples where the collocations are conventionalized with idiomatic, non-decomposable readings, although we imagine these would be possible.

We propose the following research question:

1. Do any specific collocations have idiomatic readings, where the semantics are not straightforwardly decomposable?

3.2. Auxiliaries with reduplicated or similar meanings

Some of the examples of auxiliary stacking in our dataset include two different auxiliaries with identical or at least overlapping meanings, as in (42), which is repeated from (13) for ease of reference. As far as we understand it, the second ‘again’ can add emphasis, but some speakers we consulted preferred a version without the repetition. These types of patterns require further study to understand whether the semantic contributions of auxiliaries with different forms but similar translations are truly identical; it is also important to investigate how these auxiliaries interact with adverbials with the same meaning.

(42) isiXhosa (du Plessis and Visser 1992, 247)

Ló mfázi wám à-ká-zúngè á-bè á-bùyé
 DEM 1.wife ASSC₁.POSS_{1SG} SM₁-NEG-AUX[NEVER] SM₁-AUX SM₁-AUX[again]
à-phíndè á-béth-w-è.
 SM₁-AUX[again] SM₁-beat-PASS-PERF
 ‘This wife of mine was never again given a hiding.’

We propose the following research questions:

1. How do multiple auxiliaries with similar meanings interact?
2. What is the relative frequency of examples with more than one auxiliary expressing a similar meaning?

3.3 Tone, lengthening, and constituency

In many, if not all, Southern Bantu languages, tone and lengthening can be important markers of shared constituency, although prosodic structure does not always align perfectly with syntactic structure (see Selkirk and Lee 2015). Only a few studies of auxiliary constructions (e.g., Creissels forthcoming) systematically mark tone and lengthening. Studies taking prosody into account are likely to be important for a full understanding of the syntax of auxiliary stacking constructions.

We propose the following basic but broad-ranging research question:

1. How do prosodic systems interact with auxiliary stacking constructions?

4 Summary and steps for future research

This paper has provided a brief introduction to what we currently know about auxiliary stacking in Southern Bantu in terms of ordering, morphosyntax, semantics, and compositionality. We hope that this overview will form the foundation for further investigations of these constructions. The paper developed here is based on existing descriptive accounts and a survey of auxiliary forms developed by Carbo et al. (2025). As such, while we have identified several features and patterns which we think are of interest, future dedicated research which constitutes a systematic study of auxiliary stacking constructions would naturally be able to address further questions or reveal insights which were not able to achieve in the current paper. We hope that future research will answer the questions posed here – and others – and further our understanding of auxiliary stacking constructions in Southern Bantu.

Abbreviations

Glossing and abbreviations follow the Leipzig Glossing Rules with the following additions: 1,2,3 = noun classes, ANT = anterior, ASSC = associative (usually: possessive prefix + connective *a-*), AUG = augment, AUX = auxiliary, COMP = complement, CONJ = conjunction, CONT = continuative, COP.LOC = locative copula, CSC = consecutive, DEM = demonstrative, EPEN = epenthetic vowel; FV = final vowel, IMM.FUT = immediate future, INF = infinitive, IPFV = imperfective LOC = locative, NECESS = necessity NEG = negative, OM = object marker, SIT = situative, SM = subject marker, PERS = persistent ('still'), PRON = pronoun, POSSIB = possibility prefix (modal), POT = potential (modal)

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Editorial note

Thera Marie Crane is currently serving as an Editor-in-Chief of the *Nordic Journal of African Studies* and as an editor of this special issue. This article was subject to the same double-blind review process as all other articles in this issue, and none of the authors had access to reviewer information.

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